

Deliverable 1.1

State of the Art and end-user needs review

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Editor(s)	Amir Pooyan Afghari, Eleonora Papadimitriou, TUD
Contributor(s)	Amir Pooyan Afghari & Eleonora Papadimitriou, TUD Apostolos Ziakopoulos & Maria Oikonomou, NTUA Arunava Putatunda, Christelle Al Haddad, Mohamed Abouelela, & Constantinos Antoniou, TUM Shanna Lucchesi, Monica Olyslagers & James Bradford, iRAP Antonio Pellicer & Marcel Sala, AIM Sam Chapman, FLOWW Pedro Homem de Gouveia & Andréia Lopes Azevedo, POLIS
Reviewer(s)	Ana María Pérez-Zuriaga, UPV Marko Sevrovic, EIRA
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Project summary

The EU-funded 'Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment' (PHOEBE) project aims to develop an integrated, dynamic human-centred predictive safety assessment framework in urban areas. This will be achieved by bringing together the interdisciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, mode shift and induced demand modelling and new and emerging mobility data.

Focused on vulnerable road users' safety, the 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will draw inspiration from real-world scenarios in the three pilot cities of Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK). Testing activities will be performed across the use cases to simulate and forecast the impact of changes on safety in different scenarios of disruptions or transitions across urban transport networks.

Predicting and visualising the safety and socioeconomic outcomes of new forms of transport, new technologies, or regulatory and behavioural changes from the individual (micro) level up to the network-wide (macro) level will also be a significant game-changer for urban stakeholders. The results of PHOEBE can be used as a blueprint by other European cities to develop their knowledge products, such as socioeconomic analysis model, urban road safety assessment, human behaviour and choice modelling.

PHOEBE pilot cities

List of participating cities:

- Athens (Greece)
- Valencia (Spain)
- West Midlands (United Kingdom)

Social Links:

 https://twitter.com/Project_PHOEBE

 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>

 <https://www.youtube.com/@phoebeproject>

For further information please visit WWW.PHOEBE-PROJECT.EU

Project partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
EVROPSKI INSTITUT ZA OCENJEVANJE CEST - EURORAP	SI	EIRA
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL	NTUA
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	NL	TUD
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE	TUM
AIMSUN SLU	ES	AIM
POLIS AISBL	BE	POLIS
FACTUAL CONSULTING SL	ES	FC
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	UPV
OSEVEN SINGLE MEMBER PRIVATE COMPANY	EL	O7
THE FLOW LIMITED	UK	FLOW
INTERNATIONAL ROAD ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME	UK	iRAP

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AADT	Average Annual Daily Traffic
AASHTO	American Association of State Highway Official
ABM	Agent-based Modelling
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BCA	Benefit Cost Analysis
BCR	Benefit Cost Ratio
CAV	Connected and automated Vehicle
CF	Car Following
CMF	Crash Modification Factor
CPI	Crash Potential Index
CPM	Crash Prediction Model
DR	Deceleration Rate
EC	European Commission
EVT	Expected Value Theory
FSI	Fatal and Severe Injuries
FHWA	Federal Highway Administration
ITF	International Transport Forum
MC	Mode Choice
MCP	Multi Criteria Process
ML	Machine Learning
MNL	Multinomial Logit
MS	Modal Shift
OD	Origin Destination
PET	Post Encroachment Time
RUM	Random Utility
SPF	Safety Performance function
SRIP	Safer Roads Investment Plan
SRS	Star Rating Score
SSAM	Surrogate Safety Assessment Model
TC	Task Capability
TTC	Time To Collision
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The PHOEBE Framework is a methodological approach designed for cities to improve understanding of the safety implications of future changes in the transport systems, such as behavioural changes, redesign or new infrastructure, or the introduction of a new mode. To do so, it aims to bring together several existing elements including:

- Traffic simulation environments, which provide insights into how these various elements interact in virtual traffic scenarios
- Road safety assessment, which can provide objective measures of road user safety linked to speed, flow and the physical road features
- Human behaviour models which can help anticipate how road users respond in given scenarios, how people select which mode of transport to use or when/where to take a trip (the latter coming into the category of mode shift and induced demand models, which can predict consumer choices and road user flow changes), and
- Socio-economic impact assessment which can understand the health, safety, economic and environmental impacts of changes in the transport system.

Together, these elements will enable analysis on the combined effect of future changes, as well as how this will change over time.

The development of the PHOEBE Framework involves three principle aspects:

1. First is the **theoretical development**, which includes the research, where necessary, for key principles and methodology of the framework
2. Second is the **technical developments** required to ensure that the technical components of the framework have the necessary functionality to meet the framework's needs and produced the analysis required, and
3. Third are the **tools and support materials for end users** to ensure the framework can be utilised for its stated purpose.

This deliverable, which is the direct output of Task 1.1 of the project, aims to review the state-of-the-art in each component utilized in the PHOEBE Framework, and gain a deeper understanding of the needs of cities and transport planners.

The task had three distinct components:

1. **Review of the state-of-the-art** to document the body of knowledge available (in terms of both research and practice) for each component of the PHOEBE Framework to be developed, and draw conclusions about the potential implications to be taken into account in the design of this framework, in particular the methodological framework and technical components.
2. **Online stakeholder survey** to understand the needs and gaps in current practice among the stakeholders involved in the PHOEBE use cases (Athens, Valencia, West Midlands), as well as a broader groups of transport managers reachable through the wide network of contacts of the project partners.
3. **Focus group consultations** to drill more deeply into the current uses and practices of road safety assessment and microscopic simulation on urban road networks, and the extent to which they inform decision making in urban road planning and management.

The online stakeholder survey and focus group consultations captured the current gaps and needs from the perspective of transport managers and municipalities (the intended end users of the PHOEBE Framework). These are synthesised into a **user needs statement** to inform the design of the PHOEBE Framework's end-user tools and knowledge products.

Review of the state-of-the-art

The review of the state-of-the-art covered the main components of PHOEBE (i.e. road safety assessment, traffic microsimulation, human behavioural models, modal shift, induced demand, socioeconomic analysis, and data collection technologies and methodologies). It aimed to provide an overview of what exists in the body of knowledge to select appropriate tools and methods for developing the methodological framework of PHOEBE, to better understand the current research and practice, and highlight any particular considerations which should be taken into account for the development of the framework.

The review looked to both scientific and non-scientific databases, on the basis of a dedicated review guideline, which outline the types of databases, the combinations of search terms to be used as 'keywords' and the criteria for prioritizing the studies. The literature search strategy implemented for each component is documented to provide transparency and replicability of the review. Over 300 research papers and other documents were identified and reviewed.

Summary of review findings

The PHOEBE Framework aims to advance the application of traffic simulation tools and road safety assessment to enable transport planners and managers to fully understand and address the safety implications of changes in road conditions, mode choice, new modes, road user behaviours and other factors and their impacts on safety over time.

The review found that despite the significant progress achieved for conflict-based methodologies using microsimulation to assess safety such as the Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM), there are limitations including:

- There is no clear evidence on how reliable the simulated trajectories of vehicles which are used to simulate interactions (and potential conflicts) are compared to real-life trajectories.
- VRU interaction with other motorized vehicles are not included, and
- The selection of threshold values for some surrogate safety indicators is subjective.

Only a few studies have attempted to overcome these issues through proposing alternative approaches and hence further research is required. Most of the past research modelling efforts needed better evaluation of the crash data used, as well as the corresponding modelling methods followed (e.g. limited sample size, under-reporting, unreliability are noticing). Addressing this gap could lead to the development of better strategies for mitigating crash occurrence and consequences, but it would be beyond the scope of the PHOEBE project to address it in this way.

Therefore, the findings confirmed that the priorities which had been identified for the PHOEBE project, remain valid. These are:

- a) To improve the current SSAM approach by developing new methods that incorporate the trajectory data from all road user types – not just cars – and integrate it within a simulation tool in order to identify potential conflicts between all users; and
- b) To adapt safety indicators which also account for infrastructure from existing safety assessment methodologies (e.g., Star Ratings).

The review identified several well-established methodologies which represent the current state-of-the-art of how to evaluate infrastructure-related risk of a road corridor or network. These included the Star Rating

methodology as well as several purpose-specific and/or localised methods, most of which were developed using the Star Ratings method or risk factors. Apart from the iRAP Star Rating and CycleRAP methods, most existing models do not focus on VRUs or urban areas. This review therefore confirmed that the Star Ratings are an appropriate road safety assessment methodology to meet the needs of the project aims. This method incorporates individual models for VRUs, and is applicable across all regions and road types (including urban road networks).

It is an ambition of the PHOEBE project to better incorporate human factors, such as culture, social influence, attitudes toward road rule compliance, fatigue, and risk-compensating behaviours, into microscopic traffic simulation models. Microscopic simulations currently include driver behaviour models to represent car-following and lane-changing. However, these models still assume optimal driver decision-making, rather than reflect the fact that driver perception, distraction and risk taking behaviours mean that in reality, drivers can behave in very different (and less safe) ways.

Behaviour modelling faces several major limitations. Only few studies have focused on behavioural factors and almost exclusively on car drivers. They also require detailed data – which is not often available – to validate and calibrate the models which can add significantly to computational costs. The PHOEBE project presents a unique opportunity for access to large amounts of road user data which could further research and testing of behavioural models, which can in turn help calibrate micro simulation so that it can better represent realistic road user behaviours.

The choice to make a trip with a particular mode, or make the same trip but with a different mode (for example, from a private vehicle to public transport) is another human behaviour-related issue for transportation, but at the macro (network) level. Understanding modal shift and induced demand is critical in understanding the network impacts (in terms of road user flows) of changes occurring in the transport system. Modelling the Mode Choice (MC) phenomenon and forecasting the Modal Share and Modal Shift (MS) is integral to modelling travel demand.

Although modelling MC is a relatively new field, several scientific studies have been conducted, resulting in this field's exponential development in recent years. The review found that MC modelling is one of the most critical steps in travel demand modelling. It was also concluded that there is a lot of experience in developing such models for urban areas, but not for sustainable modes of transport (other than public transport), micro mobility and automated mobility. The inclusion of some new modes, particularly micro-mobility, will be essential for the PHOEBE Framework's capacity to forecast uptake of new modes of transport. There is potential to exploit other types of data, such as land use, spatial data, route planning and social networks to understand how mode choice is informed.

To advance the state-of-the-art around socio-economic impact evaluation, the PHOEBE project aims to devise a harmonised methodology for the socio-economic impact assessment of safety measures at three levels (health and safety, environmental and economic). This would support the network-level extrapolation road safety impacts, mode shift and induced demand modelling components of the PHOEBE Framework to allow informed decision making by all stakeholders.

This review highlights several approaches including cost-benefit analysis, cost-effectiveness analysis, willingness to pay method, multi-criteria processes and before-after analysis. Of these, cost-benefit analysis is the most popular method. iRAP's Star Rating model incorporates a tool for cost benefit analyses of road safety measures. However, it only considers the economic cost of fatal and serious injuries. The project will need to pair socio-economic analyses with the economic, environmental and health impacts of mode shift & induced demand at the network level.

Summary of stakeholder consultations

The [stakeholders survey questionnaire](#) is structured based on the PHOEBE Framework that includes several new metrics, models (e.g. behavioural, socioeconomic) and techniques integration (e.g. data

collection, road safety assessment, traffic microsimulation) considering factors such as human behaviour, modal shift, and improved data exploitation through machine learning methodologies. The total duration of the questionnaire is estimated at about 20-25 minutes. Consequently, the questionnaire is composed of the following sections:

1. **Warm-up questions:** provide a basic anonymous profile to better understand the background of the participants.
 2. **Behavioural models thematic questions:** Rating the importance of a large array of human behaviours that may emerge as a result of changes in transport systems and influence risk.
 3. **Data collection methods thematic questions:** Rating the importance of new trends in data collection methods, such as (indicatively) crowdsourcing, drones, social media data, etc.
 4. **Modal shift thematic questions:** Rating the importance and impact of modal shift to the transport network.
 5. **Socioeconomic models thematic questions:** Rating the importance and influence of socioeconomic parameters of the road users, such as available income, unemployment, age profiles, to the outputs and the behaviour of the transport network.
 6. **Road safety assessment thematic questions:** Rating and assessment of currently available road safety assessment methodologies to focus on infrastructure risk and enrich the other available tools with them in turn.
 7. **Traffic microsimulation thematic questions:** Rating the importance of enhancing the currently available traffic microsimulation tools.
- Closing questions:** Assessing the relevance and importance of future tools developed within PHOEBE to the daily work and professional practice of participants.

Additionally, *the focus groups sought to collect input, via a dedicated script and process, on:*

- How local authorities make decisions in the road safety domain, particularly decisions regarding management and changes to the road network, and vulnerable road users;
- If and how local authorities assess road safety risks in the infrastructure for Vulnerable Road Users;
- If and how local authorities use traffic simulation and/or induced demand modelling, particularly in the road safety domain;
- If and how local authorities access and use emerging mobility data in mobility planning and management, and particularly in Road Safety;
- What kind of capacity gaps and needs may emerge with the adoption of a framework with the overall characteristics of the PHOEBE Framework.

The *stakeholders survey was taken by 50 participants (41 from Europe) from 36 cities.*

Key messages:

The online stakeholder survey and focus group consultations captured the current gaps and needs from the perspective of transport managers and municipalities (the intended end users of the PHOEBE Framework). These are synthesised into a user needs statement to inform the design of the PHOEBE Framework's end-user tools and knowledge products.

The survey participants indicated that the following scenarios need to be prioritised: i) implementation of regulatory measures to limit speeds; ii) introducing extensive network of bicycle lanes; iii) promotion of public transport modes; iv) introduction of new transport modes; v) implementing hierarchical schemes; vi) encouraging modal shift vii) speed calming measures and viii) expansion of cycling and walking infrastructure.

Regarding the overall professional needs relevant to PHOEBE project, areas that were identified as high priority for research were:

- 1) Traffic simulation enriched with infrastructure safety information, mode shift and induced demand, and human behavioural factors
- 2) Improved accuracy of traffic simulation, and
- 3) Road assessment enriched with traffic microsimulation information and AI/ML models.

When asked about the usefulness of a potential tool for everyday tasks, the survey participants placed a high priority on the major aspects planned under the PHOEBE project, namely traffic simulation enriched with infrastructure safety information, modal shift information, road assessment enhanced with AI/ML models. It is interesting to note that the respondents from the PHOEBE use case locations in Athens, Valencia and West Midlands revealed some variability among the needs and priorities, supporting the notion that the PHOEBE Framework needs to be able to be flexible enough to address different needs.

The **focus groups gathered 19 participants from 15 different cities.**

Key messages:

- **Road Safety Understanding**, which influences many current practices and challenges faced by practitioners. Professionals talked about the different ways and perspectives of road safety, with “issues on how we approach road safety”.
 - **Comprehensive cost-benefit analysis** should bring visibility to the social costs and the economic and health benefits
 - **Shift in society as regards road safety perceptions**; crashes should not be seen as a “normal” part of participating in traffic.
- **Organisational structures** (knowledge and practices) differ among cities, and there is need to remove the ‘silos’ between different types of transport professionals, especially with respect to safety.
 - **Main deficiencies in the current tools** are the limited incorporation of modal shift options (especially with new emerging mobility solutions) and the
 - **VRUs and new mobilities** need to be integrated not only in tools but also within the organizational knowledge and practice.
- **Organisational resources and capabilities**, including the data aspect, will influence the possible implementation of new frameworks within these authorities and organisations.
 - The new emerging data sources are costly to collect and process, and the **lack of human resources with relevant training and knowledge** may be a barrier in the exploitation of these new data.
- **Concept vs reality**: a clearer understanding is needed of the link between design guidelines and their actual safety impacts, and the validity of the respective modelling outputs.

The results of the stakeholders survey and the focus groups are summarized in the form of a **Needs Statement** on three elements: i) strategic goals; ii) decision support and daily practice; and iii) methodological needs.

Conclusions

On the basis of stakeholders’ needs, as well as the in-depth review of the scientific and grey literature over the PHOEBE Framework components, a conceptual design of the PHOEBE methodological framework will be drafted on the basis of the following design principles:

- i) **Fusion of road assessment and traffic simulation**: the strong inter-relationship between traffic simulation and road safety assessment is at the core of the PHOEBE methodology.
- ii) Incorporation of **human behaviour models** to enhance the credibility of traffic simulation and enrich the predictions of road safety outcomes

- iii) **Mode choice and modal shift models are the first step** to be taken in order to simulate traffic and safety impacts.
- iv) **Socio-economic impacts are the final outcomes** to be estimated from the traffic and safety outputs of the framework.
- v) **The new emerging data sources are a vertical dimension** that will enhance the predictive and explanatory power of all components of the framework.

1 Purpose of the deliverable

1.1 Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

This deliverable, which is the direct output of Task 1.1 of the project, aims to review the state-of-the-art in each component utilised in the PHOEBE Framework and gain a deeper understanding of the needs of cities and transport planners.

First, a literature review highlights the gaps (in terms of both research and practice) in the existing methodologies and technologies that are relevant to PHOEBE and sheds more light on the innovation and significance of PHOEBE in how it goes beyond the state-of-the-art. The literature reviews are documented by the respective technical partners (NTUA and iRAP for road safety assessment methodologies and tools, AIMSUN for traffic simulation software and models, TUD for human behavioural models, TUM for mode shift and induced demand and socio-economic models, and FLOOW for data collection and analytics).

Second, a needs statement is developed based on stakeholder consultations with the potential end-users of the PHOEBE Framework. The current gaps and needs from the perspective of transport managers and municipalities (the intended end users of the PHOEBE Framework) are captured in a needs statement to inform the design of the PHOEBE Framework. This was done via interviews and surveys with stakeholders involved in use case demonstrations (led by NTUA, FC, UPV and FLOOW), as well as with the POLIS stakeholder group and through the EuroRAP networks (led by POLIS and EIRA). The implications of these findings on the development the methodological framework in PHOEBE are then discussed.

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled. Table 1.1 below shows the distribution of work among partners in this deliverable.

Role	Who
Drafting the deliverable, coordinating the literature reviews, consolidating contributions from all partners, reviewing state-of-the-art in behavioural models, writing the conclusions	TUD
Leading the stakeholder surveys, drafting the results of stakeholder surveys, reviewing state-of-the-art in road safety assessment	NTUA
Reviewing state-of-the-art in modal shift and socio-economic analysis	TUM
Reviewing state-of-the-art in road safety assessment and emerging data collection tools and methods, contributing to the focus groups notetaking, reviewing the stakeholders' survey questionnaire	iRAP
Reviewing state-of-the-art in traffic microsimulation	AIM
Reviewing state-of-the-art in emerging data collection tools and methods	FLOOW
Designing and implementing focus groups, drafting the results of focus groups	POLIS

Table 1-1 Contributions of PHOEBE partners to the deliverable

1.2 Intended audience

The intended audience of this deliverable is the PHOEBE project partners involved in the tasks of WP1 – Methodology, the transport managers and municipalities involved in the PHOEBE use cases, and broader stakeholder groups involved in urban transport and safety management, namely those of the POLIS, EuroRAP and EIRA networks.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable and links with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable will inform the selection of tools and models to be utilized and developed for the PHOEBE Framework by the respective technical partners. Outputs will directly inform the proposition of dynamic risk assessment and socio-economic analysis methodologies (Tasks 1.2 and 1.3) and the specification of the technical aspects to be developed for demonstration of the PHOEBE Framework (Task 1.4).

The deliverable is structured into six chapters as follows:

- Chapter 1 outlines the purpose and aims of Task 1.1
- Chapter 2 describes the methodology used for the literature review and for the identification of end-user needs
- Chapter 3 provides the findings of the literature review, including existing gaps and implications for PHOEBE Framework
- Chapter 4 provides the findings from stakeholder surveys and focus groups, and
- Chapter 5 provides the overall conclusions from the state-of-the-art review and the end-user needs, and the implications for PHOEBE's theoretical and technical aspects and end-user tools and support materials.

2 Methodology

In this chapter, the methodology implemented in PHOEBE for the purposes of achieving the objectives of this deliverable is described. The methodology has three distinct components:

1. **Review of the state-of-the-art** to document the body of knowledge available for each component of the predictive safety assessment framework to be developed, and draw conclusions about the potential implications to be taken into account in the design of this framework.
2. **Online stakeholders' survey** to understand the needs and gaps in current practice among the stakeholders involved in the PHOEBE use cases (Athens, Valencia, West Midlands), as well as broader groups of transport managers reachable through the wide network of contacts of the project partners. For that purpose, a dedicated on-line survey was designed and dispatched.
3. **Focus groups consultation** to drill more deeply into the current practices of road safety assessment in urban areas and the use of microsimulation therein, and the extent to which they inform decision making in urban road planning and management.

The synthesis of the results of these components were used to draft a **user needs statement** and the clear identification of gaps in terms of both scientific knowledge and professional practice, eventually informing the development of the PHOEBE predictive assessment framework methodology. In the following sections, the specific methodological and design approaches per component are described in detail.

2.1 Literature review of the state-of-the-art

The state-of-the-art in the main components of PHOEBE (i.e. road safety assessment, traffic microsimulation, human behavioural models, modal shift, induced demand, socioeconomic analysis, and data collection technologies and methodologies) were reviewed in order to highlight the gaps (from academic and from road managers perspectives). The main purpose of the literature review was to provide an overview of what exists in the body of knowledge in order to select appropriate tools and methods for developing the methodological framework of PHOEBE.

To achieve the above objectives, the state-of-the-art was reviewed for each component of PHOEBE from academic and grey literature on the basis of a dedicated review guideline document (see Annex A). The following search engines are used for the reviews:

- Google scholar, Scopus for academic literature
- Google for grey literature (World Bank, ITF, iRAP, etc.)
- CORDIS website for previous European projects

Since each component in PHOEBE is a broad topic by and of itself, the reviews are narrowed down to the intersection of the topics e.g. road safety assessment **and** traffic microsimulation. Since there are a number of reviews about the PHOEBE components available, priority was given to recent review articles or documents. The following search strategy and selection criteria are applied for the purpose of the review in this deliverable:

- Keyword #1 [example: road safety assessment]
- Keyword #1 AND Keyword #2 [example: road safety assessment AND traffic microsimulation]
- Keyword #3 [example: human behaviour]
- Keyword #3 AND Keyword #1 [example: road safety assessment AND human behaviour]

- Keyword #3 AND Keyword #1 AND Keyword #2 [example: road safety assessment AND human behaviour AND traffic microsimulation]

The studies were selected based on the type of study, number of ‘hits’, publication year, reputation of the academic journal, and popularity of the project.

For quality assurance purposes, the literature around different topics in PHOEBE was reviewed in pairs of partners. For each subject, two partners were paired to search and select the studies separately, which was followed by a ‘consensus’ meeting for the final sources selected to be included in the review. The table below shows the topics for literature review and the distribution of partners across those topics:

Paired partners	Review topic
AIM and TUM	Review of the existing traffic micro-simulation methods and tools
iRAP and NTUA	Review of the existing road safety assessment methodologies
TUD and NTUA	Review of the existing behavioural models (focus on VRUs)
TUM and TUD	Review of the existing socio-economic analysis and modal shift modelling
FLOWW and iRAP	Review of the existing and emerging data collection tools and methods

Table 2-1 Distribution of topics

The relevant studies were stored in a virtual space that is shared among all partners. These studies were all documented in a shared table with title, author etc. and tags (corresponding with the topic of that study within the literature review) for each selected study.

2.1.1 Literature search strategies

The literature review strategies employed by each set of partners to identify appropriate literature to review is described below. In total, 325 papers were identified and reviewed.

2.1.1.1 Traffic micro-simulation methods and tools

The literature search strategy related to traffic micro-simulation methods and too started with a first search in Scopus for academic literature of the following keywords: “microsimulation”, “traffic” and “safety”. This produced a total of 410 hits. The same search was done using Google Scholar but, in this case, more than 19,500 results were found. At this stage, it was necessary to narrow down the Google Scholar search and further concept were added to the previous three keywords in the review. The first main building blocks of microscopic simulation models are ‘car-following’ models and ‘lane-changing’ models, but in this case paying an extra attention into ‘safety’ for microsimulation. Therefore, another search was done using these extra words, first ‘lane-changing’ resulting in 6,200 hits and second ‘car-following’ resulting in 7,810 hits.

Another search was done to review the literature related to the impact analysis on vulnerable road users. In this case, ‘pedestrian modelling’ was also added as an extra keyword for the search, resulting in a total of 307 hits (considering the three base keywords and this extra one). The keywords ‘cyclist modelling’ and ‘bicycle’ were also added in another search, resulting in 2,080 hits.

The general search engine Google was also used to search for any ‘grey’ literature that were not included in Google Scholar or Scopus. The reviewers have also included approaches/results or even just references from a few European projects that have already finished or are still on-going.

As observed, the number of papers found in the different searches were still too high. Therefore, in this case, a non-systematic review was done, by picking some of the most relevant papers from the reviewers' criterion. On top of the previous while reviewing papers, some interesting references appeared. Thus, some papers were not selected by a keyword strategy but rather from a 'snowballing' from existing papers. Finally, some known references by the reviewing team were added as well. As a result of this approach a total of 67 papers have been reviewed. A summary of the literature search strategy (keywords and Boolean operators) is included in the Table 3.2.

Keyword (OR)	Boolean operator	Keyword	Boolean operator	Keyword
Traffic	AND	Microsimulation	AND	Safety
Car-following		OR		Safety
Lane-changing		Microscopic		assessment
Car-following AND human factors		simulation		
Lane-changing AND human factors				
Vulnerable Road Users				
Pedestrian modelling				
Cyclist modelling				
Bicycle				
Automated vehicles				

Table 2-2 Group of keywords for the literature search

2.1.1.2 Road safety assessment

The literature search related to the existing road safety assessment methodologies used the search engines Scopus, Google Scholar and the CORDIS website for European projects. The search was conducted in two parts. The first aimed to identify existing road safety assessment methods focused on infrastructure risk. Since road safety assessment is a broad but consolidated topic, the search focuses on review papers that could speed up the review process. Therefore, "Road safety assessment" or "road risk assessment" plus "infrastructure" plus "review" were the keywords used. We selected studies published from 2018-2023; the search was performed by the end of January 2023. Based on these criteria, the Scopus search returned 54 hits, while Google Scholar had 83 hits. Titles and abstracts of these hits were reviewed. For the CORDIS research, three projects were identified as potential sources of information for PHOEBE. The papers and projects selected are discussed in the results.

The second search focused on the interaction among risk assessments and simulation. The searches on Scopus and Google Scholar returned 126 hits. Of these, 40 records were excluded after reviewing both titles and abstracts and it was found that did not meet the inclusion criteria. In addition, four studies were discarded because the full text was not available and three additional papers were not in English. Therefore, the full-text of the remaining 79 records was examined in more detail and 57 studies were found to meet the criteria to be included in the systematic review. Two relevant studies were also added by checking the references of the identified papers and searching for studies that have cited them, resulting in 59 papers in total.

2.1.1.3 Human behaviour models

The previous studies around behavioural models in transport science are extensive. A lot of these studies are related to traffic psychology and stem from psychological and behavioural science. However, and for the purpose of PHOEBE, the literature review around behavioural models in PHOEBE is limited to those studies that focused on behavioural models for the purpose of road safety in traffic microsimulation. In addition, road user (human) behaviour and human factors have been used in the transport science literature interchangeably. Therefore, the literature search included the latter term as well. More specifically, the search strategy (keywords and Boolean operators) for behavioural models is as in the Table 3.7.

Keyword	Boolean operator	Keyword	Boolean operator	Keyword
Behavioural (behavioural) model Human behaviour (behaviour) Human factors Driver behaviour (behaviour) Pedestrian behaviour (behaviour) Cyclist (cycling) (bicycle) behaviour (behaviour)	AND	Traffic Microsimulation	AND	Safety Surrogate safety Safety assessment

Table 2-3 Literature review search strategy for behavioural models in PHOEBE

The above keywords and Boolean operators were used in Google Scholar and Scopus to find relevant academic studies. In doing so, review articles were prioritized for extracting key studies in this field and cross referencing. In addition, the same search strategy was used to find relevant reports and European projects in CORDIS. Finally, the same search strategy was used in Google to find the relevant “grey” literature from universal organizations such as the World Bank, ITF, and iRAP.

The above search resulted in a total of about 200 academic articles among which around 50 articles were selected based on their title, abstract, number of citations and journal reputation. After carefully screening the main text of these 50 articles, only 26 articles were found to be relevant to PHOEBE and thus they were reviewed in detail. In addition, the search resulted in a total of 25 European projects and reports, among which 4 were selected as relevant to PHOEBE. No grey literature was found around behavioural models in traffic microsimulation.

2.1.1.4 Modal shift

Modelling the Mode Choice (MC) phenomenon and forecasting the Modal Share and Modal Shift (MS) is integral to modelling travel demand. It acts as a basis for multiple decisions made by policymakers. Although modelling MC is a relatively new field, several scientific studies have been conducted, resulting in this field's exponential development. A basis for conducting a structured literature search in this domain is based on a review question mentioned below (Atkinson & Cipriani, 2018):

What are the commonly used modal shift forecasting methods?

The review question was a basis for generating the relevant keywords for a structured literature search. The chosen keywords are:

Mode choice, Model, Random Utility, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Modal Shift, Passenger Transport

Boolean operators were used to combine these keywords to generate consistent expressions conforming to the review questions. These expressions were used to search for academic studies and grey literature in Scopus and Google scholar. The search expressions are listed below:

Google Scholar: mode choice model * "random utility" "machine learning" "artificial intelligence" -freight

Scopus: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((mod*) AND (choice OR shift) AND (model* OR forecast*) AND (method*) AND (passenger AND transport*) AND ((machine AND learn*) OR (random AND utility) OR (artificial AND intelligence)))

The search was carried out on 6th March 2023. The Scopus database rendered 51 hits, whereas the Google Scholar yielded 420 hits. The search was followed by developing selection criteria mentioned below to filter out the relevant studies. The filtering criteria are:

- Studies in peer-reviewed journals OR conference proceedings OR scientific project reports.
- Studies conducted in English OR German.
- Studies investigating the MC modelling methodologies OR MS forecasting methodologies.

Finally, 50 relevant studies were chosen to conduct the literature review.

2.1.1.5 Induce demand

The state-of-the-art review of induced demand modelling starts by briefly introducing the topic. According to Wikipedia, induced demand, or latent or generated demand, is the phenomenon that occurs or appears with the increase in supply. It results in a decline in price and an increase in consumption. In traffic and transportation, induced travel demand is interpreted as an increase in the travel demand i.e., the number of trips due to improvements in the transport supply systems, e.g., road infrastructure improvement and capacity increase (Litman, 2017). These definitions are utilised to develop a review question as a foundation for the literature search related to the induced demand modelling. The review question is:

- What is induced travel demand, and how is it modelled?

Based on the review question, relevant keywords are mapped, which are used to conduct the literature search. The keywords are:

Induced travel demand, Latent travel demand, congestion, infrastructure, rebound, model, modelling.

These keywords are combined with boolean operators to generate consistent expressions matching the review question. These expressions are used to search for the academic and grey literature in the Google Scholar database. The search expressions are as follows:

Google Scholar: *model * congestion infrastructure rebound "induced travel demand" OR "latent travel demand"*

The search was carried out on 6th March 2023. The Google Scholar database generated 155 hits. The search was followed by developing selection criteria mentioned below to filter out the relevant studies. The filtering criteria are:

- Studies in peer-reviewed journals **OR** conference proceedings **OR** scientific project reports.
- Studies conducted in English **OR** German.
- Studies which investigate and appraise the socio-economic impacts of road safety measures.

Finally, 23 relevant studies are chosen to conduct the literature review. The studies common to the travel demand modelling are not chosen explicitly as they are already considered in the review of the mode choice modelling (session 2.1.1.4).

2.1.1.6 Socio-economic analysis

The state-of-the-art review starts with the development of a literature search strategy. The terms "Socioeconomics" and "Socio-economic assessment or analysis" are formally defined as a basis of the strategy development.

According to Hellmich (2017), socioeconomics is an interdisciplinary field of study that simultaneously focuses on the interdependencies between society's economic and social factors. It also seeks to provide

an in-depth understanding (both qualitative and quantitative) of the well-being of individuals, communities, and societies (Hellmich, 2017).

According to ECHA (2008), the socio-economic assessment or analysis is a well-established approach for weighing the pros and cons of applying an action to society (ECHA, 2008).

These definitions are utilised in developing the review question relevant to carry out the literature search of the existing socio-economic methods. The review question relevant to this section is as follows:

- What are the standard qualitative and quantitative methods to conduct socio-economic analyses?

Based on the review question above, relevant keywords were identified, which are used to conduct the literature search. The keywords are:

Socioeconomic, impact, assessment, health, environment, economic, road, safety, infrastructure, cost-benefit analysis, before-after analysis,

Boolean operators combined these keywords to generate consistent expressions conforming to the review questions. These expressions were used to search for academic studies and grey literature in Scopus and Google scholar. The search expressions are listed below:

Scopus: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((socioeconomic* AND (analysis OR impact OR assessment OR method*)) AND (road AND safety AND measure*) AND NOT freight)

Google Scholar: socioeconomic* analysis OR impact OR assessment OR method* OR quantitative OR qualitative "road safety measure*" -freight

The search was carried out on 6th March 2023. The Scopus database rendered 103 hits, whereas Google Scholar generated 285 hits. The search was followed by developing selection criteria mentioned below to filter out the relevant studies. The filtering criteria are:

- Studies in peer-reviewed journals OR conference proceedings OR scientific project reports.
- Studies conducted in English OR German.
- Studies which investigate and appraise the socio-economic impacts of road safety measures.

Finally, 43 relevant studies are chosen to conduct the literature review.

2.1.1.7 Data collection tools and methods

To support a SoA systematic search related to data gathering and collection methodologies an initial exploratory and later finalised strategy was deployed. This strategy was used on both google scholar and also Scopus. The exploratory search phase aimed simply to identify candidate query terms of strong relevance to the target domain and the areas of data gathering and collection methods. The following series of terms were identified to focus query returns within the domain of interest:

- "Road Assessment"
- "Road Safety"
- "Traffic Management"
- "Vehicle Safety"
- "Vulnerable Road User"
- "Telematics"
- "Traffic Model"

- "Road Risk"
- "Road Accident"

It was found that any papers of potential interest typically used only one of the above terms without clear standardisation of any singular domain language for the area. This required search for each of these terms to ensure search returns would be relevant to the field of study by the various terms used in literature. The following search term was used to focus data collation into any of these potential interest areas:

"Road Assessment"|"Road Safety"|"Traffic Management"|"Vehicle Safety"|"Vulnerable Road User"|"Telematics"|"Traffic Model"|"Road Risk"|"Road Accident"

This search by itself found significant potential papers (Google ~415,000 search returns, Scopus 70,490 search returns). Majority papers were constrained to the target domain however they often had little to do with the specific target of data gathering or collection methodologies. To further refine this list additional key terms were explored that could help focus results to the areas of data collation and gathering methodologies. Various key terms were explored but only kept if finding valid papers related to data collation and gathering in the first 50 search returns. This generated a longer list of key terms aiming to focus search returns, those supporting the SoA search are detailed below:

- "Data gathering"
- "Data collation"
- "Data collection"
- "Traffic data"
- "Big Data"
- "Crowd-Sourcing"
- "Intelligent Transportation System"
- "Sensor Network Data"
- "Internet of Things"
- "Data Driven"
- "Road Data"
- "Transport Network Data"
- "Crash data"
- "Accident Data"

Each of these terms was used in combination with queries like the following:

- "Data gathering"AND "Road Assessment"|"Road Safety"|"Traffic Management"|"Vehicle Safety"|"Vulnerable Road User"|"Telematics"|"Traffic Model"|"Road Risk"|"Road Accident"
- "Data collation"AND "Road Assessment"|"Road Safety"|"Traffic Management"|"Vehicle Safety"|"Vulnerable Road User"|"Telematics"|"Traffic Model"|"Road Risk"|"Road Accident"
- Etc.

The results of these searches are now detailed. The results for these searches for Google are detailed in the below table.

Base Term	Search hits	Notes on term usage
<no base term>	~415,000	Very wide returns - although linked to the target area search results have low relevance without base term addition to focus on data gathering or collection methodologies.
"Data gathering"	~15,400	Reasonable returns albeit many papers with only surface level aspects of data gathering methodologies.
"Data collation"	396	Focused returns.
"Data collection"	~96,700	Many returns but with some of relevance
"Traffic data"	~22,500	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include many irrelevant papers also in the search returns.
"Big Data"	~38,500	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Crowd-Sourcing"	3130	More focused returns.
"Intelligent Transportation System"	~18,900	The returns although having some papers of relevance include wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Sensor Network Data"	589	Focused results some of relevance
"Internet of Things"	~35,100	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include many irrelevant papers also in the search returns.
"Data Driven"	~23,000	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Road Data"	5,230	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Transport Network Data"	355	More focused returns.
"Crash data"	~18,000	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Accident Data"	~18,200	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.

Table 2-4 Literature review search strategy for data collection methodologies and technologies in Google

Given the large number of search returns via google scholar a complete review of all search returns was not possible. Analysis instead sought to evaluate the first 200 papers returned from each search to review from title and abstract snippet potential relevance for the project. This found in total 52 papers highlighted for potential relevance to the SoA review of which:

- 8 were review papers
 - 2 very high value review papers of relevance.

- 4 moderate value review papers of relevance.
- 2 lesser value review papers of lower relevance.
- 43 academic journal or conference papers.
 - 25 moderate value papers
 - 18 lesser value (due to age or low coverage of the SoA interest area)
- 1 grey literature report.
 - 1 moderate value to SoA review.

Base Term	Search hits	Notes on term usage
<no base term>	70,490	Very wide returns - although linked to the target area search results have low relevance without base term addition to focus on data gathering or collection methodologies.
"Data gathering"	68	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Data collation"	0	No search returns
"Data collection"	1,162	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Traffic data"	1,848	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Big Data"	841	More focused returns.
"Crowd-Sourcing"	21	Low search returns
"Intelligent Transportation System"	2,687	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Sensor Network Data"	2	Minimal search returns
"Internet of Things"	1,420	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Data Driven"	550	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Road Data"	62	Low search returns
"Transport Network Data"	1	Minimal search returns
"Crash data"	589	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.
"Accident Data"	813	The returns, although having some papers of relevance include very wide irrelevant papers in the search returns.

Table 2-5 Literature review search strategy for data collection methodologies and technologies in Scopus

A total of 1449 were duplicated and eliminated of the final list resulting in 8,614 papers. In order to reduce the number of papers, we only consider those published after 2018, reducing the number of papers to 4,472. The title of these papers were reviewed to identify the ones relevant to PHOEBE literature review.

2.2 Stakeholders survey

2.2.1 Purpose of the survey

PHOEBE aims to holistically improve road safety prediction tools by assessing the established and proven traffic simulation tools and road safety assessment methods, with a view to subsequently enhancing these tools in light of new data sources and analytical methods. It is critically important that the outputs of PHOEBE are comprehensible and usable for its target end-users. This will ensure outcomes for stakeholders are valuable and lead to a real and observable impact in reducing the incidence of crashes in urban areas and mitigating their consequences. A dedicated on-line survey was designed in order to review the needs and gaps in current practice among those local stakeholders that are identified as hands-on practitioners, in order to establish where PHOEBE can produce the most impact. The aim of the questionnaire was to:

- Help inform the methodology of the PHOEBE Framework
- Guide the selection of scenarios to be modelled
- Identify key outputs and analysis which will support transport policy and safety objectives

2.2.2 Survey design

The questionnaire was structured based on the PHOEBE Framework that includes several new metrics, models (e.g. behavioural, socioeconomic) and techniques integration (e.g. data collection, road safety assessment, traffic microsimulation) considering factors such as human behaviour, modal shift, and improved data exploitation through machine learning methodologies. It was composed of the following sections that correspond to the domains selected along with warm-up and closing questions:

1. **Warm-up questions:** These questions aim to ease the participants into the questionnaire and to have them provide a basic anonymous profile to better understand the background of the audience and to augment the value of answers to the subsequent thematic questions.
2. **Behavioural models thematic questions:** PHOEBE will examine a large array of human behaviours that may emerge as a result of changes in transport systems and will ultimately influence risk. Some examples of these behaviours are mobile phone distraction, speeding, fatigue, sleepiness, illegal crossing, non-compliance with dedicated bicycle lanes, and risk compensation. While individual characteristics such as demographics, attitudes, experiences and risk profiles of road users underlie these behaviours, research has shown that the design of transport systems promotes these behaviours too. Therefore, this group of questions concerns the integration of human behaviours into the various utilised tools for decision making in the transport sector.
3. **Data collection methods thematic questions:** PHOEBE will take into account new trends in data collection methods, such as (indicatively) crowdsourcing, drones, social media data etc. This group of questions concerns the integration of the new data collection methods into the various utilised tools.
4. **Modal shift thematic questions:** PHOEBE will investigate the influence and impact of modal shift to the transport network. In other words, the change of shares of each mode and the effects it induces on road safety and traffic operations are going to be examined. These phenomena can refer, for instance, to a positive modal shift from private vehicles to greener public transport or active travel such as walking or cycling. This group of questions concerns the integration of the modal shift effects into the various utilised tools.
5. **Socioeconomic models thematic questions:** PHOEBE will also investigate the influence of socioeconomic parameters of the road users, such as available income, unemployment, age profiles,

to the outputs and the behaviour of the transport network. This group of questions concerns the integration of the socioeconomic parameters into the various utilised tools.

6. **Road safety assessment thematic questions:** PHOEBE will enhance certain currently available road safety assessment methodologies to focus on infrastructure risk and enrich the other available tools with them in turn. Therefore, this group of questions concerns the integration of infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies into the other utilised tools.
7. **Traffic microsimulation thematic questions:** PHOEBE will enhance certain currently available traffic microsimulation tools and enrich the other available tools with them in turn. Therefore, this group of questions concerns the integration of traffic microsimulation into the other utilised tools.
8. **Closing questions:** These questions aim to gauge the relevance and importance of future tools developed within PHOEBE to the daily work and professional practice of participants.

The questionnaire was created on Google Forms and can be found in Annex C: Stakeholders survey structure. The total duration of the questionnaire was estimated to take participants about 20-25 minutes.

2.3 Focus groups

The PHOEBE is developing a new road safety framework providing local officials and professionals with new methods and tools to assess risk and make informed decisions. Special attention was therefore given to the organisational context in which these new solutions will be used. Using this framework will most likely require local authorities and professionals to possess (or acquire) certain capabilities.

While some components of an administration's capacity or daily practices may be observed as objective facts, other components, of a more subjective nature are best researched through qualitative methods. Focus groups are one such method which can be used for a more in-depth assessment, letting professionals express opinions more flexibly and openly. Focus groups provide a safe environment for professionals to share and exchange, allowing to project team to build a picture of the current professional practices of road safety and understand how the framework being developed can be integrated into future practices.

Accordingly, the focus groups consultation was introduced as an additional method within PHOEBE Task 1.1, in order to achieve the following objectives:

1. To learn about potential gaps and needs at the organisational level that should be considered in the development of the PHOEBE Framework.
2. To collect qualitative information in the form of personal experiences, perceptions, and opinions, from transport professionals. These inputs will address the research questions directly, or enable PHOEBE to deduce the implications for the research questions.
3. To collect input on:
 - a. How local authorities make decisions in the road safety domain, particularly decisions regarding management and changes to the road network, and vulnerable road users;
 - b. If and how local authorities assess road safety risks in the infrastructure for vulnerable road users, particularly people walking, cycling, and using e-scooters;
 - c. If and how local authorities use traffic simulation and/or induced demand modelling, particularly in the road safety domain;
 - d. If and how local authorities access and use emerging mobility data in mobility planning and management, and particularly in road safety;
 - e. What kind of capacity gaps and needs may emerge with the adoption of a framework with the overall characteristics of the PHOEBE Framework.

2.3.1 Focus group recruitment, facilitation and reporting

A target group was identified to appropriately answer the above-mentioned questions and fulfil the objectives set for the focus groups. This target group represented the current professionals in the transport planning, traffic management and road safety sectors, including those working *within* and *for* public authorities. The following criteria were used:

- a) Professionals working for local authorities in the transport sector;
- b) At least two years of experience in transport planning OR traffic management OR road safety;
- c) Some present OR past experience in the use of traffic simulation (not necessarily as a modeller).

POLIS used its network, and especially the network from the Road Safety Working Group, to reach out to professionals and recruit participants. POLIS Road Safety Working Group contacts include POLIS members and non-POLIS members that work in Europe and beyond, covering a considerable variety of professionals working in different aspects of road safety and with good geographical coverage.

Prospective participants were offered around six different timeslots to choose from. The focus dates and times are shown in Table 2.2. The focus group sessions were conducted online with a duration of 1h30m and English being the primary language and no more than six participants per session. Each session had one facilitator and two note-takers. Debriefing sessions took place right after all participants logged off the online meeting. The debriefing sessions included (1) overall impressions of the session, (2) highlights of the discussion with particular relevance for the research goals, (3) prioritisation or further exploration of specific topics or angles in subsequent sessions, (4) assessment of the facilitation and (5) eventual adjustments to the script, namely in terms of group dynamics and teamwork. Facilitation was done by the POLIS Road Safety Working Group coordinator, and POLIS and iRAP did notetaking.

In total, POLIS conducted five focus groups, with 19 participants from 11 different countries and 15 different cities.

Focus group participants were invited to participate under the following privacy conditions:

- a) The report and any other material to be disseminated beyond the strict circle of PHOEBE partners involved and will not mention their names and institutions;
- b) Their inputs may be quoted *ipsis verbis*, but neither the content nor the attribution will be made in a way that can enable identification of the author or institution.

Following this privacy commitment, the notes and the sound or video recordings taken of the focus group sessions are being stored in password-protected storage (as detailed in project PHOEBE's data management plan D7.2 and data registers D1.2), and accessed and used exclusively for this project. The sound and video recordings will be eliminated after the full conclusion of WP1, including approval of respective deliverables by the European Commission's project officer.

Participants	Country	10.Feb - 11h00 to 12h30	15 Feb - 11h00 to 12h30	15 Feb- 14h00 to 15h30	17.Feb - 11h00 to 12h30	20.Feb - 15h30 to 17h00
P01	USA	-	-	-	-	1
P02	Portugal	1	-	-	-	-
P03	Japan	1	-	-	-	-
P04	Mexico	-	-	1	-	-
P05	Spain	1	-	-	-	-
P06	Norway	-	1	-	-	-
P07	Portugal	-	-	-	1	-
P08	Latvia	-	1	-	-	-
P09	Portugal	-	-	1	-	-
P10	Portugal	-	-	-	-	1
P11	Portugal	-	1	-	-	-
P12	Netherlands	-	-	1	-	-
P13	Portugal	1	-	-	-	-
P14	Germany	1	-	-	-	-
P15	Poland	-	1	-	-	-
P16	Portugal	-	-	-	1	-
P17	Portugal	-	-	-	1	-
P18	Israel	-	-	1	-	-
P19	Germany	-	-	-	1	-

Table 2-6. Focus group characteristics (country of origin, date and time)

2.3.2 Script

The focus groups followed a script that was developed to address the objectives described above and in coherence with the target group.

Partners from WP1 provided input and feedback to the script beforehand. Nonetheless, after each focus group and debriefing session, necessary adjustments or made to improve the facilitation of the focus groups and the discussion. The final detailed script is in Annex E: Focus group script

Below are the main questions from the focus groups:

Q1 - What's the importance of Road Safety for the work you're doing?

- How is it important?
- If it should be important but isn't – why is that?
- What kind of decisions are made

- Balancing of safety with other concerns (e.g., congestion)
- The role of political power, decisions

Q2 - Several decisions can have an impact on Road Safety. A direct or indirect impact. A positive or negative impact. Special decisions, but also everyday decisions. Decisions made by you – and also by your colleagues and leaders.

You've certainly seen other people (colleagues, political leaders, clients) make those types of decision. What are the issues they usually consider as important in those decisions?

- Concerns of others: cost, congestion, political pressure
- Types of decisions made
- User behaviour
- Method – description, improvement, needs to improve
- Transposition of the method to the scale of the organisation

Q3 - People walking, cycling, or using e-scooters are usually called “vulnerable road users”. Because they are considered to be at a higher risk than car drivers.

How do you evaluate the risk for these vulnerable road users?

- Practices of the OTHERS inside organisation
- Role of infrastructure on behaviour
- Traffic volumes, Speed limits, Practiced speed
- Role of infrastructure on behaviour
- Methods to assess risk
- What kind of risky behaviours are they interested in?
- Behavioural factors that affect road safety

Q4 – Some local authorities use traffic simulation to support transport planning or management. The use of traffic simulation software implies building a digital model of reality, introducing traffic data, and seeing what are the implications that some changes may have on traffic behaviour. The simulation produces results – indicating, for example, if there will be more or less traffic congestion, how traffic will be redistributed, etc.

Imagine you could order a new traffic simulation software. You could order what types of results this software would provide. What types of results would be useful for people working on Road Safety?

- Used, yes or no? Would like to? What could help YOU use it?
- Did you find it practical? Did you find it useful?
- What are the obstacles to using it – or using it more?
- Practical difficulties with using traffic simulation
- Organisational difficulties – staff, staff time, budget, IT, data

Q5 - In the past few years several new mobility services arrived on our streets. Digital technology and geolocation play an important role. These services generate large amounts of digital data. These data can be useful for mobility planning or management.

Do you think these data can be useful for Road Safety? How?

- Other types and sources of data

- Difficulties in acquiring data
- Internal organisational barriers to access or use of the data
- Lack of technical skills (knowledge, experience)
- Lack of means (software, etc.)

Q6 – We are working on a project that will bring together new techniques, new data sources, and new knowledge to advance Road Safety. Implementing a new method and tools of this kind in an organisation is usually a challenge. We're looking for the best ways to make it easy for local authorities and their professionals to adopt these solutions. Imagine we were to bring to your organisation [or a public authority you have worked for or with] a new method and tool to support decisions affecting Road Safety. Imagine this new method and tool brings together new techniques, new data sources, and new knowledge.

What kind of difficulties would you expect in your organisation?

- What could help overcome those difficulties?
- What advice do you have for us?
- Request for details about the framework – what are they asking?
- Practical advice
- Previous difficulties – own or of OTHERS

3 Review of the State of the Art

The main components of the PHOEBE Framework are road safety assessment, traffic microsimulation, human behavioural models, modal shift, induced demand, socioeconomic analysis, and data collection technologies and methodologies. During Task 1.1 the state-of-the-art for each of these components was reviewed. This chapter presents the findings of this review for each component. The chapter concludes with a discussion and key considerations arising from the reviews.

3.1 Traffic simulation, human behaviour and road safety assessment

Traffic microsimulation is the name of the technique known for reproducing the behaviour of each single vehicle in the traffic flow. This is done by simulating each vehicle trajectory with a high level of detail, this includes speed, acceleration, current lane, route, etc. This means that microsimulation is very complex, being many different models involved into the simulation. As a result, there is the need to narrow down the review to the most critical aspects for safety in microsimulation. For PHOEBE project the focus will be on:

1. The vehicle dynamics within the lane such as car-following behaviours, but also between lanes such as lane-changing behaviours and how safe/unsafe behaviour is incorporated in these models,
2. How vulnerable road users are currently modelled and considered in microsimulation tools and their interaction with other non-motorized and motorized traffic at network level, and
3. Network-level safety assessment approaches that are considered/integrated on microsimulation tools (if exist).

3.1.1 Existing microsimulation tools

There are many software packages that provide off-the-shelf solutions with all the required models integrated in one solution. Barcelo (2010) summarizes many traffic simulation tools available on the market. The microsimulation ones presented are Aimsun, SUMO, VISSIM, AVENUE, Paramics, MITSIMLab and DRACULA. Other tools also exist that were not included in Barcelo (2010) as they were not developed yet like MATsim.

What all these tools have in common is that they are designed in a way that vehicles always respect distances to other vehicles and cannot ever crash. This implies that available traffic simulator tools are designed to be safe by nature. The following sections will study more in depth different areas of traffic simulator tools, emphasizing on how safe/unsafe behaviours have traditionally been modelled, and current approaches towards the development of future traffic models that incorporate human errors, so that potential vehicle crashes might happen and safety assessments might also be done.

3.1.2 Motor vehicle microsimulation models

3.1.2.1 Longitudinal movements: car-following models and their safety modeling implications

Car following (CF) behaviour is one of the main building blocks of microscopic simulation models. It is described as a rule (or set of rules) that describe the longitudinal behaviour of a vehicle on the road. This is the acceleration, speed, position, etc. Sometimes is also considered as a control law, as in microsimulation it controls what the vehicles do in the longitudinal dimension, i.e. the direction of travel. It controls how the vehicle behaves in the presence, or absence of vehicles in front.

These models date back a long time when the pioneers in the field started to produce the first car following models. The first one was developed by Pipes (1953). He developed a very simple but effective car following where the distance between cars increases linearly with the speed. Afterwards Forbes et al. (1958), Forbes (1963) and Forbes and Simpson (1968) introduced the reaction time within the model, i.e. how fast a driver can react to external changes. This development was followed by General Motors different generations of car following models. These accounted by the last generation for reaction time, driver's sensitivity, vehicles gap and speed difference between drivers (Chandler et al., 1958; Herman et al., 1959; Helly, 1959; Gazis et al., 1961).

A breakthrough was developed by Gipps (1981), where a more complex and realistic model was proposed that enabled to better capture drivers' behaviour by a series of calibration parameters. Using the Gipps (1981) model is possible to emulate both traffic stability or instabilities depending on the calibration parameters. Although, for the sake of safety analysis this is a model that is constructed as 'safe' by definition. This means that there cannot be vehicle crashes when using this car-following.

Treiber et al. (2000) generalized a model previously developed for on- and off-ramps to work with general traffic inhomogeneities making it suitable for microscopic traffic simulation. This is known as IDM (Intelligent Driver Model). A key IDM benefit is that it is defined as differential equations that can be solved using numerical methods. Even with low precision methods, the model results are feasible but lack some of the traffic features that arise with more refined, and computationally expensive, methods to solve the equations.

Although Gipps (1981) and Treiber et al. (2000) and its derivatives are widely used in commercial software packages and in research, the models have strong shortcomings. Those models can simulate a good representation of traffic flows. Thus, they provide average speed, travel times or flows that are close enough to those measured in real life, when properly calibrated. Nonetheless, they have strong limitations when it comes to the accuracy of the vehicle's trajectories, this is the acceleration and speed profiles of the vehicles.

This was first described by Brackstone and McDonald's (1999), afterwards multiple works have done extensive CF reviews highlighting these and more drawbacks of the current approaches, especially when a safety analysis wants to be performed (Saifuzzaman and Zheng, 2014; Saifuzzaman et al., 2015; van Lint and Calvert, 2018; Calvert et al., 2020). This is in part as most models presented so far are safe, which means that vehicles following these control laws will never crash. This behaviour is explained by the fact that vehicles react in a perfect manner to the external information and additionally in some models the vehicles will do whatever necessary to avoid colliding with other vehicles. These are not the only CF shortcomings, as they typically omit that a vehicle can react to stimulus from vehicles in front of their preceding vehicle. This was introduced by Herman and Rothengatter (1965) but is a timely topic as commercial ACC have also this feature already on the road.

Hamdar et al. (2008) and Hamdar et al. (2014) developed a model for drivers risk taking behaviour in certain maneuvers such as rear-end collisions during car following scenarios. In addition, discrete efforts have been made to study the effects of human errors (e.g. action errors, cognitive and decision-making errors, observation errors, information retrieval errors, and violations) (Stanton and Salmon, 2009) and distraction (Przybyla et al., 2012) on car following behaviour and risk. Many recent studies such as Bevrani and Chung (2012), Yang and Peng (2010), Paschalidis et al. (2019), Li et al. (2021), Zhang et al. (2022), Zhang et al. (2023), Adavikottu et al. (2023) proposed car following models that are capable of taking the above behavioural uncertainties into account. However, there is no evidence of using these models in the existing commercial microsimulation software packages.

Still, safety analysis can be performed using these safe CF models. This is done by checking a series of metrics like TTC (Time To Collision), near misses, extreme deceleration values among the main ones (McKenna et al., 2006). This way is possible to assess when risky situations happen. Nonetheless, this leads to some serious limitation, and is that the CF models presented so far assume a perfect driver with

perfect information. This is that they do not account for any driver distraction, excessive risk-taking, adverse weather, perception mistakes or biases. Stanton and Salmon (2009) found out that up to 75% of road crashes have human distraction as a contribution. Thus, explicitly modelling some drivers' errors is meaningful for a microsimulation safety analysis.

3.1.2.2 Lateral manoeuvres: lane-changing models and gap acceptance

Lane-changing models is a decision model that analyses the need or desire of a lane change, the benefits of a lane change and the feasibility conditions for a lane change (Barceló, 2010). The desire or need to change depends on the distance to the next turning and the traffic conditions. If the driver is going slower than his/her desired speed, then this driver will try to overtake the preceding vehicles. Drivers will also have to check whether there will be (or not) any improvement in traffic conditions after that lane change. Drivers also must check if there is enough gap to make the lane change in a safe way (Barceló, 2010).

In recent years, there has been lots of efforts to review and collect all relevant work related to lane-changing models (Toledo et al., 2003; Moridpour et al., 2010; Rahman et al., 2013; Zheng, 2014; Jian & Ying-Shuai, 2017; Wang et al., 2019; Ji & Levinson, 2020). Although these models have received less attention compared to car-following models (Zheng, 2014), it is a matter of great interest to many researchers due to its importance in the creation of major-crash hazards. In fact, lane changing is one of the main causes of road crashes on highways (Khelifa et al., 2023) and therefore has negatively impacts on traffic safety (Pande & Abdel-Aty, 2006; Zheng et al., 2010; Rodemerk et al., 2012).

The first lane-changing model for microsimulation tools was developed by Gipps (1986). It considered the necessity, desirability, and safety of lane changes. Usually, lane changing behaviour is modelled in two steps: (1) the decision to consider a lane change, (2) the decision to execute the lane change (Toledo et al., 2003). Several microscopic simulators have implemented lane changing behaviours based on Gipps' model. As an example, Aimsun simulation tool uses this decision model to represent how drivers change lanes. Three different zones are considered: (a) Zone 1, in which decisions are governed by traffic conditions of the involved lanes; (b) Zone 2, is the intermediate zone in which drivers are looking for a safe gap, adapting their speed to find gaps; (c) Zone 3, in which vehicles are urgently reaching their correct lane, reducing speed, and looking for upstream gaps.

Another approach for lane-changing was also proposed by Sparmanns (1978). In this case, the lane-changing model classified lane changes as slower-to-faster and faster-to-slower. Depending on drivers' speed, if the front vehicle is driving at a lower speed compared to the vehicle behind, then this vehicle will change to a faster lane or vice versa. The model is a function of the speed of the front vehicle and the desired speed of the vehicle behind. As an example, Vissim uses a lane-change model which is based on Sparmann's model (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Lane-changing models are followed by gap-acceptance models because when a driver finds a gap to undertake the maneuver, the rules governing lane-changing models trigger immediately (Ahmed et al., 2021). This gap-acceptance model considers the distance of vehicles to a hypothetical collision point, their speeds and acceleration rates. And then the model also calculates the time needed by vehicles to undertake the action.

Complementary to the lane-changing models, there are other models – called look-ahead model – whose main idea is to provide the knowledge of a set of next turning movement to vehicles in order to have a clear idea on how to make lane-changing decisions and avoid not reaching the appropriate turning lane (Barceló, 2010).

However, as observed in all these models, safety is considered as the key element to undertake manoeuvres. Drivers cannot change lane if there is not a safe gap between vehicles or a safe distance and speed between the preceding and the following vehicle. As indicated in the previous section regarding car-following models, these lane-changing models are also considered to be safe by nature, which avoid

drivers to undertake decisions that might put a risk of crashing with other road users. The introduction of human factors in these microsimulation models can provide a better representation of how drivers behave in the real world and therefore, more accurate safety analysis might be able to be performed.

3.1.2.3 Human factors in car-following and lane-changing models

To create a more realistic simulation model of vehicles resulting in more frequent interactions and safety-critical conflicts, there is the need to introduce human factors in the models. This is to drop out the unrealistic assumption regarding the driver capabilities as stated by Boer (1999). In this sense, it is assumed that drivers always aim for their optimal, achieving this by applying a unique control law, which might be the result of reacting to stimulus that are not able to perceive (for instance in bad weather). But in real life, drivers typically adopt driving strategies that, rather than being optimal, are just adequate due to lack of information or time to check all the alternatives. Saifuzzaman and Zheng (2014) reviewed the existing (at the time) studies on incorporation of human factors in car-following models and found that most of these models provide no psychologically plausible characterization of how humans think about the driving task. This lack of human behaviour elements in car following models is even more acute when noting that driving behaviour is heterogeneous and can vary depending on individual attributes such as age, gender, and so forth.

Thus, there is a need to improve previously presented models to incorporate human factors than can predict and reproduce human errors like longer reaction times; while being computationally tractable, and able to be calibrated by data that can be collected. All this while keeping their ability to reproduce general traffic flow phenomena as current models do.

As an example of risky behaviours, Brackstone et al. (2002) found that on the British M27 motorway 95.8% of the drivers was following a headway shorter than the recommended 2 seconds, and 47.9% of drivers having a headway shorter than 1 second. This was not an isolated case as Treiber et al. (2006) found similar result on a German motorway, where the most common headways where in the range of 0.9 to 1 second, and some were as low as 0.3 seconds.

Several driver attributes are correlated with driving styles. A survey performed across Alabama, US, drivers showed that age and gender affects drivers in his/her perception of risky situations (Rhodes and Pivik, 2011; Ossen and Hoogendoorn, 2011). Also, the surrounding environment influences the drivers' behaviour as found by Muhrer and Vollrath (2011) and Treiber et al. (2006). Saifuzzaman et al. (2014) made a comprehensive list of multiple human factors from a literature review (Hamdar, 2012; Treiber and Kesting, 2013 among others), and they found the following factors:

- Socio-economic characteristics (e.g., age, gender, income, education, family structure)
- Reaction time
- Estimation errors: Spacing and speeds can only be estimated with limited accuracy
- Perception threshold: Human cannot perceive small changes in stimuli
- Temporal anticipation: Drivers can predict traffic situation for the next few seconds
- Spatial anticipation: Drivers consider the immediately preceding and further vehicles ahead
- Context sensitivity: Traffic situation may affect driving style
- Imperfect driving: For the same condition drivers may behave differently in different times
- Aggressiveness or risk-taking propensity
- Driving skills
- Driving needs
- Distraction

- Desired speed
- Desired spacing
- Desired time headway

To introduce drivers' errors, especially in car-following behaviours, some models have been developed. The first is the one by Wiedemann (1974), who introduces the drivers' perceptual threshold. This reflects the inability of humans to perceive precise distances and speeds so there is some trial an error when a vehicle approaches another one. This results in a driver having an oscillating over-time gap with the preceding vehicle. Figure 3-1 shows how the following vehicle has oscillations in speed and distance. to.

Figure 3-1 Wiedemann's CF model (Source: Wiedemann, 1974).

Fellendorf and Vortisch (2010) implemented a modification of the Wiedemann model in Vissim microsimulation tool. The problem is that no clear calibration methodology has been established, although several attempts have been provided in the literature (Park and Qi, 2006; Gomes et al., 2004; Ištoka Otkovic' et al., 2013; Lownes and Machemehl, 2006). This is one of the key drawbacks on introducing human factors into these motor vehicle simulation models. The calibration and validation are needed and the typical data available is not good enough for that purpose.

So far, the presented models enable to characterize the perception errors, but this does not account the risk-taking behaviour of some drivers. Based on the prospect theory of Kahneman and Tversky (1979), which is accepted as a human decision-making model for outcomes that can be risky, Hamdar et al. (2008) and Hamdar et al. (2014) develop a driving model based on the fact that driving is the sequence of potential risk-taking decisions. This is achieved by characterizing the drivers with some biases to some potential outcomes. In this case, a driver's subjective probability of being involved into a rear end collision is also included.

Nonetheless, the concept of 'human error' remains to be characterised. This is a very wide definition that traditionally have been classified as "involuntary errors and violations" (Reason, 1990). A violation is a deliberate act of the driving disobeying regulations, like speeding. An error is any behaviour that diverts drivers from the desired driving happening involuntary. This can be further subdivided into five different

categories: action errors, cognitive and decision-making errors, information retrieval errors, observation errors, and violations (Stanton and Salmon, 2009).

In the particular case of car-following models, human factors can be incorporated into these existing models. Bevrani and Chung (2012) improved Gipps' (1981) model by considering human imperfection in processing information and executing actions. More specifically, they included human perception limitations in detecting speed differences, extra delay in driving phase changes – assuming that reaction time increases after being in a fixed situation; that is, either in a constant speed or in an acceleration phase – and driver imperfection in adjusting speeds. However, human errors, such as distraction and risk taking, are omitted in their model. Hamdar and Mahmassani (2008) did also explore the modification of existing car-following models to account for some human factors, achieving some vehicular crashes. In a similar way, Treiber et al. (2006) purposed extensions to the IDM model so it could have estimation errors, finite reaction times, spatial anticipation and temporal anticipation. They argued that the model solved the unrealistic vehicular dynamics and crashes that previous human-factor models had not.

The latest relevant effort in this field is Van Lint and Calvert (2018) and Calvert et al. (2020). In Van Lint and Calvert (2018), a methodological framework to design a car-following model considering human factors is presented. This work tackled on which human factor needs to be modelled and in which hierarchy. As they proposed, there are several cognitive levels taking decisions when driving. As shown at Figure 3-2, there is the strategic level that controls the route, the manoeuvring level that controls the lane and finally the control level, which is the car-following level.

Figure 3-2 The hierarchical structure of the road user task. Performance is structured at three intertwined levels. (Source: van Lint and Calvert, 2018).

Another research stream about road user behaviour in traffic microsimulation has focused on such behaviour in lane changing maneuvers. Ulak et al. (2019) investigated the effects of age and experience of drivers on lane changing behaviour of drivers and found that varied risk perception of drivers depending on their age and experience affect driving behaviour and ultimately influence traffic safety and performance measures. Das and Ahmed (2022) studied the driving behaviour under adverse weather conditions (i.e. poor visibility) in traffic microsimulation and found that adjusted traffic microsimulation parameters in adverse weather conditions produce lower average speeds with higher total travel times and total delays than clear weather.

With the introduction of automated vehicles and the ambition to adopt these vehicles in the near future, a few studies have focused on the effects of human behaviour on driving in mixed traffic (i.e. traffic with conventional and automated vehicles). De Zwart et al. (2023) studied the effects of driving adaptation behaviour in terms of time headway, following distance, and velocity of drivers in the presence and absence of automated vehicles and found that drivers adapt their headway and speed in such

circumstances. Azam et al. (2022) have argued that despite the existing studies on human behaviour in mixed traffic, there is a lack of understanding about the interactions of vehicles in mixed traffic stream. The gap acceptance behaviour of drivers in heterogeneous and mixed traffic may be different than in regular traffic depending on aggressiveness of drivers towards automated vehicles (Asaithambi et al., 2016).

Then, there is the question on how the human factors are modelled. There is a need to have time evolving human factors for the same driver, for instance drowsiness, distraction due to a phone call, etc. A huge variability in the human factor values can be observed within the same driver as well as across different drivers, and this results in wide probabilistic distributions of the parameters (Ossen and Hoogendoorn, 2011). While perception errors can be modelled exogenously, the problem then is that many of these factors are auto correlated.

The proposed methodology in Van Lint and Calvert (2018) solves this problem by using endogenous driver models. The authors modelled the driving using two different functions: (i) on one side, the situation awareness over time (SA_t), which takes care of all the perception; and (ii) on the other side, the task demand over time (TD_t), which is the cumulative cognitive load on the driver, including those tasks that are not related to the act of driving, as they take brain power anyway. This is especially relevant for those tasks that provide visual perception, as this is the same channel used for driving (Precht et al., 2017a, 2017b; Grier et al., 2008). Then, there is the Task Capacity (TC), which is the ability of a driver to process information. All this enables to compute the driver Task Saturation (TS) which is the division between the total driver task demand and the driver task capacity.

The key is that as TS approaches 1 the driver performance worsens, so the driver is more prone to errors. Under this situation drivers' ability to assess distances and speeds decreases significantly. The example provided in Van Lint and Calvert (2018) shows how a decrease in headway increases the task demand, which is then further stressed by receiving a phone call. Now the driver is oversaturated, and this results in some human errors happening. As an example, drivers may miss some relevant information (e.g. vehicles on the adjacent lane), or considering a worse perception of gaps or increasing the overall reaction time as the driver may look at the phone regularly. When the call ends the total task demand is reduced and the driver reduces the headway again. This process is shown in Figure 3-3. Using this approach Van Lint and Calvert (2018) manages to get some collisions.

Figure 3-3 Illustrative example dynamics task demand and the use of fundamental diagrams of task demand (Source: van Lint and Calvert, 2018)

This methodology then is further improved by Calvert et al. (2020) by introducing the concept of Anticipation Reliance in the framework developed by Van Lint and Calvert (2018). This is to introduce a cognitive buffer whenever the driver anticipates that will be at a cognitive capacity for some period of time. For instance, this can be the case when a driver in a dense traffic, where performing the CF is demanding enough, wants to change lanes. A custom implementation of these models was performed at the Horizon 2020 project SAFE-UP (2021) in Aimsun.

Finally, a table adapted from Van Lint and Calvert (2018) summarizes the different human factors and the scientific references that address those (Table 3.3).

What (process)	Aspects and driver traits	Examples
Perception: How drivers translate signals from the environment to (anticipated) stimuli	Reaction time. This involves the physical delay between observing (a braking light) and responding (braking), and the delay caused by diverted attention.	Many CF models have been extended with reaction time, e.g. (Gazis et al., 1961; Treiber et al., 2006). By and large, only for small reaction times do car following laws result in stable dynamics.
	Estimation errors. Humans observe stimuli with a limited accuracy as a function of distance and visibility conditions.	There is abundant evidence that drivers have systematic biases in judging both distances and speeds (Castro et al., 2005; Nilsson, 2000; Thiffault and Bergeron, 2003), and several CF models have been extensively tested under such errors, which are generally modelled as (auto-correlated) noise processes (Hamdar and Mahmassani, 2008; Treiber et al., 2006). No attempts have been made to our knowledge in modelling these errors endogenously (i.e. as the result of a HF process).
	Perception thresholds. Humans cannot perceive small changes in stimuli.	Wiedemann was among the first to formalize driver inertia to small stimuli in CF models (Wiedemann, 1974), after which various adaptations followed (Fritzsche, 1994). See also driver inertia.
	Spatial anticipation. Drivers look ahead (downstream).	Spatial adaptation is usually modelled by incorporating gaps between leader-follower pairs further downstream (i.e. downstream density), e.g. (Hoogendoorn et al., 2006; Ossen and Hoogendoorn, 2011; Treiber et al., 2006, 2007). In general, spatial anticipation counter-effects the destabilizing effects of reaction times.
	Temporal anticipation. Drivers extrapolate conditions (over space and time).	Typically, some form of dead-reckoning (using constant speed or acceleration) is adopted (Treiber et al., 2006). Temporal anticipation also counter-effects reaction times.
	Distractions. Competing information processing activities affect perception	Distractions, and particularly visual distractions are detrimental for the driving task (Precht et al., 2017a , b; Grier et al., 2008). Various researchers have experimented with distractions in terms of consequences for the car following task (Chan and Singhal, 2015; Hansen et al., 2017; c et al., 2010; Hoogendoorn et al., 2011; Kaber et al.,

What (process)	Aspects and driver traits	Examples
		2012; Saifuzzaman et al., 2015; Schömig and Metz, 2013) and the modelling thereof.
Response: How drivers dynamically and context-specifically respond to these stimuli.	Sensitivity to stimuli (relative speed, position, etc)	Every CF model contains parameters that govern the degree in which drivers respond to stimuli. These may dynamically change due to circumstances (see context sensitivity).
	Preferences. Drivers' desired speed, spacing, headway, etc.	Similarly, most CF models contain one or more parameters describing driver preferences. In exploring inter-driver heterogeneity, these are typically modelled as distributions over drivers (Montanino and Punzo, 2015; Ossen and Hoogendoorn, 2011).
	Context sensitivity. Different contexts may (dynamically) affect driving response.	It is widely recognized that parameters in CF models are both driver and context dependent, e.g. (Laval and Leclercq, 2010; Ossen and Hoogendoorn, 2011; Zheng et al., 2013). Clearly, as contexts dynamically change, so should the parameters.
	Inertia. Even if drivers perceive (small) stimuli, they may not respond to these.	Wiedemann-type models (Fritzsche, 1994; Wiedemann, 1974) are also termed action point models, since drivers are assumed to change their responses at discrete time instants (and continue according to the last response in between) rather than continuously.
	Aggressiveness or risk-taking propensity	Laval and Leclercq (2010) show how even in very simple CF models differentiating between timid and aggressive drivers complex but realistic stop-and-go patterns can be reproduced. More generally, there is rich literature on the driver- and context specific role of risk taking in various driving tasks (Farah et al., 2008; Jamson et al., 2012; Michaels et al., 2017; Precht et al., 2017b), and a few attempts to explicitly model this endogenously in CF models (Hamdar et al., 2015, 2008).

Table 3-1 Human Factors modelling, adapted from van Lint and Calvert (2018) who in turn adapted from Saifuzzaman and Zheng (2014).

For the particular case of lane-changing models, the work developed by Shawky (2020) analysed traffic crashes that occurred as a result of the unsafe lane change. Results showed that the percentage of lane-change was high on rural roads, high-speed limit, non-junctions, wet road surface, rainy weather, and passenger cars. The most significant variables that affected the occurrence of lane-change crashes were:

1. Drivers' factors (gender, years of driving experience)
2. Location and surrounding condition factors (e.g., light and road surface conditions), and
3. Road features (e.g. road type, speed limit, number of lanes, etc.).

3.1.3 Pedestrian microsimulation modelling and interactions with other users

The coexistence of multiple road users (e.g., motorised vehicles, non-motorized vehicles, pedestrians, etc.) in the same road space creates complex situations. Traditionally, different modes of transport were modelled in microsimulation models as isolated to minimize conflicts and complex interactions (Shrivastava & Kumar, 2023). However, this approach is changing and nowadays it is unthinkable to conceive a network without an interaction between all the different road users, sharing space and reacting to each other in a way to avoid potential conflicts.

Pedestrians behaviour has been simulated in transport science mainly in two ways: from the theoretical perspective and based on pedestrian kinematics, and from empirical perspective and based on data-driven approaches (Kouskoulis et al., 2018; Kouskoulis and Antoniou, 2017).

The former simulation models include cellular automata (Flotterod and Lammel, 2015), lattice gas (Isobe et al., 2004), and social force models (Chraibi et al., 2010) which either rely on simulating the behaviour of one pedestrian (also referred to as an “agent”) based on the behaviour of other pedestrians or objects in the vicinity or are created based on Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) laws treating pedestrians as moving particles. These models have an important limitation in that they are computationally expensive and difficult to implement. The latter models (i.e. data driven models), however, address this limitation but they have lower explanatory power. These models (e.g. locally weighted regression) can be created based on pedestrian trajectories that may be collected from videos in the field. However, all of these approaches consider kinematics of pedestrian movements as their “behaviour”. A few studies have focused on simulating human factors as the behaviour of pedestrians. For example, some studies investigated the effect of age and height of pedestrians on their velocity (Teknomo, 2006; Brscic et al., 2014). In addition, the need to incorporate pedestrians decision making processes in simulating their behaviour was recognized in late 2000s. Papadimitriou et al. (2009) systematically reviewed pedestrian behavioural models and found that pedestrians route choice and crossing decisions are mostly lacking in the existing models at that time. They suggested that discrete choice models should be incorporated into traffic microsimulations to simulate the effects of a variety of contributing factors such as individual, roadway, traffic and route characteristics (and their heterogeneity) on pedestrians decision making processes.

Crossing behaviour models simulate the decision-making process of pedestrians in crossing roads. Liu et al. (2000) developed a traffic microsimulation model with pedestrian crossing behaviours in two categories of “law-obeying” and “opportunistic” and studied their interactions with vehicular traffic in a network of highways and pedestrian walkways. In general, pedestrian crossing is ultimately governed by: (i) gap acceptance theory, in which each pedestrian has a corresponding gap acceptance to cross the road, or (ii) utility theory, in which a utility of each alternative is modelled as a variable that depends on pedestrian characteristics that are making the decision and the alternative route (Papadimitriou et al., 2009). In these cases, gap acceptance models are the most included models in pedestrian decision-making. The time it takes to pedestrians to cross the road determines the gap they have, and it is calculated using the time-to-collision indicator (Rasouli & Kotseruba, 2022).

Crossing behaviour continue to be an hot topic in microsimulation and human behaviour studies with recent papers published in this field. Pekkanen et al. (2021) developed advanced drift diffusion models for pedestrians’ crossing behaviour considering sensory cues such as time and distance gaps in oncoming vehicle traffic, vehicle deceleration implicitly signalling intent to yield, as well as explicit communication of such yielding intentions and found that these models can improve road safety.

Another critical aspect of a reliable microsimulation tool is the modelling of Pedestrian-Vehicle interaction (PVI) – and not just modelling pedestrian dynamics as isolated (Zhu et al., 2021). Pedestrians are highly exposed to conflicts with other road users (Rasouli & Kotseruba, 2022). This pedestrian-vehicle interaction may be originated in a pedestrian crossing at signalised intersections (Suh et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2017; Shrivastava & Kumar, 2023; Hu et al., 2022), unsignalized crosswalks (Lu et al., 2016; Feliciani et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2021) and outside of these crossings (also known as jaywalking) (Suh et al., 2013; Amado et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). For those crossings which are controlled by traffic signals, the interaction is much more controlled due to the already established priorities.

Many studies have suggested to move towards multi-agent simulation models for pedestrians because of a variety of vision, cognition and learning capabilities that pedestrian gain in groups (Dijkstra and Timmermans, 2002). Such a group behaviour can also be studied using empirical data and discrete choice models. Zhang and Fu (2022) studied the interactions between pedestrians and vehicles in evacuation situations. Alsaleh and Sayed (2022) used on field pedestrian trajectory data and developed a game theory model for simulating the multi-agent behaviour of pedestrians. They found that the multi-agent

game theoretic model predicted pedestrian trajectories and their evasive action mechanisms with higher accuracy compared to the traditional models. A number of Horizon projects have also investigated such multi-agent behaviour of pedestrians e.g. **SIMUSAFE**¹ and **ALLEGRO** also application of a wide range of choice models such as Target Destination Choice Model, Pedestrian Route Choice Model, Pedestrian Pace State Model, and a Pedestrian Movement Model in pedestrian behavioural modelling and simulation e.g. **IPBMNES**² and **SUSTAINCITY**³.

Suh et al. (2013) analysed the waiting time of pedestrians by simulating pedestrian behaviour using Vissim software. Liu et al. (2017) considered three important aspects of pedestrian behaviour when crossing: the evasion behaviour with counter-flow pedestrians, the following behaviour with leader pedestrians, and the collision avoidance behaviour with vehicles. In case pedestrians cross on a road without using the zebra, the work done by Wang et al. (2021) indicates that pedestrians wait for a sufficient large gap ($TTC > 3s$) to cross safely.

Other work done by Papadimitriou et al. (2016) incorporated human factors in a different approach in which the pedestrian chose to cross, walk to the intersection, or not to cross. However, some authors (Rasouli & Kotseruba, 2022) argue that existing pedestrian models are situation-specific, so that pedestrian characteristics are limited to some parameters to ensure they fit to field data. Also, the estimation of the available gap for crossing is quite simplistic in current simulation tools.

Depending on the level of resolution, pedestrian simulation techniques range from macroscopic to microscopic simulations. Macroscopic models are based on pedestrian flows or queuing theory or continuum mechanics and are considered at an aggregate level (Papadimitriou et al., 2014). Microscopic models are used if individual agents are modeled in the simulation.

Traditionally, microscopic pedestrian modeling techniques are cellular automata (CA) and social force models (SFM). The former – also known as rule-based model – is considered as the first micro model for pedestrians. In this case, pedestrians move on a grid of cells following a set of rules, which in fact defines the state or occupation of a cell and a transition matrix that is used to update the cell states in the following time steps. Wang et al. (2023) proposed a method to model the interaction of pedestrians and mixed traffic based on the cellular automata approach. They analyzed the impact of pedestrian intrusion behaviours on traffic and the changes in vehicles' speed and flow rate caused by this behaviour. The latter models – also known as force-based models – uses the fluid crowd modeling method as the foundation for the model (Shrivastava & Kumar, 2023). The movement of pedestrians – also known as agents – is altered by external ('social') forces that motivate the individuals to undertake certain movements. The models contain multiple force types: driving force into the desired direction of motion, forces from other pedestrians, forces from obstacles, etc. and the summation of all these forces provide a vector that determines the direction of pedestrian movement and its velocity. However, this approach has an important limitation which is the expensive computational cost and difficulties during the implementation. During the last years, many studies have suggested that multi-agent simulation systems are the most relevant techniques to model pedestrian behaviour (Papadimitriou et al., 2014; Bazzan & Klügl, 2014).

Regarding the commercial simulation software packages, a comparison between the pedestrian simulator that Vissim and Aimsun offers was developed in the work done by Alexandersson & Johansson (2013). Viswalk, which is a plug-in in Vissim, is based on a SFM for pedestrian dynamics (Johansson, 2009). The pedestrian simulator in Aimsun is a multi-agent system that treats every pedestrian as an autonomous agent with a set of rules controlling its movements (Johansson, 2009). Results show that Viswalk is more transparent and provides more possibilities to modify parameters, whereas the Aimsun one is easier to use, provides a better visualization and can simulate pedestrians in interaction with other models of

¹<https://doi.org/10.3030/723386>

²<https://doi.org/10.3030/656349>

³<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/244557>

transport (e.g., public transport). Alexandersson & Johansson (2013) also highlight that pedestrians do not walk outside the pedestrian crossing, and they do not slow down before crossing in both simulation tools. At a non-signalized crossing, cars reduce their speed, stop when a pedestrian is approaching and wait until the crossing is empty. In a signalized crossing, everyone obeys the signal control.

Despite the importance of modeling the interaction of pedestrian and vehicles, a lack of recent studies exists, especially at unsignalized crosswalks (Amado et al., 2020). Only a few studies have combined properly the PVI and vehicle-vehicle interactions (VVI) (Zhu et al., 2021). Also, a lack of PVI algorithms is implemented in commercial simulation software packages (Amado et al., 2020) and model's outputs appeared to be highly sensitive to pedestrian parameters such as pedestrian gap acceptance criteria, priority rule configurations (Suh et al., 2013). Some studies have also identified how pedestrian may change maneuver (speed and path) during the crossing (Iryo-Asano & Alhajyaseen, 2017) and this has not been considered in microsimulation models. In fact, as indicated before, none of the commercial software packages model how pedestrians might slow down before crossing on a non-signalized intersection. This looks like that pedestrians are 100% sure that vehicles will stop before crossing (Alexandersson & Johansson, 2013). 'Illegal' pedestrian crossings – jaywalking – are not considered either in known commercial software packages. Also, some authors (Alexandersson & Johansson, 2013) identified that none of these packages are able to replicate the complex interaction behaviour of road users in a shared space environment. External factors, such as culture, weather, time of the day, site configuration, etc. might also have a strong influence on road agent behaviours (Shrivastava & Kumar, 2023). To have a more reliable simulation tool which can assess safety proactively, these limitations must be overcome.

3.1.4 Cyclist microsimulation modelling and interactions with other users

Over the past years, there has been an increasing interest in using microsimulation models to simulate cyclist behaviour. Traditionally, motor vehicle microsimulation models were the main tool to evaluate and predict traffic behaviour. The development of bicycle microsimulation models is relatively recent – still at an early stage – and the concepts from motor vehicle microsimulation models has been used to develop bicycle microsimulation models. As mentioned in previous sections, the two basic models used for motor vehicle microsimulation models are car-following and lane changing models. However, the way cyclists behave differs a lot from how drivers behave and therefore, other behaviours need to be incorporated in simulation models. For instance, initial microscopic simulation models considered cyclists' dynamics the same as cars' dynamics and therefore on congested lanes and mixed traffic lanes, cyclists waited behind cars as indicated by the corresponding car-following rules. In real life, cyclists tend to overtake vehicles, driving very close to each vehicle until they reach the front of the queue. In addition, the modeling of groups of drivers – 'bunch riding' – is not captured in traditional traffic models. In this sense, modeling the behaviour of cyclists unrealistically may lead to wrong perceptions of road capacities (Aldred et al., 2019).

A few studies have investigated cyclists behaviour in traffic microsimulation. Cellular automata and social force models are the two main used methods (Qu et al., 2017). Kodupuganti and Pulugurtha (2022) studied the effects of bicycle traffic on delays in a multi-modal network. In creating the traffic microsimulation model for their study, they used a static route behaviour of cyclists moving on bicycle lanes. Mohammed et al. (2019) simulated following and overtaking maneuvers of cyclists and clustered cyclists based on their behaviour. Kazemzadeh and Bansal (2021) have argued that developing a theory for cyclists is not viable because the off-road facilities are shared by active modes of transport with diverse speed regimes. Twaddle et al. (2014) summarized a few approaches to realistically model the movement and interactions of cyclists including cellular automata model, social force models, longitudinally continuous models, and logic models. However, they have indicated that there is a need to validate and calibrate these models with empirical data collected from a variety of locations and traffic situations.

Several models have used cellular automata to model the interaction of bike and the rest of road users (Jiang et al., 2004; Nan et al., 2014; Jin et al., 2015). However, the disadvantage of cellular automata

models is that it is conceived to be “discrete in nature” (Jasti & Higgs, 2006), meaning that it does not model the continuous interaction of mixed traffic flow (Qu et al., 2017). In fact, depending on the cellular space division, the simulation will be more/less accurate. As opposed to this, social force models simulate pedestrian flows as a continuous model. In this sense, individuals can change the direction and magnitude of their speeds according to the forces that are applied to each of them, as indicated on Newton’s second law of dynamics. Another approach for realistic modeling of movements and interactions in road simulation environments is the agent-based modeling (Mohammed et al, 2019). ABM offers the possibility of capturing the complexity of real-world behaviour (Baster et al., 2013; Hussein & Sayed, 2017). Recently, one study used a data-driven approach i.e. Inverse Reinforcement Learning (IRL) algorithm, to simulate and investigate cyclists interaction with pedestrians (Alsaleh and Sayed, 2022) and found that these models can accurately predict the trajectories of cyclists.

Existing traffic microsimulation tools, such as Aimsun, Vissim, Sumo, utilize two models to independently model the motion of road motorized users: car-following and lane-changing models that simulate longitudinal and lateral movements (Tawdiddle et al., 2014). But for cyclists, this behaviour seems not real and therefore it is not enough to use these car-based models to mimic cyclists’ behaviour. Aldred et al. (2019) studied the impact of cyclists in shared bus lanes in the center of London. The authors used Vissim microsimulation tool to simulate bicycles and buses sharing the same lane, but with a manipulation of some model parameters to better represent – approximately – the behaviour of cyclists. They also indicated that the typical approaches of microsimulation modeling software tools are problematic for representing cyclists.

In the case of Aimsun simulation software, since the release of Aimsun Next version 20, bicycles can be modeled by using a “non-lane-based behaviour” which better represent how cyclists and motorbike riders behave (Hayman, 2020). In this case, multiple vehicles can occupy the same longitudinal position within a lane as shown in Figure 3-4, and this allows cyclists to overtake other vehicles and form groups of cyclists. The model is also capable of instructing vehicles to stay close to the left/right side of the road depending on the direction of travel. A recent investigation of the effects of sport cyclists on vehicular traffic on narrow two-lane rural roads modelled them in microsimulation and found that bicycle traffic decreased average vehicular speed and increased vehicular traffic delays (Moll et al., 2021).

Figure 3-4. Screenshots of bicycle-vehicles interaction in Aimsun Next. On the left, the traditional modeling approach of bicycles considered as vehicles. On the right, the new implemented non-lane-based behaviour model in Aimsun Next. Source: Adapted from Hayman (2020).

It is clear that microscopic simulators can be configured to simulate mixed traffic conditions (e.g. between pedestrians and cyclists), by altering some parameters and without changing existing behavioural models. However, the results that the models will provide may be unrealistic. Therefore, there is a need for implementing new behavioural models to simulate traffic on paths or spaces that are shared among users.

Despite its current importance, little attention has been paid to model the interaction of two-wheeler and other road users (Shrivastava & Kumar, 2023). The way two-wheeler drivers move is different from a car and therefore further models need to be examined. In this sense, Shrivastava & Kumar (2023) proposed an extension of the SFM to incorporate interactions between pedestrians, cars, and two-wheelers at a signalized intersection. The authors incorporated a driving force term in the desired direction of movement, a repulsive term to avoid any physical contact and maintain a safe distance and a car-following feature and conflict avoidance terms in a mathematical model. Qu et al. (2017) modified and extended the SFM for mixed traffic flow considering the interaction between electric bikes and cars. Their extended model also included lane-changing behaviour of e-bikes and conflict avoidance behaviour. Note that electric bikes have higher speed than non-electric bikes, and this means electric bike riders tend to change lane more frequently and prefer to change lane into the vehicles lane when it is not occupied. Mehta et al. (2019) analyzed the overtaking behaviour of motorized vehicles when passing bicycles on urban roads.

Investigating the behaviour of cyclists through microsimulation has been the focus of a few previous horizon projects too. For example, the **ALLEGRO**⁴ project exploited a wide range of data collection methodologies such as Wi-Fi and 3D sensors, and extensive surveys and created a microsimulation model of cyclists in operational level, mid-term route choice decision making, and long term route choice decision making.

3.1.5 E-scooter rider behaviour and interactions with other users

Given new forms of e-mobility have only emerged in recent years, researchers have only just started looking into the behaviour of new forms of micromobility road users such e-scooters. Most of these studies have been conducted in an empirical-simulation fashion, meaning that they have first collected empirical data on e-scooters traffic patterns and have then created a simulation environment to study their behaviour.

- Mclean (2021) and Mclean et al., (2021) collected empirical data on e-scooter pilot program in the City of Calgary in Canada and created a synthetic workload model of e-scooter traffic. They studied the impact of e-scooters and their management policies (such as fleet size, battery re-charging strategies, and urban parking infrastructure locations) on travel demand and cost and highlighted the importance of proper site selection for parking areas and battery charging infrastructure.
- Latinopoulos et al., (2021) investigated the impact of e-scooters on traffic with surveys, expert interviews and microsimulation for Paris and found that proper adoption of this micromobility mode of transport needs a holistic analysis of behavioural and cultural elements. They further recommended that any city considering e-scooters as part of their mobility offering should consider the results in the cultural and policy context of the city to generate a set of guidelines.
- Pazzini et al., (2022) investigated the traffic behaviour of e-scooters in the city of Trondheim in Norway and found that around 60% to 90% of e-scooters used bicycle paths depending on the road environment context.
- Finally, Kazemzadeh and Sprei (2022) conducted a systematic review of e-scooter studies at microscopic level and found that their is rarely considered in the literature as a distinct group of road users. They suggest that future studies should analyse the interaction of e-scooters with other road users, particularly pedestrians.

⁴<https://doi.org/10.3030/669792>

3.1.6 Microsimulation models for mixed traffic (autonomous and conventional vehicles)

The increasing presence of connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) on transport networks has grown interest in analyzing the interaction between autonomous vehicles and other vulnerable road users (Tafidis et al., 2019). The role of CAVs in improving traffic safety is clear: less human-dependent vehicles and hence fewer human errors, which is translated into less crashes (Singh, 2015) – although new type of crashes might also appear. As real-world data is not available yet, microscopic simulation methods provide an alternative approach to test how traffic safety could change under different penetration rates of CAVs (Tafidis et al., 2019; Tumminello et al., 2023). This introduction of CAVs into the traffic network will be a gradual process and therefore, there will be a transition period in which CAVs and human-driven vehicles will coexist (Ren et al., 2023) – also known as mixed traffic environment.

Papadoulis et al. (2019) studied the impact of CAVs under different penetration rates on motorways. The authors developed a decision-making CAV control algorithm in Vissim to allow a CAV to have longitudinal control, search adjacent vehicles, identify nearby CAVs and make lateral decisions. The safety impact assessment was conducted using the SSAM model. Results showed that CAVs reduced traffic conflicts even at low penetration rates. Elawady et al. (2022) also analyzed the impact of CAVs on traffic safety in an intersection using SSAM approach and under different penetration rates, providing similar results. Tumminello et al. (2023) also investigated the impact of CAVs on the operational performances of a single-lane roundabout using Aimsun Next.

However, the implications of autonomous vehicles on vulnerable road users such as pedestrians, bicyclists, scooters are still not clear (Kutela et al., 2022). In fact, the interaction between CAVs and VRU in a mixed traffic environment has not been well studied. Although CAVs are programmed to give priority to VRUs, it is still unclear how these users will react to these vehicles. Kutela et al. (2022) investigated the interaction of VRU on CAVs by exploring the involvement patterns of VRU in CAVs crashes. Results showed that VRU were at fault in a large percentage of crashes that directly involved VRUs. The authors mentioned that future studies could also explore this topic with a larger dataset due to the current CAV-VRU collision data limitation. Kalatian & Farooq (2021) proposed a machine learning framework to explore factors affecting pedestrians' waiting time before crossing in the presence of automated vehicles. The authors developed a virtual reality experiment to collect behavioural data. Results showed that the presence of automated vehicles, among others, were the main contributing factors to longer wait times. Fewer studies have been dedicated to analyze the interaction between bicyclists and CAVs.

Despite the increasing number of studies that analyzes the impact of CAVs on traffic safety and operation, the literature on the safety implication of CAVs on VRU is still limited and needs further research to get a clear picture of their potential impact.

3.1.7 Using microsimulation models to assess safety

Previous sections described the current state-of-the-art in microscopic modelling approaches and their implications in safety analysis. For instance, how motorized vehicles or non-motorized users move on a section level, based on which rules and how they interact with the surrounding vehicles, adapting their distance and speed, and changing lanes or crossing intersections if a safe gap exists. Future potential improvements of these models will focus on better representing users' behaviours on microsimulation models to allow more 'unsafe' behaviours. This in fact might be achieved when 'human errors' are incorporating in the models, which may introduce the concept of unsafety in drivers' behaviour.

However, all these approaches are mainly focused at a microscopic level. Historically, the safety assessment of road sections (and as a result, road networks) has been done based on historical crash records, statistical modelling and/or professional field observation (Mahmud et al., 2019). However, these approaches might not be reliable due to crash reporting and biased judgement. In addition, these are also called reactive approaches as they need a considerable amount of previous crash data to evaluate safety.

Because of these limitations, researchers explored new proactive methodologies to evaluate traffic safety. These approaches evaluate traffic safety in microscopic traffic simulation models based on the computation of safety metrics by using simulation outputs. The advantage of this approach is that there is no need to alter drivers' behaviour to make the simulation unsafe and allow collisions, which in part simplifies the problem. Also, no real crash data is required to make an initial estimation of road safety. Such safety measures are traditionally called Surrogate Safety Measures (SSM). These approaches tried to identify specific surrogate indicators that are highly connected to the risk of collisions, which occurs more frequently than crashes. The usage of microsimulation modelling has improved the reliability of this surrogate approach, as human observers are no longer needed for data collection (Mahmud et al., 2019).

Over the past decades, there has been lots of efforts to develop surrogate safety measures. To measure the closeness to a collision, the most used surrogate measures are: the time to collision and post encroachment time (Zheng, et al., 2021). Time to collision (TTC) is defined as the time remaining prior to a collision when the speed and trajectory of vehicles are maintained as constant (Hayward, 1971). Similar indicators to TTC include time to collision (Hydén, 1987), time-exposed TTC (Minderhoud & Bovy, 2001), time-integrated TTC (Minderhoud & Bovy, 2001) and modified TTC (Ozbay et al., 2008). Post encroachment time (PET) is the time difference between a vehicle leaving the area of encroachment and a conflicting vehicle entering the same area (Cooper, 1984). Other similar indicators include encroachment time (Allen et al., 1978), gap time (Gettman & Head, 2003), and headway (Vogel, 2003). Both TTC and PET represent a measure of temporal proximity, in the case of TTC represents the proximity to a potential collision point on the presence of a collision course, whereas PET represents the actual safety margin without any requirement for a collision course (Zheng & Sayed, 2019). The Federal Highway Administration of the US Department of Transportation developed a tool to assess surrogate safety measures called SSAM (Pu et al, 2008), which will be described more in detail in the following section. Other indicators, such as deceleration and angle-based indicators, have been proposed in the literature to measure the intensity of evasive actions to avoid collision – such as braking or swerving. The most common and used deceleration-based indicator is the deceleration rate to avoid a crash (Cooper & Ferguson, 1976), and other similar indicators such as deceleration to safety time (Hupfer, 1997).

Despite the usage of these surrogate safety measures in simulation, none of these are systematically selected or locally validated. There have been little or no attempts to integrate network-level road safety assessment methodologies in microsimulation modeling tools. To the best of the reviewers' knowledge, the SSAM approach is the only road safety evaluation technique that has tried to integrate microsimulation tools and surrogate safety measures to assess safety impacts on a network level. The iRAP Star Score is another world-wide used approach to evaluate safety in a static way of urban road networks. The following sub sections describe both approaches, emphasizing the advantages and disadvantages of their application and integration with microsimulation tools.

3.1.7.1 Vehicle trajectory simulation for safety assessment: the SSAM approach

An approach that has been traditionally utilized to evaluate safety is based on post-processing techniques that use data output from traffic simulators. Compared to field-based observations, simulation tools are able to collect data in a more quick and accurate way (Gettman & Head, 2003; Cunto, 2008). Recently, simulation tools are the most used approaches to safety studies as they have the capability of automatically collect simulated traffic data and analyze potential traffic conflicts (Wang & Stamatidis, 2013). In this case, one of the most used models to identify traffic conflicts is the Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM) (Pu et al, 2008). SSAM is a tool, developed by the Federal Highway Administration of the US Department of Transportation, that uses vehicle trajectory data to identify traffic conflicts. This trajectory data is obtained from microscopic traffic simulation models and is used to observe vehicle-to-vehicle interactions. In doing so, this approach is able to identify areas that are more prone to incidents and therefore, assess safety impact on a network level. SSAM algorithms process one simulation time step at a time and checks for traffic conflicts using the predefined safety Time to Collision and Post Encroachment Time threshold values as surrogate safety measures. In this sense, SSAM simulates future

positions of vehicles following their trajectory and keeping the same speed for the next simulation steps and up to the duration of the predefined TTC (default value is 1.5 s). If there is an overlap of vehicles, a conflict will be identified. The latest versions of SSAM also provide heatmaps showing the concentration of conflicts along the simulated road network. Figure 3-5 presents the process to integrate traffic simulation models and SSAM.

Figure 3-5 Integration of traffic simulation models and SSAM

Recently, the SSAM approach has been extensively used in safety evaluation and it is even recognized as the only feasible methodology to use microscopic simulation for traffic safety assessment (Sha,2020).

Caliendo & Guida (2012) tried to identify a relationship between simulated conflicts and recorded crashes on unsignalized urban intersections in Italy. The authors wanted to prove that microsimulation models were a potential tool for assessing safety. The methodology the authors presented was the use of microsimulation – in this case, Aimsun traffic simulation software – to model traffic flow during peak hours. And the SSAM was also used to calculate and classify conflicts. Results showed a significant correlation between recorded crashes and critical conflicts obtained from microsimulation models. Therefore, the authors admitted that the approach was a valid alternative to predict crashes, despite some identified limitations such as the unmodelled “illegal” form of drivers or the quantification of crash severity in the analysis.

Habtemichael et al. (2014) evaluated safety implications of aggressive driving using a microscopic traffic simulator approach. In this case, the authors used SSAM in combination with VISSIM to analyze the crash risk, severity level and the perceived benefits of aggressive driving under congested and non-congested conditions. In this sense, some proportions of vehicles were simulated to behave aggressively by modifying some driver behaviour parameters for car-following and lane-changing models in VISSIM. Three ways of road aggressions were considered: (1) speeding above the legal speed limit or driving too fast for the traffic conditions; (2) following closely; (3) weaving through traffic by abrupt change of lanes. The data output from the simulation – in this case, trajectories of vehicles – was used as an input into the SSAM model to detect traffic conflicts.

Wang et al. (2018) evaluated intersection safety through a combination of microsimulation and Extreme Value Theory (EVT). They simulated 10 urban intersections in VISSIM and used field data to calibrate the model. Vehicles trajectories from the simulation model was used as an input into the SSAM which was used to extract conflict data. Extreme Value Theory (EVT) based methods were used to model simulated/field conflict data and derive the Estimated Annual Crash Frequency (EACF), used as Surrogate Safety Measures (SSM). The authors conclude that this combination of microsimulation and EVT was a promising choice for safety evaluation.

Astarita et al. (2019) compare different traffic simulation models (Aimsun, VISSIM and Tritone) to evaluate safety of typical intersections (roundabout, traffic light regulated intersection and an unregulated intersection). In order to reproduce traffic safety measures, the safety evaluations are carried out by using SSAM, which evaluates the surrogate safety measures by using vehicle trajectories. The authors used the TTC, PET, Maximum Speed (MaxS) and Deceleration Rate (DR) as a surrogate safety measures. The

authors mentioned that results were similar between different microscopic models. They concluded that SSAM analysis showed a greater danger in the scenario with the roundabout (lower TTC). All three simulators showed how a signal regulated intersection was much safer than a roundabout and safer than the unregulated intersection.

Further improvements on the previous work were developed by Astarita & Giofré (2019). The authors introduced a way of evaluating safety based on incorporating driver errors and identifying the resulting crash consequence using SSAM. The proposed methodology has been applied in VISSIM, Aimsun and Tritone. The authors proposed to simulate a driver distraction by examining all vehicle trajectories every second of the simulation and perform a “distraction” on the trajectory on certain vehicles at a constant speed. If there is a potential collision, the extent of the collision is evaluated. Three main parameters are considered in their implementation: the simulation time step, the distraction time, and the angle of the possible vehicle trajectory. With this approach, two possible results can be possible: (1) the vehicle is involved in a crash, which is detected by evaluating the points of intersection between two objects, and (2) the vehicle does not impact with any other one. However, with this approach, there is a need for a detailed calibration of certain parameters, such as the rate of distraction, which is *a priori* unknown.

This trajectory-based approach has also been used to study the safety impact of connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) using a microscopic study. In particular, Miqdady et al. (2021) applied a simulation-based safety assessment to evaluate the number of incidents after the introduction of connected and automated vehicles. The modelling of CAVs was done using Aimsun Next API. The potential conflicts were obtained by using SSAM and calculating the TTC indicator. The authors used a TTC threshold (1.5s) after undertaking a sensitivity analysis and results showed a significant difference between extreme values (0.5 and 2.5s). Results demonstrated that the higher the penetration rate of CAVs, the fewer number of potential crashes.

Another example is the Horizon2020 funded **LEVITATE project** (2021), which evaluated the safety impacts of CAVs following the same trajectory-based approach, the **SAFE-UP project** (2021) did a similar work also including some assessments with the VRUs interactions. Sha et al. (2022) studied the safety impacts of dedicated lanes for CAVs using microsimulation. The methodology integrated Aimsun as a traffic simulator with SSAM to identify traffic conflicts through vehicular trajectories. In this case, the authors presented a new approach to estimate the expected number of crashes by using traffic conflict data obtained from microsimulation. This was carried out by using a probabilistic methodology proposed by Tarko (2018). The i-DREAMS⁵ Horizon 2020 proposed different definitions of road risk on the basis of microscopic naturalistic driving data collected in 5 countries, its indicators, and its contributing factors from a micro safety assessment perspective.

Recently, a new paper developed by Leonardi & Distefano (2023) compared the operational and safety performance of multi-lane roundabouts and turbo-roundabouts. The authors followed the same approach as the previous work: they simulated traffic movements using a microscopic simulator and then used the vehicle trajectory data output as an input to the SSAM to evaluate safety impacts. The authors also mentioned that they preferred to choose Aimsun software because it was more reliable than VISSIM in generating more realistic trajectories, which is extremely important if SSAM is used afterwards.

Other studies have also evaluated the impacts of roadside safety improvements by using a computer software called Roadside Safety Analysis Program (RSAP) (Mak et al., 1998), which was developed as a tool for the 2011 Roadside Design Guide (1996), published by the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO). This tool only considers isolated drivers crashes against barriers or roadside obstacle without considering the interaction between vehicles. The software performs a series of simulations of encroachments for a typical roadway segment and estimates the crash costs.

⁵ <https://idreamsproject.eu/wp/>

The following Table 3.4 shows a summary of all reviewed models that evaluate traffic safety by analyzing the vehicle trajectory obtained from microsimulation models.

Traffic simulation methodology has been widely used and become a common practice in transportation engineering by offering the ability of analysing complex transportation aspects. In terms of safety, the use of microscopic simulation (or microsimulation) is becoming progressively feasible as well, as several approaches using suitable methodological frameworks and tools quantifying surrogate safety measures become readily available. For this case, the most common technique is the conflict-based approach that enable transportation engineers to investigate high-risk locations without the need of field crash data (Ghanim et al., 2020).

One of the most common ways to estimate conflicts using microscopic models is the **Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM) software**, a model developed by Federal Highway Administration (Pu & Joshi, 2008). The software analyses the vehicle trajectory data and identifies conflicts. Specifically, a conflict is identified when the Time-To-Collision (TTC) and Post-Encroachment Time (PET) are lower from preset thresholds, as identified in early studies exploring the possibility of using microscopic simulation for road safety assessments (Astarita et al., 2011). In addition, the identified conflicts are also classified into three manoeuver types, namely rear-end, lane change and crossing conflicts based on conflict angle. A variety of microsimulation studies have been identified conflicts using the SSAM to evaluate consequences of different transportation planning (Goh et al., 2014; Preston and Pulugurtha, 2021), control policies (Ribeiro et al. 2019; Li and Sun, 2019; Kronprasert et al., 2020; Shahdah and Azam, 2021), road configurations (Giuffrè et al., 2019; Ghanim et al., 2020; Bahmankhah et al., 2022) as well as transportation innovations (Xin et al., 2019; Mourtakos et al., 2021; Elawady et al., 2022) in terms of traffic safety.

As mentioned, the microscopic simulation has been extensively used with regards to the surrogate safety measures evaluation. For this reason, several studies have attempted to examine the validity of the results derived from microscopic models. Findings from a simulation study indicated **a strong relationship between surrogate safety measures of traffic simulation and real crash data** (Ozbay et al., 2008). Specifically, the accuracy of conflict prediction was revealed when comparing simulated conflicts with field conflicts (Zheng et al., 2019; Essa and Sayed, 2020). In a different study, So et al. (2015) proposed an approach of integrating vehicle dynamics models with traffic simulation models aiming in generating realistic vehicle trajectories, and compared its results with traditional traffic simulation model ones proving that the proposed approach integrate a stronger correlation with real crashes. Finally, conflicts derived from microscopic simulation models were also compared to predicted conflicts using statistical modeling, and it was revealed that the simulated conflict-based method indicated a significant correlation in the resulting outcomes and had a better performance in identifying high-risk locations (So et al., 2015).

Astarita et al. (2020a) proposed a novel surrogate safety indicator founded on vehicle trajectories, while simultaneously considering roadside objects. The theoretical model is validated through comparisons between the calculation of surrogate safety measures on trajectories obtained from microsimulation and crash risk obtained through real crash data obtained by several urban intersection scenarios. Apart from conflict generation, when the trajectories were overlapping (or close enough), TTC and PET indicators were also examined, while the authors concluded that a model including mean energy is statistically equivalent to a collision-based model.

One major limitation of applying traffic simulation in evaluating safety is **the absence of complete and established models for simulating potential crashes**. A few studies have attempted to overcome this issue through proposing alternative methodologies. In particular, Guido et al. (2019) presented some applications of a new procedure based on potential crash events for evaluating of safety levels in microscopic simulation models taking into account also potential crashes with roadside objects and barriers. In addition, a similar study conducted by Habtemichael and De Picado Santos (2014) used simulated conflicts to evaluate odds ratio of crash involvement. Moreover, Shahdah et al. (2014) used simulated conflicts linked formally to observed crashes to investigate an alternative approach for

estimating Crash Modification Factors (CMFs). Furthermore, a recent study by Oikonomou et al. (2023) proposed a methodological framework for estimating crash rates along with network characteristics and traffic measures using a microsimulation conflict-based analysis. Finally, a validation of estimated crashes from simulated conflicts showed that crashes were underestimated, nevertheless more accurate and reliable predicted crashes were derived with a proper simulation network calibration (Zheng et al., 2019).

3.1.8 Risk assessment of road geometric configuration

Focusing on road design, usually there is a lack of naturalistic driving data, resulting in not reliable road geometric designs implementation with limited operational and safety performances. In addition, the identification of the optimum geometric design requires detailed observations and evaluations of different geometric configurations. The traffic microsimulation method is considered as an ideal method of this kind of investigations as there is the ability to test different configuration scenarios and evaluate both safety and performance. Therefore, the microscopic simulation method has been extensively used to evaluate consequences of different traffic planning and control policies. For instance, several recent studies investigated traffic operations at roundabouts (Giuffrè et al., 2017; Giuffrè et al., 2018; Giuffrè et al., 2019; Ghanim et al., 2020; Bahmankhah et al., 2022) by testing different configurations. Furthermore, another microsimulation study examined impacts of passing lanes as well as merging area lengths, which represent a critical element in geometric design of passing lanes (Cafiso et al., 2018). In addition, research conducted by Appiah et al. (2020) investigated the risk of left-turn crash occurrence at a signalized intersection using a calibrated traffic microsimulation model.

There are also approaches focusing on particular elements of the road environment, such as the study by Astarita et al (2020b), focusing on potential conflicts with roadside objects. The authors developed a dedicated add-on to enable the estimation of new road safety indicators that can be used with Tritone, Visum and Aimsun, utilizing the 'Zombie driver' methodology to assess road safety levels. The core of the methodology is reported to be based on earlier ideas that include economical assessment of risks posed by the various roadside objects or obstacles, highlighting dangerous locations as ones with high crash energy values, such as trees or sharp turns that are potentially hazardous for run-off crash occurrences.

The extensive knowledge already gained on the influence of the road geometric configuration on road safety risk allows the incorporation of safety components into design software. The implementation of road assessment in BIM road models, for instance, will not only end in better-designed roads but also account for the complete life-cycle of infrastructure (Costin et al., 2018; Svatý et al., 2019).

However, even though SSAM is a widely used tool, there are some limitations that should be considered before carrying out the safety analysis. One of the major problems is that vehicle trajectory, that is used in SSAM to identify conflicts and generated by microsimulation models, do not reflect complicated drivers' behaviours in the real world (Caliendo & Guida, 2012; Huang, Liu, Yu, & Wang, 2013). This is because current CF are not realistic enough to produce realistic single trajectories as stated in the previous section.

Another limitation of SSAM is that only conflicts between vehicles are identified. Vulnerable road users such as pedestrians, cyclists and e-scooters or the safety impact of buses are not considered (Caliendo & Guida, 2012). And this is an area of research that gaining more importance, especially after the incorporation of introduction of connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) in microsimulation models. Also, another limitation of SSAM is the threshold values that are defined for the TTC and PET to identify conflict situations. These threshold value should be different for different interactions. For instance, there should not be the same threshold value for the interaction between human-driven vehicles or between CAVs (Weijermars et al., 2021). In fact, setting these values could also induce certain problems due to its main subjectivity.

Some authors (Wang & Stamatiadis, 2013; Astarita et al., 2019) argue that there are still no appropriate methodologies and reliable surrogate indicators for simulation-based safety studies. In fact, as microsimulation models are developed to avoid crashes with other vehicles, models produced

inaccuracies that led SSAM to identify conflicts when the TTC was to be zero (Caliendo & Guida, 2012). In this case, events in SSAM with TTC zero had been excluded from the traffic conflict analysis. An appropriate method and new simulation-based surrogate indicators need to be developed and validated (Wang & Stamatidis, 2013).

Reference	Aim of the study	Methodology	Performance/Safety indicator	Simulation software	Drawbacks / Further research
Gettman et al. (2008)	Develop and evaluate a method for the surrogate safety assessment of traffic facilities.	Vehicle trajectory data from traffic models are used as input data for SSAM. Then surrogate measures are calculated corresponding to each veh-to-veh interaction.	TTC PET	SSAM can combine with Aimsun, Paramics, Texas, Vissim.	<p>Need to research the development of a composite safety index that could factor in the multitude of contradictory safety indicators.</p> <p>Need to incorporate more conflict types (not just the three types considered: rear end, lane changing or crossing).</p>
Caliendo & Guida (2012)	Prove the potentiality of microsimulation models for assessing safety at urban unsignalized intersections	Unsignalized urban intersections from 2003-2007 were studied. Traffic flows were measured by video cameras. Microsimulation model was used to model traffic flow. Calibration & validation processes were also done. SSAM was used to identify critical conflicts	TTC PET	Combination of Aimsun and SSAM	<p>Illegal forms of drivers' behaviour are not considered in the analysis.</p> <p>Severity of crashes has not been evaluated.</p> <p>More research on conflicts with buses, cyclists, and pedestrians.</p>
Habtemichael et al. (2014)	Evaluate safety implication of aggressive driving by using a microscopic traffic simulation approach.	Traffic simulator provides trajectory information of all vehicles to SSAM, which detects vehicle conflicts. Aggressive drivers are modelled in VISSIM by changing driver behaviour parameters.	Crash risk (odds ratio) Severity levels of crashes PET Magnitude of perceived benefits of aggressive driving	Combination of VISSIM and SSAM	<p>The method does not include single vehicle crashes against static elements of road infrastructure.</p> <p>Future work should focus on use of naturalistic driving studies.</p>

Table 3-2 Summary of reviewed trajectory-based safety assessment publications

Reference	Aim of the study	Methodology	Performance/Safety indicator	Simulation software	Drawbacks / Further research
Wang et al. (2018)	Evaluate intersection safety by a combination of microsimulation and extreme Value Theory (EVT).	Ten urban intersections were simulated using VISSIM. The model was calibrated using field data. SSAM was used to extract simulated conflict data from vehicle trajectories. Then, EVT-based methods were used to model simulated/field conflict data and derive the EACF used as Surrogate Safety Measures.	Estimated Annual Crash Frequency. PET was used to obtain this safety measure.	Combination of VISSIM and SSAM	Other measures (e.g. average TTC, PET or TTC distribution) could also need to be considered in the calibration process. It is unknown if PET is the best EVT measurement for all conflict types. E.g. for lane change conflicts other indicators could also be considered. Or a combination of different indicators (e.g. PET + TTC).
Astarita et al. (2019)	Evaluate the safety of three typical intersections using traffic simulation approaches.	Simulations models were used to model the intersections and the safety evaluation approach was carried out by SSAM. Results were similar among simulators.	TTC PET Maximum speed Deceleration Rate	Combination of VISSIM, Aimsun Tritone and SSAM.	Results show that traditional SSM are not the best to assess real safety at intersections. More research is needed on SSM that consider speed of vehicles.
Astarita and Giofré (2019)	Develop a methodology to evaluate the consequences of crashes due to potential driver errors by using microsimulation packages.	The authors propose an “add-on” model that considers drivers’ distraction as anomalous behaviour. The algorithm examines all vehicle trajectories every second of the simulation, performing a “distraction” simulation inside the main simulation. Potential collisions between vehicle and other obstacles are evaluated in terms of severity according to a crash dynamic model.	Energy-based indicators for crash severity (Collision Energy)	Combination of VISSIM, Aimsun Tritone and SSAM.	Lack of calibration of parameters, such as rate of distraction.

Table 3-3 – continued Summary of reviewed trajectory-based safety assessment publications

Reference	Aim of the study	Methodology	Performance/ Safety indicator	Simulation software	Drawbacks / Further research
Miqdady et al. (2021)	Evaluate the number of incidents when sharing the human-driven vehicles and fully CAVs.	Vehicle connectivity is modelled by using the V2X Aimsun extension, which includes an On-Board Unit in each CAV. The autonomous behaviour was developed by changing model's parameters (e.g. min space headway, reaction time). Different penetration rate of CAVs were considered. Safety assessment was done by using SSAM using output of vehicles trajectories.	TTC (threshold 1.5s)	Combination of Aimsun and SSAM	Only consider one type of vehicles. In real world, there are several types. Only one type of road section is considered.
Sha et al. (2022)	Evaluate the safety impact of CAVs on dedicated lanes using microsimulation.	The methodology integrated Aimsun as a traffic simulator with SSAM to identify traffic conflicts through vehicular trajectories. In this case, the authors presented a new approach to estimate the expected number of crashes by using traffic conflict data obtained from microsimulation	Number of crashes TTC PET Conflict angle	Combination of Aimsun and SSAM	Future work on model calibration to incorporate conflict characteristics of CAVs.
Leonardi & Distefano (2023)	Compare the operational and safety performance between multi-lane roundabouts and turbo-roundabouts.	The evaluations were carried out with Aimsun for the operational performance and SSAM for the safety performance. Results showed that turbo-roundabouts are safer (less conflicts compared to standard roundabouts)	TTC PET Maximum speed Deceleration Rate	Combination of Aimsun and SSAM	No drawbacks are stated regarding the application of the SSAM. Limitations lie on the specificity of the case study, in terms of traffic conditions. Further research to create conditions for generalizing the results.

Table 3-4 – continued Summary of reviewed trajectory-based safety assessment publications

3.1.9 Incorporating human behaviour in traffic simulations

An earlier study endeavored to create what was termed a ‘nanoscopic’ model of driver agent-based behaviour through macroscopic simulation focusing on traffic safety network assessment (Yuhara & Tajima, 2006). The authors enriched their approach by considering the integration of driver activities to better validate and approach real traffic conditions. Specifically, the developed simulation models are assisted by receiving driver intentions as inputs, through real-time adjustments of the steering sub-system of vehicles. Tapani (2012) investigated the effects of Adaptive Cruise Control on acceleration and deceleration functions of vehicles utilizing driver simulation. Based on the findings, it is noted that ACC plays a considerable role and lowers acceleration and deceleration rates compared to non-ACC equipped vehicles, a result which hints positive safety benefits but also contradicts earlier relevant research. Moreover, the author notes that the effects of ACC systems in vehicles depend largely on underlying researcher assumptions on driver behaviour.

Regarding aggregation approaches, it was determined by Azevedo et al (2015) that calibrations of driving behaviour models using aggregated data are likely to produce biased detailed outputs. This study endeavored to reduce the parameters involved in traffic microsimulation calibration mathematically. In particular, the authors introduced a multi-step sensitivity analysis and exploited both vehicle trajectory and aggregated traffic data to assess the impact of model parameters uncertainty and different types of input data on relevant outputs. Crash and non-crash scenarios were also considered. It was concluded that multi-step global sensitivity analysis can make calibration much more efficient, and that calibration of complex driving behaviour models with higher detail can improve replications of more analytic traffic variables.

Attempts to produce dynamic road safety assessments already identify the need to consider use behaviour to assess road segments properly. The framework proposed by Taha (2018) suggests fusing smartphone-based and in-vehicle sensors with social media to address the safety system's safe road user component in dynamic assessments. Moreover, Outay et al. (2021) sought to investigate the behaviour of connected driving devices in extreme weather conditions using agent-based simulation. The study claimed providing detailed findings on both driving and communication aspects of connected vehicles, as well as shedding light on the behaviour of the transport network under extremely adverse weather conditions. The authors built a considerably complex microscopic simulation model which requires considerable computational power. A recurrent theme was again encountered in this study, where agent interactions with the environment needed to be closely defined, along with the manner in which these interactions will occur.

A recent study depending heavily on behavioural aspects is that of Zhao et al. (2022b), who assumed that collisions are mostly caused by particular driver profiles. The authors used the Next Generation Simulation (NGSIM) 101 dataset to derive three driver profiles, namely aggressive, inattentive, and normal drivers. Subsequently, simulation scenarios were run with varying profile percentages, linking crash occurrence with the aforementioned driver profiles. The study utilized SUMO Traffic Simulator and the IDM car-following model, noting that SUMO can detect traffic collisions when front and rear ends of simulated vehicles show any overlap of their positions. The study delved into crash severity investigations as well by calculating the speed difference of the colliding vehicles of different driver profiles. The authors conclude that both aggressive and inattentive driver percentages play a role in crash occurrence and injury severity levels. SUMO is known to utilize the Krauss car-following model, which at its core is a safe-distance model. This framework was also used by Sroczyński et al. (2022), who used a traffic simulator to collect network speed data and to make the analogous speed recommendations, also in relation to average traffic volume, weather conditions and surface conditions. A key indicator was determined to be the minimal mean distance of all vehicles, and the equations to derive the closely related maximum recommended safe speed are similar to those applied in the Gipps model. In conclusion, the authors advocate in favor of installing adaptive local systems to enforce multi-stage speed reduction on sections of ‘exceptionally high risk of sudden traffic disruption’ in order to increase road safety levels; however, it

should be noted that the study assumed perfect compliance of simulated drivers against the imposed speed limits.

In practical terms, data have been pointed out as the major issue of incorporating behaviour into road safety assessment. The results of a survey conducted with different National Road Administrations (NRAs) as part of the RIPCORDER-iSEREST research project showed that 60% of the interviews reported limited data availability to assess factor related to users behaviour (Yannis et al., 2016).

3.1.10 Road user behaviour and network-level safety

With the increased complexity of transport networks and new modes of mobility, the effects of human factors on the safety of road networks have become even more critical. Network-level road safety assessment has been accomplished mainly by the means of hotspot (or blackspot) identification techniques (Washington et al., 2018) and based on crash counts on the roads. These techniques rank roadway locations based on the total number of crashes (observed, predicted, or both). However, they do not distinguish between engineering and non-engineering i.e. behavioural crash contributing factors. Star rating scores (iRAP, 2022) has been another way of assessing safety of road networks. However, such ratings are primarily developed based on Crash Modification Factors (CMFs) which are multiplicative factors that indicates the proportion of crashes that would be expected after implementing a countermeasure (Gross et al., 2010). As such, the CMFs and in turn the star ratings are highly dependent on crash count predictions. Again, most of the existing methodologies only use engineering factors to predict crash counts. A few studies have developed advanced crash count prediction models that separates crashes caused primarily by engineering vs by behavioural factors (Afghari et al., 2016; Afghari et al., 2018; Shaon et al., 2019). These studies have shown that road risk can be identified and predicted more reliably by distinguishing the behavioural causes of crashes. However, these advanced models have not been adopted or used in any of the road safety assessment programs throughout the world.

3.1.11 Road safety assessment

Other approaches such as the one proposed by the International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP), developed a Star Rating protocol to assess the safety of roads when there are no crash data available (Lawson, 2011). During the last decade, this procedure has been widely spread all over the world. The procedure relies on visual inspections, either manually by inspectors or automatically by equipped vehicles. In this case, a score is calculated for each 100-meter segment of road and each of the four road users (vehicle occupants, motorcyclist, bicyclist, and pedestrian) and it represents the relative risk of death and serious injury for an individual road user. This provides an objective measure of the likelihood of a crash occurring and its severity (iRAP, 2009).

iRAP models are widely used to measure static safety performance of urban road networks for all road users. The advantage of this approach is that iRAP's methodology is able to assess the safety impact of all road users, including also pedestrians and bicyclists, which are the most vulnerable users on the road. However, this approach is still static, which means that it provides a score to road sections based on the data that is collected at that moment in time. Also, this approach is not able to analyze the interaction between road users and their implications in road safety, which is possible to do by using a traffic microsimulation model. Nonetheless, these models are not currently integrated with traffic simulation tools and therefore, this level of analysis cannot still be developed.

Infrastructure-based risk assessment methods were first established over 20 years ago as a consistent and objective process to evaluate the inherent (or 'built-in') risks of roads. They were seen as an alternative approach to crash-based 'reactive' approaches (such as black-spot programs) to improving the safety of high-risk roads.

There are a number of well-established methodologies which represent the current state-of-the-art of how to evaluate infrastructure-related risk of a road corridor or network. They vary in terms of the level of detail

required for their input data, where they can be applied, as well as which road users they provide risk ratings for.

Road safety assessment methods aim to evaluate the risk of fatal and serious injury crashes along a route or across a network. They can be broadly categorised into two groups. Those that rely on historical crash data are referred to as reactive approaches, whereas those that predict the likelihood of crashes occurring based on other measures are referred to as proactive approaches.

This review only sought to cover proactive approaches, that is only non-crash-related methods that consider infrastructure or conflict risks, which are suitable for network-wide assessments (as opposed to location-specific methods). This scope aligns with the proposed application of road safety assessment in the PHOEBE Framework, which are capable of predicting and assessing safety impacts at the transport system level.

3.1.11.1 The International Road Assessment Programmes (RAP), the Crash Risk Mapping and the Star Rating Methodology

iRAP Methodology facilitates both reactive and proactive road infrastructure safety assessment. A reactive method called Crash Rate Risk Mapping gives an objective view of where people are being killed or seriously injured on a road network and where their crash risk is greatest. It captures the combined risk arising from the interaction of road users, vehicles and the road environment.

The risk mapping protocols highlight the high- and medium-high risk sections of road across a country or region. As part of a policy commitment to eliminate high-risk roads it is recommended that partners set a target to eliminate all high- and medium-high risk roads and increase the percentage of the network or travel that is in the low-risk categories.

Risk Maps can help inform priorities across all pillars of road safety action (management, infrastructure, vehicles, road users and post-crash care). They include standard ways of expressing and benchmarking:

- crashes per kilometre or mile
- crashes per kilometre or mile travelled
- crashes per road user group, crash type or other metrics
- crash costs per length or distance travelled

A proactive method, iRAP Star Rating is a comprehensive, detailed, and objective measure of the likelihood of a road crash occurring and its severity (World Bank, 2021). It can be applied on rural or urban roads and focuses on identifying and recording the road attributes that influence the most common and severe types of crashes based on scientific evidence-based research (European Commission, 2018). In this way, the level of road user risk on a particular road section or network can be defined without the need for detailed crash data. Therefore, the individual's risk of death or severe injury is highest on a one-star (black) road and lowest on a five-star (green) road. The star ratings are also associated with crash costs (OECD, 2016).

Star Ratings measure individual risk based on Star Rating Scores (SRS). The iRAP models calculate an SRS at 100-meter intervals for four road user types, vehicle occupants, motorcyclists, pedestrians, and bicyclists. They are based on relative risk factors for each road attribute. The scores are developed by combining relative risk factors using a multiplicative model (EuroRAP, 2021). More on the iRAP models can be found in Annex B: Additional content of the Star Ratings, FSIs and SRIP Models.

- Star Ratings Methodological approach

The risk factors used in a Star Rating assessment are associated with road attributes, which are typically recorded based on visual imagery from a road survey and supporting data, such as that related to the traffic speeds and flows.

Star Ratings are a multiplicative model, where the risk factors are the weights of each attribute multiplied. This means that the SRS are the product of the interaction among different attributes that together will determine whether the infrastructure is or not safe in terms of crash likelihood and severity (Turner et al., 2009).

The SRS—that is, the relative risk of death and serious injury for an individual road user—is calculated using the following equation (Harwood et al., 2010):

$$SRS = \sum \text{Crash type scores}$$

where

$$\text{Crash type scores} = \text{Likelihood} \times \text{Severity} \times \text{Operating speed} \times \text{External flow influence}$$

Motorised road user scores (vehicle occupants and motorcyclists) are based on head-on, run-off-road and intersection crash types. Pedestrian scores are based on walking along- and across-the-road crash types. Bicyclist scores are based on riding along-the-road sections crash types (Lynam, 2012).

More information on the calculation of Star Rating Scores is available in the iRAP Methodology Factsheet 6 (iRAP, 2014a). Table 3.1 presents examples of typical sessions of divided and undivided roads, and which will be the resulting level of risk in the Star Rating model.

Star Rating	Vehicle occupant Star Rating Score	Motorcyclist Star Rating Score	Description of Typical Attributes	
			Divided Road	Undivided Road
5-Stars	0 to < 2.5	0 to < 2.5	Road attributes are well suited to higher speeds. Straight with clear lane markings, wide lanes, sealed shoulders, motorcycle-friendly median barriers, safe roadsides, and occasional grade-separated intersections. No at-grade intersections. Where motorcycle flows are high, motorcycle lanes.	Undivided roads typically cannot achieve a 5-Star Rating unless vehicle operating speeds are limited to 80km/h. Roads with very low-speed limits may reach five stars with relatively few safety facilities.
4-Stars	2.5 to < 5	2.5 to < 5	Deficiencies in some road feature given the prevailing speed, such as lane width, shoulder width, curvature or roadside hazards.	Straight with good line marking and safe roadsides – or low-speed environments.
3-Stars	5 to < 12.5	5 to < 12.5	Multiple deficiencies are given the prevailing speed, such as poor median protection against head-on crashes, roadside hazards and/or frequent at-grade intersections.	Multiple deficiencies include alignment, roadside hazards, and/or frequent at-grade intersections.

Star Rating	Vehicle occupant Star Rating Score	Motorcyclist Star Rating Score	Description of Typical Attributes	
			Divided Road	Undivided Road
2-Stars	12.5 to < 22.5	12.5 to < 22.5	Major deficiencies given the prevailing speed include poor median protection, poor roadside conditions and/or poorly designed intersections at frequent intervals.	Major deficiencies include poor roadside conditions, narrow lanes, and/or poorly designed intersections at frequent intervals.
1-Star	22.5+	22.5+	Given the prevailing speed, critical deficiencies include poor alignment, narrow lanes, narrow shoulders, poor median protection, severe roadside hazards, and numerous intersections.	The prevailing speed, poor alignment, narrow lanes, narrow shoulders, no median protection, severe roadside hazards, and numerous intersections are critical deficiencies.

Table 3-5 Typical characteristics of 1 to 5 stars section for vehicle occupants and motorcyclists

Star Ratings are used to calculate the collective risk for the road corridor or network. Fatal and Serious Injury (FSI) Estimates are one of the iRAP protocols for trauma estimation. It draws on the road attributes used within the Star Rating Model together with flow data for each road user and network-level crash data to estimate how many fatal and serious crashes are likely to occur along each road segment over a 20 year period.

Applied across the network, this approach enables an estimate of the number of vehicle occupants, motorcyclists, bicyclists, and pedestrians' fatalities on every 100-meter section of road. With the allocation of fatalities completed to a 100-meters level, one can also assess the benefits of treatments at a 100-metre section level. Figure 3-6 presents an example of the FSI estimations distributed on the part of the Slovakia network. This collective risk modelling is then used to support the recommendation, prioritization and cost-benefit analysis of road safety upgrades (iRAP, 2014c).

Figure 3-6 Example of FSI estimates distribution for Slovakia (Figure source: iRAP ViDA system)

iRAP Star Ratings have been used extensively around the world, as well as in the following European projects:

- **EU - SafetyNet Project :** Based on the knowledge that road infrastructure design and layout affect the level of safety of a particular network, the SafetyNet project developed Safety Performance Indicators (SPI) to allow benchmarking among European countries. The project piloted developments in the Netherlands, Portugal, Greece, and Israel. Ultimately, they present two types of SPIs: a road network SPI and a road design SPI (Yannis et al., 2013). The road design SPI relied on data from the European Road Assessment Programme (EuroRAP) and was analysed using the EuroRAP Road Protection Score, a preliminary version of the Star Rating Scores model which only provided safety evaluation for vehicle occupants.
- **EU- SLAIN Project :** The SLAIN Project aimed to assess the TEN-T core network and estimate the safety performance of roads in 4 countries: Croatia, Italy, Greece and Spain. More than 4,000km of road were assessed as part of the project (Holroyd, 2021).
- **Interreg - SABRINA Project :** The project SABRINA aimed at providing safer bicycle routes in the Danube area. SABRINA's Work Package T1 aims to Star Rate bicycle routes for safety. The focus is on pre-identified EuroVelo bicycle routes (6,8,9,11,13,14) in the Danube Area. Approx. 3500 km of bicycle route were inspected using specially equipped vehicles, software and trained analysts. Inspections focused on more than 30 road design features known to influence crash likelihood and severity of injuries to cyclists in the mixed traffic environment as they pose a higher safety threat to the cyclists. Following the completion of the video-based inspection, each relevant design feature was measured and rated according to the existing Road Assessment Programme (RAP) protocols. When the road inspection and rating process was completed, Star Ratings were produced to elucidate the risk allocation along the routes (Ursachi et al., 2022). In the SABRINA Project, the bicyclists' routes were also analysed using the European Certification Standard (ECS) developed by European Cyclists Federation (ECF) and the CycleRAP methodology below:

iRAP has developed CycleRAP, an evidence-based infrastructure risk evaluation model specifically for bicyclists and light mobility. The model focuses specifically on the features of facilities and the inherent risk they pose across a range of bicyclist and light mobility crash types, irrespective of the facility type (or whether it is part of the road network). Unlike Star Ratings, CycleRAP can be used on cycling infrastructure independent of road networks. Furthermore, the model accounts for a broader range of crash types, including bicycle-bicycle, bicycle-pedestrian or some kinds of single bicycle crash risk (iRAP, 2022).

3.1.11.2 The European Network Wide Assessment (NWA)

The European Commission recently presented its methodology for network-wide assessments on a methodological and implementation handbook (European Commission, 2023). NWA was created for a specific purpose which is evaluation of the safety of the European TEN-T and primary road network in line with the Road Infrastructure Safety Management (RISM) Directive requirements. It facilitates both reactive and proactive road infrastructure safety assessment. It is recommended for application outside urban areas, except for urban motorways. It considers the presence of vulnerable road users, such as bicyclists and pedestrians. Drawing on the Star Ratings methodology, NWA was developed to evaluate the European TEN-T primary roads network in line with the requirements of the RISM directive.

The application is divided into several steps, starting with selecting the road type. Data is collected in two stages. The first stage refers to overview data, which aims to support road segmentation in homogeneous sections or fixed-length sections. The second stage, after complete segmentation, seeks to increase the level of detail, with data collected by section. For the nine elements with data collected on phase 2, crash modification factors (CMF) and reduction factors are estimated and used to calculate the proactive score. The model presents a multiplicative structure as the iRAP model but frames the level of risk in three bands:

low, intermediate, and high risk, and does not facilitate any fatality estimation modelling procedures. The proactive NWA method does not take into account the effects of speeding related to the infrastructure in built safety since it does not consider the operating speed variable. The overall section rating is calculated based on both reactive and proactive assessment and rated in five levels of risk (Very High priority to Very Low Priority) for the purpose of reporting according to the 2019 RISM Directive NWRSA requirements. (European Commission, 2023)..

3.1.11.3 The Australian National Risk Assessment Model (ANRAM)

ANRAM is a FSI estimation protocol calibrated specifically for Australia. It uses the iRAP Star Rating model input data to provide estimates of fatal and severe injuries for a typical five-year period based on six road stereotypes, section length and AADT (Austroads, 2014). The model relies on Safety Performance Functions (SPF) estimated using crash-recorded variables for the Victoria region from 2005 to 2009, combined with road inventory and AADTs. It only accounts for vehicle occupant crashes (that is, not other road user groups) and is specific to the Australian road classification system and geometric characteristics (Austroads, 2020).

3.1.11.4 The Infrastructure Risk Assessment Model for New Zealand (IRR)

As with the NWA and ANRAM, the Infrastructure Risk Rating (IRR) developed by Waka Kotahi NZ Transport Agency used the iRAP Star Ratings as starting points to define road features and operational attributes well as the coding guideline. Yet, the IRR model is a simplified model considering only eight attributes. The attributes were defined by their contribution to risk and the potential to code automation based on data sources like aerial imagery, road asset management datasets and street view imagery. The results are the overall classification of the individual level of risk (Waka Kotahi NZ Transport Agency, 2022). In addition to risk scanning, the tool has also been used as a speed management tool (Amoh-Gyimah et al., 2019). Not application in urban areas or for VRU's safety as identified.

Table 3-6 presents a summary of the relevant attributes of the road safety assessments methodologies reviewed.

Methodology	iRAP Star Ratings, FSIs and SRIP	NWA	ANRAM	IRR
Type of approach	Reactive/ Proactive	Reactive/ Proactive	Proactive	Proactive
Number attributes considered	56	22	42	8
VRU's identification of risk	Directly	Indirectly	No	No
Application in urban areas	Yes	Only in urban motorways.	Yes. Urban roadtypes considered in the analysis	Yes. Urban environment considered in the land use attribute.
Outcomes and levels of risk identified	5 levels of risk (1 to 5 stars) Collective and/or individual risk	5 levels of risk (Very High priority to Very Low Priority) Individual risk	FSI crashes (for a five-year period) for a given road section Collective and/or individual risk	5 levels of risk (Low risk to High risk) Individual risk

Table 3-6 Summary of road safety assessment methodologies reviewed.

3.1.11.5 The academic perspective of infrastructure assessments

In an earlier study, Gregoriades (2007) proposed a safety prediction early warning system to allow more time for authorities to react to highly unsafe/risky situations. The aim of the study was to enhance traditional agent-based simulation with Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN) and, as a result, improve crash probability predictions. To achieve this, the author exploited real-time observations from a simulated network, enhanced them with a multi-agent model that provided real-time information on the state of the network and introduced crash scenarios via Monte Carlo simulation. The BBN model was ultimately developed by exploiting data including traffic volumes, road network characteristics, weather conditions, and driving behaviours, among others, and the application was characterized as successful overall.

Furthermore, Gregoriades et al. (2010) expanded on this research direction with the intent of providing validation for safety requirements of considered road safety designs of networks. This is achieved once again by integrating BBN technologies on agent-based simulations. A noteworthy strength of BBN is that it can be informed by prior knowledge, whether empirical or from estimations based on past literature. The conditional probability tables exploited by the model were populated by variables that were significant predictors in correlation with past crash records. The developed Road Safety Analyser (RoSA) tool achieved satisfactory performance, though the authors noted that further refinements were needed.

Regarding particular infrastructure elements, microsimulation models can become increasingly composite to reflect the element or environment under consideration. Specifically, Tan et al. (2012) developed a microscopic simulation model to assess the safety of signalized intersections. To create it, a number of key behavioural aspects of road users were considered, such as the stop-go decision at the onset of a yellow light, turning paths, turning speeds, start-up response time, and pedestrian gap acceptance. These aspects were independently developed as simulation sub-models and integrated in the overall model, while limited validation with a real intersection enhanced by image processing also took place in the study.

Other infrastructure elements have been also considered from different scopes, such as by the study of Testa et al. (2022) who investigated ways to obtain values for structural loads from traffic for the assessment of bridges. The authors utilized microscopic simulation to obtain OD values in order to explore

the structural safety of bridges, using pay-toll data and regional registration data as simulation inputs, along with certain assumptions for traffic behaviour. While this is not a strictly crash-based or road safety assessment per se, the traffic simulations employed in this work provided the means of solving this network-level issue.

3.1.11.6 Countries or road type-specific methodologies

The literature brings a series of initiatives of developing road safety assessments methodologies that are country specific. In Europe, they have the form of Crash Prediction Models and can be found for Italy (la Torre et al., 2019), Czech republic (Ambros et al., 2019), Portugal (da Costa et al., 2018) and other. Most of these models are also developed for set of road types like freeways or motorways (Ambros et al., 2019; la Torre et al., 2019) and national roads or highways (Ambros et al., 2019; da Costa et al., 2018).

Using the traffic conflict technique when using microscopic simulation, several safety implications were evaluated for highways in specific. For instance, a study conducted by Habtemichael and De Picado Santos (2014) investigated aggressive driving in motorways for different traffic conditions using simulated conflicts to determine crash-risk, and Post Encroachment Time (PET) and travel time to determine the severity levels of the expected crashes. A similar study explored freeway interchange merging areas by obtaining the hourly composite risk indexes as well as developing a multivariate linear regression model (Li et al., 2016). In addition, a recent study investigated specifically the influence of the left hard shoulder on the safety of vehicles traveling on multi-lane highways, based on conflict characteristics under different numbers of lanes (Zhao et al. 2022a). A critical characteristic of freeways is managed lanes, which can improve traffic mobility and generate revenue for transportation agencies. Therefore, research also focused on specifying the safest accessibility level and identifying the safest weaving length near access zones based on simulated traffic conflicts along with a conflict frequency analysis (Saad et al. 2018). Another relevant simulation study explored the traffic behaviour and vehicle interactions in a road interchange of highway by quantifying the impacts of speed limit variations on both traffic and safety (Ribeiro et al. 2019). Finally, the impacts of low-speed vehicles on expressway traffic safety has been also examined and the characteristics of the affected vehicles were defined in a study conducted by Xu et al. (2022).

Focusing on rural road environments, the potential effects of an overtaking assistant for two-lane rural roads were identified through a microscopic traffic simulation study by Hegeman et al. (2009), indicating that a safety improvement can be accomplished without negative consequences for traffic efficiency and driver comfort.

3.1.11.7 Risk assessments for urban environments

The traffic microscopic simulation approach was used on investigating the risk assessment for urban networks as well. Due to traffic congestion noticed in urban environments, signal setting and multiple turning-lane assignment at intersections was explored in a microscopic simulation study conducted by Li and Sun (2019) taking into account road safety based on vehicle conflicts and pedestrian interference. Another safety issue of urban environments related to driving behaviour is that drivers run red traffic lights at signalized intersections. Therefore, research efforts have been made in order to investigate the possible causes and effectiveness of countermeasures especially when crash data are not available or reliable for statistical analysis. Lee et al. (2018) proposed a traffic simulation conflict-based approach for evaluating the red light running countermeasures and tested the most prevalent scenarios, which were: increasing the yellow signal interval duration, installing an advance warning sign, and a camera. Moreover, a different simulation study explored the safety impacts of a protected intersection design for bicyclists concluding that improves road safety (Preston and Pulugurtha, 2022; Montella et al., 2020; Riccardi et al., 2022).

With regards to public transport, a microscopic traffic simulation modeling approach was also adopted in a study conducted by Goh et al. (2014) in order to quantify the road safety effects of implementation of bus lanes. On a similar note, Kaparias et al. (2020) wished to extend a previously created predictive

evaluation tool, covering pollution and traffic efficiency, named CONDUITS_DST. The extension aimed to take into consideration correlations of traffic characteristics to road safety indicators. As a case study, a bus priority signaling system in the city of Brussels was investigated. The simulation models had been tested based on data from simulation models obtained before and after implementing the signaling system. Both the segment level and the network level were considered. The authors note a satisfactory performance for the tool extension, which detected both positive and negative effects of the public transport priority signaling system integration in the urban center of Brussels.

Olmez et al. (2021) noted the more frequent speeding instances in urban environments. Their study was thus incentivized to exploit agent-based microsimulation modelling and to correlate collisions with speeding and traffic density parameters. The authors used autonomous agents to achieve an overall heterogeneous global sample. In addition, the authors considered the utility of higher traffic density as a speeding deterrent tool to reduce crashes caused by speeding and thus increase road safety levels. The study slightly deviates from the literature in a sense that collisions increase disproportionately highly as traffic density increases at low and modest traffic densities; however, collisions behave more proportionately after a critical point in mid-range density. Moreover, vehicles adhering closer to speed limits were found to linearly reduce collisions.

Another study (Petrov et al., 2020) proposed a privacy ensuring emergency vehicle approaching warning system (PEEV-WS), which was determined as a sub-category of Vehicular Ad hoc NETWORKS (VANETs). An interesting subtask involving microscopic simulation was created in order to determine whether PEEV-WS provided simulated drivers with sufficient reaction times, which was confirmed to be the case. An earlier study had followed a similar vein, investigating the a-priori introduction of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) through microsimulation (Lundgren & Tapani, 2005). The authors developed a longitudinal control part of the driving task described by a car-following microscopic simulation model; they concluded that ADAS-induced behavioural changes are important to consider while monitoring road safety levels.

3.1.11.8 Road safety assessment for automated mobility

Since there is lack of historical generalizable crash data especially in case of high market penetration rates of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs), microscopic simulation method is considered as an ideal approach of studying automated mobility impacts on safety. For this reason, research has been also focused on this direction. A review of several recent microsimulation studies in CAV safety impacts based on surrogate measures of safety, with focus on highway segments, can be found in Papadimitriou et al. (2022). This review concludes that while most studies indicate substantial safety improvements by higher traffic penetration rates of CAVs, the simulation methodologies and specific metrics and their thresholds vary considerably among studies, and a common framework is lacking.

In particular, a microsimulation study conducted by Elawady et al. (2022) investigated the impact of CAVs on intersection traffic safety using the SSAM under different penetration rates of CAV conditions. Additionally, Jeong and Oh (2017) proposed a methodology to assess the effectiveness of active vehicle safety systems (AVSSs) that correspond to Level 2 vehicle automation using a microscopic traffic simulator and SSAM to derive indirect safety measures. A similar research which focused on validating simulated conflicts, applied SSAM as well, for a case study of recently developed CAV application (Essa and Sayed, 2020).

An ongoing challenge facing the entire transport sector is the integration of CAVs together with conventional, human-driven traffic and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) such as pedestrians and cyclists. Koopmann et al. (2022) sought to investigate this issue by considering an intelligent controller installed on an urban intersection in a microscopic simulation scenario, which would integrate behavioural traits of conventional or automated mobility and all other road user types. The developed model featured a complex architecture per road user category, while also being enhanced by game theory applications to better express the interactions between road users while negotiating passage through the intersection.

Results are mentioned to be yet preliminary and quite demanding in implementation efforts, with possible margins in traffic efficiency.

In case of connected vehicles, there is a continuous stream of location data susceptible to tracking attacks. To that end, a microscopic traffic simulation framework was developed, synthesizing several silence-based location privacy schemes by Xin et al. (2019). Nevertheless, there is a critical element with regards to automated vehicle control systems relying on the use of either onboard range sensors or vehicle-to-vehicle wireless communications, which is the delay in data acquisition. Hence a microsimulation study by Liu et al. (2006) attempted to assess the safety impacts of delayed information of intelligent vehicle control system applications and highlighted that the vehicle control systems operation is significantly affected. Moreover, the steadily increasing of CAV levels is a fact in transit services as well, and hence insights about transit services safety such as automated point-to-point shuttle bus services (Oikonomou et al., 2020) and autonomous on-demand mobility services (Mourtakos et al., 2021) have been also given based on simulated traffic conflicts.

It is worth highlighting that connected mobility might enable the calculations of new indicators, or to facilitate application opportunities of existing ones, such as the crash potential index (CPI) computed in a study by Jo et al. (2021) with data that were also compatible with DRAC calculation. Furthermore, as the traditional surrogate safety metrics have been mostly established for conventional vehicles, there are many difficulties when they are used for the assessment of automated vehicles. For this reason, proactive metrics were used instead by Mattas et al. (2019). Specifically, the proactive fuzzy surrogate safety metric (PFS) and the critical fuzzy surrogate safety metric (CFS) for rear end collisions have been developed and the results indicated their robustness on evaluating the safety level in the longitudinal direction. These fuzzy surrogate safety metrics were further used in a different study by Mattas et al. (2021), in which a fuzzy controller was developed for adaptive cruise control (ACC) and validated using real-world data and traffic simulation. In addition, the existing models used to simulate vehicular traffic are considered as not valid to predict traffic flows under increasing amounts of vehicle automation. Hence in a study by van Lint et al. (2016), an advanced open-source simulation framework named OpenTrafficSim was proposed, offering the incremental extension of microscopic models with explanatory mental models, and going one step further for the next generation of traffic simulation models that are needed in the coming decades.

3.2 Modal shift models

The literature was reviewed in two categories: mode choice modelling with the Random Utility Models (RUM), and mode choice modelling with Machine Learning models.

3.2.1 Definition of modal shift

The concept of modal shift acts as a basis for the following sections. The expression "Modal Shift (MS)" is derived from the term "Mode Choice (MC)". MC is the decision-making process by individuals or person groups (or can also be termed as travel behaviour) while choosing a mode of transport (e.g., Bike) from a set of available alternative modes (e.g., Bike, Walk, Car or Public transport (PuT)) to travel from the origin (O) to the destination (D) (D. A. Hensher & Button, 2007; D. A. ; Hensher & Button, 2008; Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2014) for various trip purposes (e.g., Shopping, Commuting, Education or leisure). Factors like travel time, cost, convenience, comfort, safety and environmental concerns significantly influence mode choice decisions (Ilahi et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021; McCarthy et al., 2017; Rahul & Verma, 2013). Mathematically, mode choice is expressed in terms of the probability (or percentage) of using one particular mode (e.g., Bike) out of all the available modes of transport (e.g., Bike, Car and PuT).

The MS refers to the change in the probability or percentage (either an increase in the probability or a decrease from the base value) of using a specific mode out of all the available modes of transport by individuals or person groups for different purposes (Batty et al., 2015). MS may arise with or without

artificial (human) intervention, e.g., artificially, MS may be induced (by changing factors like travel cost, time, convenience etc.) to achieve particular objectives like:

- Reducing congestion
- Reducing carbon footprint
- Improving air quality
- Promoting sustainability

For example, an MS towards active modes from the mode car can reduce the carbon footprint substantially (Batty et al., 2015; Luderer et al., 2021). Naturally, MS may occur due to changes in economic and social conditions (e.g., higher economic prosperity may induce an MS towards the mode car from the mode PuT) (Pucher, 1994). After a brief definition of MC and MS, the methods and methodologies for modelling MC and, subsequently, the methods and methodologies of inducing MS will be discussed in the following sections.

3.2.2 Modelling Mode Choice (MC)

MC deals with the choice of a particular mode by a user or user group out of all other available modes. Classically, these types of problems are modelled with choice modelling technique. Although initially aggregated models were used to model or predict the MC. These models or approaches focused on the choices of the modes made by an average individual for the trips between an origin and destination (Domencich & McFadden, 1975). These approaches were:

- non-behavioural and replicated the results according to the conditions existing during the survey.
- not policy-oriented.
- based on the aggregation of the survey data.

To overcome these problems, disaggregated modelling approaches gained popularity during the 1960s. The data for this modelling typology were collected at the individual or household level. Similarly, the parameters of these models were also estimated across the individual or household level (Barff et al., 1982). Statistically, the dependent variables of the mode choice models are discrete and finite (e.g., if the mode is taken(1) or not(0)). In contrast, the independent variables are generally continuous (M. E. Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 2006). Nevertheless, the current techniques of MC modelling can be classified under two major categories, namely, Random Utility Model (RUM) and Machine Learning Models (MLM). This classification is explained in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7 Methodologies of mode choice modelling

1. **Model choice and set-up:** An in-depth identification and categorisation of the transport modes are carried out to determine the model class and type to be used for MC modelling. A suitable analytical (choice) model (some examples of analytical models used for MC modelling are Logit, Probit or Nested Logit) is then chosen based on the identification and categorisation of the transport modes. This model is then appropriately set up (steps like the declaration of the variables and variable types) to initiate the modelling process.
2. **Model estimation and assessment:** Once the first step is over, the model is estimated with the help of the stated preference survey data. After the estimation process, the MC model can produce results (in terms of probabilities or percentages) for every mode usage. These probabilities are also known as the mode share of the respective modes.
3. **Model validation and calibration:** The estimated MC model's initial results or outputs often differ vastly from the real-world scenario (observations). Thus, it is validated by comparing the outputs with real-world observations (data). The model is calibrated by altering the estimated parameters and run again to generate new outputs. The outputs are re-validated with real-world data. This process is resumed till convergence is achieved. This step ensures plausible result delivery from the MC model.
4. **Prediction and sensitivity analyses:** Once the MC model is calibrated and the model outputs are validated, the model can be used for predicting scenario-specific mode shares. The values of the input variables may also be changed accordingly to conduct sensitivity analyses of the mode shares. This step is carried out to observe the effectiveness of the modifications (e.g., modifications in time or cost) in travel demand.

The MC modelling process is described in Figure 3-8 below.

Figure 3-8 Process of MC modelling. Revised from (Pestel et al., 2016)

3.2.2.1 Random Utility Models or Methods (RUM)

RUMs are the traditional models or methods of modelling the choices of individuals or groups from an available set of discrete alternatives (Horowitz et al., 1994). The preferences of the individual or a group for a particular alternative from a set of alternatives are described by a utility function or simply utility. The individual or a group chooses the alternative (from the available set of alternatives) for which the perceived utility is highest for that individual or that group (Kamakura et al., 1982). Table 3.8 (Reproduced from (Ratrouf et al., 2014)) presents the main characteristics of the RUM (traditional mode choice modelling techniques).

3.2.2.2 Machine Learning Models or Methods

Traditionally, RUMs are used to model the mode choice for predicting travel demand. Due to the clear mathematical and statistical framework, the Multinomial Logit Model (MNL) has been widely used for MC modelling. However, the MNL model follows the independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA) assumption, i.e., the probability of choosing a particular alternative from a given set of alternatives is independent of all other alternatives. Nevertheless, multiple studies have shown that users/travellers do not follow this assumption during choosing alternatives (modes of transport), leading to biased forecasts. Several discrete models like Probit, Nested Logit or mixed logit models were proposed over time to overcome these problems. However, estimating these models is complicated compared to the MNL model (Tamim Kashifi et al., 2022). Apart from these problems, there are other problems with the standard RUM methods or models, e.g., MNL requires a particular type of input data structure which, if disturbed, may produce erroneous outputs.

On the contrary, ML modelling methods are not based on strict prior assumptions and allow the computers to probe the data structure, have a more flexible modelling architecture and often result in better predictive capabilities (Jamal et al., 2021). In order to vanquish the problems of the RUM methods, ML methods are

gaining importance in travel behaviour research. However, the research and the methodologies used in ML methods must (need to be) be more cohesive (Hillel et al., 2021). Table 3.9 (Reproduced from Tamim Kashifi et al., (2022)) below presents the main characteristics of the ML mode choice modelling techniques).

3.2.2.3 Towards Modal Shift (MS) modelling

As discussed above, MS is a term derived from MC. However, modelling MS, i.e., inducing a change in MC (from one mode to another), is a potent tool that planners, policymakers and modellers employ to bring desirable changes like congestion reduction, carbon footprint reduction or improving air quality. The methods utilised to alter the MS are often known as Pull and Push measures (Batty et al., 2015; C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, 2021).

Pull measures: These measures encourage or persuade the users to use the alternative towards which the MS is planned to be shifted, e.g., Discounted or subsidised PuT tickets (Levi et al., 2021). *Push measures:* These measures are the opposite of the pull measures. Push measures dissuade the users from using the alternative from which the MS is planned to be shifted, e.g., Heavy road tax for using cars (Levi et al., 2021). Figure 3-9 below describes pull and push measures to alter the MS. The colour green signifies the pull measures while the colour red denotes the push measures. In addition, Figure 3-9 below presents the main characteristics of the ML mode choice modelling techniques.

Some strong pull and push measures that may induce an MS are:

- **Pull Measure:** PuT pricing or cost (Witte et al., 2006), (Levi et al., 2021), Safety and Security concerning the active modes (Levi et al., 2021), Comfort concerning PuT (Foote, 2004), Information flow concerning PuT (Outwater et al., 2011), Frequency and reliability concerning PuT (Redman, Friman, Gärling, & Hartig, 2013), Speed or Journey time concerning PuT (Currie & Delbosc, 2011), Multimodality/Ease of use concerning PuT (Reis, Fabian Meier, Pace, & Palacin, 2013)
- **Push Measures:** Congestion charging/pricing concerning ca (Levi et al., 2021; Nykvist & Whitmarsh, 2008), Parking regulations concerning car (Levi et al., 2021), Urban planning/Form for respective modes.

Model	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
Probit model (1960s – till present)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The utility equations contain an error term which is mode specific and has a general covariance structure. Utility functions can be simplified because of the use of mode-specific error terms. Significance and elasticity of each variable can be easily investigated through statistical tests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extra computations required due to randomness effect considered for each mode. Difficult to develop with a large number of variables or modes because of the covariance matrices. Conflict with IIA assumption 	(Willumsen & Ortuzar, 2014), (Keane, 1992), (D. McFadden, 1973)
Logit model (MNL) (1970 – till present)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less computations are required as compared to probit models. Utility functions are of the same nature as a regression model. Significance and elasticity of each variable can be easily investigated through statistical tests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mode related randomness is not considered. They have fixed properties that have to be satisfied. Difficult to develop with a large number of variables. 	(Hensher & Greene, 2003), (Bhat, 1998a), (Daniel McFadden, 1987), (Foerster, 1979)
Nested logit models (1990 – till present)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of exogenous factors such as housing locations and policy issues. Multidimensional analysis is possible by incorporating land-use plans or infrastructure investment alternatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-classification of data and gathering sufficient data for each class to establish relationships. Shared unobserved attributes can be associated with only one of the choice dimensions. 	(Lee & Waddell, 2010), (Bhat, 1998b), (Bhat, 1998a)
Mixed multinomial and latent class logit models (1990 – till present)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of random coefficients. More suitable to capture individual taste heterogeneity. More flexibility than multinomial and nested logit model. Accounts for every individual through random components of choice through distribution of coefficients. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Selection of distribution function for coefficients. More computations than other logit models. Requires better quality and amount of data than logit models for pre classification. 	(M. Ben-Akiva et al., 2002), (J. L. Horowitz, Koppelman, & Lerman, 1986), (Foerster, 1979),

Table 3-7 Comparison of the RUM (traditional mode choice modelling techniques). Reproduced: (Ratrou et al., 2014)

ML Algorithm	Brief description	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
Logistic Regression (LR)	A supervised machine learning classification algorithm that is aimed at finding the probabilities of discrete outcome categories.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High interpretability and simple architecture • Efficient training and easy implementation • The algorithm can be extended to multiclass problems. • Works well if the data has linearly separable features 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often fails to capture the nonlinear and complicated relationships between variables • LR algorithm is efficient to predict discrete functions only • Requires large dataset for training • Requires average or no multicollinearity between the predictor variables 	(Cantarella & Luca, 2005)
Decision Tree (DT)	DT is a structured-tree classifier that implements decision nodes and leaf nodes in an iterative manner to perform classification tasks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High interpretability and easy implementation • Fast learning speed • High tolerance to missing values • Superior to process data with irrelevant/redundant features • Very little or no data pre-processing is required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prone to overfitting • Weak adaptability to process non-linear data • Output is very sensitive to any small changes in the data • A sub-trees in DT can be copied several times 	(Karlaftis, 2004)
Random Forest (RF)	RF is an ensemble classifier that employs the bagging learning technique combining individual DTs to improve the model predictive performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong and robust to outliers less prone to overfitting • Easy implementation • High tolerance to missing values • Low risk of overfitting • No requirement of feature scaling • Works well with both categorical and continuous data • The relative importance of each feature on the prediction may be measured 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • low learning speed • complex model structure like DT, the RF algorithm is sensitive to small variations in the data • Requires more computational power and resources as numerous trees are built to combine their output. 	(Rashidi & Hasegawa, 2014)

Table 3-8 Comparison of the ML mode choice modelling techniques. Reproduced: (Tamim Kashifi et al., 2022).

ML Algorithm	Brief description	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)	MLP belongs to the family of feed-forward neural networks which utilizes back propagation training algorithms and multi-layered network structure to minimize the model error.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considers nonlinear and latent relationships • Works well with large input data • Provide quick prediction after model training • Possess robust adaptive learning ability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Black box nature and lack of interpretability • Requires tuning of a large number of hyperparameters • Prone to overfitting • Selection of optimal hidden layers can be tedious • Sensitive to feature scaling • Needed more computational complexity 	(Assi, Shafiullah, Nahiduzzaman, & Mansoor, 2019)
LightGBDT	LightGBDT is a relatively new applied machine learning based on gradient facilitated DTs to solve high-dimensional and complex classification tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast training, and good interpretability this algorithm is highly efficient in terms of data handling, computational speed, and prediction accuracy • Low memory usage • Improved compatibility with large datasets compared to other boosting algorithms • Support parallel learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex model structure • Can easily overfit for small datasets 	(Tamim Kashifi et al., 2022)

Table 3-9 – continued: Comparison of the ML mode choice modelling techniques. Reproduced: (Tamim Kashifi et al., 2022).

Figure 3-9 Pull and Push measures in action. Revised from (Batty et al., 2015)

3.2.2.4 Implications on the PHOEBE predictive assessment framework

MC modelling followed by forecasting MS play a critical role in the project PHOEBE. Thus the research gaps mentioned above should guide the development of the methodological framework of the project PHOEBE. The framework should account for the emerging modes of transport like micro-mobility, electromobility and autonomous modes. These modes can be addressed in a two-step process, namely (Narayanan & Antoniou, 2023):

- Choosing and setting up proper choice models (e.g., logit or nested logit or hybrid-choice latent-class models) from the available (set of) models, and
- Accommodating the attributes of such modes into the chosen choice model as explanatory variables (including relevant latent variables) in the utility function of the chosen model.

Proper research is needed to ascertain the explanatory variables (including the latent variables capturing the properties that are difficult to quantify, e.g., driving skills and experiences) and the model selection methodology. Incorporating latent variables opens the avenue of using the hybrid-choice latent-class models for MC modelling. The following aspects need to be considered:

- The spatial impact on the mode choice. Multiple methods can be explored to solve the impacts of the spatial effects on MC (Abouelela et al., 2023; Duran-Rodas et al., 2019; Motoaki & Daziano, 2015):
- If the input dataset (to the chosen MC model) contains information regarding the origin and destination of a trip, then proper explanatory variables can be included in the utility function of the MC model. Thus the modal share can be calculated with a spatial resolution.

- Development of a suitable hybrid-choice latent-class model that will incorporate the properties related to the spatial impacts on the MC and calculate modal share with spatial resolution.
- Specific data-driven modelling methods exist that look into the historical ridership of bike sharing (dependent variable) against the built environment (independent variable) data and forecast future ridership using statistical regression techniques. Such a model can be developed and plugged in with the regular MC model to generate modal share with a spatial resolution.
- The development of innovative methods of the MC model estimation, validation and calibration by including the ML techniques. The hybrid-choice latent-class models are complex and difficult to estimate and calibrate. Therefore, innovative ML techniques can be deployed to estimate and calibrate such models. The PHOEBE Framework can also draw a scientific comparison between the traditional and upcoming methods (ML) of the MC model estimation, validation and calibration.
- Sustainable transportation by focusing on and promoting mobility equity and road safety across all the person groups (including vulnerable and marginalised road users). This can be achieved by identifying the vulnerable and marginalised road user groups (e.g., older people and families with young children) and the factors influencing the mode choice among these person groups, followed by incorporating these factors (in terms of proper explanatory variables, including latent variables) into the chosen MC model.
- The impacts of information flow and social networks on MC, travel behaviour and travel demand. This can be achieved by incorporating the latent variables pertaining to the use of social networks and respective apps into the MC models. Further, a tour-based MC model can be developed instead of a trip-based model to accommodate the effects of the information flow for a complete tour (e.g., the use of different modes for a complete tour due to information updates through social networks and travel apps during the tour) (Chaniotakis et al., 2022).

3.3 Induced demand modelling

The literature review of induced travel demand is structured in four separate sections. The sections are (i) causes of the induced demand, (ii) the need for accounting the induced demand, (iii) classification of the different induced demand types, and (iv) available modelling and analysis tools and techniques.

3.6.1.1 Causes of the induced demand

The definition of induced demand mentions the increment in the number of trips or travel demand under specific circumstances. Research shows that multiple reasons can lead to an incremental increase in travel demand or induced demand, that can be primarily categorised under:

- Infrastructure improvements
- Introduction of the new modes of travel

The Figure 3-10, below presents the different causes of the induced travel demand.

Reducing congestion is the primary motivation for **infrastructure improvements**, e.g., building new roads or introducing traffic controls like signals. According to Cascetta (2009), a transportation system consists of multiple supply and demand sub-systems that are interconnected by complicated relationships. Consequently, whenever an improvement action is planned addressing any such sub-system, there are unavoidable positive or negative impacts on the other sub-systems. E.g. on the one hand, widening roads to bring down congestion offers better driving comfort and reduces travel time; on the other hand, it attracts more travellers to carry out trips on the widened roads generating induced travel demand (Cascetta, 2009; Speck, 2018). Thus the actual reduction in congestion due to such improvements is likely to be overestimated if the effects of induced travel demand are not considered.

Figure 3-10 Reasons of the generation of the induced demand

Decorla-Souza & Cohen (1999) is one of the earliest research works demonstrating induced travel demand's role in a highway expansion project (DeCorla-Souza & Cohen, 1999). These findings are also supported by other research studies (Duranton & Turner, 2011; Hymel et al., 2010; Small, 2013). Decorla-Souza & Cohen (1999) also provides the probable sources of induced demand due to infrastructure improvements as listed below:

- Increase in person trip production (P) related development.
- Increase in person trip attraction (A) related development.
- Increase in the number of daily motorised person trip P's and A's per development unit.
- Increase in average motorised person trip distance.
- Increase in share of person travel by private motorised vehicles.
- Shift in vehicle travel to improved facilities from unimproved facilities within a corridor or to an improved corridor due to traffic diversion from other corridors.

There are research studies, that also focus on the long-term aspects of induced travel demand caused due to infrastructure improvements. Cervero (2003) utilised data from 1980 to 1994 of California's region dealing with freeway expansion, traffic volumes, demographic, geographic aspects, and vehicle-miles-travelled to calculate long-term elasticities (Cervero, 2003). Noland & Quddus (2006) found that increasing road area and introducing traffic signal control systems for decongesting the traffic flow could induce additional travel demand (Noland & Quddus, 2006). Apart from infrastructure improvements, speed increase also induces additional travel demand (Pagliara & Preston, 2013).

Additional travel demand is also generated or induced when a **new mode of transport** is appended to the existing system. Multiple research studies support that trip production and attraction are positively affected by the geographic accessibility at the ends of the trips (Koenig, 1980; Robinson & Vickerman, 1976; Thill & Kim, 2005). Often the motivation to add a new mode of transport into an existing system is to improve accessibility, comfort and to reduce travel time (Thill & Kim, 2005). Air mobility is one such mode that could

induce substantial travel demand (Lineberger et al., 2018). Recent studies show that air mobility can induce and produce enormous travel demand where the prices of air mobility are relatively low (Balać et al., 2019).

In addition to air mobility, transport modes like shared mobility can also induce additional travel demand. Shared mobility provides services between the existing public and private modes of transportation. It provides door-to-door service without vehicle ownership. (Susan Shaheen et al., 1999). Given the increased accessibility and low prices, shared autonomous vehicles can increase travel distance and considerably induce additional travel demand (Elliot & Shaheen, 2016).

3.6.1.2 The need for accounting the induced demand

Traditionally, the travel demand forecast is carried out based on the factors like land use, demographics, income and employment. These are exogenous factors. While forecasting the travel demand through a model based on the factors mentioned above, the phenomenon of traffic flow correlates strongly with fluid flow in the road network. However, according to Jacobsen (1997), traffic movements correlate to the property of gas to expand in all directions and fill up any available space (Jacobsen, 1997).

The similarities of the properties of the traffic movements with the properties of gas manifest that additional capacity on the supply side (available space) stimulates auxiliary demand. This additional travel demand is known as induced demand. The generation of induced demand can be attributed to the different transportation systems' extreme interconnectivity and complicated relationships (Cascetta, 2009). The complicated interactions create a paradox or a vicious cycle between the improved infrastructure and induced demand (Gorham, 2009). Thus any infrastructure improvement without proper consideration of induced demand may not generate desirable results. The Figure 3-, below represents the vicious cycle of the induced travel demand.

Figure 3-11 Vicious cycle of induced travel demand (Gorham, 2009)

The induced travel demand may have several other repercussions, including temporary modal shifts, temporary travel speed and time changes and safety concerns illustrating the need to model the induced demand (Lee et al., 1999; Litman, 2017).

3.6.1.3 Classification of the different induced demand types

In order to model the phenomenon of induced demand, it is crucial to categorise the different types of induced demand. The categories under which the induced demand can be classified are:

- a) Categorisation based on supply side capacity (Benjamin Schneider, 2018; Litman, 2017)
- b) Categorisation based on the types of induced demands (Benjamin Schneider, 2018; Gorham, 2009)

There are four types of induced demands according to the **categorisation based on supply side capacity** (Benjamin Schneider, 2018; Litman, 2017):

- a) Generated traffic: Additional peak-period vehicle trips on a particular roadway occur when capacity increases. This may include travel time, route, mode, destination and frequency shifts.
- b) Induced travel: An increase in total vehicle mileage due to roadway improvements that increase vehicle trip frequency and distance but exclude travel shifted from other times and routes.
- c) Latent demand: Additional trips would be made if travel conditions improved (less congested, higher design speeds, lower vehicle costs or tolls).
- d) Triple convergence: Increased peak-period vehicle traffic volumes result when roadway capacity increases, due to shifts from other routes, times and modes.

Any intervention on a selected transport supply element may lead to different kinds or **types of induced demand and impacts** (Benjamin Schneider, 2018; Gorham, 2009). These types of induced demands can be categorised as follows:

- a) Direct induced demand: It refers to the induced demands that are caused by the conscious decision of the travellers in the network. These demands are created when travellers consciously take advantage of the change in travel time by reorganising or alternating their travel patterns. These reorganisations can take place over different temporal frames, e.g., Instantaneous traveller response (immediate reorganisation in travel behaviour corresponding to the temporal, spatial or modal choice), Short-run traveller response (reorganisation in travel behaviour corresponding to their trip destination, trip chaining patterns or frequency) and Long-run traveller response (reorganisation in travel behaviour corresponding to their location choices, e.g., relocation of household or work location).
- b) Indirect induced demand: It refers to the increment in travel demand caused by a specific improvement in transport supply.
- c) Induced and diverted demand: It refers to the increment in travel demand that may have occurred anyway, i.e., either at some other place or time in a given network.

3.6.1.4 Available modelling and analysis tools and techniques

Analysing and modelling induced travel demand is similar to analysing and modelling normal travel behaviour. Discrete choice modelling is the most widely used mathematical and statistical tool to model induced travel demand. Section 3.2.2 about the State-of-the-Art of Modelling Mode Choice, should be referred to for a detailed analysis and modelling methodology. In addition to DCM, elasticity analysis is also used to analyse induced travel demand (DeCorla-Souza & Cohen, 1999).

However, the subtle difference between induced demand modelling and mode choice modelling is that the induced demand is not caused by the common reasons (e.g., population, economy etc.) that cause natural travel demand. Thus, it becomes crucial to identify the demand as induced or non-induced demand (Kalliga, 2021).

3.4 Socio-economic impact evaluation

Road traffic crashes involve economic and personal losses and implicate personal injuries and casualties. Often the costs arising due to these losses are not borne by those who have caused them. Therefore, RTA can be considered an external cost (Elvik, 1994). To eradicate these external costs, on the one hand, a detailed knowledge base about the damages that RTAs inflict on the economy needs to be acquired, and, on the other hand, proper (road) safety measures to reduce the RTAs need to be introduced. Such measures can be introduced at different stages of a crash scenario (Baum et al., 2000). The stages where these safety measures may be introduced are shown in Figure 3-12

Figure 3-12 Stages where road safety measures can be introduced. Reproduced from (Baum et al., 2000)

There exist several instruments to ensure road safety. According to United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), these instruments cover aspects like (Laurinavičius et al., 2012; UNECE, n.d.):

- Traffic rules
- Road signs and signals
- Construction and technical inspection of vehicles
- Road infrastructure
- Driving times and rest periods for professional drivers
- Safe transport of dangerous goods and hazardous materials

There are other instruments as well. The government needs to intervene by establishing road safety measures and policies to ensure road safety. To establish the measures and policies, the policymakers (often the government) must make a clear choice among these instruments to ascertain the highest social and economic returns. The socio-economic analysis is the tool or appraisal method to support the established policies and regulatory and investment priorities (Wesemann, 2000). A sound knowledge of the respective (quantitative and qualitative) methods of the socio-economic analyses is required to conduct

such an analysis of road safety measures. Some of the state-of-the-art methods of conducting socio-economic analysis are explained in the succeeding sections.

Once the selected studies are categorised, looking into the various methods deployed to carry out socio-economic analysis becomes necessary. A detailed review of the selected sources reveals the prevalent methods to carry out a socio-economic analysis of road safety measures and the principal sub-methods to sustain the cost and benefit calculations of the prevalent methods. While the "Cost-Benefit Analysis" is a very popular commonly used method (Baum et al., 2000; OECD, 2001; Wesemann, 2000a). There are also other methods for socio-economic assessment (Baum et al., 2000). The different methods of socio-economic analysis (and their sources) are shown in Figure 3-13, and the relevant studies are listed in Table 3.11.

Evaluation of the socio-economic impacts

Figure 3-13 Methods and facilitating (sub-)methods of socio-economic analysis of impacts of road safety measures

Methodology or method of analysis	Sources
Cost-Benefit Analysis	(Baum et al., 2000; Daniels et al., 2019; Elvik, 2001; Vecino-Ortiz & Hyder, 2014; Wesemann, 2000; Wijnen et al., 2009)
Cost-Effectiveness Analysis	(Baum et al., 2000; Chantith et al., 2021; OECD, 2001; Wesemann, 2000)
Willingness to Pay method	(Haddak et al., 2016; OECD, 2001; Rizzi & Ortúzar, 2006)
Multi-Criteria Processes	(Baum et al., 2000; OECD, 2001; Wesemann, 2000)
Before-After Analysis	(Elvik, 2002; Mpogas et al., 2017; Pu et al., 2021; Yanmaz-Tuzel & Ozbay, 2010)

Table 3-10 Existing methodologies of socio-economic analysis

3.4.1 Cost-Benefit Analysis

Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) is the most used quantitative method to assess or analyse the socio-economic impacts of road safety measures. CBA is a rather sophisticated and objective way of analysis. CBA traces its origins back to economic welfare theory. The cost component of the CBA is the costs incurred in setting up the measure, while the benefits are defined as savings through measures, i.e., the reduction in crash costs. A deployed measure is macro-economically profitable if (i) If the ratio of the benefits (of the measure) (BCR) to that of the costs (of the measure) is greater than or equal to 1 (Baum et al., 2000; Wesemann, 2000); and (ii) If the net present value (NPV) is positive, i.e., the difference between the benefits and the cost (Daniels et al., 2019).

To calculate the BCR and NPV, the benefits' values are expressed monetarily. Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$\text{Cost – Benefit Ratio (CBR)} = \frac{\text{Benefits}}{\text{Costs}} = \frac{\text{reduction of accident costs}}{\text{costs of measure}}$$

$$\text{Net present value (NPV)} = \text{Benefits} - \text{Costs}$$

As a way of understanding the costs and benefits, a cost-benefit balance sheet may be developed. The cost-benefit balance sheet of the construction of the second national airport in the Netherlands (in supplement to existing national airport at Schiphol) is presented below (Wesemann, 2000) in Table 3.12.

Costs	Benefits
Construction costs	Operating revenue
Modification of airspace structure	Net revenue from passengers and freight
Other costs (including road traffic infrastructure)	Indirect economic effects
	Noise nuisance at new airport
	Noise nuisance at Schiphol-
	Planning assimilation
	Employment opportunity
	Other effects

Table 3-11 Cost-benefit balance sheet of a second national airport in the Netherlands (Wesemann, 2000)

The analysis must carry out precise calculations of the RTA costs and benefits for calculating the CBR and NPV. There exist multiple methods to calculate RTA costs. Figure 3-14 presents the different methods for calculating RTA costs (Baum et al., 2000).

There are several metrics for calculating or estimating the benefits of road safety measures. One such metric is the value of statistical life (VOSL). VOSL is also called the value of life, the value of preventing fatality (VPF) or the implied cost of averting a fatality (ICAF) (Johansson, 2001; Vecino-Ortiz & Hyder, 2014).

Figure 3-14 Methods for calculating RTA costs (Baum et al., 2000)

One example of cost benefit analyses for road safety assessment is the iRAP Safer Roads Investment Plans (SRIP). The SRIP is one of the outputs of an iRAP assessment and aim to guide future road network safety upgrades. It provides a prioritised list of countermeasures that can cost-effectively reduce infrastructure-related risk. Comparing the cost of implementing the countermeasure with the reduction in crash costs resulting from its implementation, the model can identify the safety treatments that are economically advantageous to implement to prioritise investments. Some research already showed that for every increase in the star ratings the costs of the crashes per km is almost halved (Figure 3-) (McInerney and Fletcher, 2013).

The benefits are calculated based on the total estimated number of fatalities and serious injuries (FSI) on the network that the implementation of the countermeasure recommended can save. FSI estimates are made for each 100m segment of the existing road under existing conditions. Where Star Ratings represent the individual risk of a road to a user (i.e. likelihood and severity of a crash), fatality estimations represent

collective risk which accounts for exposure (i.e. road user volumes) and actual crash rates. More information about the FSI calculation can be found in the iRAP Methodology Factsheet n10 – Casualty Estimation and Calibration. (iRAP, 2014). The economic value of the benefits are represented by the Human Capital data, instead of WTP data to calculate VOSL (Vecino-Ortiz & Hyder, 2014). iRAP provides a set of equations that quantify the VOSL as a function of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita (Vecino-Ortiz & Hyder, 2014).

Figure 3-15 The relationship between Star Ratings and the cost of fatalities and serious injuries

The iRAP model can analyse more than 120 road improvement options. They represent commonly used engineering treatments that are on the list supported by their evidence on reducing road safety risk. More information about the safety treatments considered in the model can be found in the iRAP Methodology Factsheet n11. (iRAP, 2023). Some safety treatments have been developed to explicitly fulfil the need to incentive safe speeds in urban areas and promote safe travels for VRUs.

3.4.2 Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

The Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) is another method to analyse the socio-economic impact of road safety measures. Methodologically, CEA is closely related to CBA. In some instances, CEA is considered a variant of CBA (Wesemann, 2000). In CEA, we weigh the costs of road safety measures against their effects. In this case, the effects are not expressed monetarily (Baum et al., 2000; OECD, 2001). One way of carrying out CEA to evaluate a particular road safety measure is by using Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) (Chantith et al., 2021). ICER is also used to rank road safety measures in terms of their effectiveness. Mathematically, ICER is described as:

$$ICER = \frac{\text{Average Different of Cost (ADC)}}{\text{Average Different of unit of Effectiveness (ADE)}}$$

ADC represents the average change in the budget in the given time interval (the period from no road safety measure till its engagement). In contrast, ADE represents the average change in the number of deaths caused by RTA during the same time interval. The resultant ICER for each measure is then accounted for along with the four quadrants of the CEA plane shown below in Figure 3-16 and Figure 3-17 (Chantith et al., 2021).

		Number of Deaths	
		Decrease	Increase
Budget for Road Safety Policy	Increase	Quadrant II ADC > 0, while ADE < 0	Quadrant I ADC > 0, and ADE > 0
	Decrease	Quadrant III ADC < 0, and ADE < 0	Quadrant IV ADC < 0, while ADE > 0

Figure 3-16 CEA plane (four quadrant) (Chantith et al., 2021)

Quadrant II The road safety measure was effective, but still could not reduce the budget.	Quadrant I Road safety policy was not effective at all; resulting in an increase in both the cost and the deaths.
Quadrant III The expected goal. The policy was effective, the number of deaths and the budget decreased.	Quadrant IV The number of deaths increased, while the budget reduced. So, the policy was ineffective.

Figure 3-17 Quadrant explanation (Chantith et al., 2021)

3.4.2.1 Willingness to Pay method (WTP)

To explain the WTP method, a scenario is considered. Suppose a road safety measure or policy is expected to reduce the number of deaths caused by RTAs by n over a given time frame for a population of size P . Now, if v is the average amount each member of the population is willing to pay to fund the road safety measure for risk reduction, then the total amount to be paid by the population is $v \cdot P$. Thus, the willingness to pay per fatality is $v \cdot P/n$. According to the WTP method, this is also known as the value of preventing a fatality (VPF) (OECD, 2001).

Two different empirical approaches can estimate WTP for a given population:

- Revealed preference method (OECD, 2001)
- Stated preference method (also known as contingent valuation) (Antoniou, 2014; Rizzi et al., 2006).

3.4.2.2 Multi-Criteria Processes

As the name suggests, MCP relies on various explicit criteria of assessment. These criteria can differ significantly. Within MCP, scores are declared for every individual criterion. These scores have their respective individual units and thus cannot be aggregated over all the criteria. More significance can be attributed to specific criteria in MCP while conducting the assessment. The degree of importance of the criteria can be regulated by assigning suitable weights to the criteria. In case there is a significant divergence in the opinion amongst the decision-makers or policymakers, multiple sets of weighting factors can be added. Finally, the criteria are ranked according to their importance (weighting factors) (OECD, 2001; Wesemann, 2000). An example of MCP is given below in Figure 3-18.

A few MCP methods are listed below(OECD, 2001; Wesemann, 2000):

- Weighted aggregation method
- Goals achievement matrix
- Concordance analyses,
- Permutation method
- Regime method
- Multi-dimensional scale analysis
- Evamix approach.

Figure 3-18 Example of an MCP (Kanuganti et al., 2017)

3.4.2.3 Before-After Analysis

Alongside costs, the calculations of benefits are also an indispensable part of CBA. The benefits due to the introduction of a road safety measure for a period of n intervals with the level of severity s can be calculated as (Daniels et al., 2019):

$$Benefits_n = \sum_s Targetcrashes_s \times Effectiveness_s \times Crashcost_s$$

The effectiveness of the measure is expressed by employing the percentage reduction (PR) of either the number of crashes or the casualties as a consequence of the safety measure or by the Crash Modification Factor (CMF) (Daniels et al., 2019).

$$PR = 100 \times (1 - CMF)$$

The target crashes are the number of crashes that can be affected by the implemented measure. The crash cost represents the monetary value of the crashes. Several (sub-)methods could be employed to calculate the CMF. Some of such methods are listed below (Gross, 2010):

- Before-after with comparison group studies
- Empirical Bayes before-after studies
- Full Bayes before-after studies
- Cross-sectional studies
- Case-control studies
- Cohort studies

The Before-After Analysis is based on two major tasks, namely (Pu et al., 2021; Yanmaz-Tuzel & Ozbay, 2010):

1. Predicting the state of safety in the after-period in case the intervention or safety measure had not been enforced.
2. Estimating the safety in the after-period after enforcing the measure.

Bayesian methods are typically employed to carry out BAA. There are two most common Bayesian Methods, namely:

1. Full Bayesian method (FB)
2. Empirical Bayesian method (EB)

Overall and through the literature review conducted in the preceding sections, it can be deduced that there are multiple methods to carry out the socio-economic analysis of the impacts of road safety measures. Of all the available methods, CBA is the most popular method for this assignment (Baum et al., 2000; OECD, 2001; Wesemann, 2000). The popularity of CBA can be attributed to the following points (Baum et al., 2000; Wesemann, 2000):

- Data-driven decisions: CBA focuses on data and facts to help policymakers take decisions freely, thus minimising bias.
- Utilising latent costs and benefits: CBA accommodates almost all the potential costs and benefits associated with a particular road safety measure. Thus, many intangible costs and benefits can be realised through CBA.
- Primarily quantitative method: Since CBA translates all the tangible and intangible costs and benefits into monetary terms, it enables the decision-makers to make decisions more quantitatively than qualitatively.

Despite these advantages, there exist criticisms against CBA. According to Elvik (2001), there are five principal types of criticisms against CBA (Elvik, 2001):

- Rejecting the basic principle of CBA (for road safety measures)
- Excluding specific issues from the scope of calculation of costs and benefits.
- Setting policy objectives that are not amenable to CBA.
- Rejecting the need for maintaining a separation between policy objectives and policy programmes as required by CBA.
- Rejecting or denying the possibility of ever obtaining acceptably valid and reliable economic valuations of the consequences of alternative policy programmes.

The basic assumptions of CBA and common objections against these assumptions are listed in the Table 3.13.

Criterion of applicability	Basic principles or beliefs of cost-benefit analysis	Common objections to the basic tenets
Basic principles of cost-benefit analysis	Consumer sovereignty Willingness-to-pay as measure of value Welfare maximisation Irrelevance of distributive outcomes	Consumers do not know their own best Amounts paid depend on ability to pay, not just willingness Compensation of losers is rare in practice There are many invaluable goods
Types of issues	Efficient use of scarce resources desirable Fairness of distribution not an issue Basic rights not an issue	Fair distribution can be an overriding policy objective Protecting basic rights is not subject to a calculation of costs and benefits
Nature of policy objectives	Explicitly stated, but may be partly conflicting Amenable to trade-offs (not lexicographic) Policy objectives are not politically controversial	In some cases, vagueness in policy objectives is rational for politicians Some policy objectives are absolute constraints Political controversies cannot be solved by making calculations
Nature of policy programmes	Recursive in relation to policy objectives Effective in solving problem at hand Economically efficient (benefits exceed costs)	Sometimes maintaining a strict separation of means and ends is difficult Some policy programmes that are efficient may be unacceptable for other reasons
Consequences of policy programmes	All are known All can be valued monetarily	All consequences are never known Experimental policies are impossible Monetary valuations are incomplete or arbitrary

Table 3-12 Basic assumptions of CBA and common objections against these assumptions (Elvik, 2001)

It has already been explained that CEA is a close variant of CBA; thus, CEA also has these disadvantages like CBA. The methods of MCP utilise multiple weights to delineate a criterion's importance or significance. Often, these weights differ from one policymaker to another, making it an inconsistent method. However, the BAA method primarily utilises the Bayesian framework to analyse the impacts of any road safety measure. This method is mathematically and computationally more complicated than the preceding methods. However, BAA is a more evidence-oriented method that compares different candidate models (models developed to investigate the impacts of different road safety measures). Since BAA utilises the Bayesian framework and the posterior prediction capability of Bayesian approaches, it works well even when limited data are available (Pu et al., 2021; Yanmaz-Tuzel & Ozbay, 2010).

3.5 Data collection tools and methods

Accessing complete, good quality, and representative data is always a challenge for any kind of road safety risk assessment. Crash and non-crash data are relevant to comprehensive road safety assessments. The World Bank summarises the data requirements for the most common type of road safety assessments. Crash and FSI data, traffic speed and volumes, as well as road features, are the most common data needed to comprehensively assess existing roads or new projects (The World Bank, 2021a). Moreover, this data usually needs to be combined and transformed in several ways that require technical expertise (The World Bank, 2021a).

However, crash data analyses must deal with significant underreporting, even in European countries where the standardisation of crash reporting is well established (Broughton et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2013). Underreporting levels are highest for VRUs and crashes not involving a motorised vehicle (Knowles et al., 2009). A study comparing police reports with self-reported crashes, found that more than 50% of the severe injuries and more than 75% of light injuries are not reported to the police (Gildea & Simms, 2021). Moreover, behavioural aspects are not usually recorded in crash reports (Laureshyn et al., 2010). The scenario is not different for non-crash data is also incomplete and inhomogeneous. Regarding infrastructure risk assessment, the main challenge is gathering information on the multidimensional elements of roads that impact road safety. The data-collection process is usually performed manually, which is time-consuming and subject to inconsistencies (Sanjeevani & Verma, 2019). Traditional surveys tend to represent a specific moment in time, which can quickly become outdated (Verma et al., 2018), especially in dynamic environments, such as cities.

The lack of open data sources and the high cost of data collection are key barriers to conducting road safety assessments, and can usually be carried out in a fixed-location only, making it difficult to scale-up analyses network-wide. Emerging digital and information technology has the potential to fill these gaps due to the volume and diversity of data being generated (Eskandari Torbaghan et al., 2022). Improving data gaps or providing new insights is critical in the new mobility era, where travel patterns, transportation options, and solutions are changing quickly (The World Bank, 2021b).

Emerging data sources and data gathering are hot topics in both academia and industry. The number of studies exploring and testing new data collection solutions reflects the increasing interest in alternatives to traditional road safety data. On the academic side, efforts to summarise, quantify and assess the findings of these studies are presented in a series of contemporary literature reviews focused on road safety (Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza, 2020; Sohail et al., 2023; Stylianou et al., 2018; Torbaghan et al., 2022) and other societal problems, such as congestion and air quality (Ghaffarpassand et al., 2022; Karimi et al., 2021; Neilson et al., 2019; Sattar et al., 2018). Most of the academic studies reviewed aim to attest applicability and reliability of specific data sources, such as sensors (Sattar et al., 2018) and telematics (Ghaffarpassand et al., 2022; Rumobil Project, 2017), or more generally approached as big data (Karimi et al., 2021; Stylianou et al., 2018). These studies looked for case studies or simulations.

One curious aspect of the reviews is that the studies primarily focus on highways or urban roads (Torbaghan et al., 2022), demonstrating greater data availability in these environments. Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza, (2020) point out that authors combine data sources to enhance the accuracy of predictions. Reviewers highlight the difficulties in quantifying the positive effects of these new data sources on road safety applications and also the low quality of the results of studies trying to capture drivers' and pedestrians' behaviours (Torbaghan et al., 2022). Still, the potential adaptability of these types of technologies to road safety is unanimously agreed.

For industry, key organisations like The World Bank and the US FHA have supported the use of emerging data, providing guidelines on how to leverage new sources and tools into road safety projects and active demand management. (Lukasik et al., 2020; The World Bank, 2021b). Other initiatives, such as the iRAP,

aim to connect infrastructure data providers and data consumers to widen the access to standardised data on road features (iRAP, 2022).

3.5.1 Emerging data sources and data processing technologies

Apart from the above data collection methods for road safety data, a number of other data collection methodologies have been developed and used in recent road safety studies which primarily focus on user behaviour data. These include instrumented bicycles, e-scooters and motor-vehicles, and driving simulators. However, the underlying data collection technologies in all of these new methods are more or less the same. These technologies are described in the following.

3.5.1.1 Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)

The spread of GNSS-compatible devices in smartphones, watches, cameras and vehicles can be used to create large-scale locational data. A single device can provide millions of records, with data points for every minute (or less) collected over the years representing years of data (Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza, 2020). The GNSS system revolutionised the data gathered to capture movement, complementing the information obtained from fixed sensors (Sohail et al., 2023). Yu et al. (2020) listed the potential application of GPS data to the transportation field as trajectory detection, interpretation of urban mobility patterns and traffic prediction and performance metrics.

Smartphones utilise the phone's navigation system to record the location of events. Machine learning algorithms have been widely used to recognise patterns or data mining (Torbaghan et al., 2022). Additionally, image recognition technologies rely on data collected with associated coordinates matching the element detected in a map. Also, many data requirements and processing techniques are associated with data provided in geographic information systems. Each of these data sources will be discussed at length in subsequent sections.

The review papers also highlighted the interfaces and combinations of multiple devices in the data sources type (Sohail et al., 2023). However, challenges commonly faced when manipulating GNSS data are worth discussing. One common challenge is connectivity. GNSS devices still present connectivity issues in indoor environments or tunnels. A network study with public transportation reported losses in signal in 18.4% of the route (Vemula et al., 2015). However, the PHOEBE data partners generally observe losses of < 5%.

Additionally, there are still some levels of uncertainty regarding data noises. Authors usually assume the GNSS data measurements are normally distributed (Y. Wang et al., 2011), however, this is probably not a safe assumption owing to software in the device that attempts to improve on the accuracy of the reported location by taking other factors into account. The Floop observes that the local built environment can create systematic residuals in reported locations.

3.5.1.2 Digital technologies - Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine-Learning

ML methods are ideally suited for the study of traffic flow, where the objective is to predict travel times, congestion, and traffic volumes from a given set of conditions (see Shaygan et al., 2022, for review of ML and AI methods in traffic forecasting). Sohail et al. (2023) choose to distinguish between short- and long-term forecasting of traffic flow; where the short term is considered to be within 15 minutes and the long term describes timescales of days to years. This break is motivated by considerations of the underlying data required for real-time analysis versus long term projection, with the former requiring both large historical datasets with which to contextualise real-time data (see e.g. Abadi et al., 2015).

Researchers find that the best approach to short-term forecasting is to employ deep learning tools (however, see discussion in Duan et al., 2019), such as neural networks (Chen et al., 2018b) or support vector regression (Chen et al., 2018c). The work of Abadi et al. (2015) is of particular relevance to the PHOEBE project because they simulated flows over the entirety of a region's road network, despite a

paucity of real-time data. These studies have a large potential for real-world impact, for example, Walraven et al. (2016) demonstrated how artificial neural networks can be used to anticipate congestion and then immediately introduce a mitigation by varying the speed limit in real time. However, at least one barrier to adoption appears to be the lack of real-world test cases with sufficient data to test model predictions. Deep learning tools have great potential for long-term forecasting, with a growing number of studies demonstrating real-world application (e.g. Qu et al., 2019; Zang et al., 2019). Sun et al. (2020) compared various ML techniques and determined that supervised ML prediction models outperform other approaches in terms of both accuracy and computational cost. These studies overwhelmingly use count data from loop detectors (6 out of 8 studies identified by Sohail et al., 2023).

A significant body of research uses ML techniques to identify metrics that are predictive of the road risk arising from the surrounding infrastructure, conditions, or human behaviours (Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza, 2020). This research aims to predict portions of the road network where there is a higher propensity for a vehicle to crash (e.g. Wang et al., 2015; Fawcett et al., 2017; Gianfranco et al., 2018) and also to forecast the change to the road risk, in terms of both the frequency and severity of incidents, in light of changes that may occur within the system (e.g. Castro & Kim, 2016; Theofilatos et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2019; Appiah et al., 2020).

Figure 3-19 summarises common analytical techniques employed by researchers seeking to understand the propensity to crash. Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza (2020) posit that there are three common approaches to this work, involving either clustering, classifiers, or natural language processing (NLP). Of those approaches, NLP is more geared towards producing real-time notifications of events through analysis of social media (as demonstrated by D'Andrea et al., 2015; Salas et al., 2017) rather than for understanding the probability of an event occurring at a location on the network. Clustering is used in order to describe the geospatial distribution of a given parameter, most notably using crash or near-miss locations, but also with respect to other aspects of behaviour, such as harsh braking events (Cao et al., 2016). However, clustering can also be used to group similar roads together, in terms of their geospatial or behavioural properties, such as to identify groups of parameters that are frequently coincident with higher-risk roads (e.g. Moriya et al., 2018). Finally, decision tree classifiers are used to create a complex system of rules and relationships across a 17).

Figure 3-19 Analytic methods for road crash analysis

Forecasting the change in road risk from a given or changing set of input parameters requires more sophisticated ML techniques, such as Bayesian networks (Castro & Kim, 2016), genetic algorithms, artificial

neural networks (Hashmienejad & Hasheminejad, 2017), and deep learning (Ren et al., 2018). Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza (2020) note that deep learning techniques show the greatest predictive power of any single approach, however, they note the higher levels of computing power required to run the analysis and conclude that the best approach is to combine neural networks with decision tree classifiers (as per Park et al., 2016).

Strikingly, there is a significant lack of consistency between studies in terms of the data that are used to understand the propensity to crash (Mannering et al., 2016). The majority of studies present methodologies with moderate-to-high predictive power, reporting accuracy (such as Castro & Kim, 2016; Chen et al., 2018a; Xiong et al., 2018), however, these methodologies can be considered to be bespoke with respect to the case study for which the research was carried out. The choice of territory is at least partly driven by the quality of the crash data available, which can vary dramatically between individual regions and countries (Imprialou & Quddus, 2019). This inconsistency restricts the extent to which the ML technique can be useful as a forecasting tool for those who manage the road network because the requisite data for a given technique is not always available. The most useful outcomes are often limited to insights in terms of the most important features identified by the ML process. For example, Kumeda et al. (2019) identify the lighting conditions, road class, and the volume of traffic as the most important features, while Taamneh et al. (2017) highlight the importance of age and gender. Clearly, these conclusions are highly dependent on the breadth of data available. In the future, researchers could use ML to help to fill in some of the gaps that exist in a given dataset, in order to allow for a more uniform approach for crash forecasting. Indeed, Sohail et al. (2023) conclude that 'new machine learning and deep learning techniques are needed that are specifically designed for the cases when the datasets [...] are small or not up-to-date [...] to exploit the data collected for one region to do similar tasks for another region'.

Torbaghan et al. (2022) report that 9 out of 14 key studies into road surface assessment involve the use of AI or ML. The use of ML to identify damaged or degraded roads is motivated by the higher propensity to crash for less maintained surfaces and the costly nature of manual inspection. It is noteworthy that the majority of work goes into using ML analysis of crowd-sourced data to identify the condition of individual roads (e.g. Bajic et al. (2021) used telematics devices, Seraj et al. (2016) used smartphones, Quintana et al. (2016) used images captured by a single camera fixed to the underside of a truck, Jo & Ryu (2015) used black box cameras), rather than attempting to predict the surface quality by first establishing a relationship between the traffic conditions (speed, volume, weather, etc.) and road quality (see Nemas, 2019, for a brief description of such an experiment).

3.5.1.3 Image recognition technologies

Studies exploring the application of vision-based approaches divide the techniques into two groups: (i) attribute detection through semantic segmentation and (ii) video tracking. Both approaches make the most of cutting-edge AI solutions. The attribute detection predominant relies on automatic deep learning features extraction and convolutional layer in an encode/decode approach to classify new images based on previous training (Sanjeevani & Verma, 2019). The main goal is to identify the presence and distance of hazardous elements on the roadside and the characteristics and defects of the road surface. Some of these attributes can be detected by processing ML algorithms designed for satellite imaging. However, the authors reviewed recommend to use street view databases to avoid discrepancies between mapping features and on-ground experience (Biljecki & Ito, 2021; Verma et al., 2018). Capturing the on-ground experience is even more important for pedestrians and cyclists since they are more directly exposed to the environment's influence than vehicle occupants (Lucchesi et al., 2023).

Traditionally, image recognition required a geotagged video collected through a video system mounted on a vehicle (Sattar et al., 2018). Nonetheless, increased street view and satellite imagery data availability have boosted image recognition techniques. The high geographical coverage and the accelerated development of ML and AI support the scale-up of the assessments, which would not be possible to achieve through field visits (Biljecki & Ito, 2021). Different applications of image recognition are reported in the

literature. The review study conducted by Biljecki & Ito (2021) showed that this type of data has been used in road safety evaluations to conduct virtual street audits, explore relationships between crashes and road features, and understand the perception of safety. Other authors have focused on identifying flows and speeds using image recognition, which is particularly important for road safety (Yin et al., 2015). The World Bank reinforces the potential of imageries to complement or replace traditional data collection for road safety assessments (World Bank, 2021).

Many challenges exist in detecting attributes through image recognition (Sanjeevani & Verma, 2019). The accuracy of the results is highly susceptible to the quality of the images captured. Since most system semantics segment the pixels, it's essential to use the right equipment to minimise the impact of natural lighting (Torbaghan et al., 2022). Moreover, the algorithms need to be trained, which involves, once again, manual inputs and the results are highly sensitive to the number of training iterations carried out (Sanjeevani & Verma, 2019). Finally, studies report the difficulty coding specific attributes such as trees mixed in vegetation and thin objects (Lucchesi et al., 2023; Verma et al., 2018). The studies conducted by Sanjeevani & Verma (2019) and Verma et al. (2018) that aimed to detect attributes of the AUSRap model automatically obtained high levels of accuracy for bicycle paths and some types of vertical signs (e.g., speed and curvature signs) but very low for other attributes, including pavement defects and the presence of rumble strips. The authors suggested their results are promising but that more work is needed.

Nevertheless, image databases are not always accessible for academic and practitioners. Although there are currently many data providers, data is not easily licensed. Besides, extracting attributes from images usually conflicts with the terms and conditions of these platforms (Biljecki & Ito, 2021) that have continuously increased use restrictions (Fang et al., 2021). Crowdsourced platforms aim to overcome these challenges collaboratively (e.g. Mapillary), but the lack of standard and quality assurance increase processing time and reduce applicability. Also, providers tend not to provide the measurement parameters required to correct image distortions. Thus, geometric dimensions must be used with caution (Yin et al., 2015).

The second most common approach to image recognition is tracking movements using footage of streets and roads, especially from road surveillance cameras (Y. Wang et al., 2022). Presenting a growing use in behavioural studies, video tracking can provide information regarding speed, acceleration, angle of swerving, road position, follow-up parameters and others (Sohail et al., 2023; Torbaghan et al., 2022). Using video data and following the corresponding video processing techniques, the identification of traffic conflicts is applicable as have been done in many studies aiming to validating conflicts extracted through traffic simulation (Astarita et al., 2012; Li et al., 2016; Essa and Sayed, 2020) and to investigate transferability of model parameters (Essa and Sayed, 2015). Although the review papers found in this literature review present mostly video tracking for vehicles, the systematic search did find some experiments with vulnerable road users. Gruden et al. (2019) used recording from a pedestrian ramp to estimate and model pedestrian flows. An industry example came from Vivacity. The organization tracked pedestrian movements to understand changes in behaviour and use of the space after infrastructure changes implemented in Hackney, London at Fairholt Road and Rendlesham Road (Vivacity, 2023).

Surveillance camera data is a good fit for longitudinal studies, capturing information from different periods and days of the week. However, geographical coverage is limited (Torbaghan et al., 2022). On the other hand, studies report high accuracy and reliability of parameters extracted from video tracking methods (Gutierrez-Osorio & Pedraza, 2020).

3.5.1.4 Internet-of-Things (IoT)

Much of the literature concerning the application of the internet-of-things to transport is focused on the use of smartphones, which we discuss in the next section. Taha (2018) proposes an IoT architecture for assessing road safety by incorporating road condition metrics, using data obtained from within vehicles in tandem with information from other sensor systems. The authors were able to plan a route such as to minimise the exposed risk by combining data from various live sources into a dynamic road safety

assessment. Sensors inside the vehicle included stand-alone accelerometers, carbon monoxide sensors, and OBD-II devices that extract data directly from the controller area network (CAN).

3.5.1.5 Smartphone as a sensor

Smartphones containing multiple sets of sensors are now ubiquitous in many countries. These smartphones typically contain GNSS positioning systems, accelerometers, magnetometers, microphones, and cameras. The large number of smartphones in circulation means that sensors are regularly passing over a significant fraction of the road network in some territories. The widespread coverage presents a tantalising opportunity for understanding the transport networks in unprecedented detail. The size of the datasets presents its own problem in terms of incorporation into projects by transport and road safety professionals. GNSS data are usually sampled at a maximum rate of 1 Hz, whereas accelerometer data can be captured at frequencies 10 – 100 Hz. Smartphone monitoring of GNSS data for a journey lasting ten minutes and sampled at 1Hz will create a dataset of 600 entries. Recording high-frequency accelerometer data will create a dataset of 60,000 entries in the same time period. Consider that studies or projects may monitor thousands of individuals for hundreds or thousands of trips each, and the volume of data available can easily swell to tens of billions of entries. Needless to say, such data require significant amounts of aggregation, often coupled with ML, in order to produce actionable insights.

Many researchers have investigated the use of smartphones for road surface monitoring by investigating the extent to which traversals over damaged surfaces produce a characteristic signal in accelerometer data (Mednis et al., 2012; Bello et al., 2019). Recently, Matarazzo et al. (2022) demonstrated that data from smartphone accelerometers can be used to monitor the modal frequency of bridges; potentially providing a cheaper alternative to traditional methods of monitoring infrastructure.

More research has attempted to understand human behaviour using mobile telephones with GNSS capabilities, which actually predates the current era of smartphones (e.g. Gonzalez et al., 2008). Such behaviours have included those of the driver, such as the effects of fatigue (Chan et al., 2019) and the relationship between different acceleration behaviours and the propensity to crash (af Wählberg, 2008; af Wählberg, 2012). Many studies of road users concentrate on examining the extent to which the user is distracted by the smartphone. There is already a substantial market in the insurance sector for driver monitoring services that utilise in-car devices, the majority of which will be smartphones. These private companies, such as The Flow, use smartphone data to understand how individual drivers compare to established standards in terms of both the vehicle dynamics (speed, acceleration events, harsh braking) and human factors such as fatigue and the choice of travel time. The widespread use of telematics has important implications for territories where motor insurance is a mandatory prerequisite to the legal operation of a vehicle; creating a large sample of monitored drivers and frequent sampling of the road network. The data collected can be aggregated and, in turn, used to create novel solutions to established and emerging mobility-related problems. Therefore, as a consequence of providing widespread monitoring for insurance purposes, The Flow can in-turn provide statistical measures of speed and thoroughfare traffic to road safety and local government stakeholders (<https://www.theflow.com/mobilityIn/>).

There are numerous studies as well as naturalistic driving projects (e.g. [the i-DREAMS Horizon 2020 project](#)) that monitor active travel trips using smartphones, however, such studies tend to be focused on the development of an IoT system that would allow vehicles to predict the passage of pedestrians onto the road (such as Ridet et al., 2018). While some studies do collect GNSS traces from the smartphones of cyclists (e.g. Rupi & Schweizer, 2018), there is little work into using such data to create actionable insights for transport professionals.

3.5.1.6 Geographic Information System (GIS)

Cities have already recognised the importance of having solid GIS databases of urban features. Combining different layers of information into a spatial data structure permits easy to visualise and analyse any spatial dependent data (Rezvani et al., 2023). Due to volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) platforms, GIS

data have spread among developers, industry actors, researchers, and other end users. The most well-established VGI platform is Open Street Map (OSM). OSM operates collaboratively among users that map their surroundings and update the information to the global platform. OSM also captures information on publicly available GIS data for official government entities and accepts a contribution to individual GPS units (Foody et al., 2017).

Crowded-sources GIS platforms disseminate spatial data like never before. The OSM was developed to fulfil a latent need for freely available map data; the most well-known mapping system is copyrighted and data cannot be extracted for academic or commercial use. However, there are three intrinsic limitations to this type of project. The first is that more data quality assurance is needed (Goodchild & Li, 2012), as users are not required to prove experience or skills in mapping, which means there needs to be validation before the data are made available to other users (Teimoory et al., 2021). Secondly, there are no standards for data updates. While the most recent data are available, the user will have access to locational data that is temporally incompatible. Moreover, some authors indicate that the number of versions, users, and the temporal variation range are relevant for data reliability (Teimoory et al., 2021). Finally, OSM data present heterogeneous accuracy for different regions (Fogliaroni & Kauppinen, 2014). Studies that used official government data, when suitable and available, to compare with OSM agree that data is of higher quality and availability are in urbanised areas (Minghini & Frassinelli, 2019).

Besides the concerns with data quality, the OSM has been widely used as a foundation for road safety analysis as a data source for network identification, road features and road type. The World Bank (2021b) report *Detecting Urban Clues for Road Safety Leveraging Big Data and Machine Learning* reinforced the importance of using OSM data in combination with other crowd-sourced data sources like road alerts from Waze and image attribute detection based on Mapillary imagery.

The combination of different data sources brings a key element to discussion: the ability of GIS platforms to perform data fusion. A typical issue academics and practitioners face geospatial data conflation when different data sources provide information for the same feature but need the exact coordinates (Khan et al., 2010). The literature brings examples of many map-matching algorithms. They have been dependent upon the characteristics of the data elements, the level of accuracy required, the level of complexity of the road network, and the eventual use of the data. Combining GIS data with other data types, like socioeconomic data and surveys, is also common in studies with vulnerable road users. Literature review studies pointed to this approach as widely used to correlate cycling behaviour with built environment measures (Yang et al., 2019).

Moreover, GIS platforms have been reported to facilitate multicriteria analysis and geostatistical data treatment (Rueda-Villar et al., 2019). There is well-established knowledge of its potential to support crash clustering and identification of hot spots (Aghasi, 2019). GIS also plays an important role in data visualization. Geospatial data visualization can benefit decision-makers and non-experts in understanding road safety issues and advocating for change (Sanguinetti & Alston-Stepnitz, 2023).

3.5.1.7 Aerial Vehicles

Manned Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) enable arbitrary vantage points (controlled by regulated flying restrictions), which can make them attractive for data gathering across wide and remote geography and at locations not suited to ground based or other monitoring. Despite these advantages MAVs remain prohibitively expensive with very high operating costs. However, MAVs have a niche opportunistic application towards road safety when coupled with other uses such as supporting emergency traffic management, law enforcement activities, incident response, and sporadic aerial survey tasks⁶. Data from manned aerial vehicles is rarely

⁶ For instance in parts of Australia and some US states where road safety and traffic tasks may upon occasion utilise manned aerial vehicles also used for other purposes.

available without high costs and typically has very limited temporal and spatial coverage making usage impractical for the PHOEBE project and most other road safety usage.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), often referred to as ‘drones’, offer significant advantages over MAVs, with both lower purchase and operational costs. UAVs often have superior manoeuvrability, which enables precise positioned aerial data gathering (Outay et al, 2020). UAVs can be equipped with a wide range of remote sensing equipment (such as lightweight UAV LIDAR or visible spectrum cameras). However, these capabilities are limited by various factors:

- 1) Weight - sensors ,data processing and transmission hardware and battery capacity limit potential flight time (curtailing data gathering to typically much less than 1 hour).
- 2) Regulations - UAVs must operate under flight ceilings, restrictions near airfields, restrictions over urban areas, restrictions on night time flying and needs for licensed operators which challenges data gathering minimising the potential of new low cost approaches⁷.

UAVs can be utilised in a range of road safety areas such as

- 3) Extracting vehicle trajectories from imaging by remotely gathering snapshot samples of locational risk proxy data, such as the time to collision. Such data can also be harvested from connected vehicles and large scale ‘near miss’ data with higher spatial and temporal coverage than aerial methods (Khan et al, 2017).
- 4) Traffic incident scene data capture, such as capturing LIDAR data around incident sites for later forensic analysis. Despite this capability, aerial-based LIDAR offers only marginal advantage over ground-based LIDAR for road based incidents (Mehmood et al, 2018).
- 5) Speed enforcement and monitoring - (Barmounakis & Geroliminis, 2020)
- 6) Feature extraction along routes or intersections to understand attributes relevant to safety (Chen et al., 2017 and Astor, 2023). Such data can also be harvested from ground-based vehicles or surveys at a lower cost.

Despite the potential advantages from aerial approaches, the need for certified operators and the regulatory restrictions upon use in populated regions prevents adequate usage in urban settings as may be required in PHOEBE.

3.5.1.8 Social Media

Citizen social media activity can provide a potential source of opinions and shared information related to mobility and its safety. A large number of studies have explored the use of natural language processing techniques and data mining⁸ from large scale social media to support a variety of transport analysis tasks. Transport safety related tasks include:

- 1) Identifying the time, location and severity of road incidents where other data sources remain incomplete to supplement and add to road safety incident evidence (Saalm et al, 2021).
- 2) Crowdsourcing public opinion related to road safety. This may be specific and targeted to localised issues or thematic safety concerns across society. (Zayet et al, 2021).

⁷ UK regulations (seen as an exemplar in drone regulation) contain specific guidance for use of drones in relation to roads, traffic management and road Safety. Similar guidance (albeit less focused upon road safety usage) is provided in the EU, US, China as well as other international countries. <https://www.standardsforhighways.co.uk/dmrb/search/dfd64db4-6745-4d3d-ae18-62dad0ae1225>

⁸ Principal analysis utilises, sentiment analysis, geolocation NLP analysis and temporal analysis to try and define usable data from unstructured content.

- 3) Identifying network state by identifying real time traffic information that may be shared formally or informally via social media channels. (Adetiloye & Awasthi, 2018).

Despite the above aims the use of social media has several fundamental challenges:

- 1) Data protection and permitted processing - This is challenging and can present ethical and data protection concerns in the re-use of third party unstructured data that frequently contains personal identifiable information. Although legitimate interest can provide consent when processing can help public benefit, processing controls and impact assessments need very careful consideration.
- 2) Data bias - social media is fundamentally biased even in road safety usage where data extracted typically has demographic, language and community biases meaning its output should be utilised with strong caution where used in decision making, monitoring and analysis.
- 3) Geolocation challenges messages are posted globally but often without exact geolocation making reliable reuse of data hard to maintain. Most social media channels do not contain geolocation (or are minimising its usage⁹) meaning that to locate the meaning of messages the location must be inferred from text in the message, a process with distinct accuracy concerns given non unique geospatial location naming conventions.
- 4) Temporal challenges - messages frequently refer to past events or the potential of future events making it hard to determine despite message timestamps when and the duration of a messages subject with precision and accuracy.
- 5) Subject challenges - social media messages will use variable descriptors and language for topics discussed making it hard to classify and cluster events where separated descriptions may refer to one or more events and determination of singular or multiple occurrences is often hard to clarify.

Even with such challenges social media remains a useful tool for road safety but due to its concerns for accuracy, bias and data protection (Zayet et al, 2021) it may still provide some insight on citizen opinion to PHOEBE activity. Social Media however best supports dissemination activities rather than robust evidential data gathering.

3.5.2 Summary

Data gathering and collation techniques across literature (and in practice) are varied and can be seen to cover a number of base data gathering requirements:

- 1) Physical attribute data - detailing the locational attributes of an environment that may be correlated with its safety.
- 2) Location focused user behaviour data - detailing the locational use of the environment that may be correlated with its safety.
- 3) General user data - detailing the background of users as may influence risk understanding and patterns of behaviour.
- 4) Actual incident data - to indicate where negative outcomes have previously occurred to understand causation and statistical correlations for them.

Within each a number of sub data needs are detailed in literature where found to be supportive for road safety understanding.

Also as well as data needs literature details a number of methodological approaches to obtain or improve available data for road safety. These again consist of wide methodologies for data gathering that can be collated into distinct types of data gathering methodologies. These are:

⁹ For instance Twitter is in the process of removing precise geolocation from its recorded social media posts to help support data protection and align to global data protection good practices.

- 1) Individual collated data - manual and human collected information gathering or its analysis and application. Data gathered via direct inspection, manual methods or direct consultation with stakeholders or public opinions. Such data gathering is often time consuming and costly so is typically only performed when no alternative is available and the need justifies the direct efforts required.
- 2) Travel route remote sensing and monitoring - mobile sensing from vehicles or along a transport route to determine characteristics along infrastructure. Methodologies include device based means to gather data and analysis for application to road safety.
- 3) Overhead and network data - aerial, satellite, mapping or transport network data when utilised to obtain features or insight for road safety.
- 4) Fixed point mobility sensing - infrastructure fixed point sensors observing mobility and behaviours. Methodologies use a range of hardware fitted in proximity to mobility infrastructure coupled with analysis techniques to gain insight related to safety.
- 5) Incident data - the gathering and reuse of prior incident records, statistics and near miss data. Approaches use various methods to collate data related to locational incidents or risk proxies for them (e.g. near miss data).
- 6) Third party data reuse - road safety supporting data such as weather or ticketing data that may be reutilised when supporting road safety analysis.

Across the needs and methodologies in literature some methodologies are commonly reported to solve a particular need, whilst others are merely supportive to the data need and may be used alongside other approaches. In many cases methodologies are only suited to specific needs, these are shown in the following matrix in Figure 3-20.

3.5 Discussion on review findings

The development of the PHOEBE Framework involves three principal aspects:

1. First is the theoretical development, which includes the research, where necessary, for key principles underpinning the framework, and the methodology of the framework
2. Second is the technical developments required to ensure that the technical components of the framework have the necessary functionality to meet the framework's needs and produced the analysis required, and
3. Third are the tools and support materials for end users to ensure the framework can be utilised for its stated purpose.

The purpose of this review was to document the current state-of-the-art for each component of the PHOEBE Framework and highlight any particular considerations which should be taken into account in its development.

Type of data need	Sub type of data need	Data gathering methodology																		
		Individually collated data		Travel route remote sensing and monitoring			Overhead and network data		Fixed point mobility sensing		Incident data		Third Party Data Reuse							
		Manual inspections, physical survey or attribute encoding	Social Media, public opinions, (via data mining or direct collation)	Stakeholder questionnaires, survey and consultation data (or use of)	Video/Still imagery (vehicle based)	Electromagnetic emission and reflection scanning (LIDAR, RADAR, UTLRASONIC)	Infrared imagery (vehicle based)	Telematics journey records and vehicle dynamics analysis	Origin Destination, sat nav and journey endpoint patterns	Aerial Photography (MAV and UAV's)	Satellite and earth observation data	Mapping data and network data	Vehicle mode passage and count measurement	Video/Still imagery (fixed point)	Journey time (ANPR, travel gate recording)	Individual incident forensic and report information	near miss and risk occurrence proxy data (telematics and other sources)	Statistical accident records	Ticket and paid travel data analysis	Weather, condition and environmental measurement and modeling
Physical attribute data	Marking, medians and signage	Red																		
	Topology/geography	Red																		
	Curvature	Red																		
	Road type classification	Red																		
	Mapping data segments	Red																		
	Visibility	Red																		
	Route surrounding environment data	Red																		
	Intersections	Red																		
	VRU crossings	Red																		
	Speed limits and enforcement	Red																		
	Obstructions	Red																		
	Weather, condition and environment data	Red																		
	Georeference point data	Red																		
Location focused user behaviour data	Traffic mode measurement - Speed	Red																		
	Traffic mode measurement - Flow/counts/density/AADT	Red																		
	Traffic mode measurement - Extreme events, acceleration, brakings and movement risk proxy data	Red																		
	Rule compliance behaviours and risk taking	Red																		
	origin / destination, journey purpose, route choice and patterns	Red																		
	Traffic mode share percentages	Red																		
User data	Attitudes to travel and risk in users	Red																		
	Demographics and statistics	Red																		
	Individualised mode choice	Red																		
Other	Crash incident and statistics	Red																		

LEGEND ■ common data gathering method ■ supportive data gathering method ■ no identified data gathering method in explored literature

Figure 3-20 Data needs versus identified data gathering methodologies

3.5.1 Traffic simulation, human behaviour and road safety assessment

The PHOEBE Framework aims to advance the application of traffic simulation tools and road safety assessment to enable transport planners and managers to fully understand and address the safety implications of changes in road conditions, mode choice, new modes, road user behaviours and other factors and their impacts on safety over time.

Traffic microsimulation is the name of the technique known for reproducing the behaviour of each single vehicle in the traffic flow. This is done by simulating each vehicle trajectory with a high level of detail, this includes, speed acceleration, current lane, route, etc. This means that microsimulation is very complex, being many different models involved into the simulation.

For the PHOEBE project, the focus will be on: (1) the vehicle dynamics within the lane such as car-following behaviours, but also between lanes such as lane-changing behaviours and how safe/unsafe behaviour is incorporated in these models; (2) how vulnerable road users are currently modelled and considered in microsimulation tools and their interaction with other non-motorized and motorized traffic at network level; and (3) network-level safety assessment approaches that can be used to improve safety analysis.

3.5.1.1 Microscopic traffic simulation tools

Traffic microsimulation is typically performed using one of many commercial and open-source software packages. The development of, and market for, traffic simulation models has been driven in past decades by the need to design and optimise roads and road networks with a view to minimising congestion and maximising throughput.

While there are many differences among them, when it comes to safety most of them behave in a similar manner. This is because vehicle dynamics, while realistic on an aggregate level, do not reflect the driver's behavioural details at a microscopic (or disaggregated) level.

Car-following and lane-changing models that mainly govern the longitudinal and lateral movements of vehicles do not account for human factors that might lead to different safety outcomes in reality. This means most microsimulation models are conceived as inherently 'crash free'.

3.5.1.2 Evaluating safety using conflict-based methodologies

Conflict-based methodologies which use surrogate safety measures (such as time to collision and gap acceptance) are used to evaluate traffic safety in microscopic traffic simulation tools based on the computation of safety metrics by using simulation outputs. This approach does not need to alter the modelled behaviour of drivers to consider human errors – allowing vehicle crashes – in the simulation environment, which in part simplifies the problem.

One of the most extensively used approaches to evaluate safety impact is the combination of microscopic simulation outputs with the Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM). This method uses vehicle trajectory data from simulation outputs to observe vehicle-to-vehicle interactions, identify traffic conflicts and therefore, assess safety impacts on a network level.

Despite the significant progress achieved related to conflict-based methodologies, there are limitations due to the absence of complete and established models for simulating potential crashes. Traffic conflicts are an important indicator of a potential crash risk, but not all conflicts result in crash occurrences. Therefore, crash estimation provides a more accurate and reliable assessment of road safety compared to just estimating conflicts.

While these techniques are mainly used from microsimulation data (e.g., SSAM), there is no clear evidence on how reliable the results are when compared to real trajectories. Other drawbacks of SSAM are that VRU interaction with other motorized vehicles are not included and the selection of threshold values for some surrogate safety indicators is subjective. Only a few studies have attempted to overcome these issues through proposing alternative approaches and hence further research is required. Most of the past research modelling efforts needed better evaluation of the crash data used, as well as the corresponding modelling methods followed (e.g. limited sample size, under-reporting, unreliability are noticing). Addressing this gap could lead to the development of better strategies for mitigating crash occurrence and consequences, **but would be beyond the scope of the PHOEBE project** to address it in this way.

Therefore, to the best of the reviewers' knowledge, there are at least two potential approaches to overcome these limitations: (a) **improve the current SSAM approach by developing new methods that incorporate the trajectory data from all road user types – not just cars – and integrate it within a simulation tool in order to identify potential conflicts between all users**; and (b) **adapt and improve safety indicators from existing safety assessment methodologies (e.g., Star Ratings)**.

3.5.1.3 Micro-simulation of non-vehicular road user movements and interactions

It is very important that the PHOEBE Framework can identify risks for vulnerable road users. The coexistence and interaction of multiple road users (e.g., motorized, non-motorized traffic and pedestrians) in the same road space creates complex situations that have not been properly addressed in current simulation models.

Traditionally, traffic simulation software packages have focused primarily on vehicular traffic and heavy vehicles, and have given little or no attention to non-motorized road users. This is changing towards a more interactive simulation environment where all road users share space and react to each other.

The Horizon 2020 Project MOMENTUM developed an initiative to enhance traffic models to support sustainable urban mobility planning. The project simulates scenarios to study innovations related to bicyclists (e.g., bike-sharing) and other micro-mobility trends to help policymakers plan, manage and regulate new transport options (NOMMON, 2019)¹⁰. However, the safety component of this new mobility technology for VRU is still not modelled and general models for understanding the interaction between pedestrians and non-motorised vehicle flows do not yet exist, despite these modes being central to sustainable transport strategies around the world.

Situations such as pedestrian crossing flows and the response of drivers at designated crossings, and the presence of e-bikes and e-scooters and their interaction with other road users are some scenarios which need to be considered in current simulation tools to better understand their safety implications. External factors, such as weather, culture, time of day, site configuration, etc. can also have a strong influence on road user behaviours.

3.5.1.4 Road safety assessment

The review identified a number of well-established methodologies which represent the current state-of-the-art of how to evaluate infrastructure-related risk of a road corridor or network. These included the Star Rating methodology which calculates risk scores for standard road lengths based on risk factors. The risk factors used by the Star Rating method are based on published Crash Modification Factors (CMFs) and other evidence into road crash likelihood and severity. The Star Ratings provide individual road risk scores for VRUs (pedestrians, bicyclists and motorcyclists) as well as vehicle occupants.

The review also identified several purpose-specific and/or localised methods, most of which were developed using the Star Ratings method or risk factors. These approaches tend to be more specific in their application to the types of roads, road users, geographic regions, data inputs or analysis which affects their transferability (e.g., high focus on highway elements and simplistic considering urban elements) and calibration (e.g., risk factors calibrated to local crash data). Only a few models have been proven to be applicable in broader contexts. Apart from the iRAP Star Rating and CycleRAP methods, most existing models do not focus on VRUs or urban areas despite their critical importance in urban road safety assessment.

This review confirmed that the Star Ratings are an appropriate road safety assessment methodology to meet the needs of the project aims. This method incorporates individual models for VRUs, and is applicable across all regions and road types (including urban road networks).

It is well-known that vulnerable road user safety is highly dependent on the traffic and vehicle speed levels, which in cities, can widely vary throughout the day due to congestion levels. All the methodologies reviewed in this report do not represent the variability of these speed and flow parameters over the course of a day.

¹⁰ NOMMON (2019). New Mobility Options and Urban Mobility: Challenges and Opportunities for Transport Planning and Modelling. MOMENTUM - Horizon 2020. URL: <https://h2020-momentum.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/MOMENTUM-D2.1-New-Mobility-Options-and-Urban-Mobility.pdf>

As yet, the Star Rating methodology uses static values for traffic speeds and flows. It is planned under the PHOEBE project that **variable speed and flow values, informed by traffic simulation models, could be used to produce dynamic risk ratings for different times of the day**. This could be used to inform better FSI Estimation modelling of changes (and thus the socio-economic impacts), as well as help transport planners understand and address peak risk times.

3.5.1.5 Using human behaviour factors to calibrate microscopic traffic simulation

Human factors, such as culture, social influence, attitudes toward road rule compliance, fatigue, and risk-compensating behaviours, can all impact traffic safety outcomes. If human factors were introduced in microscopic traffic simulation models, richer behavioural modelling detail could be achieved, and vehicle crashes would also be able to be modelled within the simulation.

While the literature shows that the interaction between road user behaviour and road risk has potential to further our understanding about road risk on roads, only a few behavioural factors such as risk perception, errors, and distraction has been studied in the past, and of those, most focussed on car drivers from the perspective of the individual's behaviour.

However, these human factors are difficult to incorporate in current traffic simulation models and more detailed data – which is not often available – is needed to validate and calibrate the models. Furthermore, by adding more parameters and factors inside models, it might also have an impact on increasing the computational cost, as it might slow down simulation running times.

It also raises the question on which human factors should be prioritised. Currently, typical detector data might be sufficient to calibrate traditional traffic flow-oriented models like Gipps (1981) and Treiber et al. (2000) but are not enough to calibrate the level of detail required for human factor -based models. While progress has been made in recent years (Calvert et al., 2020), there is not any model that fulfils all the requirements. **Hence, decisions must be made to decide which human factors are more relevant for the PHOEBE project and what data is available to calibrate models and validate any new developments.**

3.5.1.6 Key considerations

The methodological framework in PHOEBE should:

- Be developed considering not just traditional driving kinematic factors, such as speed, acceleration, etc., but also incorporate other human factors that may lead to potential human errors when driving in simulation models. In doing so, potential conflicts – and even vehicle crashes – might be able to be represented and quantified in a simulation environment.
- Investigate which high-resolution human behavioural data could be collected throughout the project, establishing a data collection methodology that will be used to calibrate and validate traffic microsimulation models. It is also important to consider that highly complex human factor models will significantly increase the simulation running time.
- Consider the improvement of current SSAM approaches by developing new methods that incorporate the trajectory data from all road user types – not just cars – and integrate it within a traffic microsimulation tool to identify potential conflicts between all users.
- Build on the H2020 MOMENTUM project advances to VRUs and shared mobility simulation and the iRAP VRU fatality and serious injury estimation models to establish a methodological process for incorporating non-motorised/light transport modes in traffic simulation to predict road safety outcomes for these road user groups.
- Utilise existing safety indicators, namely the iRAP Star Ratings, to build on the current state-of-the-art and expand their application into new contexts (in this case, microscopic traffic

simulation), and use dynamic speed and flow variables outputs from traffic simulation tools and mode shift to enable enhanced FSI Estimations for specific times of day or for different mode share profiles. This will improve accuracy of FSI Estimations (and thus the calculation of socio-economic impacts over time) as well as better understand the network impacts of changes (such as decreasing speeds along a particular corridor).

- Incorporate knowledge generated in the i-DREAMS¹¹ about the definition of road risk, its indicators, and its contributing factors from a micro safety assessment perspective.
- There are a few recent promising examples of including human factors at the operational level of traffic simulation (CF) (Calvert et al., 2020), by means of using a 'situation awareness' and 'task saturation' framework, and its impacts on e.g. headways. Much of this work has been done within the SAFE-UP¹² Horizon project. It could be an opportunity for PHOEBE to liaise with this project and exchange about these developments.

3.5.2 Modal shift and induced demand

The choice to make a trip with a particular mode, or make the same trip but with a different mode (for example, from a private vehicle to public transport) is another human behaviour-related issue for transportation, but at the macro (network) level. Understanding modal shift and induced demand is critical in understanding the network impacts (in terms of road user flows) of changes occurring in the transport system.

Modelling the Mode Choice (MC) phenomenon and forecasting the Modal Share and Modal Shift (MS) is integral to modelling travel demand. It acts as a basis for multiple decisions made by policymakers. Although modelling MC is a relatively new field, several scientific studies have been conducted, resulting in this field's exponential development in recent years.

The review found that MC modelling is one of the most critical steps in travel demand modelling. This step acts as the basis for the policymakers or decision-makers to make informed and targeted decisions regarding MS that can induce desired outcomes such as emissions reductions, improvement of air quality and reduced congestion.

The current techniques of MC modelling can be classified under two major categories, namely, Random Utility Model (RUM) and Machine Learning Models (MLM). Traditionally, the principles of RUM are utilised to carry out MC modelling. Although these are robust enough to carry out MC modelling, they have certain shortcomings, namely that they are mathematically complex, using them is challenging, and they are often based on certain assumptions about which mode users will choose, which are often contradicted in real world testing and thus leads to biases.

With the exponential growth of computational capacity, along with the focus on overcoming the limitations of the RU models mentioned above and flexibility, the applications of ML and Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods are getting attention from the scientific communities. Although the ML and AI methods are nascent, they show great potential for the future. Quality scientific research is needed to make ML and AI methods robust for modelling choices (or MC, in this case).

An important recent development is the combined use of both techniques, for improved computation. There is a lot of experience in developing such models for urban areas, however sustainable modes of transport (other than public transport), micro mobility and automated mobility have not been included. **The inclusion of some new modes, particularly micro-mobility, will be essential for the PHOEBE Framework's capacity to forecast uptake of new modes of transport.**

¹¹ <https://idreamsproject.eu/wp/>

¹² <https://www.safe-up.eu>

Land use and traffic conditions also affect mode choice. For example, individuals may be more inclined to use public transport or micro-mobility modes in dense urban areas with mixed land uses. **The MC modelling methods used in PHOEBE must capture the complex relationships between land use, the spatial environment and travel behaviour.**

The review also found that none of the existing models or approaches consider the availability of information, such as route planning and navigation and social networks, which inform mode choice. **The PHOEBE project will explore the potential incorporation of such data which can be derived from telematics and other sources.**

3.5.2.1 Key considerations

The methodological framework in PHOEBE should:

- Account for new/emerging modes of transport, particularly micro-mobility, by choosing and setting up proper choice models (e.g., logit or nested logit or hybrid-choice latent-class models) from the available (set of) models. This will require
 - Further research to ascertain the explanatory variables to account for the spatial impact on the mode choice. If the input dataset (to the chosen MC model) contains information regarding the origin and destination of a trip, then proper explanatory variables can be included in the utility function of the MC model. Thus the modal share can be calculated with a spatial resolution.
 - Identification of vulnerable and marginalised road user groups (e.g., older people and families with young children) and the factors influencing the mode choice among these person groups, followed by incorporating these factors (in terms of proper explanatory variables, including latent variables) into the chosen MC model.
- Accommodate the attributes of such modes into the chosen choice model as explanatory variables (including relevant latent variables) in the utility function of the chosen model. Specific data-driven modelling methods exist that investigate the historical ridership of bike sharing (dependent variable) against the built environment (independent variable) data and forecast future ridership using statistical regression techniques. Such a model can be developed and plugged in with the regular MC model to generate modal share with a spatial resolution.
- Account for developing innovative methods of the MC model estimation, validation and calibration by including the ML techniques. The hybrid-choice latent-class models are complex and difficult to estimate and calibrate. Therefore, innovative ML techniques can be deployed to estimate and calibrate such models. The PHOEBE Framework can also draw a scientific comparison between the traditional and upcoming methods (ML) of the MC model estimation, validation and calibration.
- Account for the impacts of information flow and social networks on MC, travel behaviour and travel demand. This can be achieved by incorporating the latent variables pertaining to the use of social networks and respective apps into the MC models. Further, a tour-based MC model can be developed instead of a trip-based model to accommodate the effects of the information flow for a complete tour (e.g., the use of different modes for a complete tour due to information updates through social networks and travel apps during the tour) (Chaniotakis et al., 2022).

3.5.3 Socio-economic impact evaluation

Policy makers, network managers and safe system stakeholders require robust impact assessment techniques to support policy, regulatory and investment priorities. Quantifying the social and economic impact of new mobility options and patterns within a city will provide informed decision making and a good use of public and private funds in supporting safe and sustainable mobility.

A range of social and economic appraisal tools are in place to support decision makers. This includes systems that measure the safety impact of infrastructure and speed management investment for all road users in the iRAP models, traffic modelling tools that measure travel time impacts and costs of transport, project appraisal and cost-benefit analysis tools implemented by EIB and other regional and national agencies and the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan guidelines are some examples.

This paper reviewed several approaches including cost-benefit analysis, cost-effectiveness analysis, willingness to pay method, multi-criteria processes and before-after analysis. Of these, cost-benefit analysis is the most popular method. The review found that there are several handbooks to conduct cost-benefit analyses for road safety, for example, Elvik's numerous scientific papers and books, and a SafetyCube paper by Daniels et al (2019) "a cost-benefit analysis of 29 road safety measures".

iRAP's Star Rating model incorporates a tool for cost benefit analyses of road safety measures. Referred to as a *Safer Roads Investment Plan* (SRIP), the SRIP uses FSI Estimation (that is the individual safety rating together with road user flows), the estimated cost of safety upgrades and a value of statistical life (VOSL) to calculate the benefit to cost ratio (BCR) for over 120 road improvement options, such as engineering treatments including those specific to urban areas, such as reducing vehicle speeds and VRU facilities. These are typically modelled over 20 years.

To advance the state-of-the-art around socio-economic impact evaluation, the PHOEBE project aims to devise a harmonised methodology for the socio-economic impact assessment of safety measures at three levels (health and safety, environmental and economic) through network-level extrapolation road safety evaluation mode shift and induced demand modelling components of the PHOEBE Framework to allow informed decision making by all stakeholders.

Currently the SRIP only considers the economic cost of fatal and serious injuries based on VOSL. The project will need to pair socio-economic analyses with the economic, environmental and health impacts of mode shift & induced demand at the network level. To this end, the project will draw on the existing approaches to develop a standardised and reproducible checklist for the socio-economic analyses of the impacts of road safety measures.

3.5.3.1 Key considerations

The methodological framework in PHOEBE should:

- Using quantitative methods to conduct the socio-economic analysis. Utilising quantitative methods will ensure the production of objective data and information, which can be processed with clarity with the help of available statistical methods, increasing the understanding of the effectiveness of the impacts of the safety measures. This should include the application of iRAP FSI Estimation module and cost-benefit analysis of safety upgrades, and the outcomes of the LEVITATE and SAFE-10-T projects, in terms of data harmonization and combination techniques for multiple impacts stemming from simultaneous road network interventions..
- Develop a standardised and reproducible checklist for conducting socio-economic analyses of the impacts of road safety measures. This should use a modular structure to enable an integrated feedback loop between the PHOEBE Framework and the socio-economic analyses module, thus integrating the process methodologically and technically. Such a framework can make the testing process of proposed policies easier, quicker and more transparent.

3.5.4 Innovative data exploitation for road safety

The OECD International Transport Forum has identified the exploitation of big data for road safety purposes as one of the highest potential gains, but one where significant barrier remains, particularly for VRUs (ITF,

2021)¹³. There is also a technological capacity gap on sharing data from private to public organisations (POLIS, 2021)¹⁴. Accurate and reliable data for VRUs is usually costly and hard to obtain, particularly VRU crash data which has consistently high levels of underreporting (Schepers et al. 2015)¹⁵.

As discussed in the preceding sections, innovative data exploitation is the nexus of advancing the state-of-the-art for each component of the PHOEBE Framework, particularly for understanding the implications of human behaviour and decision making on mode choice and safety outcomes. It also has the potential to unlock greater uses and scale of existing simulation and road safety assessment tools, especially for VRUs for which traditional methods of data collection used for transport planning and road safety are poor.

Besides understanding the potential uses of emerging data sources, the review found that academia and industry are also interested in learning more about barriers and unresolved issues that will continue to impact the applicability and magnitude of road safety assessments, such as the time, skills and costs required for collection, as well as the unavailability of real-time and large datasets. The genuine demand of data consumers is for cost-effective data collection methods instead of sophisticated and expensive options (Sohail et al., 2023).

3.5.4.1 Key considerations

Data quality and availability are key framework components and can impact the sustainability and replicability of the risk assessment structure proposed on PHOEBE. In order to overcome the remaining and new challenges of using emerging data sources, the project team identified four key actions to guide the PHOEBE development phase. These are:

1. Provide protocols and tools that release the cities of the burden of collecting, manipulating, and analysing data to increase the likelihood of adopting emerging data sources.
2. Investigate the potential of crowd-source platforms like OSM and Mapillary, privileging open-source databases over expensive alternatives when suitable. The framework should also provide a clear understanding of open-source limitations for the needs of the framework and protocols to ensure the quality of the information gathered.
3. Map possible interactions among data sources that can fulfil data gaps or be complementary alternatives to leverage information for single data banks.
4. Recommend alternative sources for relevant but inaccessible data, specifying the gains and losses of adhering to substitutes. Alternatively, data collection methodologies should be specified to obtain the necessary information to apply the framework.

¹³ ITF (2021), Artificial Intelligence in Proactive Road Infrastructure Safety Management: Summary and Conclusions, ITF Roundtable Reports, No. 187, OECD Publishing, Paris. URL: <https://www.itf-oecd.org/sites/default/files/docs/artificial-intelligence-road-infrastructure-safety-management.pdf>

¹⁴ POLIS (2021), Sharing data for shared micromobility. Survey Report. URL: https://www.polisnetwork.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/SHARING-DATA-FROM-SHARED-MICROMOBILITY_FINAL.pdf

¹⁵ Schepers P. et al. (2015). An international review of the frequency of single-bicycle crashes (SBCs) and their relation to bicycle modal share. *Injury Prevention* 2015;21:e138-e143.

4 Stakeholder consultations

Consultations with stakeholder groups aimed to capture the current practices, needs and gaps from the perspective of transport managers and municipalities (the intended end users of the PHOEBE Framework). These are synthesised into a **user needs statement** to inform the design of the PHOEBE Framework's end-user tools and knowledge products. The consultations involved two components:

- **Online stakeholder survey** to understand the needs and gaps in current practice among the stakeholders involved in the PHOEBE use cases (Athens, Valencia, West Midlands), as well as a broader groups of transport managers reachable through the wide network of contacts of the project partners.
- **Focus group consultations** to drill more deeply into the current uses and practices of road safety assessment and microscopic simulation on urban road networks, and the extent to which they inform decision making in urban road planning and management.

The results are summarised in the following sections.

4.1 Overview of survey results

As mentioned in Section 2.2, the stakeholder survey was composed of six main domains along with warm-up and closing questions, it can be found in full in Annex C: Stakeholders survey structure of the present document. The complete results for the use case stakeholders are presented in Annex D: Additional stakeholders survey results graphs. A total of 50 responses were received. The majority (58%) of respondents are master degree holders, while 20% of respondents have doctoral degree and remaining 20% have a university or college-level degree or diploma. In terms of city coverage, the distribution of respondents covers 36 cities. Specifically, most respondents (41 in total) work in Europe, while two work in North America, three in South America, one in Africa and one in Asia as shown in Figure 4-1. In Figure 4-1, it can be also seen that the 41 respondents cover 29 European cities and therefore the sample is considered as adequate with respect to European coverage.

Respondents have categorised their main role in cities according to the eleven proposed categories (Question 1.3). The largest group (22%) of respondents work in the private sector involved in road safety and have more than 20 years of experience in their role. Furthermore, 20% of respondents selected the open text option and stated the following roles: research project on vision zero, professor, proving ground, geometric road design, road safety NGO, mobility advisor, research on mobility, road safety researcher, investment bank with an aim to finance sustainable urban transport and academia.

In addition, respondents have categorised the type of software or tool that they use in their daily activities according to the thirteen proposed categories. There are many cases where stakeholders indicated that they use both Road safety assessment methodology and Road safety assessment software or several cases that stated using Microscopic, Mesoscopic, as well as Macroscopic traffic simulation. The majority (17%) of respondents has experience in Road safety assessment methodology, while 10% of respondents use Macroscopic traffic simulation and 10% Routing software. Furthermore, the 4% of respondents selected the open text option and stated the following: AutoCAD, Planning, GIS app, Street lighting for safety and none directly.

Figure 4-2 illustrates the importance of different scenarios investigation (question 1.6). According to these findings, it seems that most stakeholders tend to agree that is very important to investigate scenarios such as implementation of regulatory measures to limit speeds (32%), introducing extensive network of bicycle lanes (32%), promotion of public transport modes (38%), introduction of new transport modes (28%), implementing hierarchical schemes (36%), encouraging modal shift (36%), speed calming measures (34%) and expansion of cycling and walking infrastructure (24%). In addition, it is clear that a lower importance is

stated from 22% of the respondents in case of investigating the implementation of newer standards for bike lanes design. Finally, the 20% of the respondents are of the opinion that the investigation of modernising sustainable travel aligning with existing and predicted demand in advance of major events is moderately important.

Figure 4-1 Distribution of respondent city coverage worldwide and in Europe

Respondents also had the opportunity to indicate other scenarios in an open question. The scenarios that the respondents stated are the following:

- Larger sidewalks, encourage walking, quality of pedestrian network, decentralisation of administration from central urban areas throughout the city, foreseeing wider distances between new buildings for the construction of pedestrian and cycling infrastructure, more bike lanes in parks and green spaces, non-motorized modes investment increase, electric scooters, fines solutions for e-scooters
- Public transport as first priority over all other modes, public transport divestment, public transport development/urban/interurban, fast, constant and convenient public transport, at a low price etc., a reorganisation of traffic and mobility with an emphasis on accessibility, multi-modality and quality public transport, connecting bike lanes with metro stations, enforcing low speed (30 or 20 km/h) around metro stations, connecting bus lines with more metro/suburban rail stations
- Motorcyclists helmet use, safety problems of motorcycles
- Effect of hot and cold weather conditions to automated systems and sensors
- Proven effectiveness of street lighting on road safety in urban environments, proven effectiveness of street lighting on road safety in rural environments
- Parking spaces/parking system

- Digital transformation
- Capacity building of Road Safety professionals
- Implementing hierarchical, safe and connected road schemes is essential in road safety tools and measures, ensuring sustainability is a key element in modernising travel
- Simulation of traffic distribution in the event of temporary traffic organisation for the implementation of several road investments at the same time; management of the so-called green wave in traffic lights for public transport

Figure 4-2 Distribution of scenario investigation importance

The next sessions of the survey aimed to deep dive into the PHOEBE thematic areas. From the **Behavioural models**, it seems that the respondents tend to agree that it is highly important to include human behaviour in microscopic traffic simulation (38%), and in a road assessment tool (36%), as well as deriving human behaviour patterns from telematics data (23%) are highly important. Respondents also indicated the types of behaviours that PHOEBE should explore for drivers, pedestrians and cyclists (Table 4-1)

User Type	Suggested behaviours
<p>Drivers</p>	<p>Headways, gaze, vehicle position, acceleration, actual speed on junctions, reaction times, dispersion of speeds within the traffic flow</p> <p>Level of imprudence, speeding, dangerous manoeuvres, aggressive driving, disregard for traffic rules, driver fatigue, aggressive driving, late lane change, not stopping on pedestrian crossing, red light running, driving on public transport lane, violations to signage or yielding to pedestrians/bikes</p> <p>Pedestrian (and VRU) respect, respect to speed limits and signs</p> <p>All kind of distractions e.g. drink driving, mobile phone distraction</p> <p>Poor visibility issues due snow, ice, flat light conditions (zero contrasts condition)</p> <p>Driver responsibility on the road for himself and other road users</p> <p>Connections between driving (micro-)patterns</p> <p>Look at different mood and thus behaviour: respective; practically respective; dangerously respective, driving behaviour pattern: speed/traffic code compliance/drinking habits</p> <p>Legal/illegal parking, parking on right side of lane for 5-15 minutes (quick shopping, bakery, lottery etc.), walking distance from parking to destination, finding parking area</p> <p>Whichever ones have the greatest impact on traffic flow/interactions</p> <p>How often does a car driver check his car mirrors?</p> <p>Preventive behaviour</p>
<p>Pedestrians</p>	<p>Mobile phone distraction (messages, social networks, etc.), use of headphones on public roads while walking</p> <p>Jaywalking (crossing midblock when not allowed), crossing with very little time left on the pedestrian cycle, red light violations, mid-block crossing, walking on bicycle path, crossing road near (10-20m) pedestrian crossing (especially when pedestrian leaves public transport)</p> <p>Visibility (high-vis materials), poor visibility issues due snow, ice, flat light conditions (zero contrasts condition)</p> <p>Heart rate, gaze, position</p> <p>Level of imprudence</p> <p>Look at different mood and thus behaviour: respective; partially respective; dangerously respective</p> <p>Walking distance; waiting time to cross</p> <p>Age, mobility disabilities, attention to the surroundings, alone/groups</p> <p>How far ahead of time, does a car driver look at a pedestrian crossing an intersection?</p> <p>Relationship with the cyclists and cycle lanes</p> <p>Integrating walking with public transport, bus stops; distance walking</p> <p>Preventive behaviour</p>

User Type	Suggested behaviours
Cyclists	<p>Compliance with traffic regulations: speeding, red light violations, crossing road wherever they want, riding on pedestrian path or wherever they want to even when there is bicycle path, compliance to signage (e.g. stop/yield signs) or yielding to pedestrians, dangerous manoeuvres; aggressive driving; disregard for traffic rules; not circulating on cycle paths when there are</p> <p>Distraction: mobile phone distraction (messages, social networks, etc.), use of headphones on public roads while cycling, earphones use and fixation,</p> <p>Speed, headways, acceleration pedestrian (and other cyclists) respect, fatigue, helmet use, heart rate, gaze, vehicle position, age</p> <p>Riding with visibility, poor visibility issues due snow, ice, flat light conditions (zero contrasts condition)</p> <p>Deviant behaviour, careless leaving of micro scooters in the midst of walkways</p> <p>Look at different mood and thus behaviour: respective; partially respective; dangerously respective</p> <p>Lack of protective equipment, safety measures</p> <p>Preventive behaviour</p> <p>Parking places</p>

Table 4-1 Suggested behaviours PHOEBE should consider to assess.

Most respondents also tend to agree that **new data collection methods** inclusion in a microscopic traffic simulation and in a road assessment tool as well as inclusion of data obtained by a telematics recording device are highly important. Specifically, 27% of the respondents stated that it is very important in a microscopic simulation to include new data collection methods, while 34% and 31% stated that it is very important in a road safety assessment tool and in a telematics recording device respectively. Stakeholders also highlighted the types of data that can be useful in these models:

- cameras, telematics, mobile phone data, floating vehicle data, sensors (e.g. at lighting poles), AI, iRAP
- Micro mobility origin-destination, passenger origin-destination, pedestrian demand
- Floating car data (probe data), vehicle speed, vehicle type division
- Vehicular conflicts and interactions with vulnerable users
- Behavioural data related to users of the road environment, be they pedestrians, drivers and users of soft modes of mobility, while using the road
- Walking trips, bike trips
- Quality of the data provided (and our understanding of that data and how it could integrate with our current analysis tools)

Again, most respondents tend to agree that **modal shift** effects inclusion in a microscopic traffic simulation (38%) and in a road assessment tool (32%) as well as monitoring modal shift effects using a telematics recording device (36%) are highly important. The most important mode shifts to explore are:

- From passenger cars to Public Transport
- From passenger cars to smooth modes of mobility: cycling, walking and shared mobility services
- From public transport to cycling
- Micro perspective

- To/from strategic / longer distance highway trips
- Increase of bike share
- Incentivize non-motorized modes and transit
- Safe System

Some questions are presented but asking for **Socioeconomic models**. Most respondents tend to agree that socioeconomic parameters inclusion in a microscopic traffic simulation and in a road assessment tool, although the percentage are lower than the previous thematic areas (22% and 24% respectively). Here the suggestions are to explore:

- Age, gender, education level, ethnicity, education level, family size
- Ownership of vehicle, distance home-work, attitudes/perception, area of residence, transport mode
- Local GDP, purchasing power, average family income, value of time, value of life and injury, operation costs
- Negative externalities due to construction or car usage
- Space for pedestrians, bikes, bus lanes, and also delivery
- Concept of 'levelling up' (perhaps some parameters that could inform that)
- Socio-economic inequality

In the case of the **“Road safety assessment”**, when asked about the importance of including infrastructure-related safety risk in a microsimulation tool, the stakeholders divided their opinions into slightly important (39%) and very important (30%), but the majority agree that use telematics data is fundamental to enrich road safety assessments (32%). Respondents suggested the following elements as essential to be considered in road safety assessments.

- Speed limits, lane width, sidewalk width, road surface, horizontal and vertical signs, curvature, visibility, traffic volume, traffic speed (V85)
- Whether Street Lighting makes a difference
- Urban road network risk assessment
- VRU, vulnerability-based, pedestrian crossing
- Walking and Cycling
- Methodology defined in the ISO 31000 Standard

The tendency remains for **traffic microsimulation** inclusion in a road assessment tool (33% as very important) and telematics data inclusion in a microsimulation tool (27% as very important). When asked about what should be simulated, stakeholders suggested:

- Intersection micro-simulation - pedestrian
- Lane changing in highways
- Differentiating type of vehicle
- Conflicts
- Detection systems of speed and traffic density

After ranking importance of integrate the different PHOIEBE thematic areas, stakeholders were asked to report their professional needs and the usefulness of having these integrations. The complete results can be found in Annex C. It seems that most stakeholders see relevance to their needs of enriching traffic simulation with infrastructure safety information (30%), with modal shift information (28%), with induced

demand models (36%) and with human behaviour models (26%). In addition, most respondents stated that it is very important to improve accuracy of traffic simulation (40%) and to enrich traffic simulation with all these aforementioned aspects (34%). Regarding road assessment, most stakeholders stated that it is very important to enrich road assessment with traffic microsimulation information (26%) and with AI/ML models (28%). On the other hand, a slight importance is stated from the 24%, 28% and 26% of respondents in case of the need of road assessment enhanced with modal shift information, with induced demand models and with human behaviour models respectively. Finally, 32% of stakeholders stated that the need to enrich road assessment with all these aspects is very important.

In the case of usefulness, most stakeholders tend to agree that it would be very useful in everyday tasks to have a PHOEBE-developed tool that could enrich traffic simulation with infrastructure safety information (24%) and with modal shift information (22%). On the other hand, a moderate usefulness is stated from the 22% and 24% of respondents in case of a PHOEBE-developed tool that could enrich traffic simulation with induced demand models and with human behaviour models respectively. Regarding road assessment, the majority of stakeholders stated that a PHOEBE-developed tool would be slightly useful if could enrich road assessment with microsimulation information (22%), with modal shift information (26%), induced demand models (26%) and with human behaviour models (22%). Finally, a tool that could enhance road assessment with AI/ML models and with all the aforementioned aspects would be very useful for the majority of stakeholders (28% and 26% respectively).

The two final questions aimed to understand with what frequency a user will use the PHOEBE Framework and if they believed the framework could impact the actual number of crash data. Around 70% of the respondents agree that they will use the expected PHOEBE-developed tool from often enough to very frequently. Stakeholders are more sceptical about the real impact of the tool, with 58% of the respondent replying with rates varying from will impact enough to an extreme impact.

4.1.1 Use case stakeholders examination

In order to highlight any possible diversity of stakeholders opinion of the three different PHOEBE use cases (Athens, Valencia and West Midlands), similar analyses were generated for each use case group of stakeholders. For this reason, the answers of the stakeholders working in Athens, Valencia and West Midlands were grouped resulting in seven stakeholders in the group of Athens, five in Valencia and three in West Midlands region. It should be acknowledged that the particular investigations presented in this chapter are an effort to glean specific needs and individual characteristics of each use case city rather than general-use transferable statistics. First of all, there are no differences regarding education levels, since the Specifically, the majority of stakeholders hold a master degree for all the three groups (71% for Athens, 60% for Valencia and 67% for West Midlands stakeholders). On the other hand, the tools they use in their daily activities seems to vary among the groups as showed in Figure 4-3. The majority (17%) of Athens stakeholders use traffic signal optimization software, while the majority (21%) of Valencia stakeholders use routing software and the majority (25%) of West Midlands stakeholders use macroscopic traffic simulation.

Figure 4-3 Distribution of software/tool type usage per use case stakeholders

In Figure 4-4, the importance of different scenarios investigation is presented. According to these findings, it seems that the three different groups of stakeholders tend to agree that it is highly important to investigate the majority of the scenarios. On the other hand, there are some cases where it can be noticed that the opinions of the three different groups of stakeholders are differentiated. Specifically, Athens stakeholders stated a moderate importance in case of investigating the implementation of regulatory measures to limit speeds (29%), the management of conflict due to introduction of new transport modes (29%), the implementation of newer standards for bike lanes design (29%) and modernising sustainable travel aligning with existing and predicted demand in advance of major events (43%), while the rest groups reported a higher importance. Furthermore, West Midlands stakeholders stated a moderate importance for investigating promotion of public transport (33%), while Athens (57%) and Valencia (80%) stakeholders stated that this kind of investigation is very important.

The importance of integrating the thematic areas also varies between use cases. For Athens, stakeholders integrating modal shift and socioeconomic parameters into microscopic simulation tools, socioeconomic parameters into road safety assessment and human behaviour in telematic recording devices are the most rated integrations. In the case of Valencia, the highest percentage of responses are distributed among human behaviour and socioeconomic parameters into microscopic simulation tools and modal shift into road safety assessment tools. The reduced number of responses from the West Midlands regions and the high value given to the integrations suggested making it challenging to determine the most valued integration. Nevertheless, for the given responses, integrating modal shift is important for all the respondents. The same applies to human behaviour integration with road safety assessment and telematic recording devices.

Integration of PHOEBE thematic areas			Very important (scores 9 to 10)		
			Athens	Valencia	West Midlands
Human behaviour	→	Microscopic traffic simulation tools	34%	60%	67%
New data collection methods			33%	20%	33%
Modal shift			50%	40%	100%
Socioeconomic parameters			50%	60%	67%
Human behaviour	→	Road assessment tools	17%	40%	100%
New data collection methods			33%	20%	67%
Modal shift			33%	60%	100%
Socioeconomic parameters			50%	40%	67%
Human behaviour	→	Telematics recording devices	50%	40%	100%
New data collection methods			33%	40%	67%
Modal shift			29%	40%	100%

Table 4-2 Integration into PHOEBE thematic areas considered very important for the use case stakeholders

Furthermore, no significant differentiation between the opinions of the different stakeholder groups is noticed for the rest of the aspects evaluated. Specifically, most of all stakeholder groups stated a high importance of the following cases: infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies in a microsimulation tool, telematics data in infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies, microsimulation tools in a road assessment tool and telematics data in a microsimulation tool.

Importance of an investigation of each of the following scenarios in stakeholders daily work

Figure 4-4 Distribution of scenario investigation importance per use case stakeholders

According to the overall professional needs, it seems that the three different groups of stakeholders tend to agree on the needs that are highly important. Nevertheless, there are few cases where it can be noticed that the opinions of the three different groups of stakeholders are differentiated. Specifically, Valencia stakeholders stated a moderate importance of the need of enhancing road assessment with traffic microsimulation, with modal shift information, with induced demand models, with human behaviour models and with AI/ML models as well.

In the case of the usefulness of a PHOEBE-developed tool the majority of West Midlands stakeholders tend to agree that all kinds of the possible features of a PHOEBE-developed tool would be very useful in their everyday tasks. On the other hand, a moderate usefulness is stated from the Valencia stakeholders for all the proposed capabilities of a tool. Focusing on the answers given from the Athens stakeholders, they agreed with Valencia stakeholders for features of enriching traffic simulation with induced demand models, road assessment with modal shift information, with induced demand models and with AI/ML models as well. For the rest of capabilities, Athens stakeholders stated a higher usefulness agreeing with West Midlands stakeholder opinion.

Most respondents (43% from Athens, 40% from Valencia and 30% from West Midlands) stated that they will use the expected PHOEBE-developed tool often enough. Regarding the effectiveness of the expected PHOEBE tool on real crash numbers, it seems that the majority (67%) of West Midlands stakeholders are quite optimistic stating an adequate impact, while the majority (43%) of Athens ones pointed to a more moderate impact. In the case of Valencia stakeholders, a more pessimistic point of view is noticed, as the 40% stated that it will not impact at all the real crash numbers.

The complete results for the use case stakeholders are presented in Annex D: Additional stakeholders survey results graphs. In closing, some additional comments have been provided by the interviewers regarding the interviews with Valencia City Hall, and specifically:

- Interactions between cyclists and pedestrians are a constant concern for the Valencia City Hall.
- The Valencia City Hall considers cars as the strongest danger for both pedestrians and cyclists, thus they are committed to reducing their presence and can be interested in tools that help them prove this fact.
- Road safety is considered very important and an urgent matter by ETRA EMT and ATMV, especially when related to the interactions between cyclists and pedestrians.
- There is a great interest (Valencia City Hall, EMT, ATMV) in boosting modal shift) connection public transport and non-motorised vehicles.
- A great interest has been shown in introduction of AI in data collection methods.
- For what relates to socio economic analysis: Its inclusion in microscopic analysis has not been considered useful by the majority of the interviewees, but they would include this kind of analysis when connecting type of transport mode to area of residence, and revenues per year, to better understand correlations.

According to EMT, it would be interesting to study divestment in public transport and its redirection (if any) toward non-motorised public transportation options.

4.2 Focus groups

From the five sessions of the focus groups, key issues were identified. These issues are linked and overlap with one another, and they appeared throughout all the questions, not following a linear discussion, as expected.

Key issues identified:

- Road Safety Understanding

- Organisational structures (knowledge and practices)
- Organisational resources and capabilities
- Concept vs reality

The Figure 4-5 demonstrates how these issues are connected and influence one another.

Figure 4-5 Key issues identified in focus groups and their interdependencies

4.2.1 Road Safety Understanding

Among the topics that emerged from the focus groups, one essential and underlying issue is **Road safety understanding**, which influences many current practices and challenges faced by practitioners. Professionals talked about the different ways and perspectives of road safety, with “issues on how we approach road safety”.

Participants see a deficiency in how the link between road deaths and other decisions (towards other modes) made in transport and mobility are perceived, relating to politicians’ real understanding of vision zero. When the financial and political reasons for road safety weigh in decisions (perceived versus real risk), it can lead to misleading or dangerous processes since politicians do not have a proper understanding of road safety. When is a financial decision, the priority will be on the return on investment. When it is a political decision, the importance is to please someone or a group.

That issue also relates to the organisational structures that will be discussed below, which lead cities, and citizens not to have the full point of view. It was argued that showing the wider benefits of road safety is needed and that a tool that could support professionals in doing so would be useful.

How to show that a lack of road safety indirectly impacts other city goals like sustainable transport, liveliness and attractiveness of the cities? Professionals agreed that comparing impacts on collision and road safety

is currently problematic. i.e. to compare the number of saved lives and the increase in travel time, “congestion is tangible. Can we calculate traffic safety?”.

“it would be easier to say we will save five lives rather than five minutes from your commute”.

Professionals raised the issue that the *cost-benefit analysis* of road safety measures should bring visibility to the social costs and the economic and health benefits. A more comprehensive cost-benefit analysis could minimise bad perceptions that could arise, mainly linked to reducing speeds, traffic flows, reallocation of space and other measures. There should be possibilities to enable politicians to show that the implemented solutions are the best way to go.

Even though it is relevant that road safety needs to be economically viable, comprehensive road safety interventions do not necessarily mean a considerable cost increase. However, concerning the political costs, for example, congestion, or other unpopular decisions, where politicians fear the complaints, participants argued that road safety needs to be made more visible to prevail. The population is not fully aware of road safety and what it might entail. Thus, there also needs to be an inevitable *shift in society* in relation to road safety. Participants noted that people are often “talking about perceptions, bias perceptions”.

“Accidents with cars are perceived as normal.”

The trade-offs make the conversation and decision-making processes difficult, for example, when it involves removing parking, changing traffic flows, or implementing one-way streets. Moreover, because cities and citizens are not having a complete picture of all that implies in taking measures for increased road safety, especially for VRUs.

“No one is against road safety, but the trade-offs make the decision complicated.”

So, what could help with these trade-offs? It was highlighted that figuring out the problem first and establishing priorities is important. So, what is the real problem, and what is the city trying to tackle?

Participants talked about a lack of methodology for prioritisation – lack of evaluation methods for different users – prioritisation and risk evaluation can still be linked with different lobbying (cars, trucks, buses, bikes). They also discussed that current tools and processes for road safety do not accommodate the coexistence among different users. One participant noted that “you think you are doing it safe for pedestrians, but it is not”, because processes are still very much car-focused and using car-oriented solutions to VRUs.

“We work with the intention of increasing road safety but sometimes goes by the other way.”

The issues on how road safety is understood and perceived raise questions such as is road safety currently biased? Are VRUs being fully considered in road safety decisions? The participants of the focus groups provided more insights into these questions that will be discussed further. However, it is clear that these issues are more deeply rooted and that they overlap and reflect in the other key topics identified.

4.2.2 Organisational structures (knowledge and practices)

Looking into the *Organisational structures (knowledge and practices)*, it is possible to recognise that these structures are not disassociated with the overall understanding of road safety and the very own capabilities of organisations, and these will also greatly influence the current road safety processes and decisions and might pose challenges in the acceptance of future approaches. Participants also considered the *deficiencies in the current tools* and the assessment of *VRUs and new mobilities* within the organisational knowledge and practices.

Throughout the questions, participants brought up issues on how knowledge and expertise about road safety are very much fragmented within institutions. The participants highlighted the importance of spreading expertise amongst different departments and areas within institutions and undoubtedly connecting with the issue of road safety understanding that was previously discussed.

Participants debated that it is currently common to have narrow points of view, the different professional areas do not communicate, and each has its own perspectives and understanding of road safety. In addition, depending on the department they work for, professionals will bring priorities – the traffic department worries about congestion, public transport about the speed of buses, and so on. For example, while talking about how professionals assume that others are thinking in similar ways, without questioning. However, in reality, there is a lack of communication and understanding.

“As technicians, we think we understand each other”.

The participants indicated that a framework that could bring all the different professionals together and include all points of view is needed. As mentioned, “road safety is about more than one thing” and not linking all the aspects of road design/space design/road safety within a city will only result in suboptimal results and affect the desired outcomes of reducing road fatalities, improving quality of life and others.

What is presently more common is the lack of awareness of different ways of looking at and addressing things in road safety because technicians have different sensibilities and approaches. There is an “easiness to implement versus correct way”, and sometimes it can be seen as more of a “ticking a box” than having a holistic understanding of road safety. Participants noted that for a new framework to be relevant, the information it will provide needs to be applicable to the key domains of road safety. It should not be a “specific tool, but an overall tool”.

“It should address road safety horizontally and not vertically”.

That raised the issue that the processes within institutions need to change, to move away from this segregated, silo-type approach towards a holistic process. Therefore, it is pertinent to have a framework that is useful and available to all the different kinds of professionals working on road safety, allowing the needed change to take place and enabling a more comprehensive attitude towards road safety.

However, participants highlighted that organisations move slowly and that there is resistance to doing things differently. As a result, it is hard to change processes and the question “how the new method can be integrated in the existing processes?” arose.

Nevertheless, participants also examined how the current tools are not fully addressing road safety needs. The *deficiencies in the existing tools* become more evident when the professionals talk about the modal shift, all the different users and transportation systems.

While debating over this aspect of modal shift, one participant noted, “the model is not able to capture the modal shift, the choices made when the (new) infrastructure is built”, for example, if they are proposing a new tram line, a new cycle line or others, so when there is a redistribution of modes. Another participant elaborated further when considering the behavioural aspects that cannot be inputted in the current tools “I mean, not only the distribution of the traffic but the behaviours in terms of some anxiety in moving because of some road narrowing or some so-called conflicts with other users of the road”. Finally, participants noted that looking into the relationship between behaviour and modal shift/ mode share will become increasingly more relevant if cities hope for a more balanced distribution between modes or prioritising more sustainable and active modes.

Following on that, participants pondered if it was possible to “flip the conversation” by using models to find network inefficiencies.

“Conversations about traffic models are still focused on what happens to motor vehicles - We already know we want to build a bike lane – the question we want to ask is at what volume this street will work, working backwards - to help make our vision to help achieve our vision of having safer walking and cycling routes”.

Complemented by another, “if you don’t take up the space there will never be a modal shift”. That might reflect on participants noting that there has not been as much innovation in road safety as it should be.

Accordingly, *VRUs and new mobilities* considerations within the current organisational structures, practices and tools fall short. Participants argued that there is a lack of detailed knowledge of VRUs. It is far behind if compared to car/vehicle knowledge.

There was an overall perception that in the tools, ‘everything’ is car related or that much of the attention is dedicated to cars. It was discussed that the safety of vehicles can be relatively easy since it is visible and there are easy-fix (e.g. seat belts, airbags, etc.). On the other hand, it is not the case when talking about the safety of pedestrians (and micromobilities). Participants discussed that it is a more complex issue, and opinions can get easily dispersed.

Considering models, participants expressed that modelling for pedestrians, cyclists and micromobilities should differ from modelling for vehicles. They discussed how current tools are not considering how people move, their rhythm and other particularities. One participant detailed:

“It is always built upon people going from A to B, and that is how usually works for cars, but not so much for pedestrians and cyclists (...) You do some unexpected things more than go from A to B, and that is the thing that the models are still far away from reproducing, even though they can model the way people walk and the way they queue and so on. It is still on, people are still going from A to B and only doing that and being predictive. They are not turning around doing that kind of stuff. (...) It is hard to modulate people doing erratic behaviour.”

Another participant noted another discrepancy between the tools to their needs, “We are not interested in how fast people can get from one place to another. But like how safe and what their experience is”.

Considering also the lack of proper data regarding VRUs and micromobilities, the professionals find it hard to understand the possible conflicts and interactions between the different types of VRUs. This leads to difficulties in assessing the risks and what may be seen as risky behaviours from VRUs, consequently generating a perverse habit of blaming VRUs for some of their behaviours and possible crashes. The participants debated that these behaviours usually resulted from a lack of space or gaps in the infrastructure and argued that it would be possible to use that to move the conversation forward, evolving from this perspective. For instance, data could help show these gaps in the infrastructure, “but we oftentimes see that the problem in itself is not sidewalk riding. The problem in itself is people are trying to choose their most efficient way of getting to their destination. How? Making the choice based on how safe they think the facility is.” exemplified by one participant.

A participant challenged, “will the traffic simulation models software of today help with the increase of new mobilities?”. The relevance of this question is highlighted when participants also discuss the issue of mixing or segregating VRUs from car traffic because of road safety. Although segregating VRUs and car traffic can provide increased safety for VRUs, this type of solution has a limit - How much space is needed to segregate all the different modes that exist and will appear? How can the safety of VRUs and new mobilities be addressed within future realities of cities? Can current and new tools and processes provide new ways of addressing VRUs’ safety?

Participants reflected that road safety has always been reactive, especially towards VRUs, and it should take a more proactive position instead.

4.2.3 Organisational resources and capabilities

But how are the **resources and capabilities** of local and regional authorities? Participants discussed the resources and capabilities of the organisations that are affecting their current practices and decision making process. Moreover, they also discussed how the resources and capabilities, including the data aspect, will likewise influence the possible implementation of new frameworks within these authorities and organisations.

Participants talked openly about a 'lack of knowledge' towards the possibilities of modelling and simulation tools. Statements about the "lack of specialists for specialised tools" or "very hard to find transport simulation experts" were frequent examples of the lack of human resources and the right qualifications. In addition to a lack of human resources, there is also a problem with staff turnover and the transfer of knowledge from those leaving to those arriving or staying in the organisations. That refers to the already mentioned problem of fragmented and siloed working practices toward road safety.

So, for example, it demands such specific training or knowledge to use these tools or methods (modelling and simulation), and it is being so centralised in a few professionals that when they leave the public organisations, no one can take up that knowledge. Low financial resources also account for not being able to retain or hire specialised staff and professionals. The lack of time and personnel also creates a lack of autonomy, making it difficult for local governments to make some decisions related to road safety.

The participants discussed that public organisations and institutions might lack the capacity to absorb new approaches and methodologies and might not be able to receive these changes. Consequently, municipalities and local governments might be overwhelmed by new data sources, new techniques and the possibilities these might bring, maybe leading them to not being able to respond to the needs of citizens. One possible solution for the inability to act would be that the framework could support cities in establishing response priorities.

"They believe they are doing the best, so they take as an insult when they are offered new and better ways of doing things",

The statement above could indicate that introducing a new method might demand a soft approach, showcasing the added value for the current practice.

There was an overall consensus that there must be an organisational change from the inside, but it is difficult to change that mindset, partially due to the deficiencies organisations face. A participant observed, "they are not ready for that" leading to the consideration that changes need to happen parallelly for new frameworks to be absorbed.

While specifically discussing **data**, many concerns emerged. Participants highlighted that many cities and professionals have difficulty getting the data, which is the first challenge. Even when this first challenge might not exist or be overcome, other challenges remain. For instance, a participant emphasised, "for us, data is free, we collect a lot of it ourselves, but still very expensive to work on". An issue that was raised by many.

The need to treat data, the transformations and requirements pose challenges to many authorities, leading them to question the costs over the value of what they can get from this data. In addition, the lack of organisational capacity and resources creates difficulties with data, exposing organisations to the wrong input of data and inadequate or insufficient data.

Participants debated that even though, in theory, data is welcome and might be very useful, in reality, it is trickier. Due to the above-mentioned constraints, the real challenge may be in understanding what to do

with data to make the cost value worth it. In addition, local and regional authorities might be overwhelmed by data and its uses, which might outweigh the value that exist in it.

Nevertheless, participants also discussed the lack of data and knowledge to solve VRUs issues. For example, some participants discussed the difficulty of getting relevant data on pedestrians or micromobilities. It was also noted that traditional data (e.g. police reports) is the only data fully available to professionals (e.g. consultants). Furthermore, in general, operators of micromobilities or even public transport might have better insights into where people are travelling than cities.

4.2.4 Concept vs reality

The last issue underlying the previous topics was the *concept vs reality*, referring to the current practices and a new framework.

Much was argued about ‘false safety’ or ‘safety on paper’, meaning that road safety measures are often not genuine or do not translate into reality. Instead, they stay in conceptual ideas or just fulfil technical recommendations. Participants stated that having recommendations does not mean putting them into place.

Participants debated that authorities, or even professionals, often do not see the implications that the lack of connection between design guidelines and road safety has in reality, which leads to “safety on paper”. Problems with integrating information were also raised - How a new tool, or framework, can be applied in different departments – reflecting on how things are now. If a new framework cannot integrate tools and information, the discrepancy between real safety and safety on paper will persist.

Participants also reasoned that simulation and modelling software are only supporting tools, and one participant noted, “there are things we can never ever simulate”. The professionals emphasised that the software packages have an important role in road safety. Still, it is essential to understand what that role is. They highlighted the relevance of promoting a conscious understanding of road safety to have the ability to interpret and understand its many facets. A participant mentioned, “Having the sensibility to understand what you are doing, what does it represent?”. It was also debated that these points become even more relevant when considering road safety from a VRUs perspective.

For VRU safety, statements such as “models assume you follow the rules - If the level of safety is a product of a bad design, the model can detect, but if it is a production of bad behaviour no” and “models can give hints, but it is my experience that will say this will not be safe” show that currently, the gap between concept and reality is still significant. Participants debated that presently such software packages can be counterproductive towards VRUs safety.

“Traffic simulations are used as a weapon of decision, not as a tool”.

Moreover, it was also reasoned that, in the end, decisions are made by humans, and one participant assertively said, “we have to change the paradigm to use these technologies in our everyday lives”.

While discussing a future framework (e.g. PHOEBE Framework) for road safety, participants talked about the concerns they see in trying to implement it. For instance, demonstrating the added value of such a framework is important. Because it is something new, a new way of working, cities may argue that it does not apply to their context, will this framework be applicable to the different typologies of cities on a different scale? The framework must also assess the right road safety level – local level x city level x regulatory level (national or European).

Besides the financial and practical side of implementing a new framework, it might be hard to sell this idea to decision makers. A participant exemplified, “the challenge would be for cities and people working in those issues to see how we integrate these new tools into our existing processes and how they can either complement or how they might be in conflict with what people are doing today.”

The participants debated that understanding the possibilities of a new framework is essential and might not be a simple task, “it will definitely take time to actually fully understand what this model will do”, – concluded one participant.

A final remark from one participant about a possible new framework raises a relevant point:

“When you talk about traffic simulation and new modelling and new software, are you coming from still, the more traditional motor vehicle planning lens, or are we now thinking potentially like more purpose-built models to address either multimodal operations or even focus on vulnerable road users? (...) purpose-built for people walking and cycling, and thinking through that, maybe we will find that we are interested in different things.”

4.3 User Needs Statements for the design of the PHOEBE Framework

In this Deliverable, a broad survey-based consultation of European and global stakeholders was carried out, together with an in-depth consultation via focus groups. This section synthesizes the needs of stakeholders at three levels: i) their strategic goals relevant to PHOEBE themes; ii) their decision support needs and the implications of the envisaged developments on their daily practice, and iii) their methodological and technical recommendations on the PHOEBE framework. A separate summary is made for the PHOEBE use cases stakeholders.

The project can benefit greatly from this knowledge, allowing a consistent framework development, encouraging its usefulness beyond the project’s lifetime, and increasing the possibilities to adapt to cities realities and expanding impacts. Moreover, stakeholders support the consortium in identifying the possible limitations of the framework, allowing it to be realistic about what it can or cannot address. That will make the PHOEBE framework more effective in its own merits and contribute to a broader discussion on road safety and the needed advancements and changes in higher-level spheres.

The needs statements below will be used in the development of the methodological framework in tasks 1.2 and 1.3, as well as to set up a systematic and meaningful exchange with relevant stakeholders throughout the project.

4.3.1 Revisiting strategic goals

- The stakeholders consulted see a deficiency in how the link between road deaths and other decisions (towards other modes) made in transport and mobility are perceived, relating to politicians’ and citizens’ **real understanding of strategies such as “vision zero”**.
- **A shift in society is urgent: to better explain what it means to improve road safety.** It is clear to stakeholders and citizen what it means to redesign urban areas or reallocate public space. The cities typically think in terms of sustainability, liveability, public space, value of time, inequality, incomes, but current software are very car focused.
- To that end, more transparent and **explainable cost-benefit analyses** can support better communication, justification and prioritization of road safety actions by bringing visibility to the social costs, and the economic and health benefits, and spreading the understanding of the reasoning behind each road safety intervention.
- It is important to **clearly highlight in what ways a lack of road safety indirectly impacts other city goals** like sustainable transport, liveliness and attractiveness of the cities. Moreover, to establish an equally clear link between urban planning and infrastructure design, and road safety.

- Accordingly, it is important to make a clear decision about **broadening the planning lens by a shift of focus to include VRUs, and their safety**. That is becoming increasingly evident from the road safety perspective, where approaches, processes, organisational structures and capacities still depart from a car/vehicle way of thinking, unable to address many issues and, at times, reinforcing road risks.
- Therefore, new methodologies should support **a holistic view of urban issues, in which safety will have a core role, thus breaking the ‘silos’ approach** in which urban planning, traffic planning and management, safety assessment, sustainability / liveability and other similar goals are tackled.
- The PHOEBE framework needs to be promoted in a transparent and explainable way, to clearly demonstrate how it fits in or complements the current practice. Thereby avoiding false expectations and ensure more effective outcomes, it is important that PHOEBE fully recognises its limitations, not as shortcomings, but as leverage as a key player in the road safety discussion, advocating for the necessary changes and new ways to address them. **PHOEBE should support and advocate for the cities needs, but set a clear scope so that expectations are properly aligned.**
- A more comprehensive method for **socioeconomic impact analysis could minimise erroneous perceptions**, mainly linked to the scopes of reducing speeds, managing traffic flows, reallocating space, and other measures that have clear safety impacts.
- PHOEBE should take a multi-disciplinary approach involving stakeholders from various sectors to guide the selection of use case sites and the collection of data.

4.3.2 Decision support and daily practice needs statements

- In many cases, the different professional areas within local authorities do not communicate, and each has its own perspectives and understanding of road safety. **A framework that could bring all the different professionals together and include all points of view is needed.**
- Traffic simulation is used as a tool to support planning but there are concerns that it may be **counterproductive as long as default users are programmed to follow the rules**, thereby not allowing to estimate real safety impacts.
- Most stakeholders tend to agree that it is **very important to enrich traffic simulation** with infrastructure safety information, with modal shift information, with induced demand models and with human behaviour models as well.
- In addition, the majority of respondents stated that it is very important to **improve accuracy of traffic simulation and to enrich road assessment with traffic microsimulation** information and with AI/ML models
- Participants also considered the deficiencies in the current tools and the **assessment of VRUs and new mobility types within the organisational knowledge and practices**. Processes and tools are still very car-focused and we use car-oriented solutions for VRUs modelling.
- Current focus is on modal shift from cars to public transport, whereas there is need to **incorporate new sustainable modes (including micromobility)**. Modal shift should be included in conjunction with new data sources and clearer links to the road safety impacts.
- Compared to other components of the system, it is less clear to stakeholders how the PHOEBE approach to enhance modal shift models could be operationalized in their decision support tools.
- Stakeholders agree that all these potential developments are important, but it is less clear to them **how they could make a difference in their “daily” practice**.

4.3.3 Methodological and technical needs statements

- In order to induce modal shift, there is a **need to backcast, looking at the traffic and safety effects given the selected policy goal** e.g. a goal to reallocate the space for cyclists.
- It is important to acknowledge that VRU behaviour is more random, it cannot be modelled on the origin-destination trajectory way like cars.
- **The random and unpredictable way of movement of pedestrians** should be seen as a means to get an efficient path *given* the deficiencies of the facilities, and not necessarily as a reckless and violating behaviour.
- **The following human factors are prioritized** by the consulted stakeholders:
 - Distraction (all types, incl. mobiles and social networks)
 - Speeding, compliance
 - Jaywalking, path violation
 - Aggressiveness
- **The following new data source are prioritized** by the consulted stakeholders:
 - Smartphones, cameras, sensors' data
 - Floating car data
 - Origin-destination data for micromobility
 - Telematics data that can be usable for risk assessment:]
- At the same time, **new data sources might overwhelm local authorities, in the lack of human resources** that would be trained and knowledgeable on using them
- **Data accessibility and the high cost to work with the emerging data** is a barrier for their exploitation by cities. It is not clear to many participant how data on VRU movements can be obtained or even systematically collected.
- Participants expressed the need for opening a dialogue with **operators of micromobilities in order share data**, and indicated that it would be an added value for PHOEBE to demonstrate the use of such data.

4.3.4 PHOEBE use cases

While there was broad consensus among the survey participants, a number of points can be highlighted in terms of the particularities of the three distinct PHOEBE use case cities.

- **Athens** stakeholders stated a moderate importance in case of investigating the implementation of regulatory measures to limit speeds, the management of conflict due to introduction of new transport modes, the implementation of newer standards for bike lanes design and modernising sustainable travel aligning with existing and predicted demand in advance of major events, while the rest groups reported a higher importance.
- **West Midlands** stakeholders stated a moderate importance for investigating promotion of public transport, while **Athens** and **Valencia** stakeholders stated that this kind of investigation is very important.
- **Athens** and **Valencia** stakeholders tend to agree that is moderately important to include human behaviour in a road assessment tool as well as to derive human behaviour patterns from telematics data, while **West Midlands** stakeholders opinion is that for both cases is very important.
- **Athens** and **West Midlands** stakeholders tend to agree that it is highly important to include new data collection methods in a microsimulation and road assessment tool as well as data

obtained by a telematics recording device. On the other hand, the **Valencia** stakeholders stated a moderate importance for all these cases.

- Overall **Valencia** stakeholders appeared to have more moderate views for the overall professional needs when it comes to most of the aspects to be integrated in the PHOEBE framework.

These particularities do not reflect major disagreements, they do highlight the need for a tailored approach in each use case. Overall, it is important to make sure **that tested use cases are aligned with actual needs and priorities – also in light of data availability. This can be seen as a challenge and an opportunity to develop a holistic but case-sensitive tool.** Alongside PHOEBE's pilots, the framework should continue an honest and open discussion with cities. This will ensure that the project outcomes are applicable and relevant to real-world scenario, making the interventions and framework more effective and impactful.

Undoubtedly what the PHOEBE Framework can achieve has a limitation since such a shift encompasses many other aspects beyond the project scope. The focus groups' participants raised many questions and challenges that PHOEBE certainly will encounter. The reality of cities and public authorities is filled with resistance and lack many resources, making it challenging for them to adopt new ways of working even when there is the intention to. Thus, to avoid false expectations and ensure more effective outcomes, it is important that PHOEBE fully recognises its limitations, not as shortcomings, but as leverage as a key player in the road safety discussion, advocating for the necessary changes and new ways to address them. Alongside PHOEBE's pilots, continuing with an honest and open discussion with cities and other stakeholders is essential for that. The focus groups were an initial step in this process of acknowledging their needs and will continue throughout the project in many ways.

5 Conclusions and recommendations

The PHOEBE Framework is a methodological approach designed for cities to improve understanding of the safety implications of future changes in the transport systems, such as behavioural changes, redesign or new infrastructure, or the introduction of a new mode. To do so, it aims to bring together several existing elements including:

- Traffic simulation environments, which provide insights into how these various elements interact in virtual traffic scenarios
- Road safety assessment, which can provide objective measures of road user safety linked to speed, flow and the physical road features
- Human behaviour models which can help anticipate how road users respond in given scenarios, how people select which mode of transport to use or when/where to take a trip (the latter coming into the category of mode shift and induced demand models, which can predict consumer choices and road user flow changes), and
- Socio-economic impact assessment which can understand the health, safety, economic and environmental impacts of changes in the transport system.

Together, these elements will enable analysis on the combined effect of future changes, as well as how this will change over time.

This deliverable, which is the direct output of Task 1.1 of the project, aims to review the state-of-the-art in each component utilized in the PHOEBE Framework, and gain a deeper understanding of the needs of cities and transport planners. The findings of the state-of-the-art review will be to inform the theoretical development, including the key principles and methodology of the PHOEBE Framework (Task 1.2). The User Needs Statement will inform the development and design of tools and support materials for end users to ensure the framework can be utilised for its stated purpose.

The development of the PHOEBE Framework involves three principal aspects:

1. First is the **theoretical development**, which includes the research, where necessary, for key principles and methodology of the framework
2. Second is the **technical developments** required to ensure that the technical components of the framework have the necessary functionality to meet the framework's needs and produced the analysis required, and
3. Third are the **tools and support materials for end users** to ensure the framework can be utilised for its stated purpose.

The following sections break down the discussion and implications of the review and stakeholder consultation findings for each aspect.

5.1 Implications on the theoretical development of the PHOEBE Framework

The development of the PHOEBE methodology relates directly to the first objective of the PHOEBE project, which is to **develop a new, replicable methodology for dynamic safety prediction and socio-economic evaluation**. This methodology needs to:

- Be both harmonised and scalable for all types of road users
- Link appropriate risk indicators at micro-, meso- and macro-level

- Contain replicable methods for modelling and simulating modal shift and risk of future new modes, behavioural adaptation and road user safety, and
- Allow the estimation of social costs and benefits in terms of health and safety, environmental, and economic aspects.

The concept of the PHOEBE Framework is to establish a methodological framework around the integrated applications of traffic simulation tools, road safety assessment and data.

The review highlighted the pivotal role of human behaviour models in traffic simulation tools, particularly for the inclusion of vulnerable road user groups, such as pedestrians and bicyclists, which relies on the simulation of more realistic road user behaviours. Human behaviour is also understanding demand, including mode choice and mode shift.

Human behaviour is currently captured in road safety assessment models, such as the Star Ratings, primarily through operating speeds and road user flow data, such as the frequency of pedestrians crossing at a given location. Behaviour is also an inherent part of the infrastructure risk factors, which are based on established crash modification factors (CMF). CMF capture road user behaviours change in response to infrastructure. For example, where drivers slow down in response to narrower road lanes.

This review confirmed that the Star Ratings are an appropriate road safety assessment methodology to meet the needs of the project aims. This method incorporates individual models for VRUs, and is applicable across all regions and road types (including urban road networks). However, Star Ratings provide static safety ratings. To allow for dynamic safety prediction, and a better representation of human behaviour, speed and flow variables from traffic simulation models will be incorporated.

For the socio-economic evaluation, the review identified several methodologies, all with their advantages and limitations. In Task 1.3, a more in-depth review into previous work will be carried out in terms of the theoretical framework for safety impacts on the socio-economics of the different VRUs and the different population groups. Different direct and indirect impacts of the safety externalities will be identified and the measures to quantify them. It is noted that this evaluation is initially considered as a post-hoc task to the safety and traffic outputs of the enhanced simulation models.

Every component of the PHOEBE framework relies on novel data applications, and utilisation of these data sources is a key part of the methodological approach. There are a number of successful experiences with using these data sources, enabling several important messages to be taken as regards the PHOEBE Framework:

- Artificial Neural Networks are very appropriate for short term traffic forecasting, whereas deep learning models can be successful for longer term forecasting
- Forecasting the change in road risk would require Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN) or other advanced probabilistic models
- Open platforms like OSM should be used for network identification, despite the heterogeneity of accuracy – given that their use is not costly, they should be promoted as a first line data source.

It is important to distinguish the data needs of the different PHOEBE components for the methodology.

The PHOEBE project aims to advance the state-of-the-art for each of its components in some way. But the true advance of the state-of-the-art is the integration of traffic simulation and road safety assessment which have traditionally been used in isolation of each other, and for different purposes. Achieving a methodological framework which can utilise these components and then using this to model mode shift and induced demand, and calculate socio-economic impacts requires linking the micro- (individual actions), meso- (groups of road users) and macro-levels (the network). How these levels connect will need to be carefully considered in Task 1.2 and described in Deliverable 1.2, the *Theoretical principles and methodological approach of the PHOEBE framework and selection of tools* (due in month 12).

Figure 5-1 Depiction of the multi-level analysis proposed by the PHOEBE framework

5.2 Implications on the technical development of the PHOEBE Framework

Several technical components will be developed as part of the PHOEBE project to support the PHOEBE Framework and demonstrate and facilitate its use.

The development of technological aspects relates directly to objectives 2, 3 and 4 of the PHOEBE project, which are:

- To develop a road safety module in the traffic simulation software which employs harmonised safety definitions
- To develop enhanced and integrated urban risk assessment models and tools for the application of the methodological framework through optimised model design, enhanced risk factors and dynamic inputs and outputs for urban safety assessments of challenging scenarios in future road traffic, and
- To embody social components into risk assessments so that changes in human behaviour, and mode and trip choices can be better understood for their consequences on safety.

The PHOEBE framework includes a number of intersecting components that need to be enhanced, upgraded and interlinked to achieve the scientific objectives of the methodological framework and result in a usable and efficient policy support tool. The results of the present state-of-the art highlighted the existing scientific and policy gaps. Moreover, they shed light on the strong inter-relationship between traffic simulation, road safety assessment and the role of human behaviour models to enhance the credibility of both; this 'triangle' lies at the core of PHOEBE methodology.

At the same time, the mode choice and modal shift models can be seen as the first step to be taken in order to simulate traffic and safety impacts, while socioeconomic impacts are the final outcomes to be estimated from the traffic and safety outputs of the framework. The new emerging data sources are a horizontal dimension that will enhance the predictive and explanatory power of all components of the framework.

Figure 6.1 below attempts to demonstrate these inter-relations, as they are clarified from the in-depth review of the SoA.

Figure 6.5-2 Conceptual design of PHOEBE methodological framework

3.5.3 Specific issues to be considered in the development of the PHOEBE technical aspects

The review identified a range of issues which would need to be closely considered during the technical developments of simulation models (particularly with regard to incorporating human behaviour models), road safety assessment and mode shift/induced demand modelling.

The review of the state of the art revealed that, while there is a strong relationship between surrogate safety measures, typically used in traffic simulation, and real crash data, typically available from crash records, there is lack of complete and holistic established mechanisms for simulating potential crashes.

iRAP risk assessment methodology and the resulting star ratings are a very well established and globally applicable approach, however the estimates are static. The risk assessment methods need to be further developed to account for the variability of speeds and flow. The new emerging data sources can play a key role in that.

Surrogate measures of safety are the standard way of assessing safety via traffic simulation. The FHWA Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM) mainly uses TTC and PET, and there are some studies with enhanced, angle-based conflict estimates. However the method does not have detailed trajectories, and has been only applied to vehicle-vehicle conflicts. The network safety estimation is based on the aggregation of the total numbers of conflicts.

Commercial traffic simulation tools, e.g. Aimsun, Vissim and SUMO, are designed in a way that vehicles always respect distances to other vehicles and cannot ever crash. This implies that available traffic simulation tools are designed to be 'safe by nature'. However, studies have shown that it is possible to

simulate crashes via these tools (e.g. by relaxing certain assumptions about the compliance and ‘obedience’ of vehicles and observing crashes as overlapping vehicle positions).

There are two types of models: the ‘operational level’ models, namely car following (CF) looking at longitudinal behaviours, and the ‘tactical’ level models, namely lane changing (LC) looking at lateral behaviours. Both existing models presented so far assume a perfect driver with perfect information. This means that they do not account for any driver distraction, excessive risk-taking, adverse weather, perception mistakes or biases. Therefore, there are concerns whether they indeed represent how drivers behave in the real world. For example, empirical studies have shown much smaller headways and gaps accepted than the typical thresholds used in simulation tools.

In terms of simulation theories and models, pedestrian simulation is moving from social force models to multi-agent models for more flexibility and less computational cost. Again, commercial packages like Aimsun and Vissim include agent-based pedestrian plug-ins, but assume an ideal behaviour of cars and pedestrians.

From the traffic simulation modelling perspective, in theory it is possible to introduce human behaviour, heterogeneity & choices in the driving / walking models, but the problem is their calibration and validation – it is expected that in most cases this is highly challenging due to lack of data.

The lack of data on VRUs behaviour is a key barrier to the introduction of human behaviour in simulation, and its validation. Research shows that human behaviour in terms of perception errors, visibility etc. is easier to account for in simulation, than violations and risk taking. Human factors such as distraction and fatigue show large distributions, and there are correlations of these behaviours with speed, headways etc.

There are a few recent promising examples of including human factors at the operational level of traffic simulation (CF) (Calvert et al., 2020), by means of using a ‘situation awareness’ and ‘task saturation’ framework, and its impacts on e.g. headways. Much of this work has been done within the SAFE-UP Horizon project. It could be an opportunity for PHOEBE to liaise with this project and exchange about these developments.

There is a different understanding of the meaning of ‘human behaviour’. As mentioned, in traffic simulation driving behaviour models are mostly kinematics-based, and human variations are also taken from a ‘parameter’ perspective – for instance, pedestrian simulation models that allow different heights of pedestrians. However, from the viewpoint of the discipline of human factors in road safety, human behaviour has a much broader and more complex analysis.

It is well known that there is a two-way relationship between human factors and traffic behaviour; one aspect is behavioural adaptation, in which drivers adjust to a certain road safety measure thereby not allowing its full expected effect to be observed. Another example is endogeneity, for example fatigued drivers maintaining longer headways because they are aware of their impairment, but fatigue may also be more likely at nighttime when there is less traffic and headways are longer. This “chicken and egg” problem makes it difficult to identify which is the dependent variable of the analysis, and specific modelling techniques are needed to account for this.

The two-way relationship between human factors and resulting traffic behaviour needs to be credibly represented in the dynamics of traffic simulation; this can be a very complex research task. There are several theories and models for human behaviour in traffic. In many cases, human factors are unobserved (related to perceptions, motivations, personality traits) and therefore are modelled as latent variables. In many cases, surveys are needed to measure these constructs; in other cases, they can be measured by means of other observable indicators – here too new data sources can play a role, as will be discussed later.

From the literature review, two ways seem more promising for PHOEBE to incorporate human behaviour in traffic simulation:

- i) **Choice models** seems a well-established, flexible and appropriate methodology to introduce human behaviour as a discrete input on a specific entry point of the traffic simulation model. For example, a pedestrians' choice to cross outside a crosswalk could be estimated as a probability.
- ii) **Driver profiling** is feasible to be introduced in the form of different types of drivers (such as normal, inattentive, aggressive) by changing certain simulation parameters for a proportion of drivers. For example, a time rate of distraction could be defined, and the behaviour of the driver changed accordingly.

A prioritisation of human risk factors is needed, to enable a feasible and meaningful computation of their dynamics in traffic simulation. A very important question is: which human factors can be addressed, and by what data? Although ideally one would want to include all the key risk factors, i.e. speeding, close-following, illegal overtaking, fatigue, distraction etc., it will be computationally unfeasible to do so, especially if different road user types are concerned, i.e. drivers, and pedestrians, and cyclists.

Regarding cyclists' simulation in particular, existing tools are very basic; e.g. Aimsun has a lane filtering module. However, new behavioural models are needed to model reliably the actual interactions in modern urban settings, e.g. with shared space conditions, e-bikes which are much faster etc.

Overall, there are larger variations of infrastructures, traffic, road user groups, and the resulting safety effects from their interaction within cities, compared to interurban areas – this requires a share of dynamic inputs in traffic simulations.

Both road assessment and traffic simulation need to sharpen their ability to capture behaviours of VRUs (pedestrians, cyclists, e-scooters) in a dynamic way, on the basis of new datasets and methods.

From the literature, the following ways seem promising for PHOEBE to equitably incorporate motorised and non-motorised road users in traffic simulation and safety assessment, particularly with regard to trajectory data from all road user types – not just cars – and integrate it within a simulation tool in order to identify potential conflicts between all users.

VRUs and micromobility also need to be included as distinct travel options into mode choice and modal shift models.

Mode choice and modal shift are the first steps to simulate traffic on a network. There are two types of modelling techniques: choice models, and Machine Learning models. An important recent development is the combined use of both techniques, for improved computation. There is a lot of experience in developing such models for urban areas, however sustainable modes (other than public transport), micromobility and automated mobility have not been included. Land use and traffic conditions will certainly affect mode choice, however their incorporation should be improved. Moreover, none of the existing models consider the availability of prior information which is largely available to road users, through telematics and social networks.

There are three methodological directions for the PHOEBE mode choice and modal shift models:

- a) Including micromobility, VRUs and their latent attributes via advanced choice models, enhanced with ML for improved computation.
- b) Calculate modal share with finer spatial resolution than the typical origin-destination level, through proper explanatory variables.
- c) Accordingly, consider “tour-models” instead of “trip-models”, taking into account that users will switch between different modes along a journey, on the basis of dynamic flow information through apps and social networks.

Methodological details of these models will be processed within PHOEBE Task 1.3, however it is important at this stage to establish their role and “entry points” into the overall methodological framework.

5.3 Implications on the design of end-user tools and knowledge products

The online stakeholder survey and focus group consultations captured the current gaps and needs from the perspective of transport managers and municipalities (the intended end users of the PHOEBE Framework). These are synthesised into a user needs statement to inform the design of the PHOEBE Framework's end-user tools and knowledge products.

The online stakeholder survey was used to understand the needs and gaps in current practice among the stakeholders involved in the PHOEBE use cases (Athens, Valencia, West Midlands), as well as a broader groups of transport managers reachable through the wide network of contacts of the project partners.

The survey participants indicated that the following scenarios need to be prioritised: i) implementation of regulatory measures to limit speeds; ii) introducing extensive network of bicycle lanes; iii) promotion of public transport modes; iv) introduction of new transport modes; v) implementing hierarchical schemes; vi) encouraging modal shift vii) speed calming measures and viii) expansion of cycling and walking infrastructure.

Regarding the overall professional needs relevant to PHOEBE project, areas that were identified as high priority for research were:

- 1) Traffic simulation enriched with infrastructure safety information, mode shift and induced demand, and human behavioural factors
- 2) Improved accuracy of traffic simulation, and
- 3) Road assessment enriched with traffic microsimulation information and AI/ML models.

When asked about the usefulness of a potential tool for everyday tasks, the survey participants placed a high priority on the major aspects planned under the PHOEBE project, namely traffic simulation enriched with infrastructure safety information, modal shift information, road assessment enhanced with AI/ML models. It is interesting to note that the respondents from the PHOEBE use case locations in Athens, Valencia and West Midlands revealed some variability among the needs and priorities, supporting the notion that the PHOEBE Framework needs to be able to be flexible enough to address different needs.

The focus group consultations drilled more deeply into the current uses and practices of road safety assessment and microscopic simulation on urban road networks, and the extent to which they inform decision making in urban road planning and management.

The results of the stakeholders survey and the focus groups are summarized in the form of a Needs Statement on three elements: i) strategic goals; ii) decision support and daily practice; and iii) methodological needs.

The focus groups' participants raised many questions and challenges that PHOEBE will encounter. The reality of cities and public authorities makes it challenging for them to adopt new ways of working even when there is the intention to. Thus, to avoid false expectations and ensure more effective outcomes, it is important that PHOEBE fully recognises its limitations, not as shortcomings, but as leverage as a key player in the road safety discussion, advocating for the necessary changes and new ways to address them. Alongside PHOEBE's pilots, continuing with an honest and open discussion with cities and other stakeholders is essential for that. The focus groups were an initial step in this process of acknowledging their needs and will continue throughout the project in many ways.

6 References

- 1 Abadi, A, Rajabioun, T & Ioannou, PA (2015), 'Traffic flow prediction for road transportation networks with limited traffic data,' IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, 16(2), pp. 653–662, doi:10.1109/TITS.2014.2337238.
- 2 Adavikottu, A., Velaga, N.R. and Mishra, S., 2023. Modelling the effect of aggressive driver behaviour on longitudinal performance measures during car-following. Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour, 92, pp.176-200.
- 3 af Wåhlberg, A (2008), 'Driver celeration behaviour and accidents - an analysis,' Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science, 9, pp. 383–403, doi:10.1080/14639220701596722.
- 4 af Wåhlberg, A (2012), 'Changes in driver celeration behaviour over time: Do drivers learn from collisions?' Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour, 15(5), pp. 471–479, doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2012.04.002.
- 5 Afghari, A. P., Haque, M. M., Washington, S., & Smyth, T. (2016). Bayesian latent class safety performance function for identifying motor vehicle crash black spots. Transportation research record, 2601(1), 90-98.
- 6 Afghari, A. P., Imani, A. F., Papadimitriou, E., van Gelder, P., & Hezaveh, A. M. (2021). Disentangling the effects of unobserved factors on seatbelt use choices in multi-occupant vehicles. Journal of choice modelling, 41, 100324.
- 7 Afghari, A. P., Ismail, K., Saunier, N., Sharma, A., & Miranda-Moreno, L. (2014, January). Pedestrian-cyclist interactions at bus stops along segregated bike paths: a case study of Montreal. In Proceedings of the 93rd Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board, Washington, DC.
- 8 Afghari, A. P., Papadimitriou, E., Li, X., Kaye, S. A., & Oviedo-Trespalacios, O. (2021). How much should a pedestrian be fined for intentionally blocking a fully automated vehicle? A random parameters beta hurdle model with heterogeneity in the variance of the beta distribution. Analytic methods in accident research, 32, 100186.
- 9 Afghari, A. P., Papadimitriou, E., Pilkington-Cheney, F., Filtness, A., Brijs, T., Brijs, K., ... & Rodrigues, L. (2022). Investigating the effects of sleepiness in truck drivers on their headway: An instrumental variable model with grouped random parameters and heterogeneity in their means. Analytic methods in accident research, 36, 100241.
- 10 Afghari, A. P., Washington, S., Haque, M. M., & Li, Z. (2018). A comprehensive joint econometric model of motor vehicle crashes arising from multiple sources of risk. Analytic methods in accident research, 18, 1-14.
- 11 Aghasi, N. H. M. (2019). Application of GIS for Urban Traffic Accidents: A Critical Review. *Journal of Geographic Information System*, 11(01), 82–96. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jgis.2019.111007>
- 12 Ahmed, H. U., Huang, Y., & Lu, P. (2021). A review of car-following models and modeling tools for human and autonomous-ready driving behaviours in micro-simulation. Smart Cities, 4(1), 314-335.
- 13 Aldred, R., Best, L., & Jones, P. (2019). Cyclists in shared bus lanes: could there be unrecognised impacts on bus journey times?. In Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers-Transport (Vol. 172, No. 3, pp. 135-151). Thomas Telford Ltd.
- 14 Alexandersson, S., & Johansson, E. (2013). Pedestrians in microscopic traffic simulation. Comparison between software Viswalk and Legion for Aimsun. Master's Thesis. Chalmers University of Technology.
- 15 Ali, M., & Richter, T. (2022). A Framework for Road Safety Assessment and Behavioural Change. SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4281920>
- 16 Ali, Y., Haque, M. M., Zheng, Z., & Afghari, A. P. (2022). A Bayesian correlated grouped random parameters duration model with heterogeneity in the means for understanding braking behaviour in a connected environment. Analytic methods in accident research, 35, 100221.
- 17 Allen, B., Shin, B., Cooper, P. (1978). Analysis of traffic conflicts and collisions. Transportation Research Record 667, 67–72.

- 18 Alsaleh, R., & Sayed, T. (2022). Do road users play Nash Equilibrium? A comparison between Nash and Logistic stochastic Equilibriums for multiagent modeling of road user interactions in shared spaces. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 205, 117710.
- 19 Alsaleh, R., & Sayed, T. (2022). Microscopic modeling of cyclists interactions with pedestrians in shared spaces: a Gaussian process inverse reinforcement learning approach. *Transportmetrica A: transport science*, 18(3), 828-854.
- 20 Al-Salih, W. Q., & Esztergar-Kiss, D. (2021). Effects of Individual Characteristics on Travel Behaviour: An Application of the Multinomial Logit Model on the Travellers Behaviour in Budapest City. 2021 7th International Conference on Models and Technologies for Intelligent Transportation Systems (MT-ITS), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MT-ITS49943.2021.9529295>
- 21 Amado, H., Ferreira, S., Tavares, J. P., Ribeiro, P., & Freitas, E. (2020). Pedestrian–vehicle interaction at unsignalized crosswalks: a systematic review. *Sustainability*, 12(7), 2805
- 22 Ambros, J., Turek, R., Brich, M., & Kubeček, J. (2019). Safety assessment of Czech motorways and national roads. *European Transport Research Review*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-018-0328-2>
- 23 Ameen, N., & Kamga, C. (2013). Forecast of Airport Ground Access Mode Choice with the Incremental Logit Model. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*, 2336(1), 97–104. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2336-12>
- 24 Antoniou, C. (2014). A stated-preference study of the willingness-to-pay to reduce traffic risk in urban vs. rural roads. *European Transport Research Review*, 6(1), 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12544-013-0103-3>
- 25 Appiah, J., King, F. A., Fontaine, M. D., & Cottrell, B. H. (2020). Left turn crash risk analysis: Development of a microsimulation modeling approach. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 144, 105591.
- 26 Asaithambi, G., Kanagaraj, V., & Toledo, T. (2016). Driving behaviours: Models and challenges for non-lane based mixed traffic. *Transportation in Developing Economies*, 2, 1-16.
- 27 Assi, K. J., Shafiullah, M., Nahiduzzaman, K. M., & Mansoor, U. (2019). Travel-To-School Mode Choice Modelling Employing Artificial Intelligence Techniques: A Comparative Study. *Sustainability*, 11(16), 4484. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164484>
- 28 Astarita, V., Caliendo, C., Giofrè, V. P., & Russo, I. (2020a). Surrogate safety measures from traffic simulation: Validation of safety indicators with intersection traffic crash data. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 6974.
- 29 Astarita, V., Festa, D. C., & Giofrè, V. P. (2020b). Microsimulation and the evaluation of safety levels in the presence of roadside obstacles. *Eur. Transp. Trasp. Eur.*, 77, 1-12.
- 30 Astarita, V., Festa, D. C., Giofrè, V. P., & Guido, G. (2019). Surrogate safety measures from traffic simulation models a comparison of different models for intersection safety evaluation. *Transportation research procedia*, 37, 219-226.
- 31 Astarita, V., Giofrè, V., Guido, G., & Vitale, A. (2011). Investigating road safety issues through a microsimulation model. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 20, 226-235.
- 32 Astarita, V., Guido, G., Vitale, A., & Giofrè, V. (2012). A new microsimulation model for the evaluation of traffic safety performances.
- 33 Atkinson, L. Z., & Cipriani, A. (2018). How to carry out a literature search for a systematic review: a practical guide. *BJPsych Advances*, 24(2), 74–82. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bja.2017.3>
- 34 Austroads. (2014). Australian National Risk Assessment Model. Austroads Ltd. http://data.vicroads.vic.gov.au/metadata/Austroads_AP-R451-1-Australian-National-Risk-Assessment-Model.pdf
- 35 Austroads. (2020). Road Cross-section Design for Road Stereotypes (including Network Safety Plans) and a Safe System. Austroads Ltd. www.austroads.com.au
- 36 Azam, M. S., Bhaskar, A., & Haque, M. M. (2022). Driving behaviour modelling in the context of heterogeneous traffic and poor lane discipline conditions: the state-of-the-art and beyond. *Transportmetrica A: transport science*, 18(3), 367-434.

- 37 Azevedo, C. L., Ciuffo, B., Cardoso, J. L., & Ben-Akiva, M. E. (2015). Dealing with uncertainty in detailed calibration of traffic simulation models for safety assessment. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 58, 395-412.
- 38 Bahmankhah, B., Macedo, E., Fernandes, P., & Coelho, M. C. (2022). Micro driving behaviour in different roundabout layouts: pollutant emissions, vehicular jerk, and traffic conflicts analysis. *Transportation research procedia*, 62, 501-508.
- 39 Bajic, M., Pour, SM, Skar, A, Pettinari, M, Levenberg, E & Alstrøm, TS (2021), 'Road roughness estimation using machine learning,' *CoRR*, abs/2107.01199.
- 40 Balać, M. ;, Vetrella, A. R. ;, Rothfeld, R. ;, & Schmid, B. (2019). ETH Library Demand estimation for aerial vehicles in urban settings. *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine*, 11(3), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000274798>
- 41 Barceló, J. (2010). *Fundamentals of traffic simulation* (Vol. 145, p. 439). New York: Springer.
- 42 Barff, R., Mackay, D., & Olshavsky, R. W. (1982). A Selective Review of Travel-Mode Choice Models. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 8(4), 370. <https://doi.org/10.1086/208877>
- 43 Baster, B., Duda, J., Maciol, A., & Rębiasz, B. (2013, October). Rule-based approach to human-like decision simulating in agent-based modeling and simulation. In *2013 17th International Conference on System Theory, Control and Computing (ICSTCC)* (pp. 739-743). IEEE.
- 44 Batty, P., Palacin, R., & González-Gil, A. (2015). Challenges and opportunities in developing urban modal shift. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 2(2), 109–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2014.12.001>
- 45 Baum, H., Höhnscheid, K.-J., & Gladbach, B. (2000). Economic evaluation of road traffic safety measures.
- 46 Bazzan, A. L., & Klügl, F. (2014). A review on agent-based technology for traffic and transportation. *The Knowledge Engineering Review*, 29(3), 375-403.
- 47 Bello, I, Salau, Onumanyi, AJ, Aibinu, AM, Onwuka, EN, Dukiya, JJ & Ohize, HO (2019), 'A survey of accelerometerbased techniques for road anomalies detection and characterization,' .
- 48 Ben-Akiva, M. E., & Lerman, S. R. (2006). *Discrete choice analysis: Theory and application to travel demand* (Vol. 9). The MIT Press.
- 49 Ben-Akiva, M., Mcfadden, D., Train, K., Walker, J., Bhat, C., Bierlaire, M., Bolduc, D., Boersch-Supan, A., Brownstone, D., Bunch, D. S., Daly, A., De Palma, A., Gopinath, D., Karlstrom, A., & Munizaga, M. A. (2002). Hybrid Choice Models: Progress and Challenges. *Marketing Letters*, 13(3), 163–175. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020254301302>
- 50 Benjamin Schneider. (2018, September 6). CityLab University: Induced Demand. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018-09-06/traffic-jam-blame-induced-demand>
- 51 Bevrani, K., & Chung, E. (2012). A safety adapted car following model for traffic safety studies. *Advances in Human Aspects of Road and Rail Transportation*, 550-559.
- 52 Bharti, S., Bandyopadhyaya, R., & Raju, N. K. (2022). Estimation of Willingness to Pay and Value of Statistical Life for Road Crash Fatality Reduction for Motorcyclists: A Case Study of Patna, India. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series A*, 103(4), 1315–1323. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40030-022-00680-y>
- 53 Bhat, C. R. (1998a). Analysis of travel mode and departure time choice for urban shopping trips. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 32(6), 361–371. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-2615\(98\)00004-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-2615(98)00004-6)
- 54 Bhat, C. R. (1998b). Accommodating flexible substitution patterns in multi-dimensional choice modeling: formulation and application to travel mode and departure time choice. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 32(7), 455–466. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-2615\(98\)00011-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-2615(98)00011-3)
- 55 Bic Byaruhanga, C., & Evdorides, H. (2021). A systematic review of road safety investment appraisal models. *Cogent Engineering*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2021.1993521>
- 56 Biljecki, F., & Ito, K. (2021). Street view imagery in urban analytics and GIS: A review. In *Landscape and Urban Planning* (Vol. 215). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2021.104217>
- 57 Boehm, M., Arnz, M., & Winter, J. (2021). The potential of high-speed rail freight in Europe: how is a modal shift from road to rail possible for low-density high value cargo? *European Transport Research Review*, 13(1), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-020-00453-3>

- 58 Boer, E. R. (1999). Car following from the driver's perspective. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 2(4), 201-206.
- 59 Bora, B., Landge, V., & Dalai, B. (2018). Socio-economic costing of road traffic accidents: evidence from Nagpur city, Maharashtra, India.
- 60 Brackstone, M., & McDonald, M. (1999). Car-following: a historical review. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 2(4), 181-196.
- 61 Brackstone, M., Sultan, B., & McDonald, M. (2002). Motorway driver behaviour: studies on car following. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 5(1), 31-46.
- 62 Broughton, J., Keigan, M., Yannis, G., Evgenikos, P., Chaziris, A., Papadimitriou, E., Bos, N. M., Hoeglinger, S., Pérez, K., Amoros, E., Holló, P., & Tecl, J. (2010). Estimation of the real number of road casualties in Europe. *Safety Science*, 48(3), 365–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2009.09.012>
- 63 Bršćic, D., F. Zanlungo, and T. Kanda. Density and Velocity Patterns During One Year of Pedestrian Tracking. *Transportation Research Procedia*, Vol. 2, 2014, pp. 77–86.
- 64 C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, C. K. H. (2021, August). How to drive a modal shift from private vehicles to public transport, walking and cycling. https://www.c40knowledgehub.org/s/article/How-to-drive-a-modal-shift-from-private-vehicle-use-to-public-transport-walking-and-cycling?language=en_US
- 65 Cafiso, S., D'Agostino, C., Kieć, M., & Bak, R. (2018). Safety assessment of passing relief lanes using microsimulation-based conflicts analysis. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 116, 94-102.
- 66 Caliendo, C., & Guida, M. (2012). Microsimulation approach for predicting crashes at unsignalized intersections using traffic conflicts. *Journal of transportation engineering*, 138(12), 1453-1467.
- 67 Calvert, S. C., Schakel, W. J., & van Lint, J. W. C. (2020). A generic multi-scale framework for microscopic traffic simulation part II–Anticipation Reliance as compensation mechanism for potential task overload. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 140, 42-63.
- 68 Cantarella, G. E., & de Luca, S. (2005). Multilayer feedforward networks for transportation mode choice analysis: An analysis and a comparison with random utility models. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 13(2), 121–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2005.04.002>
- 69 Cao, G, Michelini, J, Grigoriadis, K, Ebrahimi, B & Franchek, MA (2016), 'Cluster-based correlation of severe driving events with time and location,' *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 20(6), pp. 516–531, doi:10.1080/15472450.2016.1152891.
- 70 Cascetta, E. (2009). *Transportation Systems Analysis (Vol. 29)*. Springer US. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-75857-2>
- 71 Castro, C., Martínez, C., Tornay, F. J., Fernández, P. G., & Martos, F. J. (2005). Vehicle distance estimations in nighttime driving: a real-setting study. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 8(1), 31-45.
- 72 Castro, Y & Kim, YJ (2016), 'Data mining on road safety: factor assessment on vehicle accidents using classification models,' *International Journal of Crashworthiness*, 21(2), pp. 104–111, doi:10.1080/13588265.2015.1122278.
- 73 Cervero, R. (2003). Road Expansion, Urban Growth, and Induced Travel: A Path Analysis. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 69(2), 145–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944360308976303>
- 74 Chan, M., & Singhal, A. (2015). Emotion matters: Implications for distracted driving. *Safety science*, 72, 302-309.
- 75 Chan, TK, Chin, CS, Chen, H & Zhong, X (2019), 'A comprehensive review of driver behaviour analysis utilizing smartphones,' *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 21(10), pp. 4444–4475.
- 76 Chandler, R. E., Herman, R., & Montroll, E. W. (1958). Traffic dynamics: studies in car following. *Operations research*, 6(2), 165-184.
- 77 Chantith, C., Permpoonwiwat, C. K., & Fowles, R. (2021). Cost-Effectiveness of Road Safety Policy for Preventing and Reducing Road Traffic Fatalities in Thailand. *Thailand and The World Economy*, 39(2), 1–17. <https://so05.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/TER/article/view/251882>
- 78 Chen, C, Fan, X, Zheng, C, Xiao, L, Cheng, M & Wang, C (2018a), 'Sdcae: Stack denoising convolutional autoencoder model for accident risk prediction via traffic big data,' in 2018 Sixth

- International Conference on Advanced Cloud and Big Data (CBD), pp. 328–333, doi:10.1109/CBD.2018.00065.
- 79 Chen, M, Yu, X & Liu, Y (2018b), ‘Pcnn: Deep convolutional networks for short-term traffic congestion prediction,’ *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 19(11), pp. 3550–3559, doi:10.1109/TITS.2018.2835523.
- 80 Chen, X, Cai, X, Liang, J & Liu, Q (2018c), ‘Ensemble learning multiple lssvr with improved harmony search algorithm for short-term traffic flow forecasting,’ *IEEE Access*, 6, pp. 9347–9357, doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2805299.
- 81 Chraibi, M., Seyfried, A., & Schadschneider, A. (2010). Generalized centrifugal-force model for pedestrian dynamics. *Physical Review E*, 82(4), 046111.
- 82 Comendador, J., Monzón, A., & López-Lambas, M. E. (2014). A General Framework to Testing the Effect of Transport Policy Measures to Achieve a Modal Shift: A Sequential Hybrid Model. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 162, 243–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.12.205>
- 83 Comi, A., Polimeni, A., Crisalli, U., & Nuzzolo, A. (2021). A METHODOLOGY BASED ON FLOATING CAR DATA FOR THE ANALYSIS OF THE POTENTIAL RAIL-ROAD FREIGHT DEMAND. *International Journal of Transport Economics*, 48(3–4), 315–337. <https://doi.org/10.19272/202106704002>
- 84 Cooper, P. (1984). Experience with traffic conflicts in Canada with emphasis on post encroachment time techniques. *International Calibration Study of Traffic Conflicts*, NATA ASI Series F5, 75-96.
- 85 Costin, A., Adibfar, A., Hu, H., & Chen, S. S. (2018). Building Information Modeling (BIM) for transportation infrastructure – Literature review, applications, challenges, and recommendations. *Automation in Construction*, 94, 257–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2018.07.001>
- 86 Cunto, F. (2008). Assessing Safety Performance of Transportation Systems Using Microscopic Simulation. PhD dissertation. Department of Civil Engineering, University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.
- 87 D’Andrea, E, Ducange, P, Lazzerini, B & Marcelloni, F (2015), ‘Real-time detection of traffic from twitter stream analysis,’ *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 16(4), pp. 2269–2283, doi:10.1109/TITS.2015.2404431.
- 88 da Costa, J. O., Jacques, M. A. P., Pereira, P. A. A., Freitas, E. F., & Soares, F. E. C. (2018). Portuguese two-lane highways: Modelling crash frequencies for different temporal and spatial aggregation of crash data. *Transport*, 33(1), 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.3846/16484142.2015.1073619>
- 89 Daniels, S., Martensen, H., Schoeters, A., Van den Berghe, W., Papadimitriou, E., Kaiser, S., Aigner-Breuss, E., Soteropoulos, A., Wijnen, W., Weijermars, W., Carnis, L., Elvik, R., Martin Perez, O., & Ziakopoulos, A. (2019). A Systematic Cost-Benefit Analysis Of 29 Road Safety Measures.
- 90 Das, A., & Ahmed, M. M. (2022). Adjustment of key lane change parameters to develop microsimulation models for representative assessment of safety and operational impacts of adverse weather using SHRP2 naturalistic driving data. *Journal of safety research*, 81, 9-20.
- 91 De Brabander, B., Nuyts, E., & Vereeck, L. (2005). Road safety effects of roundabouts in Flanders. *Journal of Safety Research*, 36(3), 289–296. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2005.05.001>
- 92 de Zwart, R., Kamphuis, K., & Cleij, D. (2023). Driver behavioural adaptations to simulated automated vehicles, potential implications for traffic microsimulation. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 92, 255-265.
- 93 DeCorla-Souza, P., & Cohen, H. (1999). Estimating induced travel for evaluation of metropolitan highway expansion. *Transportation*, 26(3), 249–262. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005161903828>
- 94 Dell’Orco, M., & Ottomanelli, M. (2012). Simulation of Users Decision in Transport Mode Choice Using Neuro-Fuzzy Approach (pp. 44–53). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-31075-1_4
- 95 Dijkstra, J., & Timmermans, H. (2002). Towards a multi-agent model for visualizing simulated user behaviour to support the assessment of design performance. *Automation in construction*, 11(2), 135-145.
- 96 Domencich, T. A., & McFadden, D. (1975). URBAN TRAVEL DEMAND - A BEHAVIOURAL ANALYSIS.

- 97 Duan, P, Mao, G, Liang, W & Zhang, D (2019), 'A unified spatio-temporal model for short-term traffic flow prediction,' IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, 20(9), pp. 3212–3223, doi:10.1109/TITS.2018.2873137
- 98 Duranton, G., & Turner, M. A. (2011). The Fundamental Law of Road Congestion: Evidence from US Cities. *American Economic Review*, 101(6), 2616–2652. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.101.6.2616>
- 99 ECHA. (2008). Sozioökonomische analyse bei reach. In ECHA. <https://echa.europa.eu/de/support/socio-economic-analysis-in-reach>
- 100 Elawady, A., Abuzwidah, M., & Zeiada, W. (2022). The benefits of using connected vehicles system on traffic delay and safety at urban signalized intersections. In 2022 Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences (ASET) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- 101 Elliot, M., & Shaheen, S. (2016). Impacts of car2go on Vehicle Ownership, Modal Shift, Vehicle Miles Traveled, and Greenhouse Gas Emissions: An Analysis of Five North American Cities | Transportation Sustainability Research Center. <https://tsrc.berkeley.edu/publications/impacts-car2go-vehicle-ownership-modal-shift-vehicle-miles-traveled-and-greenhouse-gas>
- 102 El-Tantawy, S., Djavadian, S., Roorda, M. J., & Abdulhai, B. (2009). Safety evaluation of truck lane restriction strategies using microsimulation modeling. *Transportation research record*, 2099(1), 123-131.
- 103 Elvik, R. (2000). Which are the relevant costs and benefits of road safety measures designed for pedestrians and cyclists? In *Accident Analysis and Prevention* (Vol. 32). www.elsevier.com/locate/aap
- 104 Elvik, R. (2001). Cost-benefit analysis of road safety measures: applicability and controversies. In *Accident Analysis and Prevention* (Vol. 33). www.elsevier.com
- 105 Elvik, R. (2002). The importance of confounding in observational before-and-after studies of road safety measures. In *Accident Analysis and Prevention* (Vol. 34). www.elsevier.com/locate/aap
- 106 Essa, M., & Sayed, T. (2015). Transferability of calibrated microsimulation model parameters for safety assessment using simulated conflicts. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 84, 41-53.
- 107 Essa, M., & Sayed, T. (2020). Comparison between surrogate safety assessment model and real-time safety models in predicting field-measured conflicts at signalized intersections. *Transportation research record*, 2674(3), 100-112.
- 108 European Commission. (2018). Preparatory work for an EU road safety strategy 2020-2030 Final Report. https://visaozero2030.pt/wp-content/uploads/Preparatory_work_EU_road_safety_strategy_2020_2030_Final_Report.pdf
- 109 European Commission. (2023). Network Wide Road Safety Assessment Methodology and Implementation Handbook.
- 110 EuroRAP. (2021). Discussion paper on Technical Justification for Network-Wide Road Assessment, “black spot”, route safety and network-wide road assessment.
- 111 Faboya, O. T., Ryan, B., Figueredo, G. P., & Siebers, P.-O. (2020). Using agent-based modelling for investigating modal shift: The case of university travel. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 139, 106077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2019.106077>
- 112 Faboya, O. T., Siebers, P.-O., Ryan, B., & Figueredo, G. P. (2017). A Novel Modal Shift Modelling Framework for Transport Systems. <https://nottingham-repository.worktribe.com/index.php/output/1446140/a-novel-modal-shift-modelling-framework-for-transport-systems>
- 113 Fan, R., Yu, H., Liu, P., & Wang, W. (2013). Using VISSIM simulation model and Surrogate Safety Assessment Model for estimating field measured traffic conflicts at freeway merge areas. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 7(1), 68-77.
- 114 Fang, F., Yu, Y., Li, S., Zuo, Z., Liu, Y., Wan, B., & Luo, Z. (2021). Synthesizing location semantics from street view images to improve urban land-use classification. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 35(9), 1802–1825. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2020.1831515>
- 115 Farah, H., Yechiam, E., Bekhor, S., Toledo, T., & Polus, A. (2008). Association of risk proneness in overtaking maneuvers with impaired decision making. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 11(5), 313-323.

- 116 Fawcett, L., Thorpe, N., Matthews, J. & Kremer, K. (2017), 'A novel bayesian hierarchical model for road safety hotspot prediction,' *Accident Analysis Prevention*, 99, pp. 262–271, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2016.11.021>.
- 117 Feliciani, C., Crociani, L., Gorrini, A., Vizzari, G., Bandini, S., & Nishinari, K. (2017). A simulation model for non-signalized pedestrian crosswalks based on evidence from on field observation. *Intelligenza Artificiale*, 11(2), 117-138.
- 118 Fellendorf, M., & Vortisch, P. (2010). Microscopic traffic flow simulator VISSIM. *Fundamentals of traffic simulation*, 63-93.
- 119 Filtness, A. ; Thomas, P. ; Talbot, R. ; Quigley, C. ; & Papadimitriou, E. (2016). The application of systems approach for road safety policy making Deliverable 8.1 of the H2020 project SafetyCube.
- 120 Flötteröd, G., & Lämmel, G. (2015). Bidirectional pedestrian fundamental diagram. *Transportation research part B: methodological*, 71, 194-212.
- 121 Foerster, J. F. (1979). Mode choice decision process models: A comparison of compensatory and non-compensatory structures. *Transportation Research Part A: General*, 13(1), 17–28. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2607\(79\)90083-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-2607(79)90083-9)
- 122 Foody, G., See, L., Fritz, S., Mooney, P., Olteanu-Raimond, A.-M., Fonte, C. C., & Antoniou, V. (eds.). (2017). *Mapping and the Citizen Sensor*(G. Foody, L. See, S. Fritz, P. Mooney, A.-M. Olteanu-Raimond, & C. C. Fonte, Eds.). Ubiquity Press. <https://doi.org/10.5334/bbf>
- 123 Forbes, T. W. (1963). Human factor considerations in traffic flow theory. *Highway Research Record*, (15).
- 124 Forbes, T. W., & Simpson, M. E. (1968). Driver-and-Vehiele Response in Freeway Deceleration Waves. *Transportation science*, 2(1), 77-104.
- 125 Forbes, T. W., Zagorski, H. J., Holshouser, E. L., & Deterline, W. A. (1958). Measurement of driver reactions to tunnel conditions. In *Highway Research Board Proceedings* (Vol. 37).
- 126 Fritzsche, H. T. (1994). A model for traffic simulation. *Traffic Engineering Control*, 35(5), 317-21.
- 127 García-García, J. C., García-Ródenas, R., López-Gómez, J. A., & Martín-Baos, J. Á. (2022). A comparative study of machine learning, deep neural networks and random utility maximization models for travel mode choice modelling. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 62, 374–382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2022.02.047>
- 128 Gazis, D. C., Herman, R., & Rothery, R. W. (1961). Nonlinear follow-the-leader models of traffic flow. *Operations research*, 9(4), 545-567.
- 129 Gettman, D., & Head, L. (2003). Surrogate safety measures from traffic simulation models. *Transportation Research Record*, 1840(1), 104-115.
- 130 Gettman, D., Pu, L., Sayed, T. & Shelby, S. (2008). Surrogate Safety Assessment Model and Validation: Final Report. FHWA-HRT-08-051. Final Report: 2003-2007.322
- 131 Ghaffarpasand, O., Burke, M., Osei, L. K., Ursell, H., Chapman, S., & Pope, F. D. (2022). Vehicle Telematics for Safer, Cleaner and More Sustainable Urban Transport: A Review. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 14, Issue 24). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416386>
- 132 Ghanim, M. S., & Shaaban, K. (2019). A case study for surrogate safety assessment model in predicting real-life conflicts. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 44, 4225-4231.
- 133 Ghanim, M., Kharbeche, M., Hannun, J., Hannun, J., & Shamiyeh, K. (2020). Safety and operational performance of signalized roundabouts: a case study in Doha. *Procedia Computer Science*, 170, 427-433.
- 134 Gianfranco, F., Soddu, S & Fadda, P (2018), 'An accident prediction model for urban road networks,' *Journal of Transportation Safety & Security*, 10(4), pp. 387–405, doi:10.1080/19439962.2016.1268659.
- 135 Gipps, P. G. (1981). A behavioural car-following model for computer simulation. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 15(2), 105-111.
- 136 Gipps, P. G. (1986). A model for the structure of lane-changing decisions. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 20(5), 403-414.
- 137 Giuffrè, O., Granà, A., Tumminello, M. L., Giuffrè, T., & Trubia, S. (2019). Surrogate measures of safety at roundabouts in AIMSUN and VISSIM environment. In *Roundabouts as Safe and Modern Solutions*

- in Transport Networks and Systems: 15th Scientific and Technical Conference “Transport Systems. Theory and Practice 2018”, Katowice, Poland, September 17–19, 2018, Selected Papers (pp. 53-64). Springer International Publishing.
- 138 Giuffrè, O., Granà, A., Tumminello, M. L., Giuffrè, T., Trubia, S., Sferlazza, A., & Rencelj, M. (2018). Evaluation of roundabout safety performance through surrogate safety measures from microsimulation. *Journal of Advanced Transportation*, 2018, 1-14.
- 139 Giuffrè, T., Trubia, S., Canale, A., & Persaud, B. (2017). Using microsimulation to evaluate safety and operational implications of newer roundabout layouts for European Road networks. *Sustainability*, 9(11), 2084.
- 140 Goh, K. C., Currie, G., Sarvi, M., & Logan, D. (2014). Experimental microsimulation modeling of road safety impacts of bus priority. *Transportation research record*, 2402(1), 9-18.
- 141 Gomes, G., May, A., & Horowitz, R. (2004). Calibration of VISSIM for a Congested Freeway. California Partners for Advanced Transit and Highways (PATH).
- 142 Gonzalez, MC, Hidalgo, CA & Barabasi, AL (2008), ‘Understanding individual human mobility patterns,’ *nature*, 453(7196), pp. 779–782.
- 143 Gorham, R. (2009). Demystifying induced travel demand. https://city2030.org.ua/sites/default/files/documents/GIZ_SUTP_TD1_Demystifying-Induced-Travel-Demand_EN.pdf
- 144 Gregoriades, A. (2007). Towards a user-centred road safety management method based on road traffic simulation. In *2007 Winter Simulation Conference* (pp. 1905-1914). IEEE.
- 145 Gregoriades, A., Sutcliffe, A., Papageorgiou, G., & Louvieris, P. (2010). Human-centered safety analysis of prospective road designs. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics-Part A: Systems and Humans*, 40(2), 236-250.
- 146 Grier, R., Wickens, C., Kaber, D., Strayer, D., Boehm-Davis, D., Traflet, J. G., & St. John, M. (2008, September). The red-line of workload: Theory, research, and design. In *Proceedings of the human factors and ergonomics society annual meeting* (Vol. 52, No. 18, pp. 1204-1208). Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications.
- 147 Gross, F., Persaud, B. N., & Lyon, C. (2010). A guide to developing quality crash modification factors (No. FHWA-SA-10-032). United States. Federal Highway Administration. Office of Safety.
- 148 Gruden, C., Campisi, T., Canale, A., Tesoriere, G., & Sraml, M. (2019). A cross-study on video data gathering and microsimulation techniques to estimate pedestrian safety level in a confined space. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 603(4). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/603/4/042008>
- 149 Guido, G., Giofrè, V. P., Astarita, V., & Vitale, A. (2019, October). Using traffic microsimulation to evaluate potential crashes: Some results. In *2019 IEEE/ACM 23rd International Symposium on Distributed Simulation and Real Time Applications (DS-RT)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- 150 Guido, G., Saccomanno, F., Vitale, A., Astarita, V., & Festa, D. (2011). Comparing safety performance measures obtained from video capture data. *Journal of transportation engineering*, 137(7), 481-491.
- 151 Gutierrez-Osorio, C., & Pedraza, C. (2020). Modern data sources and techniques for analysis and forecast of road accidents: A review. In *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English Edition)* (Vol. 7, Issue 4, pp. 432–446). Chang’an University. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtte.2020.05.002>
- 152 Habtemichael, F. G., & de Picado Santos, L. (2014). Crash risk evaluation of aggressive driving on motorways: Microscopic traffic simulation approach. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 23, 101-112.
- 153 Habtemichael, F. G., & de Picado Santos, L. (2014). Crash risk evaluation of aggressive driving on motorways: Microscopic traffic simulation approach. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 23, 101-112.
- 154 Haddak, M. M., Lefèvre, M., & Havet, N. (2016). Willingness-to-pay for road safety improvement. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 87, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2016.01.010>
- 155 Hamdar, S. (2012). Driver behaviour modeling. In: Eskandarian, A. (Ed.), *Handbook of Intelligent Vehicles*. Springer, pp. 537–558.

- 156 Hamdar, S. H., & Mahmassani, H. S. (2008). From existing accident-free car-following models to colliding vehicles: exploration and assessment. *Transportation research record*, 2088(1), 45-56.
- 157 Hamdar, S. H., Mahmassani, H. S., & Treiber, M. (2015). From behavioural psychology to acceleration modeling: Calibration, validation, and exploration of drivers' cognitive and safety parameters in a risk-taking environment. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 78, 32-53.
- 158 Hamdar, S. H., Treiber, M., Mahmassani, H. S., & Kesting, A. (2008). Modeling driver behaviour as sequential risk-taking task. *Transportation research record*, 2088(1), 208-217.
- 159 Hansen, J. H., Busso, C., Zheng, Y., & Sathyanarayana, A. (2017). Driver modeling for detection and assessment of driver distraction: Examples from the UTDive test bed. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 34(4), 130-142.
- 160 Harwood, D.; Bauer, K.M.; Gilmore, D.K.; Souleyrette, R.; Hans, Z.N. (2010). Validation of U.S. Road assessment program star rating protocol: Application to safety management of U.S. roads. *Transportation Research Record*, 2147, pp. 33-41.
- 161 Hashmienejad, SHA & Hasheminejad, SMH (2017), 'Traffic accident severity prediction using a novel multi-objective genetic algorithm,' *International Journal of Crashworthiness*, 22(4), pp. 425-440, doi:10.1080/13588265.2016.1275431.
- 162 Hayman, T. (2020). How to model cyclists in Aimsun Next. Technical note. URL: <https://www.aimsun.com/technical-notes/how-to-model-cyclists-in-aimsun-next/>
- 163 Hayward, J. (1971). Near misses as a measure of safety at urban intersections. Dissertation, The Pennsylvania State University.
- 164 Hegeman, G., Tapani, A., & Hoogendoorn, S. (2009). Overtaking assistant assessment using traffic simulation. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 17(6), 617-630.
- 165 Hellmich, S. N. (2017). What is Socioeconomics? An Overview of Theories, Methods, and Themes in the Field. *Forum for Social Economics*, 46(1), 3-25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07360932.2014.999696>
- 166 Helly, W. (1959). Simulation of bottlenecks in single-lane traffic flow. In *Proceedings of the Symposium on Theory of Traffic Flow*
- 167 Hensher, D. A. ; & Button, K. J. ; (2008). *Handbook of transport modelling: Vol. Volume 1* (D. A. Hensher & K. J. Button, Eds.; Second edition). Emerald. <https://doi.org/10.1108/9780857245670>
- 168 Hensher, D. A., & Button, K. J. (Eds.). (2007). *Handbook of Transport Modelling (Vol. 1)*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/9780857245670>
- 169 Hensher, D. A., & Greene, W. H. (2003). The Mixed Logit model: The state of practice. *Transportation*, 30(2), 133-176. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022558715350>
- 170 Herman, R. (1959). Car-following and steady state flow. In *Theory of Traffic Flow Symposium Proceedings* (pp. 1-13).
- 171 Hillel, T., Bierlaire, M., Elshafie, M. Z. E. B., & Jin, Y. (2021). A systematic review of machine learning classification methodologies for modelling passenger mode choice. *Journal of Choice Modelling*, 38, 100221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocm.2020.100221>
- 172 Holló, P., Eksler, V., & Zukowska, J. (2010). Road safety performance indicators and their explanatory value: A critical view based on the experience of Central European countries. *Safety Science*, 48(9), 1142-1150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2010.03.002>
- 173 Holroyd, S. (2021). SLAIN Project - Final Report.
- 174 Hoogendoorn, R. G., Hoogendoorn, S. P., Brookhuis, K. A., & Daamen, W. (2011). Adaptation longitudinal driving behaviour, mental workload, and psycho-spacing models in fog. *Transportation research record*, 2249(1), 20-28.
- 175 Hoogendoorn, S. P., Ossen, S., & Schreuder, M. (2006). Empirics of multianticipative car-following behaviour. *Transportation Research Record*, 1965(1), 112-120.
- 176 Horowitz, J. L., Bolduc, D., Divakar, S., Geweke, J., Gonul, F., Hajivassiliou, V., Koppelman, F. S., Keane, M., Matzkin, R., Rossi, P., & Ruud, P. (1994). Advances in random utility models report of the workshop on advances in random utility models duke invitational symposium on choice modeling behaviour. *Marketing Letters*, 5(4), 311-322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00999207>
- 177 Horowitz, J. L., Koppelman, F. S., & Lerman, S. R. (1986). A SELF-INSTRUCTING COURSE IN DISAGGREGATE MODE CHOICE MODELING. FINAL REPORT.

- 178 Hu, L., Ou, J., Huang, J., Wang, F., Wang, Y., Ren, B., ... & Zhou, L. (2022). Safety evaluation of pedestrian-vehicle interaction at signalized intersections in Changsha, China. *Journal of Transportation Safety & Security*, 14(10), 1750-1775.
- 179 Huang, F., Liu, P., Yu, H., & Wang, W. (2013). Identifying if VISSIM simulation model and SSAM provide reasonable estimates for field measured traffic conflicts at signalized intersections. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 50, 1014--1024. doi:10.1016/j.aap.2012.08.018
- 180 Hultkrantz, L., Lindberg, G., & Andersson, C. (2006). The value of improved road safety. *Journal of Risk and Uncertainty*, 32(2), 151–170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11166-006-8291-z>
- 181 Hupfer, C. (1997). Deceleration to safety time (DST)-a useful figure to evaluate traffic safety. In *ICTCT Conference Proceedings of Seminar (Vol. 3, pp. 5-7)*.
- 182 Hussein, M., & Sayed, T. (2017). A bi-directional agent-based pedestrian microscopic model. *Transportmetrica A: Transport Science*, 13(4), 326-355.
- 183 Hydén, C. (1987). The development of a method for traffic safety evaluation: The Swedish traffic conflicts technique. Lund University, Lund, Sweden, Department of Traffic Planning and Engineering.
- 184 Hymel, K. M., Small, K. A., & van Dender, K. (2010). Induced demand and rebound effects in road transport. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 44(10), 1220–1241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trb.2010.02.007>
- 185 Id, P. M., Contreras, D., & Nica Moreno, M. (2020). Safe mobility, socioeconomic inequalities, and aging: A 12-year multilevel interrupted time-series analysis of road traffic death rates in a Latin American country. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224545>
- 186 Ilahi, A., Balac, M., Li, A., & Axhausen, Kay. W. (2019). The first agent-based model of greater Jakarta integrated with a mode-choice model. *Procedia Computer Science*, 151, 272–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.04.039>
- 187 Imprialou, M & Quddus, M (2019), 'Crash data quality for road safety research: Current state and future directions,' *Accident Analysis Prevention*, 130, pp. 84–90, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2017.02.022>, road Safety Data Considerations.
- 188 International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP), 2009. Star Rating Roads for Safety: The iRAP Methodology. iRAP504.04. Site: www.irap.org
- 189 iRAP (2022), A world free of high-risk roads. HOW SAFE ARE THE WORLD'S ROADS? WHERE ARE WE NOW?
- 190 iRAP. (2014a). iRAP Methodology Fact Sheet # 6 Star Rating Score equations Star Rating Scores. <https://irap.org/methodology/>
- 191 iRAP. (2014b). iRAP Methodology Fact Sheet # 6 Star Rating Score equations Star Rating Scores. <https://irap.org/methodology/>
- 192 iRAP. (2014c). IRAP Methodology Factsheet #10 - Casualty estimation and calibration. <http://irap.org/about-irap-3/research-and-technical-papers?download=47:vehicle-speeds-and-the-irap-protocols>.
- 193 iRAP. (2022). *Process for aiRAP attribute accreditation*. <https://irap.org/project/ai-rap/>
- 194 iRAP. (2022a). CycleRAP - Methodology Factsheet. www.irap.org/cyclerap
- 195 iRAP. (2022b). CycleRAP - User guide. www.irap.org/cyclerap
- 196 Iryo-Asano, M. & Alhajyaseen, W.K.M. (2017). Modeling pedestrian crossing speed profiles considering speed change behaviour for the safety assessment of signalized intersections. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* 108, 332–342
- 197 Isobe, M., Adachi, T., & Nagatani, T. (2004). Experiment and simulation of pedestrian counter flow. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 336(3-4), 638-650.
- 198 Jabbar, R, Shinoy, M, Kharbeche, M, Al-Khalifa, K, Krichen, M & Barkaoui, K (2020), 'Urban traffic monitoring and modeling system: An iot solution for enhancing road safety,' *CoRR*, abs/2003.07672.
- 199 Jacobsen, P. (1997, May 14). 'Liquid' vs. 'Gas' Models for Traffic.
- 200 Jamal, A., Zahid, M., Tauhidur Rahman, M., Al-Ahmadi, H. M., Almoshaogeh, M., Farooq, D., & Ahmad, M. (2021). Injury severity prediction of traffic crashes with ensemble machine learning techniques: a comparative study. *International Journal of Injury Control and Safety Promotion*, 28(4), 408–427. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17457300.2021.1928233>

- 201 Jamroz, K., Romanowska, A., & Budzyński, M. (2018). ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT ON ROAD SAFETY BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF BALTIC SEA REGION COUNTRIES.
- 202 Jamson, S., Chorlton, K., & Carsten, O. (2012). Could intelligent speed adaptation make overtaking unsafe?. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 48, 29-36.
- 203 Jasti, V. K., & Higgs, C. F. (2006). A lattice-based cellular automata modeling approach for granular flow lubrication. *Journal of Tribology*, Volume 128, Issue 2. April 2006.
- 204 Jeong, E., & Oh, C. (2017). Evaluating the effectiveness of active vehicle safety systems. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 100, 85-96.
- 205 Ji, A., & Levinson, D. (2020). A review of game theory models of lane changing. *Transportmetrica A: transport science*, 16(3), 1628-1647.
- 206 Jian, L. U., & Ying-shuai, L. I. (2017). Review and outlook of modeling of lane changing behaviour. *Journal of Transportation Systems Engineering and Information Technology*, 17(4), 48.
- 207 Jiang, R., Jia, B., & Wu, Q. S. (2004). Stochastic multi-value cellular automata models for bicycle flow. *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and General*, 37(6), 2063.
- 208 Jin S, Qu X, Xu C, et al. (2015). An improved multi-value cellular automata model for heterogeneous bicycle traffic flow. *Phys Lett A*; 379: 2409–2416
- 209 Jo, Y & Ryu, S (2015), 'Pothole detection system using a black-box camera,' *Sensors*, 15(11), pp. 29316–29331, doi:10.3390/s151129316.
- 210 Jo, Y., Jang, J., Park, S., & Oh, C. (2021). Connected vehicle-based road safety information system (CROSS): Framework and evaluation. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 151, 105972.
- 211 Johansson, A. F. (2009). *Data-driven modeling of pedestrian crowds*. Dresden: Technische Universität Dresden.
- 212 Johansson, P.-O. (2001). Is there a meaningful definition of the value of a statistical life? *Journal of Health Economics*, 20(1), 131–139. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-6296\(00\)00073-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-6296(00)00073-4)
- 213 Kaber, D. B., Liang, Y., Zhang, Y., Rogers, M. L., & Gangakhedkar, S. (2012). Driver performance effects of simultaneous visual and cognitive distraction and adaptation behaviour. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 15(5), 491-501.
- 214 Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (2013). Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. In *Handbook of the fundamentals of financial decision making: Part I* (pp. 99-127).
- 215 Kalatian, A., & Farooq, B. (2021). Decoding pedestrian and automated vehicle interactions using immersive virtual reality and interpretable deep learning. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 124, 102962.
- 216 Kalliga, V. (2021). *Who Does New Trips and Why?-An Analysis Towards the Modelling of Induced Demand* [Master thesis]. Technical University of Munich.
- 217 Kamakura, W., Manski, C. F., & McFadden, D. (1982). Structural Analysis of Discrete Data with Econometric Applications. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 19(4), 614. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151745>
- 218 Kanuganti, S., Agarwala, R., Dutta, B., Bhanegaonkar, P. N., Singh, A. P., & Sarkar, A. K. (2017). Road safety analysis using multi criteria approach: A case study in India. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 25, 4649–4661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.299>
- 219 Kany, M. S., Mathiesen, B. V., Skov, I. R., Korberg, A. D., Thellufsen, J. Z., Lund, H., Sorknæs, P., & Chang, M. (2022). Energy efficient decarbonisation strategy for the Danish transport sector by 2045. *Smart Energy*, 5, 100063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segy.2022.100063>
- 220 Kaparias, I., Liu, P., Tsakarestos, A., Eden, N., Schmitz, P., Hoadley, S., & Hauptmann, S. (2020). Predictive road safety impact assessment of traffic management policies and measures. *Case studies on transport policy*, 8(2), 508-516.
- 221 Karimi, Y., Hagh Kashani, M., Akbari, M., & Mahdipour, E. (2021). Leveraging big data in smart cities: A systematic review. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, 33(21). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6379>
- 222 Karlaftis, M. G. (2004). Predicting Mode Choice through Multivariate Recursive Partitioning. *Journal of Transportation Engineering*, 130(2), 245–250. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-947X\(2004\)130:2\(245\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-947X(2004)130:2(245))

- 223 Katrakazas, C., Quddus, M., & Chen, W. H. (2017). A simulation study of predicting real-time conflict-prone traffic conditions. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 19(10), 3196-3207.
- 224 Kazemzadeh, K., & Bansal, P. (2021). Electric bike level-of-service: towards the integration of hindrance-based and microsimulation approaches. Available at SSRN.
- 225 Kazemzadeh, K., & Sprei, F. (2022). Towards an electric scooter level of service: A review and framework. *Travel behaviour and society*, 29, 149-164.
- 226 Keane, M. P. (1992). A Note on Identification in the Multinomial Probit Model. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 10(2), 193. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1391677>
- 227 Khan, G., Santiago-Chaparro, K. R., Chiturri, M., & Noyce, D. A. (2010). Development of data collection and integration framework for road inventory data. *Transportation Research Record*, 2160, 29–39. <https://doi.org/10.3141/2160-04>
- 228 Khattak, Z. H., Miller, J. S., & Ohlms, P. (2021). Ride-hailing and taxi versus walking: Long term forecasts and implications from large-scale behavioural data. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 22, 101121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2021.101121>
- 229 Khelfa, B., Ba, I., & Tordeux, A. (2023). Predicting highway lane-changing maneuvers: A benchmark analysis of machine and ensemble learning algorithms. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 128471.
- 230 Knowles, J., Adams, S., Cuerden, R., Savill, T., Reid, S., & Tight, M. (2009). *Collisions involving pedal cyclists on Britain's roads: establishing the causes*. https://trl.co.uk/uploads/trl/documents/PPR445_new.pdf
- 231 Kodupuganti, S. R., & Pulugurtha, S. S. (2023). Are Facilities to Support Alternative Modes Effective in Reducing Congestion?: Modeling the Effect of Heterogeneous Traffic Conditions on Vehicle Delay at Intersections. *Multimodal Transportation*, 2(1), 100050.
- 232 Koenig, J. G. (1980). Indicators of urban accessibility: Theory and application. *Transportation*, 9(2), 145–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00167128>
- 233 Koopmann, B., Puch, S., Ehmen, G., & Fränzle, M. (2022). Cooperative maneuvers of highly automated vehicles at urban intersections: a game-theoretic approach. arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.01633.
- 234 Kouskoulis, G., & Antoniou, C. (2017). Systematic review of pedestrian simulation models with a focus on emergency situations. *Transportation Research Record*, 2604(1), 111-119.
- 235 Kouskoulis, G., Spyropoulou, I., & Antoniou, C. (2018). Pedestrian simulation: Theoretical models vs. data driven techniques. *International journal of transportation science and technology*, 7(4), 241-253.
- 236 Kronprasert, N., Kuwiboon, P., & Wichitphongsa, W. (2020). Safety and operational analysis for median U-turn intersections in Thailand. *GEOMATE Journal*, 18(68), 156-163.
- 237 Kumeda, B, Zhang, F, Zhou, F, Hussain, S, Almasri, A & Assefa, M (2019), 'Classification of road traffic accident data using machine learning algorithms,' in 2019 IEEE 11th International Conference on Communication Software and Networks (ICCSN), pp. 682–687, doi:10.1109/ICCSN.2019.8905362.
- 238 Kutela, B., Das, S., & Dadashova, B. (2022). Mining patterns of autonomous vehicle crashes involving vulnerable road users to understand the associated factors. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 165, 106473.
- 239 la Torre, F., Meocci, M., Domenichini, L., Branzi, V., Tanzi, N., & Paliotto, A. (2019). Development of an accident prediction model for Italian freeways. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 124, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2018.12.023>
- 240 Latinopoulos, C., Patrier, A., & Sivakumar, A. (2021). Planning for e-scooter use in metropolitan cities: A case study for Paris. *Transportation research part D: transport and environment*, 100, 103037.
- 241 Lareshyn, A., Svensson, Å., & Hydén, C. (2010). Evaluation of traffic safety, based on micro-level behavioural data: Theoretical framework and first implementation. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 42(6), 1637–1646. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2010.03.021>
- 242 Laurinavičius, A., Juknevičiūtė-Žilinskienė, L., Ratkevičiūtė, K., Lingytė, I., Čygaitė, L., Grigonis, V., Ušpalytė-Vitkūnienė, R., Antov, D., Metsvahi, T., Toth-Szabo, Z., & Várhelyi, A. (2012). POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR MANAGING ROAD SAFETY ON EU-ROADS. *TRANSPORT*, 27(4), 397–404. <https://doi.org/10.3846/16484142.2012.751934>

- 243 Laval, J. A., & Leclercq, L. (2010). A mechanism to describe the formation and propagation of stop-and-go waves in congested freeway traffic. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 368(1928), 4519-4541.
- 244 Lawson, S. (2011). Crash rate–Star Rating comparisons. Review of available evidence. Working Paper 504.2, EuroRAP, Brussels.
- 245 Lee, B. H. Y., & Waddell, P. (2010). Residential mobility and location choice: a nested logit model with sampling of alternatives. *Transportation*, 37(4), 587–601. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-010-9270-4>
- 246 Lee, C., So, J., & Ma, J. (2018). Evaluation of countermeasures for red light running by traffic simulator–based surrogate safety measures. *Traffic injury prevention*, 19(1), 1-8.
- 247 Lee, D. B., Klein, L. A., & Camus, G. (1999). Induced Traffic and Induced Demand. <https://doi.org/10.3141/1659-09>, 1659, 68–75. <https://doi.org/10.3141/1659-09>
- 248 Leonardi, S., & Distefano, N. (2023). Turbo-Roundabouts as an Instrument for Improving the Efficiency and Safety in Urban Area: An Italian Case Study. *Sustainability*, 15(4), 3223.
- 249 Levi, S., Wolf, I., Flachsland, C., Koch, N., Koller, F., & Edmondson, D. (2021). Klimaschutz und Verkehr: Zielerreichung nur mit unbequemen Maßnahmen möglich. *Ariadne-Analyse*. <https://elib.dlr.de/147088/>
- 250 Levitate (2021). Societal Level Impacts of Connected and Automated Vehicles. Horizon 2020.
- 251 Li, L., Li, Y., & Ni, D. (2021). Incorporating human factors into LCM using fuzzy TCI model. *Transportmetrica B: Transport Dynamics*, 9(1), 198-218.
- 252 Li, S., Xiang, Q., Ma, Y., Gu, X., & Li, H. (2016). Crash risk prediction modeling based on the traffic conflict technique and a microscopic simulation for freeway interchange merging areas. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 13(11), 1157.
- 253 Li, X., & Sun, J. Q. (2019). Turning-lane and signal optimization at intersections with multiple objectives. *Engineering Optimization*, 51(3), 484-502.
- 254 Li, X., Zhang, S., Wu, Y., Wang, Y., & Wang, W. (2021). Exploring Influencing Factors of Intercity Mode Choice from View of Entire Travel Chain. *Journal of Advanced Transportation*, 2021, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9454873>
- 255 Lineberger, R., Hussain, A., Mehra, S., & Pankratz, D. (2018, January 18). Elevating the future of mobility Passenger drones and flying cars. Deloitte.
- 256 Litman, T. (2017). Generated traffic and induced travel. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Todd-Litman-2/publication/235360397_Generated_Traffic_and_Induced_Travel_Implications_for_Transport_Planning/links/5a69f90d4585154d15465728/Generated-Traffic-and-Induced-Travel-Implications-for-Transport-Planning.pdf
- 257 Liu, M., Zeng, W., Chen, P., & Wu, X. (2017). A microscopic simulation model for pedestrian-pedestrian and pedestrian-vehicle interactions at crosswalks. *PLoS one*, 12(7), e0180992.
- 258 Liu, Q., & Garber, N. J. (2007). Identifying the impact of truck-lane restriction strategies on traffic flow and safety using simulation (No. UVACTS-14-5-103). University of Virginia. Center for Transportation Studies.
- 259 Liu, R., da Silva, J. C., & da Maia Seco, A. J. (2000, July). A bi-modal microsimulation tool for the assessment of pedestrian delays and traffic management. In *The Proceedings of the 9th International Association of Travel Behaviour Research Conference*, Gold Coast, Australia.
- 260 Liu, Y., Dion, F., & Biswas, S. (2006). Safety assessment of information delay on performance of intelligent vehicle control system. *Transportation research record*, 1944(1), 16-25.
- 261 Lorenzo Varela, J. M., Börjesson, M., & Daly, A. (2018). Public transport: One mode or several? *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 113, 137–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2018.03.018>
- 262 Lownes, N. E., & Machemehl, R. B. (2006). Sensitivity of simulated capacity to modification of VISSIM driver behaviour parameters. *Transportation Research Record*, 1988(1), 102-110.
- 263 Lu, L., Ren, G., Wang, W., Chan, C. Y., & Wang, J. (2016). A cellular automaton simulation model for pedestrian and vehicle interaction behaviours at unsignalized mid-block crosswalks. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 95, 425-437.

- 264 Lubis, H. al-R., Pantas, V. B., & Farda, M. (2019). Demand Forecast of Jakarta-Surabaya High Speed Rail based on Stated Preference Method. *International Journal of Technology*, 10(2), 405. <https://doi.org/10.14716/ijtech.v10i2.2442>
- 265 Lucchesi, S. T., E Silva, J. de A., Larranaga, A. M., Zechin, D., & Cybis, H. B. B. (2023). Machine Learning and Image Recognition Technologies to Identify Built Environment Barriers and Incentives to Walk. In *Transportation Research Record* (Vol. 2677, Issue 1, pp. 14–24). SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981221097965>
- 266 Luderer, G., Günther, C., Sörgel, D., Kost, C., Benke, F., Auer, C., Koller, F., Herbst, A., Reder, K., Böttger, D., Ueckert, F., Pfluger, B., Wrede, D., Strefler, J., Merfort, A., Rauner, S., Siala, K., & Schlichenmaier, S. (2021). Deutschland auf dem Weg zur Klimaneutralität 2045 - Szenarien und Pfade im Modellvergleich (Zusammenfassung). Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research. <https://doi.org/Gunnar>
- 267 Lukasik, D., Hale, D., Ma, J., Shibley, P., Malone, T., Chandler, A., Cleary, C., Matout, N., & Adebisi, A. (2020). *Enhancing Active Transportation and Demand Management (ATDM) with Advanced and Emerging Technologies and Data Sources*. <https://rosap.ntl.bts.gov/view/dot/49721>
- 268 Lundgren, J., & Tapani, A. (2006). Evaluation of safety effects of driver assistance systems through traffic simulation. *Transportation research record*, 1953(1), 81-88.
- 269 Lynam, D. (2012). Development of Risk Models for the Road Assessment Programme. www.irap.org.
- 270 Mahmud, S. S., Ferreira, L., Hoque, M. S., & Tavassoli, A. (2019). Micro-simulation modelling for traffic safety: A review and potential application to heterogeneous traffic environment. *IATSS research*, 43(1), 27-36.
- 271 Mak, K. K., Sicking, D. L., & Zimmerman, K. (1998). Roadside safety analysis program: A cost-effectiveness analysis procedure. *Transportation research record*, 1647(1), 67-74.
- 272 Mannering, FL, Shankar, V & Bhat, CR (2016), 'Unobserved heterogeneity and the statistical analysis of highway accident data,' *Analytic Methods in Accident Research*, 11, pp. 1–16, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amar.2016.04.001>.
- 273 Martensen, H., Diependaele, K., Daniels, S., Van den Berghe, W., Papadimitriou, E., Yannis, G., Van Schagen, I., Weijermars, W., Wijnen, W., Filtness, A., Talbot, R., Thomas, P., Machata, K., Aigner Breuss, E., Kaiser, S., Hermitte, T., Thomson, R., & Elvik, R. (2019). The European road safety decision support system on risks and measures. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 125, 344–351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AAP.2018.08.005>
- 274 Maśniak, D. (2007). SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC COSTS OF ROAD ACCIDENTS IN EUROPE.
- 275 Matarazzo, TJ, Kondor, D, Milardo, S, Eshkevari, SS, Aanti, P, Pakzad, SN, Buehler, MJ & Ratti, C (2022), 'Crowdsourcing bridge dynamic monitoring with smartphone vehicle trips,' *Communications Engineering*, p. 29, doi:10.1038/s44172-022-00025-4.
- 276 Mattas, K., Botzoris, G., & Papadopoulos, B. (2021). Safety aware fuzzy longitudinal controller for automated vehicles. *Journal of traffic and transportation engineering (English edition)*, 8(4), 568-581.
- 277 Mattas, K., Makridis, M., Botzoris, G., Ciuffo, B., & Papadopoulos, B. (2019). Fuzzy surrogate safety metrics. In 2019 6th International Conference on Models and Technologies for Intelligent Transportation Systems (MT-ITS) (pp. 1-11). IEEE.
- 278 McCarthy, L., Delbosc, A., Currie, G., & Molloy, A. (2017). Factors influencing travel mode choice among families with young children (aged 0–4): a review of the literature. *Transport Reviews*, 37(6), 767–781. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2017.1354942>
- 279 McFadden, D. (1974). Conditional logit analysis of qualitative choice behaviour. *Frontiers in Econometrics*.
- 280 McFadden, D. (1987). Regression-based specification tests for the multinomial logit model. *Journal of Econometrics*, 34(1–2), 63–82. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076\(87\)90067-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076(87)90067-4)
- 281 McKenna, F. P., Horswill, M. S., & Alexander, J. L. (2006). Does anticipation training affect drivers' risk taking?. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied*, 12(1), 1.
- 282 Mclean, R. (2021). Simulation Modeling of Calgary's E-Scooter System (Master's thesis, Science).

- 283 Mclean, R., Williamson, C., & Kattan, L. (2021, November). Simulation Modeling of Urban E-Scooter Mobility. In 2021 29th International Symposium on Modeling, Analysis, and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems (MASCOTS) (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
- 284 Mednis, A, Elsts, A & Selavo, L (2012), 'Embedded solution for road condition monitoring using vehicular sensor networks,' pp. 1 –5, doi:10.1109/ICAICT.2012.6398502.
- 285 Mehta, K., Mehran, B., & Hellinga, B. (2019). A methodology to estimate the number of unsafe vehicle-cyclist passing events on urban arterials. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 124, 92-103.
- 286 Michaels, J., Chaumillon, R., Nguyen-Tri, D., Watanabe, D., Hirsch, P., Bellavance, F., ... & Faubert, J. (2017). Driving simulator scenarios and measures to faithfully evaluate risky driving behaviour: A comparative study of different driver age groups. *PloS one*, 12(10), e0185909.
- 287 Minderhoud, M. & Bovy, P. (2001). Extended time-to-collision measures for road traffic safety assessment. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 33 (1), 89–97.
- 288 Miqdady, T., Oña López, R. D., & Oña López, J. D. (2021). Quantifying the safety impact of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles in motorways: A simulation-based study. *R-Evolucionando el transporte*, 2653-2671.
- 289 Mitra, S., & M. Leon, S. (2014). Discrete choice model for air-cargo mode selection. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 25(3), 656–672. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLM-04-2012-0027>
- 290 Mohammed, H., Bigazzi, A. Y., & Sayed, T. (2019). Characterization of bicycle following and overtaking maneuvers on cycling paths. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 98, 139-151.
- 291 Mohammed, H., Sayed, T., & Bigazzi, A. (2019). Toward agent-based microsimulation of cyclist following behaviour: Estimation of reward function parameters using inverse reinforcement learning. In 98th Annual Meeting of the transportation research Board.
- 292 Molina, F. E. E., Ramirez, B. D. V. A., Izquierdo, F. A., & Ortega, D. C. Z. (2021). Road safety perception questionnaire (RSPQ) in Latin America: A development and validation study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(5), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18052433>
- 293 Moll, S., López, G., & García, A. (2021). Analysis of the influence of sport cyclists on narrow two-lane rural roads using instrumented bicycles and microsimulation. *Sustainability*, 13(3), 1235.
- 294 Montanino, M., & Punzo, V. (2015). Trajectory data reconstruction and simulation-based validation against macroscopic traffic patterns. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 80, 82-106.
- 295 Montella, A., Guida, C., Mosca, J., Lee, J., & Abdel-Aty, M. (2020). Systemic approach to improve safety of urban unsignalized intersections: Development and validation of a Safety Index. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 141, 105523.
- 296 Moridpour, S., Sarvi, M., & Rose, G. (2010). Lane changing models: a critical review. *Transportation letters*, 2(3), 157-173.
- 297 Moriya, K, Matsushima, S & Yamanishi, K (2018), 'Traffic risk mining from heterogeneous road statistics,' *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 19(11), pp. 3662–3675, doi:10.1109/TITS.2018.2856533.
- 298 Mourtakos, V., Oikonomou, M. G., Kopelias, P., Vlahogianni, E. I., & Yannis, G. (2022). Impacts of autonomous on-demand mobility service: A simulation experiment in the City of Athens. *Transportation Letters*, 14(10), 1138-1150.
- 299 Mpogas, K., Kopelias, P., Mitropoulos, L., & Kepaptsoglou, K. (2017). Road Safety in urban areas in Greece during economy downturn. A before - After comparison. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 24, 228–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.112>
- 300 Muhrer, E., & Vollrath, M. (2011). The effect of visual and cognitive distraction on driver's anticipation in a simulated car following scenario. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 14(6), 555-566.
- 301 Nan T-W, Mao B-H, Chen Z-J, et al. (2014). Urban mixed nonmotor vehicle flow character simulation based on cellular automata. *J Highw Transp Res Dev* 2014; 31: 104–109
- 302 Nazif-Munoz, J. I., Quesnel-Vallée, A., & van den Berg, A. (2021). Global diffusion of three road safety policies, 1964–2015. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 2021 8:1, 8(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00954-z>

- 303 Neilson, A., Indratmo, Daniel, B., & Tjandra, S. (2019). Systematic Review of the Literature on Big Data in the Transportation Domain: Concepts and Applications. In *Big Data Research* (Vol. 17, pp. 35–44). Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bdr.2019.03.001>
- 304 Nemas, ASDPSMMCSR, R Khatry (2019), 'Applications of machine learning in transport,' ISBN: 978-1-912433-44-5.
- 305 Nigro, M., Castiglione, M., Maria Colasanti, F., De Vincentis, R., Valenti, G., Liberto, C., & Comi, A. (2022). Exploiting floating car data to derive the shifting potential to electric micromobility. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 157, 78–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2022.01.008>
- 306 Nilsson, R. (2000). Drivers' impressions of front and rear gaps in queues. *Ergonomics*, 43(12), 1985–2000.
- 307 Noland, R. B., & Quddus, M. A. (2006). Flow improvements and vehicle emissions: Effects of trip generation and emission control technology. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 11(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2005.06.003>
- 308 OECD. (2001). *Economic Evaluation of Road Traffic Safety Measures*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789282112861-en>
- 309 OECD. (2016). *Zero Road Deaths and Serious Injuries: Leading a paradigm shift to a safe system*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789282108055-en>
- 310 Oikonomou, M. G., Orfanou, F. P., Vlahogianni, E. I., & Yannis, G. (2020). Impacts of autonomous shuttle services on traffic, safety and environment for future mobility scenarios. In 2020 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- 311 Oikonomou, M. G., Ziakopoulos, A., Chaudhry, A., Thomas, P., & Yannis, G. (2023). From conflicts to crashes: Simulating macroscopic connected and automated driving vehicle safety. *Accid. Anal. Prev.* 187, 107087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2023.107087>
- 312 Olmez, S., Douglas-Mann, L., Manley, E., Suchak, K., Heppenstall, A., Birks, D., & Whipp, A. (2021). Exploring the Impact of Driver Adherence to Speed Limits and the Interdependence of Roadside Collisions in an Urban Environment: An Agent-Based Modelling Approach. *Applied Sciences*, 11(12), 5336.
- 313 Ortúzar, J. de D., & Willumsen, L. G. (2014). *Modelling Transport*. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119993308>
- 314 Ossen, S., & Hoogendoorn, S. P. (2011). Heterogeneity in car-following behaviour: Theory and empirics. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 19(2), 182-195.
- 315 Otković, I. I., Tollazzi, T., & Šraml, M. (2013). Calibration of microsimulation traffic model using neural network approach. *Expert systems with applications*, 40(15), 5965-5974.
- 316 Outay, F., Galland, S., Gaud, N., & Abbas-Turki, A. (2021). Simulation of connected driving in hazardous weather conditions: General and extensible multiagent architecture and models. *Engineering applications of artificial intelligence*, 104, 104412.
- 317 Oviedo-Trespalacios, O., Afghari, A.P. and Haque, M.M., 2020. A hierarchical Bayesian multivariate ordered model of distracted drivers' decision to initiate risk-compensating behaviour. *Analytic methods in accident research*, 26, p.100121.
- 318 Ozbay, K., Yang, H., Bartin, B., Mudigonda, S. (2008). Derivation and validation of new simulation-based surrogate safety measure. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board* 2083, 105–113.
- 319 Pagliara, F., & Preston, J. (2013). An Induced Demand Model for High Speed 1 in UK. *Journal of Transportation Technologies*, 03(01), 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jtts.2013.31005>
- 320 Pande, A., & Abdel-Aty, M. (2006). Assessment of freeway traffic parameters leading to lane-change related collisions. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 38(5), 936-948.
- 321 Papadimitriou E., Farah H., Van de Kaa G., Santoni de Sio F., Hagenzieker M., Van Gelder P.H.A.J.M. (2022). Towards common safe 'behaviour' standards for automated vehicles. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, Volume 174, September 2022, 106723.
- 322 Papadimitriou, E., & Yannis, G. (2014). Needs and priorities of road safety stakeholders for evidence-based policy making. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2014.06.006>

- 323 Papadimitriou, E., Auberlet, J. M., Yannis, G., & Lassarre, S. (2014). Simulation of Pedestrians and Motorised Traffic: existing research and future challenges. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Telecommunications and Networking (IJITN)*, 6(1), 57-73.
- 324 Papadimitriou, E., Lassarre, S., & Yannis, G. (2016). Introducing human factors in pedestrian crossing behaviour models. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 36, 69-82.
- 325 Papadimitriou, E., Yannis, G., & Golias, J. (2009). A critical assessment of pedestrian behaviour models. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 12(3), 242-255.
- 326 Papadoulis, A., Quddus, M., & Imprialou, M. (2019). Evaluating the safety impact of connected and autonomous vehicles on motorways. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 124, 12-22.
- 327 Park, B., & Qi, H. (2006, September). Microscopic simulation model calibration and validation for freeway work zone network-a case study of VISSIM. In 2006 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (pp. 1471-1476). IEEE.
- 328 Park, S, Sung-min, K & Young-guk, H (2016), 'Highway traffic accident prediction using vds big data analysis,' *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 72, pp. 2815–2831.
- 329 Paschalidis, E., Choudhury, C. F., & Hess, S. (2019). Combining driving simulator and physiological sensor data in a latent variable model to incorporate the effect of stress in car-following behaviour. *Analytic methods in accident research*, 22, 100089.
- 330 Pazzini, M., Cameli, L., Lantieri, C., Vignali, V., Dondi, G., & Jonsson, T. (2022). New Micromobility Means of Transport: An Analysis of E-Scooter Users' Behaviour in Trondheim. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(12), 7374.
- 331 Pekkanen, J., Giles, O. T., Lee, Y. M., Madigan, R., Daimon, T., Merat, N., & Markkula, G. (2021). Variable-drift diffusion models of pedestrian road-crossing decisions. *Computational Brain & Behaviour*, 1-21.
- 332 Petrov, T., Pocta, P., Roman, J., Buzna, L., & Dado, M. (2019). A feasibility study of privacy ensuring emergency vehicle approaching warning system. *Applied Sciences*, 10(1), 298.
- 333 Phillips, R. O., Ulleberg, P., & Vaa, T. (2011). Meta-analysis of the effect of road safety campaigns on accidents. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 43(3), 1204–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2011.01.002>
- 334 Pilkington-Cheney, F., Afghari, A. P., Filtness, A., Papadimitriou, E., Lourenço, A., & Brijis, T. (2021, June). The i-DREAMS intervention strategies to reduce driver fatigue and sleepiness for different transport modes. In 2021 7th International Conference on Models and Technologies for Intelligent Transportation Systems (MT-ITS) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- 335 Pineda-Jaramillo, J. D. (2019). A review of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms used for modeling travel mode choice. *DYNA*, 86(211), 32–41. <https://doi.org/10.15446/dyna.v86n211.79743>
- 336 Pipes, L. A. (1953). An operational analysis of traffic dynamics. *Journal of applied physics*, 24(3), 274-281.
- 337 Prasertsubpakij, D., & Nitivattananon, V. (2012). Evaluating accessibility to Bangkok Metro Systems using multi-dimensional criteria across user groups. *IATSS Research*, 36(1), 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iatssr.2012.02.003>
- 338 Precht, L., Keinath, A., & Krems, J. F. (2017a). Identifying effects of driving and secondary task demands, passenger presence, and driver characteristics on driving errors and traffic violations—Using naturalistic driving data segments preceding both safety critical events and matched baselines. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 51, 103-144.
- 339 Precht, L., Keinath, A., & Krems, J. F. (2017b). Identifying the main factors contributing to driving errors and traffic violations—Results from naturalistic driving data. *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 49, 49-92.
- 340 Preston, A., & Pulugurtha, S. S. (2021). Simulating and assessing the effect of a protected intersection design for bicyclists on traffic operational performance and safety. *Transportation research interdisciplinary perspectives*, 9, 100329.
- 341 Przybyla, J., Taylor, J., Jupe, J. and Zhou, X., 2012, September. Simplified, data-driven, errorable car-following model to predict the safety effects of distracted driving. In 2012 15th International IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (pp. 1149-1154). IEEE.

- 342 PTV AG (2003). VISSIM user manual. Karlsruhe: PTV Corporation.
- 343 Pu, L., & Joshi, R. (2008). Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM)--software user manual (No. FHWA-HRT-08-050). Turner-Fairbank Highway Research Center.
- 344 Pu, L., Joshi, R., & Energy, S. (2008). Surrogate Safety Assessment Model (SSAM)--software user manual (No. FHWA-HRT-08-050). Turner-Fairbank Highway Research Center.
- 345 Pu, Z., Li, Z., Jiang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2021). Full Bayesian Before-After Analysis of Safety Effects of Variable Speed Limit System. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 22(2), 964–976. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2019.2961699>
- 346 Pucher, J. (1994). Modal shift in Eastern Germany. *Transportation*, 21(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01119632>
- 347 Qu, L, Li, W, Li, W, Ma, D & Wang, Y (2019), 'Daily long-term traffic flow forecasting based on a deep neural network,' *Expert Systems with Applications*, 121, pp. 304–312 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2018.12.031>.
- 348 Qu, Z. W., Cao, N. B., Chen, Y. H., Zhao, L. Y., Bai, Q. W., & Luo, R. Q. (2017). Modeling electric bike–car mixed flow via social force model. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, 9(9), 1687814017719641.
- 349 Quintana, M, Torres, J & Menéndez, JM (2016), 'A simplified computer vision system for road surface inspection and maintenance,' *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 17(3), pp. 608–619, doi:10.1109/TITS.2015.2482222.
- 350 Rahman, M., Chowdhury, M., Xie, Y., & He, Y. (2013). Review of microscopic lane-changing models and future research opportunities. *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems*, 14(4), 1942–1956.
- 351 Rahul, T. M., & Verma, A. (2013). Study of Impact of Various Influencing Factors on NMT Mode Choice. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 104, 1112–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.11.207>
- 352 Rasca, S. (2022). Numerical estimation of travel mode preferences for agents in agent-based simulations. 2022 Smart City Symposium Prague (SCSP), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SCSP54748.2022.9792570>
- 353 Rashidi, T. H., & Hasegawa, H. (2014). An Innovative Simultaneous System of Disaggregate Models for Trip Generation, Mode, and Destination Choice.
- 354 Rasouli, A., & Kotseruba, I. (2022). Intend-Wait-Cross: Towards Modeling Realistic Pedestrian Crossing Behaviour. In 2022 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV) (pp. 83-90).
- 355 Ratrou, N. T., Gazder, U., & Al-Madani, H. M. N. (2014). A review of mode choice modelling techniques for intra-city and border transport. *World Review of Intermodal Transportation Research*, 5(1), 39–58. <https://doi.org/10.1504/WRITR.2014.065055>
- 356 Reason, J. (1990). Human error. Cambridge university press.
- 357 Ren, H, Song, Y, Wang, J, Hu, Y & Lei, J (2018), 'A deep learning approach to the citywide traffic accident risk prediction,' in 2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), pp. 3346–3351, doi:10.1109/ITSC.2018.8569437.
- 358 Ren, R., Li, H., Han, T., Tian, C., Zhang, C., Zhang, J., ... & Feng, Y. (2023). Vehicle crash simulations for safety: Introduction of connected and automated vehicles on the roadways. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 186, 107021.
- 359 Rezvani, S. M., Falcão, M. J., Komljenovic, D., & de Almeida, N. M. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review on Urban Resilience Enabled with Asset and Disaster Risk Management Approaches and GIS-Based Decision Support Tools. *Applied Sciences*, 13(4), 2223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13042223>
- 360 Rhodes, N., & Pivik, K. (2011). Age and gender differences in risky driving: The roles of positive affect and risk perception. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 43(3), 923–931.
- 361 Ribeiro, P., Araújo, C., Gonçalves, L. A., Dias, G. J., & Cunto, F. (2019). Micro-simulation of the impact of different speeds on safety road travel and urban travel time: case study in the city of Guimarães.
- 362 Riccardi, M. R., Augeri, M. G., Galante, F., Mauriello, F., Nicolosi, V., & Montella, A. (2022). Safety Index for evaluation of urban roundabouts. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 178, 106858.
- 363 Richmund DE LEON Graduate Student, M. M., Cal, P. C., Sigua, R. G., & Professor, A. (2005). ESTIMATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC COST OF ROAD ACCIDENTS IN METRO MANILA.

- 364 Ridel, D, Rehder, E, Lauer, M, Stiller, C & Wolf, D (2018), 'A literature review on the prediction of pedestrian behaviour in urban scenarios,' in 2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), pp. 3105–3112, doi:10.1109/ITSC.2018.8569415.
- 365 Rizzi, L. I., & Ortúzar, J. de D. (2006). Estimating the willingness-to-pay for road safety improvements. *Transport Reviews*, 26(4), 471–485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441640600602302>
- 366 Rizzi, L. I., De Dios, J., & Ortúzar, O. (2006). Road Safety Valuation under a Stated Choice Framework. *Journal of Transport Economics and Policy*, 40(1), 69–94.
- 367 Roadside Design Guide (1996). American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials, Washington, D.C.
- 368 Robinson, R. V. F., & Vickerman, R. W. (1976). The demand for shopping travel: a theoretical and empirical study. *Applied Economics*, 8(4), 267–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036847600000023>
- 369 Rodemerk, C., Habenicht, S., Weitzel, A., Winner, H., & Schmitt, T. (2012, June). Development of a general criticality criterion for the risk estimation of driving situations and its application to a maneuver-based lane change assistance system. In 2012 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (pp. 264-269). IEEE.
- 370 Rumar, K. (1985). The role of perceptual and cognitive filters in observed behaviour. *Human behaviour and traffic safety*, 151-170.
- 371 Rumobil Project. (2017). Opportunities and boundaries of transport network telematics.
- 372 Rupi, F & Schweizer, J (2018), 'Evaluating cyclist patterns using gps data from smartphones,' IET Intelligent Transport Systems, doi:10.1049/iet-its.2017.0285
- 373 Saad, M., Abdel-Aty, M., Lee, J., & Wang, L. (2018). Safety analysis of access zone design for managed toll lanes on freeways. *Journal of Transportation Engineering, Part A: Systems*, 144(11), 04018067.
- 374 Safarpour, H., Khorasani-Zavareh, D., & Mohammadi, R. (2020). The common road safety approaches: A scoping review and thematic analysis. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjtee.2020.02.005>
- 375 SAFE-UP (2021). D2.5 Description metrics for traffic interactions. Horizon 2020.
- 376 Saifuzzaman, M. and Zheng, Z., 2014. Incorporating human-factors in car-following models: a review of recent developments and research needs. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 48, pp.379-403.
- 377 Saifuzzaman, M., Zheng, Z., Haque, M. M., & Washington, S. (2015). Revisiting the Task–Capability Interface model for incorporating human factors into car-following models. *Transportation research part B: methodological*, 82, 1-19.
- 378 Salas, A, Georgakis, P, Nwagboso, C, Ammari, A & Petalas, I (2017), 'Traffic event detection framework using social media,' in 2017 IEEE International Conference on Smart Grid and Smart Cities (ICSGSC), pp. 303–307, doi:10.1109/ICSGSC.2017.8038595.
- 379 Salvucci, R., Tattini, J., Gargiulo, M., Lehtilä, A., & Karlsson, K. (2018). Modelling transport modal shift in TIMES models through elasticities of substitution. *Applied Energy*, 232, 740–751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2018.09.083>
- 380 Sanjeewani, T. G. P., & Verma, B. (2019). Learning and Analysis of AusRAP Attributes from Digital Video Recording for Road Safety 2019. In *International Conference on Image and Vision Computing New Zealand (IVCNZ)*. IEEE.
- 381 Sattar, S., Li, S., & Chapman, M. (2018). Road surface monitoring using smartphone sensors: A review. In *Sensors (Switzerland)* (Vol. 18, Issue 11). MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18113845>
- 382 Schömig, N., & Metz, B. (2013). Three levels of situation awareness in driving with secondary tasks. *Safety Science*, 56, 44-51.
- 383 Seraj, F, van der Zwaag, BJ, Dilo, A, Luarasi, T & Havinga, P (2016), 'Roads: A road pavement monitoring system for anomaly detection using smart phones,' in Atzmueller, M, Chin, A, Janssen, F, Schweizer, I & Trattner, C (eds.), *Big Data Analytics in the Social and Ubiquitous Context*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 128–146.
- 384 Sha, H. (2020). Investigating the system-level performance of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles against transport and broader societal impacts (Doctoral dissertation, Loughborough University).

- 385 Sha, H., Singh, M.K., Haouari, R., Chaudhry, A., Quigley, C., Papazikou, E., Quddus, M., Weijermars, W., Thomas, P. and Morris, A. (2022). Safety impact of dedicated lanes for connected and autonomous vehicles—a traffic microsimulation study. 8th Road Safety & Simulation International Conference. Athens, Greece.
- 386 Shahdah, U. E., & Azam, A. (2021). Safety and mobility effects of installing speed-humps within unconventional median U-turn intersections. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 12(2), 1451-1462.
- 387 Shahdah, U., Saccomanno, F., & Persaud, B. (2014). Integrated traffic conflict model for estimating crash modification factors. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 71, 228-235.
- 388 Shaheen, S., Sperling, D. and Wagner, C.. (1999). A Short History of Carsharing in the 90's. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/6p3305b0>
- 389 Shaon, M. R. R., Qin, X., Afghari, A. P., Washington, S., & Haque, M. M. (2019). Incorporating behavioural variables into crash count prediction by severity: A multivariate multiple risk source approach. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 129, 277-288.
- 390 Shawky, M. (2020). Factors affecting lane change crashes. *IATSS research*, 44(2), 155-161.
- 391 Shaygan, M, Meese, C, Li, W, Zhao, XG & Nejad, M (2022), 'Traffic prediction using artificial intelligence: Review of recent advances and emerging opportunities,' *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 145, p.103921, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2022.103921>.
- 392 Shrivasa, A., & Kumar, A. (2023). Modified social force model for pedestrian–vehicle interactions at a signalized intersection. *Transportation Letters*, 1-13.
- 393 SILVA, D., FOLDES, D., & CSISZAR, C. (2021). The effect of modal shift to micromobility upon the parking demand. 2021 Smart City Symposium Prague (SCSP), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SCSP52043.2021.9447396>
- 394 Singh, S. (2015). Critical reasons for crashes investigated in the national motor vehicle crash causation survey (No. DOT HS 812 115).
- 395 Šinko, S., Prah, K., & Kramberger, T. (2021). Spatial Modelling of Modal Shift Due to COVID-19. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 7116. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137116>
- 396 Šinko, S., Rupnik, B., Prah, K., & Kramberger, T. (2021). SPATIAL MODELLING OF THE TRANSPORT MODE CHOICE: APPLICATION ON THE VIENNA TRANSPORT NETWORK. *Transport*, 36(5), 386–394. <https://doi.org/10.3846/transport.2021.16128>
- 397 Small, K. (2013). *Urban Transportation Economics*. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315014821>
- 398 So, J., Lim, I. K., & Kweon, Y. J. (2015). Exploring traffic conflict-based surrogate approach for safety assessment of highway facilities. *Transp. Res. Rec*, 2513(1), 56-62.
- 399 So, J., Park, B., Wolfe, S. M., & Dedes, G. (2015). Development and validation of a vehicle dynamics integrated traffic simulation environment assessing surrogate safety. *Journal of computing in civil engineering*, 29(5), 04014080.
- 400 Sohail, A., Cheema, M. A., Ali, M. E., Toosi, A. N., & Rakha, H. A. (2023). Data-driven approaches for road safety: A comprehensive systematic literature review. In *Safety Science* (Vol. 158). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2022.105949>
- 401 Sonnleitner, J., Friedrich, M., & Richter, E. (2022). Impacts of highly automated vehicles on travel demand: macroscopic modeling methods and some results. *Transportation*, 49(3), 927–950. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-021-10199-z>
- 402 Sparmann, U. (1978). Spurwechselforgänge auf zweispurigen BAB-Richtungsfahrbahnen. *FORSCH STRASSENBAU U STRASSENVERKEHRSTECH* 263, (263).
- 403 Speck, J. (2018). *Walkable City Rules*. Island Press/Center for Resource Economics. <https://doi.org/10.5822/978-1-61091-899-2>
- 404 Sroczyński, A., Kurowski, A., Zaporowski, S., & Czyżewski, A. (2022). Examining Impact of Speed Recommendation Algorithm Operating in Autonomous Road Signs on Minimum Distance between Vehicles. *Remote Sensing*, 14(12), 2803.
- 405 Stanton, N. A., & Salmon, P. M. (2009). Human error taxonomies applied to driving: A generic driver error taxonomy and its implications for intelligent transport systems. *Safety Science*, 47(2), 227-237.

- 406 Stanton, N.A. and Salmon, P.M., 2009. Human error taxonomies applied to driving: A generic driver error taxonomy and its implications for intelligent transport systems. *Safety Science*, 47(2), pp.227–237.
- 407 Stylianou, K., Dimitriou, L., & Abdel-Aty, M. (2018). Big data and road safety: A comprehensive review. In *Mobility Patterns, Big Data and Transport Analytics: Tools and Applications for Modeling* (pp. 297–343). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812970-8.00012-9>
- 408 Suh, W., Henclewood, D., Greenwood, A., Guin, A., Guensler, R., Hunter, M. P., & Fujimoto, R. (2013). Modeling pedestrian crossing activities in an urban environment using microscopic traffic simulation. *Simulation*, 89(2), 213–224.
- 409 Sun, P, Aljeri, N & Boukerche, A (2020), 'Machine learning-based models for real-time traffic flow prediction in vehicular networks,' *IEEE Network*, 34(3), pp. 178–185, doi:10.1109/MNET.011.1900338.
- 410 Svatý, Z., Kocián, K., & Mičunek, T. (2019). Integration of safety assessment in bim for transportation infrastructure. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives*, 42(5/W3), 143–148. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-5-W3-143-2019>
- 411 Taamneh, M, Alkheder, S & Taamneh, S (2017), 'Data-mining techniques for traffic accident modeling and prediction in the united arab emirates,' *Journal of Transportation Safety & Security*, 9(2), pp. 146–166, doi:10.1080/19439962.2016.1152338.
- 412 Tafidis, P., Farah, H., Brijs, T., & Pirdavani, A. (2022). Safety implications of higher levels of automated vehicles: a scoping review. *Transport reviews*, 42(2), 245–267.
- 413 Tafidis, P., Pirdavani, A., Brijs, T., & Farah, H. (2019). Can automated vehicles improve cyclist safety in urban areas?. *Safety*, 5(3), 57.
- 414 Taha, A.-E. M. (2018). A Framework for Dynamic Assessment of Road Safety in Smart Cities. *IEEE*, 1–4.
- 415 Taha, AE (2018), 'An iot architecture for assessing road safety in smart cities,' *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2018, pp. 1–11, doi:10.1155/2018/8214989.
- 416 Tamim Kashifi, M., Jamal, A., Samim Kashefi, M., Almoshaogeh, M., & Masiur Rahman, S. (2022). Predicting the travel mode choice with interpretable machine learning techniques: A comparative study. *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 29, 279–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2022.07.003>
- 417 Tan, D. M., Alhajyaseen, W. K., Asano, M., & Nakamura, H. (2012). Development of microscopic traffic simulation model for safety assessment at signalized intersections. *Transportation research record*, 2316(1), 122–131.
- 418 Taniform, P., Persia, L., Usami, D. S., Kunsoan, N. B., Karumba, M. M., & Wijnen, W. (2023). An Assessment of the Social Costs of Road Traffic Crashes in Cameroon. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021316>
- 419 Tapani, A. (2012). Vehicle trajectory effects of adaptive cruise control. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 16(1), 36–44.
- 420 Tarko, AP (2018). Estimating the expected number of crashes with traffic conflicts and the Lomax Distribution – A theoretical and numerical exploration. *Accident Analysis Prevention*, Vol. 113, No. January, pp. 63–73.
- 421 Teknomo, K. (2006). Application of microscopic pedestrian simulation model. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 9(1), 15–27.
- 422 Testa, G., Zaccaria, G., Montanino, M., Baltzopoulos, G., Bilotta, A., Iervolino, I., & Punzo, V. (2022). Infrastructure-level traffic micro-simulation for probabilistic analysis of bridge loads. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*.
- 423 The World Bank. (2021a). Detecting Urban Clues for Road Safety Leveraging Big Data and Machine Learning.
- 424 The World Bank. (2021b). Detecting Urban Clues for Road Safety Leveraging Big Data and Machine Learning in World Bank Transport Projects.
- 425 Theofilatos, A, Chen, C & Antoniou, C (2019), 'Comparing machine learning and deep learning methods for real-time crash prediction,' *Transportation Research Record*, 2673(8), pp. 169–178, doi:10.1177/0361198119841571.

- 426 Thiffault, P., & Bergeron, J. (2003). Monotony of road environment and driver fatigue: a simulator study. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 35(3), 381-391.
- 427 Thill, J.-C., & Kim, M. (2005). Trip making, induced travel demand, and accessibility. *Journal of Geographical Systems*, 7(2), 229–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10109-005-0158-3>
- 428 Toledo, T., Koutsopoulos, H. N., & Ben-Akiva, M. E. (2003). Modeling integrated lane-changing behaviour. *Transportation Research Record*, 1857(1), 30-38.
- 429 Torbaghan, M. E., Sasidharan, M., Reardon, L., & Muchanga-Hvelplund, L. C. W. (2022). Understanding the potential of emerging digital technologies for improving road safety. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2021.106543>
- 430 Treiber, M., & Kesting, A. (2013). Traffic flow dynamics. *Traffic Flow Dynamics: Data, Models and Simulation*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 983-1000.
- 431 Treiber, M., Hennecke, A., & Helbing, D. (2000). Congested traffic states in empirical observations and microscopic simulations. *Physical review E*, 62(2), 1805.
- 432 Treiber, M., Kesting, A., & Helbing, D. (2006). Delays, inaccuracies and anticipation in microscopic traffic models. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 360(1), 71-88.
- 433 Treiber, M., Kesting, A., & Helbing, D. (2007). Influence of reaction times and anticipation on stability of vehicular traffic flow. *Transportation Research Record*, 1999(1), 23-29.
- 434 Tumminello, M. L., Macioszek, E., Granà, A., & Giuffrè, T. (2023). A Microsimulation-Based Modelling Approach for Connected and Automated Vehicles on Roundabouts. In *Advanced Solutions and Practical Applications in Road Traffic Engineering* (pp. 49-68). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- 435 Turner, B., Affum, J., Tziotis, M., & Jurewicz, C. (2009). Review of iRAP risk parameters for iRAP Reviewed Project Leader.
- 436 Twaddle, H., Schendzielorz, T., & Fakler, O. (2014). Bicycles in urban areas: Review of existing methods for modeling behaviour. *Transportation research record*, 2434(1), 140-146.
- 437 Twaddle, H., Schendzielorz, T., & Fakler, O. (2014). Bicycles in urban areas: Review of existing methods for modeling behaviour. *Transportation research record*, 2434(1), 140-146.
- 438 Ulak, M. B., Ozguven, E. E., Moses, R., Sando, T., Boot, W., AbdelRazig, Y., & Sobanjo, J. O. (2019). Assessment of traffic performance measures and safety based on driver age and experience: A microsimulation based analysis for an unsignalized T-intersection. *Journal of traffic and transportation engineering (English edition)*, 6(5), 455-469.
- 439 UNECE. (n.d.). Road Traffic Safety. Retrieved March 20, 2023, from <https://unece.org/transport/road-traffic-safety-0>
- 440 Ursachi, G., Ursachi, G., Ljubotina, L., Marunica, A., Leš, S., Rozi, O., Ševrović, M., & Soršak, A. (2022). Deliverable D.T1.3.2 - Danube Bicycle Routes Star rating Results Report. www.interreg-danube.eu/SABRINA
- 441 Vallejo-Borda, J. A., Giesen, R., Basnak, P., Reyes, J. P., Mella Lira, B., Beck, M. J., Hensher, D. A., & Ortúzar, J. de D. (2022). Characterising public transport shifting to active and private modes in South American capitals during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 164, 186–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2022.08.010>
- 442 van Lint, H., Schakel, W., Tamminga, G., Knoppers, P., & Verbraeck, A. (2016). Getting the human factor into traffic flow models: new open-source design to simulate next generation of traffic operations. *Transportation Research Record*, 2561(1), 25-33.
- 443 Van Lint, J. W. C., & Calvert, S. C. (2018). A generic multi-level framework for microscopic traffic simulation—Theory and an example case in modelling driver distraction. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 117, 63-86.
- 444 Vecino-Ortiz, A. I., & Hyder, A. A. (2014). The use of cost-Benefit analysis in road assessments: A methodological inquiry. *Injury Prevention*, 20(1), 50–53. <https://doi.org/10.1136/injuryprev-2012-040708>
- 445 Vedagiri, P., & Arasan, V. T. (2009). MODELLING MODAL SHIFT DUE TO THE ENHANCED LEVEL OF BUS SERVICE. *TRANSPORT*, 24(2), 121–128. <https://doi.org/10.3846/1648-4142.2009.24.121-128>

- 446 Vemula, A., Patil, N., Paharia, V., Bansal, A., Chaudhary, M., Aggarwal, N., Bansal, D., Ramakrishnan, K. K., & Raman, B. (2015, April 30). Improving public transportation through crowd-sourcing. *7th International Conference on Communication Systems and Networks, COMSNETS 2015 - Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMSNETS.2015.7098724>
- 447 Verma, Z. J. and B., Affum, J., Atabak, S., & Moir, L. (2018). Convolutional Neural Network based Deep Learning Technique for Identifying Road Attributes. *2018 International Conference on Image and Vision Computing New Zealand (IVCNZ)*.
- 448 Vivacity (2023). School Streets' impact on the decision to walk to school. Webpage. Available at <https://vivacitylabs.com/evaluating-impact-of-school-streets/>
- 449 Vogel, K. (2003). A comparison of headway and time to collision as safety indicators. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 35, 427–433.
- 450 Walraven, E., Spaan, MT & Bakker, B (2016), 'Traffic flow optimization: A reinforcement learning approach,' *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 52, pp. 203–212, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2016.01.001>.
- 451 Wang, C., & Stamatiadis, N. (2013). Surrogate safety measure for simulation-based conflict study. *Transportation Research Record*, 2386(1), 72-80.
- 452 Wang, C., Quddus, M. A., & Ison, S. G. (2013). The effect of traffic and road characteristics on road safety: A review and future research direction. In *Safety Science* (Vol. 57, pp. 264–275). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.02.012>
- 453 Wang, C., Xu, C., Xia, J., Qian, Z., & Lu, L. (2018). A combined use of microscopic traffic simulation and extreme value methods for traffic safety evaluation. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 90, 281-291.
- 454 Wang, J, Kong, Y & Fu, T (2019), 'Expressway crash risk prediction using back propagation neural network: A brief investigation on safety resilience,' *Accident Analysis Prevention*, 124, pp. 180–192, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2019.01.007>
- 455 Wang, J., Lv, W., Jiang, Y., & Huang, G. (2023). A cellular automata approach for modelling pedestrian-vehicle mixed traffic flow in urban city. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 115, 1-33.
- 456 Wang, L, Abdel-Aty, M, Shi, Q & Park, J (2015), 'Real-time crash prediction for expressway weaving segments,' *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 61, pp. 1–10, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2015.10.008>.
- 457 Wang, Y., Liu, D., & Luo, J. (2022). Identification and Improvement of Hazard Scenarios in Non-Motorized Transportation Using Multiple Deep Learning and Street View Images. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192114054>
- 458 Wang, Y., Shen, B., Wu, H., Wang, C., Su, Q., & Chen, W. (2021). Modeling illegal pedestrian crossing behaviours at unmarked mid-block roadway based on extended decision field theory. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 562, 125327.
- 459 Wang, Y., Zhu, Y., He, Z., Yue, Y., & Li, Q. (2011). Challenges and opportunities in exploring large-scale GPS probe data.
- 460 Wang, Z., Shi, X., & Li, X. (2019). Review of lane-changing maneuvers of connected and automated vehicles: models, algorithms and traffic impact analyses. *Journal of the Indian Institute of Science*, 99, 589-599.
- 461 Washington, S., Afghari, A. P., & Haque, M. M. (2018). Detecting high-risk accident locations. In *Safe Mobility: Challenges, Methodology and Solutions* (Vol. 11, pp. 351-382). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- 462 Wasserman, L. (2000). Bayesian Model Selection and Model Averaging. *Journal of Mathematical Psychology*, 44(1), 92–107. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmps.1999.1278>
- 463 Wegman, F., & Oppe, S. (2010). Benchmarking road safety performances of countries. *Safety Science*, 48(9), 1203–1211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SSCI.2010.02.003>
- 464 Weijermars, W. et al. (2021). Road safety related impacts within the Levitate project. Working paper of the road safety working group of the H2020 project LEVITATE
- 465 Wesemann, P. (2000). Economic evaluation of road safety measures.
- 466 Wiedemann, R. (1974). Simulation des StraBenverkehrsflusses. In: *Proceedings of the Schriftenreihe des Instituts fir Verkehrswesen der Universitiit, Karlsruhe, Germany*.

- 467 Wijnen, W. (2013). 6th Road Safety on Four Continents Conference SOCIAL COSTS OF ROAD CRASHES: AN INTERNATIONAL ANALYSIS.
- 468 Wijnen, W. (2021). Socio-economic costs of road crashes in middle-income countries: Applying a hybrid approach to Kazakhstan. *IATSS Research*, 45(3), 293–302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iatssr.2020.12.006>
- 469 Wijnen, W., Wesemann, P., & de Blaeij, A. (2009). Valuation of road safety effects in cost–benefit analysis. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 32(4), 326–331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EVALPROGPLAN.2009.06.015>
- 470 World Bank. (2021). *Detecting Urban Clues for Road Safety Leveraging Big Data and Machine Learning*. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/37029>
- 471 World Bank. (2021). Detecting Urban Clues for Road Safety Leveraging Big Data and Machine Learning. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/37029>
- 472 Xie, K, Yang, D, Ozbay, K & Yang, H (2019), 'Use of real-world connected vehicle data in identifying high-risk locations based on a new surrogate safety measure,' *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 125, pp. 311–319, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2018.07.002>.
- 473 Xin, W., Moonam, H. M., Petit, J., & Whyte, W. (2019). Towards a balance between privacy and safety: microsimulation framework for assessing silence-based pseudonym-change schemes. *Transportation research record*, 2673(2), 71-84.
- 474 Xiong, X, Chen, L & Liang, J (2018), 'A new framework of vehicle collision prediction by combining svm and hmm,' *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 19(3), pp. 699–710, doi:10.1109/TITS.2017.2699191.
- 475 Xu, C., Ma, J., & Tang, X. (2022). A Simulation-Based Study of the Influence of Low-Speed Vehicles on Expressway Traffic Safety. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12165.
- 476 Yang, H. H., & Peng, H. (2010). Development of an errorable car-following driver model. *Vehicle System Dynamics*, 48(6), 751-773.
- 477 Yanmaz-Tuzel, O., & Ozbay, K. (2010). A comparative Full Bayesian before-and-after analysis and application to urban road safety countermeasures in New Jersey. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 42(6), 2099–2107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2010.06.023>
- 478 Yannis, G., Dragomanovits, A., Laiou, A., Richter, T., Ruhl, S., la Torre, F., Domenichini, L., Graham, D., Karathodorou, N., & Li, H. (2016). Use of Accident Prediction Models in Road Safety Management - An International Inquiry. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 14, 4257–4266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2016.05.397>
- 479 Yannis, G., Weijermars, W., & Kauppila, J. (2012). A review of International Sources for Road Safety Measures Assessment. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 48, 2876–2886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SBSPRO.2012.06.1256>
- 480 Yannis, G., Weijermars, W., Gitelman, V., Vis, M., Chaziris, A., Papadimitriou, E., & Azevedo, C. L. (2013). Road safety performance indicators for the interurban road network. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 60, 384–395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2012.11.012>
- 481 Yasin, Y. J., Grivna, M., & Abu-Zidan, F. M. (2021). Global impact of COVID-19 pandemic on road traffic collisions. *World Journal of Emergency Surgery*, 16(1), 51. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13017-021-00395-8>
- 482 Yin, L., Cheng, Q., Wang, Z., & Shao, Z. (2015). 'Big data' for pedestrian volume: Exploring the use of Google Street View images for pedestrian counts. *Applied Geography*, 63, 337–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2015.07.010>
- 483 Yu, J., Stettler, M. E. J., Angeloudis, P., Hu, S., & Chen, X. (Michael). (2020). Urban network-wide traffic speed estimation with massive ride-sourcing GPS traces. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 112, 136–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2020.01.023>
- 484 Yuhara, N., & Tajima, J. (2006). Multi-driver agent-based traffic simulation systems for evaluating the effects of advanced driver assistance systems on road traffic accidents. *Cognition, Technology & Work*, 8(4), 283-300.

- 485 Zang, D, Fang, Y, Wei, Z, Tang, K & Cheng, J (2019), 'Traffic flow data prediction using residual deconvolution based deep generative network,' *IEEE Access*, 7, pp. 71311–71322, doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2919996
- 486 Zalmeh-Kanj, S., & Toledo, T. (2021). Car Following and Microscopic Traffic Simulation Under Distracted Driving. *Transportation Research Record*, 2675(8), 643–656.
- 487 Zhang, X., Shi, Z., & Chen, J. (2023). A bi-directional visual angle car-following model considering collision sensitivity. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 609, 128326.
- 488 Zhang, Y., Chen, X., Wang, J., Zheng, Z., & Wu, K. (2022). A generative car-following model conditioned on driving styles. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 145, 103926.
- 489 Zhang, Z., & Fu, D. (2022). Modeling pedestrian–vehicle mixed-flow in a complex evacuation scenario. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 599, 127468.
- 490 Zhao, L., Farhi, N., Christoforou, Z., & Haddadou, N. (2022b). Analysis of driver behavior and intervehicular collision: a data-based traffic modeling and simulation approach. *Journal of advanced transportation*, 2022.
- 491 Zhao, P., Ma, J., Xu, C., Zhao, C., & Ni, Z. (2022a). Research on the safety of the left hard shoulder in a multi-lane highway based on safety performance function. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 15114.
- 492 Zheng, L. & Sayed, T. (2019). From univariate to bivariate extreme value models: Approaches to integrate traffic conflict indicators for crash estimation. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* 103, 211–225.
- 493 Zheng, L., Sayed, T., & Mannering, F. (2021). Modeling traffic conflicts for use in road safety analysis: A review of analytic methods and future directions. *Analytic methods in accident research*, 29, 100142.
- 494 Zheng, L., Sayed, T., Essa, M., & Guo, Y. (2019). Do simulated traffic conflicts predict crashes? An investigation using the extreme value approach. In 2019 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC) (pp. 631-636). IEEE.
- 495 Zheng, Z. (2014). Recent developments and research needs in modeling lane changing. *Transportation research part B: methodological*, 60, 16-32.
- 496 Zheng, Z., Ahn, S., & Monsere, C. M. (2010). Impact of traffic oscillations on freeway crash occurrences. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 42(2), 626-636.
- 497 Zheng, Z., Ahn, S., Chen, D., & Laval, J. (2013). The effects of lane-changing on the immediate follower: Anticipation, relaxation, and change in driver characteristics. *Transportation research part C: emerging technologies*, 26, 367-379.
- 498 Zhu, H., Almukdad, A., Iryo-Asano, M., Alhajyaseen, W. K., Nakamura, H., & Zhang, X. (2021). A novel agent-based framework for evaluating pedestrian safety at unsignalized mid-block crosswalks. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 159, 106288.

Annex A: Literature review guidelines

A.1. PHOEBE Task 1.1 – Literature review guidelines

Partners will review the different topics in pairs, for quality assurance purposes. It is advised that both partners make the literature search and selection of studies separately, followed by a ‘consensus’ meeting for the final sources to be included in the review.

A.2. Distribution of topics (topics appear in bold)

Partners	Topics
iRAP, NTUA	Review of the existing road safety assessment methodologies (iRAP, AusRAP, QRAM, KiwiRAP, CycleRAP, HSM, ...)
AIM, TUM	Review of the existing traffic micro-simulation methods and tools (Aimsun, Vissim, Syncro, ...)
TUD, NTUA	Review of the existing behavioural models (focus VRUs) (risk compensating models, task-capability interface model, etc.)
TUM, TUD	Review of the existing socio-economic analysis and modal shift methods (CBA, before-after analysis, etc.)
FLOOW, iRAP	Review of the existing emerging data collection tools and methods (video cameras and image processing, telematics, road infrastructure data, etc.)

A.3. Search engines

Academic studies and gray literature:

- Google scholar, Scopus for academic literature
- Google for gray literature (World Bank, ITF, iRAP, etc.)
- CORDIS website for previous European projects

A.4. Search strategy and selection criteria

- Keyword #1: road safety assessment (risk assessment) (NTUA, IRAP)
- Keyword #2: traffic micro-simulation (microsimulation) (AIM, TUM)
- Keyword #3 (depending on topic, see Table above): behavioural models (human factors, driver behaviour, human behaviour) (TUD, NTUA); socio-economic analysis (cost benefit analysis) (TUM, TUD); modal shift (TUM, TUD); emerging data collection (FLOOW, IRAP)

Note number of ‘hits’ for:

- Keyword #1
- Keyword #1 AND Keyword #2
- Keyword #3
- Keyword #3 AND Keyword #1

- Keyword #3 AND Keyword #1 AND Keyword #2

Example:

Behavioural models AND road safety assessment

Behavioural models AND road safety assessment AND traffic micro-simulation

A.5. Selection of studies

- Prioritize the existing reviews (from previous projects or review papers), then select studies published after the year of publication of the existing review
- Prioritise highly cited (or highly viewed / high number of hits) documents
- Prioritise articles from renowned journals, authors

Fill in the Excel file (on Google Drive Task 1.1 folder) with title, author etc. and tags for each selected study.

Annex B: Additional content of the Star Ratings, FSIs and SRIP Models

The iRAP star rating model has been developed for more than 20 years. It started with EuroRAP in 1999, and since then, the iRAP has implemented several updates based on the latest evidence available in road safety. The iRAP's Global Technical Committee (GTC) oversee the changes and discusses implementation and impacts on the road safety community (ADB, 2022). The major recent implementation was moving from a 4-star model (version 1) to a 5-star model (version 3.02). Unlike the previous versions, version 3.02 considers crashes' likelihood and severity.

As part of PHOEBE, iRAP will deliver model version 3.1, with changes focused on the pedestrian and bicyclist models. The objective of the model review is to support PHOEBE implementation considering the project ambitions, but also feedback from users and current road safety evidence. The changes will ensure alignment with safe system principles and consistency between risk factors for different road user types. The update might include changes to risk factors for existing attributes, changes to the Star Rating bandings for pedestrian and bicyclist road user types and the introduction of decimal star ratings.

Star Ratings represent a risk to an individual user type (vehicle occupant, motorcyclist, bicyclist, and pedestrian) and is the sum of individual crash type scores (run-off-road, heads-on, intersections and access points, travelling along the road and crossing the road).

They are an objective measure of:

- I. How likely it is a road crash will occur for an individual road user, based on the speed, volume and physical features of the road, and
- II. The severity of the outcome when a crash does occur.

The iRAP models consider the contribution of several infrastructure and operational elements and their contribution to one or both previously discussed components. They are combined in a multiplicative model to determine total risk, associated Star Rating, and fatal and serious injury (FSI) estimations. The Star Rating model indicates a risk to an individual road user. At the same time, the FSI Estimation Model considers the star rating results to estimate how many FSI crashes will occur on the road network, considering exposure (road user flows).

Star Rating Scores are the sum of crash type scores for each road user type. Crash-type scores are products of:

- Infrastructure risk factors for the likelihood
- Infrastructure risk factors for severity
- 85th percentile operating speed or speed limit (whichever is highest), and
- External flow influence

An example of a Star Rating Score equation is provided below in **Error! Reference source not found.** Full details on each equation are provided in *iRAP Methodology Factsheet 6* (iRAP,2014).

Figure B- 1 Example Star Rating Score equation

B.1. Considerations of speeds in the iRAP models

Speed contributes to both the likelihood of a crash and the severity of a crash outcome.

- For likelihood, the relationship between speed and crash risk is linear. That is, the crash risk increases by the same proportion for every incremental increase in speed. This is discussed in greater detail below.
- For severity, the relationship between speed and the severity of a crash outcome is determined using Nilsson's Power Model (PM) (1), which is generally represented by a fourth/third/square curve, depending on the levels of injuries considered.

The iRAP models combine likelihood (linear model – x^1) and severity (based on the kinetic energy – $1/2 m^2 - x^2$), resulting in a third power curve, as Nilsson's cubic model for serious casualty crashes. To do this, the two components' risk factors are multiplied, resulting in the curves in Error! Reference source not found.. Five trajectories (or 'curves') are shown, categorized by crash type—three for vehicle occupants and motorcyclists and one each for pedestrians and bicyclists—the risk factor curve's risk factors for the risk of a fatal injury (iRAP, 2022).

The point at which a trajectory switches from being a curve to linear is where, if a crash were to occur, the outcome would certainly result in a fatality (=1). Subsequent increases in speed then only increase the likelihood of a crash occurring. For pedestrians, a certain fatal crash outcome is approximately 75km/h, and for bicyclists, at approximately 95km/h. The yellow line represents crash types with a severity outcome independent of speed (e.g., risk of being hit by a train or driving off a cliff). Therefore, only likelihood applies (iRAP, 2022). The pedestrian and cyclist curves will be reviewed as part of the enhancements planned for PHOEBE.

Figure B- 2 The combined (likelihood x severity) speed risk factor curves used in the Star Rating models (v3.02)

It's important to notice that the speed risk factors used in the iRAP models, like infrastructure-related risk factors, relate to fatalities only. The iRAP models predict severe injuries in its FSI Estimation model as a serious injury to fatality ratio. The default ratio is 10:1, which can be adjusted based on local data.

The speed value used to calculate the **Star Rating Score** is the **greater speed recorded between the operating speed and speed limit**. This approach aims to properly acknowledge the effect of speed (and speed limit compliance) on road safety promoted by the Safe System.

In the case of **FSIs**, the casualty estimates along a road section and the determination of economic benefits associated with an iRAP countermeasure are based on **mean speed**. The estimation of casualties and associated economic benefits are based on a multiplicative relationship between the full traffic volume and the associated speed risk factors (in addition to other attributes). As a result, the use of the risk factors for the average (or mean) speed provides the best estimate for actual casualties and economic benefits (iRAP, 2010).

On the other hand, the **operating speeds** are the basis of the **countermeasures triggered** as part of an iRAP Safer Roads Investment Plan. The iRAP Global Technical Committee has determined that the need for any countermeasures must be based on the actual operating conditions at the location (iRAP, 2010).

B.2. Considerations of flows for the pedestrians and cyclists Star Ratings

This subsection highlights relevant content for PHOEBE from the *iRAP Methodology Factsheet 5 –External Flow and Median Traversability* (iRAP, 2013).

The presence and quantity of traffic are related to the likelihood of a certain crash type happening. For example, a pedestrian cannot be involved in a crash unless a vehicle uses the road. Similarly, a head-on crash can only occur if two vehicles are travelling in opposite directions. The external flow influence depends on media transversality. Median types are categorized as 'traversable' (factor = 1) or 'non-traversable' (factor = 0).

The risk for pedestrians or cyclists increases with the flow of heavier mass vehicles and motorcyclists at the location. For the individual pedestrian or bicyclist, the road attribute factors - such as footpaths, pedestrian fencing, traffic calming and pedestrian crossings - are used to reflect the likelihood that they will be struck by a vehicle/motorcycle.

The external flow influence factors are used to reflect the effect of the total number of vehicles using the road. There is a flow influence factor approaches zero at very low flows, and as vehicle flows increase and lanes approach full saturation, the external flow influence increases. The factors are based on a relationship between risk and vehicle flow of AADT per lane (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure B- 3 Pedestrian (along and crossing inspected road) and bicyclist (along and run-off) external flow risk factors

In the case of a pedestrian crossing a side road and bicyclists at an intersection, the lane saturation is calculated based on the flows of the side road. Considering the side road flows categories coded in the model, the risk graph is shaped as a graph bar. For the purpose of the iRAP model where the highest side road volume category is >15,000 (7,500 vehicles per lane assuming a two-lane side road), the peak value of 0.5 has been adopted for any intersecting road with lane flows greater than 7,500.

Figure B- 4 Pedestrian (crossing side road) and bicyclist (at intersection) external flow risk factors

For the FSI estimations, it is important to highlight that the model also allows for a non-linear relationship between the number of fatalities and AADT through the use of the AADT multiplier and AADT power. This

is encouraged in countries where good evidence-based research is available to define a non-linear relationship between vehicle flow, and road crashes, although variance across a network must be managed if this approach is taken. For the purpose of iRAP assessments in countries with limited crash data and underlying research of this type, these values are typically set to 1.

B.3. Further information on the Fatal and Severe Injuries Estimations

This subsection highlights relevant content for PHOEBE from the *iRAP Methodology Factsheet 10 – Casualty estimation and calibration* (iRAP, 2014).

Fatal and Serious Injury (FSI) Estimates are one of the iRAP protocols for trauma estimation¹⁶. It draws on the road attributes used within the Star Rating Model, flow data for each road user and network-level crash data to estimate the FSIs along each road segment and support the prioritization of investments (38).

The process is based on a hierarchical set of equations. The total number of fatalities is estimated as the sum of the estimated fatalities for each user type in Equation 4.

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^n (VO_F + MC_F + P_F + B_F) \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

Where F is the number of fatalities, n is the number of 100 meters segment of roads under analysis, VO_F is the vehicle occupants estimated fatalities, MC_F is the motorcyclist estimated fatalities, P_F is the pedestrian estimated fatalities, and B_F is the bicyclist estimated fatalities (38).

VO_F , MC_F , P_F , and B_F are the sum of the fatality estimation for each crash type. In this report, we will use the vehicle occupants' crashes as an example of the sequence of the equations.

(31)(31)

$$VO_F = VO_{RO-D} + VO_{RO-P} + VO_{HO-LC} + VO_{HO-O} + VO_{INT} + VO_{PA} \quad \text{(Equation 2)}$$

Where, VO_{RO-D} is the vehicle occupants' fatalities because of a run-off from the driver's side, VO_{RO-P} are the vehicle occupants' fatalities because of a run-off from the passenger side, VO_{HO-LC} represents the vehicle occupants' fatalities due to head-on – loss of control, VO_{HO-O} represents the vehicle occupants' fatalities due to head-on – overtaking, VO_{INT} are the vehicle occupants' fatalities in intersections and VO_{PA} is the vehicle occupants' fatalities in property access.

Each vehicle occupant fatality is calculated by an equation similar to the one presented below. As an example, we use the vehicle occupants' fatalities because of a run-off from the driver's side.

$$VO_{RO-D} = SRS_{RO-D} * a(AADT_{NON-MC})^b * CF_{VO,RO-D} * 365/10^9 \quad \text{(Equation 3)}$$

Where SRS_{RO-D} is the star rating scores for the run-off from drivers type of crash; $AADT_{NON-MC}$ is the annual average daily traffic excluding motorcyclists; a and b are the annual average daily traffic multiplier and power that allows a not linear relationship to vehicle flows effect on safety; and $CF_{VO,RO-D}$ is the calibration factor for vehicle occupant run-off driver side.

¹⁶ See more at: [Fatal and Serious Injury \(FSI\) Estimates - iRAP](#)

The SRS considers the number of fatalities due to the infrastructure condition, speeds, and flows. There are differences between the SRS calculated to show the road star ratings and the one used in the FSI estimations. The main one is speed. Here, the mean speed will be used as opposed to the 85th percentile speed. Then, the calibration factor helps ensure that the total estimated number of fatalities on the network equals the actual number. For the example of vehicle occupant's run-off-road (driver side), the calibration factors can be calculated as presented in (Equation 4)).

$$CF_{VO\ RO-D} = \frac{\text{Actual number of VO RO - D crash fatalities on the road network}}{\sum_{i=1}^n SRS_{RO-D} * a(AADT)^b * V_{NON-MC} * FG} \quad \text{(Equation 4)}$$

Where the actual number of fatalities on the road network for the crash type under analysis (in this case, vehicle occupants run-off – driver side) is divided by the sum of star rating scores for the run-off from driver type of crash (SRS_{RO-D}); the annual average daily traffic (AADT) multiplied and powered by a and b parameters; non-motorcycle AADT (V_{NON-MC}) and a fatality growth exponent (FG).

Applied across the network, this approach enables an estimate of the number of vehicle occupant, motorcyclist, bicyclists, and pedestrian fatalities on every 100-meter section of road. With the allocation of fatalities completed to a 100-meters level, one can also assess the benefits of treatments at a 100-metre section level.

B.4. iRAP models for urban areas.

The Star Rating model, the FSIs estimation and the Safer Road Investment Plans can be applied to urban or rural areas. Some examples of how the star ratings will rank different street configurations are provided in the iRAP Star Ratings of NACTO-GDCI's Global Street Design Guide. Figure B- 5 presents the differences between the two street designs of a multilane avenue.

Grand Streets | 62m

Figure B- 5 Star Rating evaluation for two different types of street designs.

The area type is a trigger for countermeasures being considered in the Safer Road Investment Plans. Urban areas can demand different safety treatments, or the triggers for a specific treatment can differ from rural environments. The iRAP also recommend using the urban enhanced SRIP in dense urban centers. This version of the SRIP presents additional 29 countermeasures specifically designed to promote safe speeds, safe crossings, safe intersections and safe pedestrian and bicyclist facilities in cities.

B.5. Annex references

ADB (2022). CAREC Road Safety Engineering Manual 5 Star Ratings for Road Safety Audits Manual. Available at https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/806631/carec-rse-manual-5-star-ratings-road-safety-audit_0.pdf

GDCI and iRAP (2020). iRAP Star Ratings of NACTO-GDCI's Global Street Design Guide. Available at: <https://globaldesigningcities.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/iRAP-Star-Ratings-of-the-GSDG.pdf>

iRAP (2010). Vehicle Speeds and iRAP Protocols. Available at: <https://irap.org/project/speed-management/>

iRAP (2013) iRAP Methodology Factsheet n° 5 –External Flow and Median Traversability. Available at: <https://irap.org/methodology/>

iRAP (2014). iRAP Methodology Factsheet n° 6 –Star Rating Score Equations. Available at: <https://irap.org/methodology/>

iRAP (2014). iRAP Methodology Factsheet n° 10 – Casualty estimation and calibration. Available at: <https://irap.org/methodology/>

iRAP (2022). Vehicle Speeds and iRAP Protocols: A Review. Available at <https://irap.org/research-and-technical-papers/>

Annex C: Stakeholders survey structure

PHOEBE - Predictive Approaches For Safer Urban Environments: Stakeholder Questionnaire

PHOEBE aims to holistically improve road safety prediction tools. The project established the following framework in order to create a dedicated module in traffic simulation tools.

The first step includes assessing the established traffic simulation tools and road safety assessment methods, with a view to subsequently enhancing these tools in light of new data sources and analytical methods. This work will include integrating several new metrics, models and techniques, considering factors such as modal shift, human behaviour, and improved data exploitation through machine learning methodologies.

One of the greatest challenges we face is that the outputs of PHOEBE must be comprehensible and usable in order for them to have true value for stakeholders, leading to a real and observable impact in reducing the incidence of crashes in urban areas and mitigating their consequences.

The present questionnaire will be provided to those local stakeholders that are identified as hands-on practitioners in order to establish where the project can produce the most impact.

The aim of the questionnaire is to:

- i. help inform the methodology of the PHOEBE framework
- ii. guide the selection of scenarios to be modelled
- iii. identify key outputs and analysis which will support transport policy and safety objectives

Please note that all Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

The questionnaire duration is estimated at about 20-25 min.

Thank you very much for your participation and overall interest in PHOEBE!

Phoebe Framework Overview

Warm-up questions

Introductory questions to ease the transition to the subsequent thematic questions.

What is your highest education level? *

- Secondary education diploma
- University/College-level degree/diploma
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree/Postdoctoral studies
- Other: _____

Which city do you work in? *

Your answer _____

What is your main role in your city? *

- Road administration
- Road maintenance
- Implementation of infrastructure interventions
- Public transport design/operations
- Mobility service provider
- Traffic police
- Traffic management/optimization
- Other city authority
- Private sector involved in road safety
- Private sector involved in public transport
- Other private sector
- Other: _____

How many years of experience do you have in that role? *

Your answer _____

Which of the following software/tool types do you use in your daily activities? *
Select any that apply.

- Microscopic traffic simulation
- Mesoscopic traffic simulation
- Macroscopic traffic simulation
- Pedestrian microscopic simulation
- Traffic signal optimization software
- Road safety assessment methodology (Road Safety Inspections, Road Safety Audits, etc.)
- Road safety assessment software
- Road safety telematics software
- Video image processing software
- Routing software
- Logistics software
- Public transport scheduling/management software
- Public transport telematics software (e.g. Bus telematics systems)
- Other: _____

How important would an investigation of each of the following scenarios be for your daily work?

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

Implementation of regulatory measures to limit speeds to 30 km/h (or 20mph) limit across the city network (from nominal enforcement to police presence to radars and speed cameras). Compliance with new and established speed limits. *

- | | | | | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | 8 | 9 | 10 |
| <input type="radio"/> |

The implications of introducing an extensive network of bicycle routes as a part of the existing road network (either as mixed traffic, or with separate bike/bus lanes, or with separate bike lanes on the road shoulders). *

- | | | | | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | 8 | 9 | 10 |
| <input type="radio"/> |

Promotion of public transport modes through campaigns and/or more attractive pricing *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Management of conflict due to the introduction of new transport initiative (such as a new bike hire scheme), new modes (e.g. e-scooters), and new vehicle types (e.g. e-unicycles) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Implementing hierarchical, safe and connected road schemes *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Encouraging modal shift towards more sustainable modes and active travel *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Implementation of newer/modernized standards for bike lanes design *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Effectiveness of speed-calming measures/Low traffic Neighbourhoods/Superblocks *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Connection & expansion of the urban cycling and walking infrastructure that lies separately to the rest of the road network. *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Modernising sustainable travel aligning with existing and predicted demand in advance of major events (e.g. Olympics/Commonwealth games) *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Which other scenarios are the most critical for you? Please provide up to three one-sentence descriptions.

Your answer _____

Human Behaviours

PHOEBE will examine a large array of human behaviours that may emerge as a result of changes in transport systems and will ultimately influence risk. Some examples of these behaviours are mobile phone distraction, speeding, fatigue, sleepiness, illegal crossing, non-compliance with dedicated bicycle lanes, and risk compensation. While individual characteristics such as demographics, attitudes, experiences and risk profiles of road users underlie these behaviours, research has shown that the design of transport systems promotes these behaviours too. Therefore, the following group of questions concerns the integration of human behaviours into the various utilised tools for decision making in the transport sector.

If you do not possess any expertise/familiarity with this group of questions, you can go to the next topic.

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

How useful would it be for you to include human behaviour in a microsimulation tool?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

How useful would it be for you to include human behaviour in a road assessment tool?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

The recording of human behaviours has been facilitated by telematics in recent years, i.e. systems collecting and transmitting data on drivers' heart rate, mobile phone use instances, gaze, vehicle position, speed, acceleration and others. How useful would it be for you to derive human behaviour patterns from telematics data ?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Which types of behaviours ought to be integrated for drivers?

Your answer _____

Which types of behaviours ought to be integrated for pedestrians?

Your answer _____

Which types of behaviours ought to be integrated for cyclists or other light mobility users (e.g. microscooters)?

Your answer _____

Data collection methods

PHOEBE will take into account new trends in data collection methods, such as (indicatively) crowdsourcing, social media data (e.g. from taxi-hailing or deriving origin-destination) etc. The following group of questions concerns the integration of the new data collection methods into the various utilised tools.

If you do not possess any expertise/familiarity with this group of questions, you can go to the next topic.

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

How useful would it be for you to include new data collection methods in a microsimulation tool?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

How useful would it be for you to include new data collection methods in a road assessment tool?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

How useful would it be for you to include data obtained by a telematics recording device ?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Which types of new data collection methods ought to be integrated?

Your answer _____

Modal shift

PHOEBE will investigate the influence and impact of modal shift to the transport network. In other words, the change of shares of each mode and the effects it induces on road safety and traffic operations are going to be examined. These phenomena can refer, for instance, to a positive modal shift from private vehicles to greener public transport or active travel such as walking or cycling. The following group of questions concerns the integration of the modal shift effects into the various utilised tools.

If you do not possess any expertise/familiarity with this group of questions, you can go to the next topic.

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

How useful would it be for you to include modal shift effects in a microsimulation tool?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

How useful would it be for you to include modal shift effects in a road assessment tool?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

How useful would it be for you to monitor modal shift effects using a telematics recording device?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Which types of modal shift matter the most to you?

Your answer _____

Socioeconomic models

PHOEBE will also investigate the influence of socioeconomic parameters of the road users, such as available income, unemployment, age profiles, to the outputs and the behaviour of the transport network. The following group of questions concerns the integration of the socioeconomic parameters into the various utilised tools.

If you do not possess any expertise/familiarity with this group of questions, you can go to the next topic.

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

How useful would it be for you to include socioeconomic parameters in a microsimulation tool?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

How useful would it be for you to include socioeconomic parameters in a road assessment tool?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Which types of socioeconomic parameters ought to be integrated?

Your answer _____

Road safety assessment

PHOEBE will enhance certain currently available road safety assessment methodologies focus on infrastructure risk and enrich the other available tools with them in turn. Therefore, the following group of questions concerns the integration of infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies into the other utilised tools.

If you do not possess any expertise/familiarity with this group of questions, you can go to the next topic.

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

How useful would it be for you to include infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies in a microsimulation tool?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

How useful would it be for you to incorporate telematics data into infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Which types of infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies ought to be integrated?

Your answer _____

Traffic microsimulation

PHOEBE will enhance certain currently available traffic microsimulation tools and enrich the other available tools with them in turn. Therefore, the following group of questions concerns the integration of road safety assessment methodologies into the other utilised tools.

If you do not possess any expertise/familiarity with this group of questions, you can go to the next topic.

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

How useful would it be for you to include traffic microsimulation tools in a road assessment tool?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

How useful would it be for you to incorporate telematics data into a traffic microsimulation tool?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Which types of traffic microsimulation tools ought to be integrated?

Your answer _____

Closing questions:

These questions aim to gauge the relevance and importance of future tools developed within PHOEBE to the daily work and professional practice of participants.

Rate your overall professional needs relevant to PHOEBE:

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

Traffic simulation enriched with infrastructure safety information (e.g. the ability * to estimate road safety risk when simulating different scenarios of urban interventions)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enriched with modal shift information (e.g. how modal share * changes from specific interventions)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enriched with induced demand models (e.g. additional trips * being generated as a result of interventions)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enriched with human behaviour models (e.g. capturing varying * behaviours of drivers, VRUs or other road users, such as decision making or risk compensation)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Improved accuracy of traffic simulation (e.g. by improving the quality of model * input information, such as road geometry data)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enhanced by incorporating all of the above functionalities *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with traffic microsimulation informatio (e.g. the ability to calculate traffic conflicts generated from specific road infrastructure elements) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with modal shift information (e.g. how modal share changes from specific interventions affect the individual level of risk) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with induced demand models (e.g. measurement impacts on the individual risk considering additional trips being generated as a result of interventions) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with human behaviour models (e.g. capturing varying behaviours of drivers, VRUs or other road users, such as decision making or risk compensation) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with AI/ML models (e.g. identification of variation of risk based on speed and flow daily profiles) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with all the above *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

How much would a PHOEBE-developed tool help you in your everyday tasks?

Likert scales range from 1 meaning "not important at all" to 10 meaning "very important".

Traffic simulation enhanced with infrastructure safety information (e.g. the ability to estimate road safety risk when simulating different scenarios of urban interventions) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enhanced with modal shift information (e.g. how modal share changes from specific interventions) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enhanced with induced demand models (e.g. additional trips being generated as a result of interventions) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Traffic simulation enhanced with human behaviour models (e.g. capturing varying behaviours of drivers, VRUs or other road users, such as decision making or risk compensation) *

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Road assessment enhanced with traffic simulation information (e.g. the ability to calculate traffic conflicts generated from specific road infrastructure elements) *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Road assessment enhanced with modal shift information (e.g. how modal share changes from specific interventions affect the individual level of risk) *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Road assessment enhanced with induced demand models (e.g. measurement impacts on the individual risk considering additional trips being generated as a result of interventions) *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Road assessment enhanced with human behaviour models (e.g. capturing varying behaviours of drivers, VRUs or other road users, such as decision making or risk compensation) *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Road assessment enhanced with AI/ML models (e.g. identification of variation of risk based on speed and flow daily profiles) *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Road assessment enhanced with all the above *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Road assessment enhanced with all the above *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

How often would you expect to use a PHOEBE-developed tool? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

How much would you estimate a PHOEBE-developed tool can impact real crash numbers? *

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Would you like to provide any additional comments relevant to our survey?

Your answer _____

Thank you very much for your participation!

Annex D: Additional stakeholders survey results graphs

D.1. Overall sample

Stakeholders main role in cities

- Road administration
- Road maintenance
- Implementation of infrastructure interventions
- Public transport design/operations
- Mobility service provider
- Traffic police
- Traffic management/optimization
- Other city authority
- Private sector involved in road safety
- Private sector involved in public transport
- Other private sector
- Other

Stakeholder years of experience

- 0-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years
- >20 years

Software/tool types that stakeholders use in daily activities

- Microscopic traffic simulation
- Mesoscopic traffic simulation
- Macroscopic traffic simulation
- Pedestrian microscopic simulation
- Traffic signal optimization software
- Road safety assessment methodology
- Road safety assessment software
- Road safety telematics software
- Video image processing software
- Routing software
- Logistics software
- Public transport scheduling/management software
- Public transport telematics software
- Other

Importance of human behaviour inclusion

Importance of new data collection methods inclusion

Importance of modal shift inclusion

Importance of socioeconomic parameters inclusion

Importance of infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies inclusion in a microsimulation tool

Importance of telematics data inclusion in infrastructure safety risk assessment methodologies

Importance of telematics data inclusion in a microsimulation tool

Importance of microsimulation tools inclusion in a road assessment tool

Expected PHOEBE-developed tool use frequency

Estimation of how much a PHOEBE-developed tool can impact real crash numbers

Usefulness of the PHOEBE-developed tool in everyday tasks

D.2. Use cases groups

Stakeholders highest education level

Athens stakeholders

Valencia stakeholders

West Midlands stakeholders

- Secondary education diploma
- University/College-level degree/diploma
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree/Postdoctoral studies
- Other

Importance of human behaviour inclusion

Athens stakeholders

Valencia stakeholders

- In a microsimulation tool
- In a road assessment tool
- In a telematics recording device

West Midlands stakeholders

Importance of new data collection methods inclusion

Importance of modal shift inclusion

Overall professional needs relevant to PHOEBE

Usefulness of the PHOEBE-developed tool in everyday tasks

Expected PHOEBE-developed tool use frequency

Estimation of how much a PHOEBE-developed tool can impact real crash numbers

Annex E: Focus group script

[START MEETING]

Welcome to our focus group about Road Safety.

A focus group is basically a group interview. Our questions have no “right” or “wrong” answers. Our goal is to listen to your personal experiences and opinions. So please – share your thoughts.
[SMILE]

We have prepared this meeting to make the most of your precious time – so, let me share some notes on the method that we’ll be following.

1. Our team has prepared a few questions. We’ll be going over those questions, one by one. I will ask the questions – and we’ll hear what you have to say. We’ll ask you about your personal experience and opinions. Also about your difficulties, your needs – and your advice.
2. This is a group session. So it’s OK to comment on what the other participants say. Agree, disagree, add on top of it. Just please talk only one at a time, to make sure we understand what you say. Relax, we’ll have time to listen to all. [SMILE]
3. Please make sure there is no background noise, and keep your camera ON, so we can all see each other.
4. As mentioned in our invitation, we planned for a maximum of 1h30. Please stay until the end.
5. Finally, regarding privacy: your input will be kept anonymous. We’ll take note of the things you say and may share them later, but we will not mention neither your name nor where you work.
6. It would be very helpful for us to record a video of this session. This recording will be used ONLY to better analyze what you said. It will never be shared outside of our team, and it will be deleted as soon as the first part of our project ends.

May we record this session?

[IF “YES” START RECORDING]

For a quick introduction to our conversation:

Local authorities have a key role to play in the advancement of Road Safety. They can advance with the work of their professionals. Professionals working on special projects, or in everyday decisions.

Their decisions have a direct or indirect impact in Road Safety. Some of those professionals work specifically on Road Safety. Others work on urban planning, transport planning, traffic management, etc.

New methods and tools can help these professionals evaluate risk and make informed decisions. How can we ensure these new methods and tools will be usable by those professionals? This is a challenge.

Especially when these solutions bring together new techniques, new data sources, and a new understanding of Road Safety. Just “inventing” a new tool is not enough. We must understand the needs and challenges of the professionals and the organizations that will use them.

This is what we’ll be talking about – is that OK?

Then, let’s move to our questions. And let’s start with a “difficult” question:

[QUESTION] What’s your name, and what do you do?

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

Next question:

[QUESTION] What’s the importance of Road Safety for the work you’re doing?

[Check for]

- How is it important?
- If it should be important but isn’t – why is that?
- What kind of decisions are made
- Balancing of safety with other concerns (e.g., congestion)
- The role of political power, decisions

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

Several decisions can have an impact on Road Safety. A direct or indirect impact. A positive or negative impact. Special decisions, but also everyday decisions. Decisions made by you – and also by your colleagues and leaders.

[QUESTION] You’ve certainly seen other people (colleagues, political leaders, clients) make those types of decision. What are the issues they usually consider as important in those decisions?

[Check for]

- Concerns of others: cost, congestion, political pressure
- Types of decisions made
- User behaviour
- Method – description, improvement, needs to improve
- Transposition of the method to the scale of the organization

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

People walking, cycling, or using e-scooters are usually called “vulnerable road users”. Because they are considered to be at a higher risk than car drivers.

[QUESTION] How do you evaluate the risk for these vulnerable road users?

[Check for]

- Practices of the OTHERS inside organization
- Role of infrastructure on behaviour
- Traffic volumes, Speed limits, Practiced speed
- Role of infrastructure on behaviour
- Methods to assess risk
- What kind of risky behaviours are they interested in?
- Behavioural factors that affect road safety

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

Some local authorities use traffic simulation to support transport planning or management. The use of traffic simulation software implies building a digital model of reality, introducing traffic data, and seeing what are the implications that some changes may have on traffic behaviour.

The simulation produces results – indicating, for example, if there will be more or less traffic congestion, how traffic will be redistributed, etc.

[QUESTION] Imagine you could order a new traffic simulation software. You could order what types of results this software would provide. What types of results would be useful for people working on Road Safety?

[Check for]

- Used, yes or no? Would like to? What could help YOU use it?

- Did you find it practical? Did you find it useful?
- What are the obstacles to using it – or using it more?
- Practical difficulties with using traffic simulation
- Organizational difficulties – staff, staff time, budget, IT, data

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

In the past few years several new mobility services arrived on our streets. Digital technology and geolocation play an important role. These services generate large amounts of digital data. These data can be useful for mobility planning or management.

[QUESTION] Do you think these data can be useful for Road Safety? How?

[Check for]

- Other types and sources of data
- Difficulties in acquiring data
- Internal organizational barriers to access or use of the data
- Lack of technical skills (knowledge, experience)
- Lack of means (software, etc.)

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

We are working on a project that will bring together new techniques, new data sources, and new knowledge, to advance Road Safety.

Implementing a new method and tools of this kind in an organization is usually a challenge. We're looking for the best ways to make it easy for local authorities and their professionals to adopt these solutions.

Imagine we were to bring to your organization [or a public authority you have worked for or with] a new method and tool to support decisions affecting Road Safety. Imagine this new method and tool brings together new techniques, new data sources, and new knowledge.

[QUESTION] What kind of difficulties would you expect in your organization?

[Check for]

- What could help overcome those difficulties?
- What advice do you have for us?
- Request for details about the framework – what are they asking?
- Practical advice
- Previous difficulties – own or of OTHERS

[MOVE TO NEXT SECTION]

We're almost finishing! Last question:

[QUESTION] Before we go, is there something you'd like to add?

Thank you for all your contributions! [smile]

[STOP RECORDING + END MEETING]

[CONDUCT DEBRIEFING WITH NOTE-TAKERS: (1) general impressions of the meeting, (2) comment on the specific input, particularly key or new insights, aggregation of input, (3) adjustments to the script.]

